

Reciprocation strategies and the syntax of reciprocal constructions

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ABSTRACT

Reciprocal constructions in the world's languages are typically associated with unusual syntactic behaviour and other anomalous properties. This thesis examines reciprocal constructions in Icelandic (Germanic), Malagasy (Austronesian) and Swahili (Bantu) in order to: firstly, determine the variability of their non-standard syntax; and secondly, to analyse these constructions within the theoretical framework of Lexical Functional Grammar (LFG) with a view to explaining the relationship between them and the reasons for their non-standard behaviour. These analyses reveal that the syntactic and, to a lesser extent, semantic behaviour of reciprocal constructions arise not from structural features (such as whether the reciprocal construction is formed from a clitic, affix *etc.*), but from more fundamental reciprocation strategies by which asymmetric predicates are made to describe symmetric situations.

I demonstrate that the highly irregular case marking and word order associated with the Icelandic (nominal) reciprocal construction is intimately related to two of these reciprocation strategies. As a result of two extensive surveys undertaken to document its behaviour and history (a corpus based survey of the reciprocal construction in Old Icelandic (*c.* 1200 CE) and an online survey of its usage by 500 Icelanders), I show that the variable word order and case marking of this construction can be understood as a consequence of a change in its underlying reciprocation mechanism from the compositional to the pronominal – a change that is for the most part indiscernible in its morphosyntactic expression.

In contrast to the phrasally formed Icelandic reciprocal construction, the Malagasy and Swahili reciprocal constructions are both verbally marked. As existing analyses of

apparently similar constructions in Romance, Hungarian (Uralic) and Chicheŵa (Bantu) are unable to explain their syntax, I propose two alternative analyses. The first is a novel analysis of the reciprocal construction in Malagasy as being derived from a covert application of the pronominal reciprocation strategy. This introduces a mismatch between functional and constituent structure and I show that this mismatch is required to explain the presence of reciprocated control and possession constructions, as well as its surprising similarities to the Icelandic reciprocal construction.

The reciprocal morpheme in Swahili is associated with two, distinct, reciprocal constructions: a monadic construction that groups the participants in the relation into the subject NP while losing an object NP; and a dyadic construction that places one participant in the subject NP and another in a comitative phrase. I show that the syntax of these constructions (and the relation between them) results from a reciprocation strategy that derives symmetric lexemes (much like the naturally symmetric verbs in English, *e.g.*, *quarrel*, *argue*).

Most of these reciprocation strategies require that the participants in the symmetric event be in a single NP. This means the normative syntactic principles that link a predicate to its grammatical functions cannot straightforwardly accommodate reciprocated predicates – requiring that these principles be abused or at least stretched. I show this to be the root cause of the unusual syntactic behaviour associated with many of these constructions. Finally, as the morphosyntactic expression of a reciprocal construction is largely divorced from its underlying reciprocation strategy, I advance the view that typologies of reciprocal constructions should be orientated around these mechanisms rather than structural properties.

DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- i. this thesis comprises only my original work towards the PhD except where indicated in the Preface,
- ii. due acknowledgement has been made in the text to all other material used,
- iii. this thesis is fewer than 100,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND GLOSSES

1, 2, 3	1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd person	O	transitive object
1/2/3:x	1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd person, class <i>x</i>	PL	plural
ABS	absolutive	POSS	possessive
ACC	accusative	PPL	past participle
ACT	active	PRES	present tense
AG	agent	PST	past tense
APP	applicative	PT	patient
APRX	proximal to addressee	REC	reciprocal
ART	article	REFL	reflexive
ASSERT	assertative	S	subject
BENE	beneficiary	SBJ	subjunctive
CAUS	causative	RR	reciprocal/reflexive
CNJ	conjunction	SG	singular
COM	comitative		
COMP	complementizer		
DAT	dative		
DEM	demonstrative		
DO	direct object		
DU	dual		
ERG	ergative		
F	feminine gender		
FV	final vowel		
GEN	genitive		
GF	grammatical function		
HAB	habitual		
INF	infinitive		
INSTRUM	instrument		
M	masculine gender		
MV	middle voice		
N	neuter gender		
NEG	negation		
NMLZ	nominalizer		

1 OVERVIEW AND BACKGROUND

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Prior to the 1990s, descriptions of reciprocal constructions were often mere footnotes or brief examples in otherwise comprehensive grammars. The lack of focus on these constructions was perhaps due to the assumption that they were relatively straightforward and that a single theoretical analysis would be able to accommodate them all. In the last two decades however, there has been a surge in the research of reciprocal constructions, the result of which has blunted this optimism (see König & Kokutani, 2005; Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001; Dalrymple, Kanazawa, Kim, Mchombo & Peters, 1998; Heim, Lasnik & May, 1991, Frajzyngier & Curl, 1999; Beck, 2001; Evans, 2008, 2006; Nedjalkov, 2007; König & Gast, 2008; Evans, Gaby, Levinson & Majid, 2011; Siloni, 2011). From a typological perspective it has been revealed that the morphosyntactic expression of reciprocal constructions varies enormously. So much so, that Evans (2008) commences his typology of reciprocal constructions by imagining all the conceivable ways languages could encode mutuality, and then exemplifying as many of them as possible with language data. Of the 21 possibilities he considers, 19 are attested by various languages and the remaining two have marginal candidates (see sections 3.1.5 and 3.1.6 in Evans, 2008). Adding to this complexity is the fact that reciprocal constructions are often associated with unusual

syntactic behaviour. For example, we see this in the highly unusual case marking in Icelandic (see chapter 2), and it is particularly prevalent with respect to the transitivity of reciprocal constructions which may be marked by contradictory morphosyntactic features (see chapter 3, also Evans, Gaby & Nordlinger, 2007). A further complication is that reciprocal constructions that share the same morphosyntactic expression can behave very differently, both with respect to the types of mutual situations they can encode (see Evans, Gaby, Levinson & Majid, 2011), but also in the types of constructions with which they may co-occur or license (see Siloni, 2011; Hurst, 2011, 2006; Reinhart and Siloni, 2005).

As the focus of this thesis, I have chosen reciprocal constructions from three languages to explore the issues discussed above; Icelandic (Germanic), Malagasy (Austronesian) and Swahili (Bantu). As we will see, the analysis I provide for them has application to many other reciprocal constructions in the world's languages (as illustrated by discussion of French (chapters 3 and 4), Hungarian (chapter 5), as well as intrinsically symmetric verbs – see chapters 4 and 5).

The Icelandic reciprocal construction is formed from two words; *hver* – “each” (or *hver*) and *annar* – “other” (realised as *aðra* below):^{1,2}

- (1) *María og Lilja sáu hver aðra.*
 Maria.F.NOM and Lilja.F.NOM see.3PL.PST each.F.SG.NOM other.F.SG.ACC
 “María and Lilja saw each other.”

This construction has direct counterparts in many Germanic languages (*e.g.*, English, German and Dutch, *etc.*). What is remarkable about it is that both *hver* and *annar* are separately assigned relational case. For example, *hver* in (1) has the same case as its antecedent while *aðra* is carrying the accusative case assigned to it by the verb *sáu* – “see”. That this really is the case (and not, for example, an instance of *hver*'s case simply being fixed to nominative) is illustrated in (2) below where we see the same case assignment principles applied again:

1 *Hvor* is used for antecedents with two entities, *hver* for antecedents with more than two (although see discussion in chapter 2. *Aðra* is the feminine singular accusative form of *annar*.
 2 Unless otherwise attributed, language data was elicited from native speakers. Further details appear in subsequent chapters.

- (2) *Ég kynnti menni-na tvo*
 I.1SG.NOM introduce.1SG.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the two.M.PL.ACC
- hvorn fyrir öðrum.* (or *fyrir hvor/n öðrum*)
 each.M.SG.ACC for other.M.SG.DAT
- “I introduced the two men to each other.”

In this instance, *hvor* now has accusative case like its antecedent (*mennina tvo* – “the two men”), and *annar* has been assigned dative case by its controlling preposition *fyrir* – “for”.³ These data raise two questions that need to be addressed: (i) how can a NP (e.g., *hvor aðra* in (1)) have two words that are both assigned separate relational case from outside the NP? and (ii), how is this case assignment linked to the various word orders of the construction when associated with prepositional phrases? (see (2) above). As we will see, what makes this discussion particularly illuminating is not just the provided analysis of this construction, but how it relates to other, apparently unrelated, languages. For example the Malagasy reciprocal construction, in terms of morphosyntactic expression, is completely different from the Icelandic reciprocal construction being formed via the application of a reciprocal prefix *-if-* to the verb:

- (2) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001)
- M-if-an-ome vola Rabe sy Rakoto.*
 PRES-REC-ACT-give money Rabe and Rakoto
- “Rabe and Rakoto give money to each other.”

Typically, analyses of verbally marked reciprocal constructions treat them as undergoing a decrease in valency – effectively becoming detransitivised (e.g., Alsina, 1996, for Catalan and other Romance languages; Mchombo, 1991, for Chicheŵa; Rákosi, 2008, for Hungarian, and Siloni, 2011, for Hebrew among other languages). However in one completely unexpected respect, Malagasy behaves identically to the Icelandic reciprocal construction, namely in that it allows object possession to co-occur with reciprocated verbs. For example, compare the Malagasy reciprocal sentence below with its Icelandic

3 Although *hvor* has the same case as its antecedent, its position in the clause is relatively unconstrained. See discussion in chapter 2.6.

equivalent:

(3) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001)

- a. *M-if-an-ome vola zananaka Rasoa sy Ravelo.*
PRES-REC-ACT-give money child Rasoa and Ravelo
“Rasoa and Ravelo give money to each other's children.”

Icelandic

- b. *Mennir-nir tveir gáfu börnum*
men.M.PL.NOM-the two.m.pl.com give.3PL.PST child.N.PL.DAT

hvor annars peninga.
each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.GEN money.M.PL.ACC
“The two men gave each other's children money.”

The existence of sentences such as (3a) in Malagasy are surprising if we treat the reciprocated verb as having lost an object because we would usually analyse *zananaka* – “child” as heading an object NP. The Malagasy example above illustrates one of the unusual features associated with reciprocal constructions more generally, which is the contradictory indications they have with respect to transitivity. For example the reciprocal construction in (2) lacks an object NP (and is not able to co-occur with an object NP), yet in (3a) an apparent NP object becomes possible in a possessive construction. The nature of these verbally marked reciprocal possessor constructions is not well-understood and an analysis of reciprocal constructions needs to explain their formation. However, there are two, more important, issues that need to be addressed: (i) why reciprocal constructions are so commonly associated with contradictory markers of transitivity in the first place, and (ii) why two reciprocal constructions (as illustrated by Malagasy and Icelandic), with such extreme differences in morphosyntactic expression, can have unexpectedly similar behaviour in other syntactic environments.

These issues are further illustrated by examining the Swahili reciprocal construction. It is formed almost identically to the Malagasy reciprocal construction, using a verbal affix to indicate that the predicate has been reciprocated:

(4) Swahili – Monadic reciprocal construction⁴

Juma na Halima wa-li-tekeny-an-a.

Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-tickle-REC-FV

“Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

Although the parallels in morphosyntactic expression are evident, in several crucial aspects it behaves very differently to both the Icelandic and Malagasy reciprocal constructions. For example, ignoring verbal morphology which adds an argument to the verb's predicate (such as the applicative or causative), there are no circumstances that allow the Swahili reciprocal construction in (4) to co-occur with an object, or be related to an object possession construction, unlike in Malagasy. Additionally, reciprocated verbs in Swahili productively license two constructions, the monadic (e.g., (4) above) and the dyadic:

(5) Swahili – Dyadic reciprocal construction

Juma a-li-tekeny-an-a na Halima.

Juma 3SGS-PST-tickle-REC-FV COM Halima

“Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

lit. “Juma tickled each other with Halima”

Neither the Icelandic nor Malagasy reciprocal constructions above allow for the productive formation of a dyadic reciprocal construction. However, there are very surprising parallels between the dyadic reciprocal construction in (5) and the Icelandic middle voice construction, and intrinsically symmetric verbs in English – both of which also appear to have a dyadic alternate, and both of which, despite being unrelated to Bantu, are formed identically using a comitative phrase:

(6) Icelandic

Transitive verb

a. *Madonna sló Lady Gaga.*

Madonna hit.3SG.PST Lady Gaga

4 Called the “monadic reciprocal construction” to distinguish it from its “dyadic” equivalent – see (5) below.

Middle voice / monadic reciprocal construction

- b. *Madonna og Lady Gaga slógu-st* (*i beinni*)^{5,6}
Madonna and Lady Gaga brawl.3PL.PST-MV live
“Madonna and Lady Gaga brawled (live).”

Middle voice / dyadic reciprocal construction

- c. *Madonna sló-st við Lady Gaga.*
Madonna brawl.3SG.PST-MV with Lady Gaga
“Madonna brawled with Lady Gaga.”

- (7) a. *Madonna and Lady Gaga fought.*
b. *Madonna fought with Lady Gaga.*

Understanding the nature of the relationships between the transitive base, monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions in Swahili forms a significant part of the later chapters of this thesis. However, by comparing the Swahili reciprocal construction with the other languages examined, we see that there are more profound questions that need to be answered. For example, why is it that some languages like Swahili have both a monadic and dyadic reciprocal construction, but other languages, with apparently very similar reciprocal constructions, do not? Why do very disparate language groups that do have dyadic reciprocal constructions form them almost identically and what is the relation between the dyadic reciprocal construction and intrinsically symmetric verbs?

We have seen that there are languages which have reciprocal constructions with nearly identical morphosyntactic expression (*e.g.*, Malagasy and Swahili) but which behave very differently with respect to a host of other features (such as the ability to license a comitative phrase, object possession *etc.*). Also, we have seen languages with very different reciprocal constructions that behave very similarly with respect to these same features (*e.g.*, Malagasy and Icela). Finally, we have seen that reciprocal constructions are frequently associated with unusual syntactic properties (such as atypical case assignment, word order or contradictory indications regarding transitivity).

What is needed is an analysis of reciprocal constructions that views these seemingly

5 Language examples referenced with a URL have been collected from the internet (for the most part, during 2010).

6 <http://www.dv.is/abendig/email/18361/>

unconnected properties as different facets of a cohesive whole, rather than as a collection of disparate syntactic phenomena. In this thesis I will show that the dominant factor dictating reciprocal constructions' syntactic behaviour (for example, whether they licence a comitative construction or not) is not their morphosyntactic expression, but their reciprocation strategy. That is to say, it is one of just a few reciprocation strategies (to be explained below) that underlie a particular reciprocal construction that determines how the construction behaves with respect to the features discussed above.

A reciprocation strategy describes the means by which an asymmetric predicate may come to refer to a symmetric situation. As mentioned above, these reciprocation strategies are critical to understanding a reciprocal construction because they determine the construction's behaviour in wider syntactic contexts and in some instances profoundly affect the types of symmetry they may encode. I identify five reciprocation strategies:

1. Compositional strategy (*e.g.*, “Each man saw the other.”)

This mechanism creates a symmetric interpretation of an event through the compositional interaction of a quantifier (such as *each*) with an alterity word (*e.g.*, *other*). This strategy is thought to be the origin of many Germanic reciprocal constructions (see Plank, 2008) and it is discussed in detail in chapter 2 with respect to the Old Icelandic reciprocal construction.

2. Operator based mechanisms (either from a pronoun or a bound morpheme)

This strategy described by Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) uses a reciprocal operator, RECIP, that is applied to an asymmetric predicate to produce a symmetric interpretation of an event. This operator is usually associated with a reciprocal pronoun (see chapter 3, although see comments in chapter 4.3.6) and in appendix A, I provide an example of how this operator is connected to syntax using the theory of LFG and glue logic.

3. Argument unification

Argument unification creates a symmetric interpretation of an event by linking both arguments of an asymmetric predicate to a single grammatical function (typically the subject). For example, the asymmetric predicate *push* has two arguments, a proto-agent and a proto-patient and the argument unification strategy maps both of these arguments

to the subject. Alsina (1996) uses this mechanism to explain the syntax and formation of the Romance reciprocal constructions (see chapter 3).

4. Intrinsic strategy⁷

All languages have available to them a set of verbs which are intrinsically symmetric. A verb is intrinsically symmetric when the symmetry of the event it expresses simply forms part of its meaning. For example, the verb *exchange* (e.g., “They exchanged glances”) in English is intrinsically symmetric. This strategy is discussed in detail in chapters 4 and 5 where it is contrasted with theta-role synthesis.

5. Theta-role synthesis

Theta-role synthesis creates symmetric predicates by changing the argument structure of a predicate when it is reciprocated. I argue that this strategy takes two thematic roles associated with a predicate and synthesises them together to form a new symmetric predicate. Reinhart and Siloni (2005) argue that this is a lexical strategy and I show how this claim is supported by the Swahili reciprocal construction in chapters 4 and 5.

The following chapters demonstrate that to understand the syntax of a reciprocal construction, we need to know by which strategy it was formed. However, determining which reciprocation strategy a reciprocal construction uses is not straightforward. This is because these strategies are often only weakly connected to a reciprocal construction's morphosyntactic expression.⁸ This means that it is not usually possible to determine a reciprocal construction's strategy simply by examining its morphosyntax.

For example, it is possible that two reciprocal constructions with nearly identical expression can be formed from very different strategies (as I demonstrate for the Malagasy and Swahili reciprocal constructions), or that very different reciprocal constructions can share the same underlying reciprocation strategy (as I show for Malagasy and one type of Icelandic reciprocal construction). The reciprocal constructions in Icelandic, Malagasy and Swahili are formed by the compositional,

7 The use of an intrinsically symmetric verb is not strictly a strategy as the event's symmetry is entailed by the meaning of the verb and is not derived. However, because of their close relationship with the other reciprocation strategies discussed, I include them here.

8 Although there are some generalisations to be made, for example, both θ -role synthesis and argument unification are incompatible with phrasal reciprocal constructions.

(pronominal) operator and theta-role synthesis reciprocation strategies respectively, each of which is described in detail in later chapters. However, to contextualise the following discussion I describe them briefly below. The intrinsic reciprocation strategy relies on the use of inherently symmetric verbs to express symmetry. These verbs, as part of their meaning, describe symmetric events, for example “kiss” in “They kissed”. The compositional reciprocation strategy is one where the symmetric interpretation of the event is captured by the interplay of a distributive operator (*e.g.* *each*) with an indefinite pronoun (*e.g.* *other* – known as an “alterity” word – see Plank, 2008):

(8) *Each man saw the other.*

Operator based reciprocation strategies utilise an operator (RECIP) to create a symmetric interpretation from an asymmetric predicate. For example:

(9) $\text{RECIP}(\{\text{John}, \text{Mary}\}, \lambda x. \lambda y. \text{see}(x, y))$

This operator may be linked to a reciprocal pronoun (*e.g.*, *each other* in English) or to a reciprocal morpheme (for example see the discussion of the work by Dalrymple *et al.* 1998 on the Chicheŵa reciprocal construction in chapter 4.2.2). The argument unification strategy allows a single grammatical function (usually the subject) to be linked to two arguments. In this case, the symmetric nature of the event follows not from the application of an abstract operator to a predicate, but rather from a speaker or hearer understanding the participants described by the predicate to be both initiators and endpoints of an event (see Alsina, 1996). Finally theta-role synthesis is an altogether different strategy where two thematic roles are merged and the resulting predicate is interpreted as being symmetric – and consequently behaves much like intrinsically symmetric verbs described above.

Several of these reciprocation strategies are also behind the unusual syntactic behaviour associated with reciprocal constructions. For example, the atypical case assignment of the Icelandic reciprocal construction arises as a consequence of it undergoing a gradual transition from one reciprocation mechanism to another. Likewise, the mixed signals with respect to transitivity that so often accompany reciprocal constructions are shown to be an artefact of certain reciprocation strategies that result in

the reciprocated verb having one less operand when compared to its non-reciprocated counterpart. Languages can accommodate this missing operand in a number of ways, some of which maintain the syntactic transitivity of the reciprocated verb, even though it has one fewer NP. The theory of Lexical Functional Grammar (LFG) in which I situate my analysis is uniquely well suited to analysing these constructions. It uses several independent, but linked, levels of syntactic structure which interact together to explain the grammaticality and structure of sentences. Each reciprocation strategy I identify is situated within one of these levels of structure and it is through the interaction of a reciprocation mechanism with other levels of structure that both the reciprocal construction's wider syntactic behaviour is played out but also that a more nuanced conception of valency can be utilised to understand the uncomfortable relationship reciprocals have with transitivity.

I use these different strategies to explain both the unusual word order and case marking of the Icelandic reciprocal construction, as well as the syntactic similarities it shares with the Malagasy reciprocal construction – despite their very different morphosyntactic expression. Furthermore, the syntactically divergent behaviour of the verbally formed Malagasy and Swahili reciprocal constructions can be understood as resulting from different underlying reciprocation mechanisms. Finally, the interaction of these strategies with different levels of syntactic structure is used to explain the Malagasy reciprocal construction's apparently ambivalent indications of valency. However, before commencing a review of the literature of reciprocal constructions, I begin by more clearly defining what reciprocal constructions are, and the domain of semantics they describe.

1.2 WHAT IS A RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION?

In English, the prototypical reciprocal construction is one that uses “each other” or “one another” to indicate a symmetric event with two participants. For example:

(10) *John and Mary visited each other / one another.*

In (10) above, John visits Mary, and Mary visits John. Because they are each initiators and endpoints to the relation defined by the predicate, we say that the event is

symmetric. However, in order to be able to identify reciprocal constructions in more complex situations, as well as in other languages, we will need a more general description of what a reciprocal construction is. As a place to start, I follow the definition of a reciprocal construction used by Evans (2008) in his structural typology of reciprocal constructions. He defines a construction as a “... conventionalized triplet linking a meaning with a signifier and combinatorics” (Evans, 2008:35). A reciprocal construction is then a construction that is specialized for, and conventionalized for, the expression of symmetrical events. By specialized, Evans means that at least one of the senses of a reciprocal construction must denote a symmetric situation. Evans adds another requirement to the definition of a reciprocal construction and this is that the reciprocal construction itself must also be non-compositional. That is to say, the symmetric meaning cannot arise simply from a simple listing of events such as in (11a) or (11b) below:

- (11) a. Golin – Chimbu; Papuan (Evans, 2008:79)
Abal su i yal paunan aato-n-g-w-e
 woman two DEM man jaw touch-3-ASSERT-3-APRX

i yal su abal su paunan aato-n-g-w-e.
 DEM man two woman two jaw touch-3-ASSERT-3-APRX
 “Two girls touch the two men on the jaw, and the two men touch the two girls on the jaw.”
 [*i.e.* the girls and the men are touching each other’s jaws]
- b. *Each of the nurses saw the other nurses.*

Instead, the reciprocal construction itself must act as the sign that signifies the reciprocal meaning. Note however, that between a simple listing of events such as in (11a) above and full blown reciprocal constructions (such as in (10)), are what I call semi-conventionalized reciprocal constructions. For example, consider (12) below:

- (12) *Each of the different possibilities is superimposed on the others...*⁹

⁹ from: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Formal_charge

In terms of meaning, the context of sentence (12) requires that it mean exactly the same as “The different possibilities are superimposed on each other” – that is to say, the semi-conventionalized reciprocal construction and the regular reciprocal construction have the same meaning. The symmetric event in (12) can be seen as being compositional in nature through the application of the quantifier “each” on the pronoun “others”. Nevertheless, this construction is conventionalised insofar as the symmetric interpretation comes about from interpreting “the others” as referring to “the other possibilities” rather than some other entities. I refer to constructions formed in this way as being formed via the compositional reciprocation strategy.

Like Evans, I use the word “reciprocal” to refer to a construction type. However, Evans (2008:35) does not use the phrase “reciprocal situations”, opting instead to use the terms “*mutual* situations”. I understand his use of “mutual” as an attempt to capture both the sense of symmetry that is associated with reciprocal constructions, and the sense that the participants in this relationship are usually both engaged together in the situation (see Evans, 2008:33,34 and footnotes – also chapter 4). The most important aspect of this definition though is the symmetric sense of the event. For an event to be symmetrical, I understand Evans to mean that most of the participants in the event exchange thematic roles with each other, so that in a sentence like “John and Mary love each other”, both John and Mary will be agents and patients:

“The thematic roles of the participants in these events are permuted, and as a result, there is a double linking of participants to thematic roles: each participant is linked to both thematic roles (John is both lover and beloved), and each thematic role is linked to both participants (the lover role is linked to both John and Mary).” Evans (2008:34)

However, this definition of symmetry maybe too narrow depending on whether the thematic roles which are exchanged must belong to the same predicate. I do not wish to exclude sentences from the definition of symmetry such as (13) below where each participant is no longer linked to both of the thematic roles selected by the verb:

(13) *John and Mary visited each other's parents.*

I will include these sorts of relations as symmetric events because although the participants in the relationship might not exchange roles as defined by the verb, there is still a high degree of symmetry. This can be seen by representing (13) as (14) below:

(14) *visit(John, parents_of(Mary))* and *visit(Mary, parents_of(John))*

In other words, the symmetry of (13) arises from the fact that they are in identical grammatical relationships with one another.¹⁰ It is possible that Evans would consider these types of situations as not being mutual, but in a category related to mutual situations. Evans notes that in the languages of the world it is not uncommon for some asymmetric situations to also be encoded using a reciprocal construction. For example, in English and many other languages the following situations, despite not being symmetrical, can be described using a reciprocal construction:

(15) “...a motorboat (a real one) comes in behind Bond and begins a pursuit... The boats chase each other through the canals, finally coming across a gondola occupied by two lovers.”¹¹

(16) Picture of 4 stones standing in a stack captioned: “Stones balanced on each other.”¹²

(17) *The last to enter the car is a tall man about forty, dressed in black. He leads four small boys, each holding the other's hands.*¹³

Note that in the film referred to in (15) has only one boat is chasing the other and in (16) the bottom stone is not balanced on another stone.

These additions to purely symmetric events mean that for many languages certain classes of asymmetric situations are conventionalised using reciprocal constructions as well. As these types of situations are so commonly associated with reciprocal

10 John and Mary in this example do exchange thematic roles (*e.g.*, John is an agent, Mary the possessor and *vice versa*), but the thematic role of possessor is not defined by the predicate.

11 <http://www.agonybooth.com/moonraker/default.asp?Page=4>

12 <http://www.bigstockphoto.com/photo/view/583078>

13 http://www.greatwardifferent.com/Great_War/Liege/Liege_02.htm

constructions, they need to be included as part of their corresponding semantic domain (which perhaps could be referred to as reciprocal semantics rather than symmetric or mutual semantics for this reason). I have no more to say on these asymmetric reciprocal events (such as chasing) – however, possessive reciprocal constructions such as those in (13) will feature in my analysis of Icelandic and are central to the analysis of Malagasy. As such, my definition of a reciprocal construction is broader in the specifics than that of Evans (2008), but at its heart, it is trying to capture the same semantic phenomena. And so, I define a reciprocal construction that is conventionalised to encode situations with a plurality of participants that exhibit some degree of symmetry; whether thematic (by an exchange of thematic roles), or spatial (for example where participants are, in a metaphorical or physical sense, mirrored).¹⁴

1.3 TYPOLOGIES OF RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTIONS

In order to address the lack of information about reciprocal constructions worldwide, over the last few years a number of projects, whose purpose is to provide basic typological information on reciprocal constructions, have been undertaken and are now coming to fruition. The largest of these so far completed is the recently published "Reciprocal Constructions" edited by Vladimir Nedjalkov (2007). This five volume work undertakes a survey of the reciprocal constructions of forty languages and Nedjalkov uses this data to identify features relevant for the creation of a typology of reciprocal constructions. The recently published "Reciprocals and reflexives: theoretical and typological explorations" is another typology of reciprocal constructions edited by Ekkehard König and Volker Gast (2008), which also collected data on many languages with a view to creating a reciprocal typology. This book contains a comprehensive article by Evans introducing the typology of reciprocal constructions from a structural point of view. This article is important not only for its research into the syntactic structure of the various reciprocal constructions examined, but also because it includes a discussion on the logically possible ways symmetric situations could be encoded – but which are not seen in the world's languages. Another project being run as a

14 An illustrative example of this spatial symmetry occurs when hands are placed together. The following is from the Urban Dictionary (<http://www.urbandictionary.com>) and describes "the awkward turtle" as "A motion performed by stacking one's hands on top of one another, extending the thumbs and rotating the thumbs slowly. Performed after a friend has said/done something awkward, either to ease the tension or further humiliate the friend."

collaboration between the Utrecht institute of Linguistics OTS and the Free University of Berlin called “A typology of reciprocal markers: analysis and documentation”¹⁵ focuses on structural features and is still under way but has collected data on the reciprocal constructions of 65 languages. The ultimate goal of this project is to be able to understand various features of reciprocal constructions both specific to a language and also in a cross-linguistic context. This project is considerable in scale and the first stage (collection of data) is expected to be completed by the start of 2012. Finally, an edited volume by Evans, Gaby, Levinson & Majid (2011) explores reciprocal constructions from a semantic point of view by surveying the types of situations encoded using a reciprocal construction in twenty languages.

As more and more data has become available, the criteria by which the constructions are classified has evolved. For example, Kemmer (1993) chose to classify reciprocal constructions according to a heavy or light system of marking that had relevance to two classes of reciprocal situations:

- Reciprocal proper (associated with heavy marking)
- Naturally reciprocal events (associated with light marking)

Naturally reciprocal events are ones like “kissing” or “quarreling”. They generally occur with verbs related to the interaction between people or objects where the action described is inherently reciprocal. Reciprocal proper events are those situations that would not express a reciprocal situation without the use of overt marking. For example, in (18b) below, if “each other” is omitted, there is no sense that Rakoto and Mary might be seeing each other. This is not the case when using a verb that describes a naturally reciprocal event such as “kiss”:

(18) Reciprocal proper:

- a. *Rakoto and Mary saw each other.*
- b. **Rakoto and Mary saw.*

(19) Natural reciprocal event (referred to as intrinsically symmetric):

- a. *Rakoto and Mary kissed each other.*
- b. *Rakoto and Mary kissed.*

15 <http://languagelink.let.uu.nl/burs/>

By examining reciprocal constructions in several languages, Kemmer noted that naturally occurring reciprocal events will typically attract “light reciprocal” marking, while reciprocals proper will be heavily marked (Kemmer, 1993:103). Light and heavy marking refers to the relative number of phonological segments used to create the reciprocal marker. For example, this situation is seen in English if we allow (as Kemmer does) that light marking may include no overt marking at all. Thus, in (19b) above, “kissed” does not require a reciprocal marker to indicate the reciprocity that is intrinsic to the situation described – and so is lightly marked. Kemmer also identified other properties that pattern with semantic differences between naturally reciprocal events and reciprocals proper. She groups these properties under the continuum of “elaboration of events” (Kemmer, 1993:97). In particular, the naturally reciprocal events have a low elaboration of events – they are strongly associated with simultaneity of action and participants cannot be contrasted. Proper reciprocals, on the other hand, are temporally indifferent and are better able to emphasise contrast. For example, Kemmer argues to create a contrast with a naturally symmetric verb (such as *fight* in (20)), the use of a heavy reciprocal marker is preferred:

(20) Kemmer (1993:115)

*The boys fought **each other**, not the girls.*

As we will see, the approach that Nedjalkov (2007) and Evans (2008) take is more heavily influenced by the syntactic properties of the reciprocal constructions. After studying reciprocal constructions in a variety of languages, Nedjalkov (2007:8) identifies two main types of reciprocal constructions with several subcategories. In the following paragraphs, I examine his work, and compare it with Evans' in order to frame my investigation of reciprocal constructions and grammatical functions within the current research into the typology of reciprocal constructions more generally. I will defer a discussion on the semantic aspects of these constructions to section 1.4 below.

For the most part, I will be commenting on the similarities and differences between their two works – Nedjalkov's “Overview of the Research” as it appears in his edited volumes (Nedjalkov, 2007:6-114), and Evans' (2008) “Reciprocal constructions: towards a structural typology” which forms the introductory chapter of König and Gast's (2008) own edited volume.

The first division Nedjalkov makes in his typology is between *grammatical* and *lexical* reciprocals. Grammatical reciprocals (alternatively called derived reciprocals) are those reciprocal constructions that are formed from some sort of overt marking – whether that be with the use of a pronoun, a verbal affix or by some other means. As they are derived, this means that all grammatical reciprocals have an underlying non-symmetric base from which they are formed. For example, in Malagasy the reciprocal verbal affix (-*if-*) turns the non-symmetric predicate *nandaka* – 'kick' into symmetric one *nifandaka* – 'kick each other':

(21) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:47)

a. *N-an-daka an-dRabe Rakoto.*

PST-ACT-kick ACC.Rabe Rakoto

V O S

“Rakoto kicked Rabe.”

b. *N-if-an-daka Rabe sy Rakoto.*

PST-REC-ACT-kick Rabe and Rakoto

V S

“Rabe and Rakoto kicked each other.”

For prototypical grammatical reciprocal constructions, Nedjalkov (2007:10) notes that the derived constructions enter into semantic opposition with their base verb (that is to say, both the symmetric and non-symmetric meanings are available to speakers) and that the base verb must describe a situation with at least two participants. Of the derived reciprocal constructions, Nedjalkov introduces a further two divisions between those formed from one predicate, and those formed from two predicates. Nedjalkov includes those events formed from two predicates “with the concomitant inversion of the arguments” (Nedjalkov, 2007:11) which are explicit statements of a symmetric event. For example:

(22) Nedjalkov (2007:151)

*Miranda **stared** at him and he **stared** back (at her).*

We saw in section 1.2 that Evans (2008:35) requires that a reciprocal construction must also be non-compositional. Therefore although these sentences do describe a symmetric situation, they do not constitute reciprocal constructions according to Evans' definition. Note however, that both researchers do discuss constructions where the boundaries between single and bi-clausal constructions are harder to determine. Evans observes:

... clause fusion can make it difficult to decide whether we are dealing with one predicate or two: should the Japanese construction *V-au* (literally 'V meet') for 'V each other' be treated as a multiple predicate 'V, meeting', or as involving a predicate affix which happens to be of verbal origin (*i.e.* *-au* would now be analysed as a reciprocal suffix to the verb that happens to be etymologically related to the verb 'meet'), or as some intermediate category, which is the way I have treated it here. (Evans, 2008:45)

The next sub-classifications Nedjalkov makes are with respect to mono-clausal derived reciprocal constructions. He identifies several possible ways a reciprocal construction maybe indicated using a verb and some component:

Syntactically using:

- some sort of noun/pronoun (the analysis he uses for English)
- reciprocal adverbs of various varieties (*e.g.*, *mutually*)

Morphologically using:

- verbal affixation
- verbal reduplication

Clitic reciprocals

Figure 1.1 Classification of mono-clausal reciprocal constructions

Even on initial inspection, it is clear that the boundaries between these categories can become blurred, if for no other reason that many of these constructions will be related historically. For example, it is possible that some reciprocal constructions formed from root reduplication found their origins as bi-clausal reciprocal constructions.¹⁶

As opposed to derived reciprocal constructions, Nedjalkov identifies lexical reciprocal constructions. A lexical reciprocal is one whose symmetric meaning is inherent to the base from which it is formed (a reciprocation strategy which I call intrinsic here). That is to say, unlike grammatical reciprocals, a lexical reciprocal cannot be broken down into a non-symmetric base which is modified to give the symmetric meaning. More broadly, Nedjalkov's overall typology of lexical versus derived reciprocal constructions is very similar to Kemmer's classification of heavy versus light reciprocal constructions. For example:

Example	Kemmer (1993)	Nedjalkov (2007)
<i>Rakoto and Mary saw each other.</i> vs. <i>*Rakoto and Mary saw.</i>	Reciprocal Proper Event – heavily marked with pronoun <i>each other</i>	Derived Reciprocal (namely syntactic construction formed with pronoun <i>each other</i>)
<i>Rakoto and Mary kissed.</i>	A naturally reciprocal event – lightly marked (in this case, zero marked)	Lexical Reciprocal

Table 1.1 Comparison of Nedjalkov and Kemmer's typologies

Ultimately, Nedjalkov keeps the semantic distinction that Kemmer makes implicitly between naturally reciprocal events (*i.e.*, those events which do not have as their root a non-symmetric base) and proper reciprocal events (*i.e.*, Nedjalkov's derived reciprocal constructions). However, he rejects the claim that this semantic distinction is always reflected by the weight of the phonetic material used in the reciprocal construction. For example, by their nature, verbal markers will usually be phonetically light when

¹⁶ For example, see discussion in Evans (2008:85)

compared to their pronominal counterparts. Nedjalkov identifies several languages all of which have reciprocal constructions that pose problems to Kemmer's typology (*e.g.*, German, Indonesian and others – see Nedjalkov, 2007:13,455 for discussion). Nevertheless, it is notable that Kemmer's classification and linkage of the weight of reciprocal constructions to their origin as being either derived or lexical is very much in line with Nedjalkov's later work.

Within this typology of reciprocal constructions, both Evans and Nedjalkov further distinguish a difference between simple and dyadic reciprocal constructions. A simple reciprocal construction is one where the participants taking part in the symmetric situation are expressed in a single NP (typically the subject – see Nedjalkov, 2007:27). As mentioned previously, one of the interesting questions these reciprocal constructions raise is how to interpret the thematic roles of the NP – can the subject NP of a simple reciprocal construction be said to have two thematic roles? To do so violates the theta criterion which states that “Each argument bears one and only one θ -role and each θ -role is assigned to one and only one argument” (Chomsky, 1981:36) – yet this is essentially the analysis Alsina (1996) proposes for reciprocal constructions in the Romance languages.

Contrasted to simple reciprocal constructions are dyadic reciprocal constructions where participants engaged in the symmetric situation appear in more than one grammatical function. For example, in Chicheŵa, the participants in the reciprocal relation can appear in the subject and oblique grammatical functions:

(23) Chicheŵa (Mchombo, 1991:4)

Nkhandwe zi-ku-mény-án-á ndí mbidzi.

10:foxes SM-PRES-hit-REC-FV COM 10:zebras

“Foxes and zebras are hitting each other.”

Dyadic reciprocal constructions pose their own problems with respect to thematic role assignment. They have been analysed as changing the mapping between the thematic arguments selected by the verb and the grammatical functions (for example, see Mchombo, 1991; Dalrymple *et al*, 1994). However the analysis I put forward in chapter 5 for the dyadic construction (or sometimes called discontinuous construction in the literature) in Swahili is that the reciprocated predicate gains an additional argument

when compared with its monadic counterpart.

More generally, reciprocal constructions are often polysemous with sociative, comitative and assistive constructions. For the most part these constructions do not form a central part of this thesis – for an extensive discussion see Evans (2008), and Nedjalkov (2007:32-40) and Maslova (1999). This polysemy is illustrated in English where comitative constructions can be re-construed using a reciprocal construction. For example, both the comitative construction in (24b) below and its reciprocated equivalent in (24c) are fairly tight paraphrases of (24a):¹⁷

- (24) a. *Gunnar and Kolskegg stood on the deck of the ship.*
 b. *Gunnar stood with Kolskegg on the deck of the ship.*
 c. *Gunnar and Kolskegg stood with each other on the deck of the ship.*

Gunnar and Kolskegg in (24) are in a spatial relationship – and any two entities in a spatial relationship can be thought of as being in a symmetric relationship, and hence encoded using a reciprocal construction. Note though that there is a fundamental difference between this spatially symmetric interpretation of an event (which is, in principle, available to all semantically appropriate predicates) and symmetry which is based upon the exchange of those thematic roles defined by the predicate. For example, in (25) the symmetry between Gunnar and Kolskegg is related to an exchange of thematic roles rather than a spatial symmetry:

- (25) *Gunnar and Kolskegg hunted each other.*

Evans uses this idea of non-thematic symmetry in his discussion of non-symmetric events encoded using reciprocal constructions. He observes that, as well as certain construction types being typically associated with reciprocity in the world's languages, there are certain non-symmetric semantic situations which, time and time again, can be described using a reciprocal construction. Evans (2008) gives the example of Mary and John running down the road (with John always behind Mary) being described by “John and Mary chased each other down the road” – a reciprocal construction being formed

¹⁷ Comitative phrases are instrumental in the analysis of the dyadic construction in chapter 5.

from a special class of verbs Nedjalkov calls *converse base*.¹⁸ A converse base is one which has two underlying constructions describing two participants in a converse semantic (spatial or temporal) relation. For example, *chase* above requires someone *to follow* and someone *to precede*. Nedjalkov (2007:46) observes that “Reciprocals derived from converse bases are as a rule marked in the same way as proper reciprocals, although there are no prototypical relations between the participants”. These observations by Evans and Nedjalkov have implications for how the semantics of reciprocal constructions should be understood. There is a strong motivation amongst transformational grammarians (*e.g.*, Heim *et al.*, 1991a,b) to describe reciprocal constructions in English as being derived from a compositional construction through movement. For example, the reciprocal pronoun in (26a) can be understood as being formed from the movement of *each* from the subject NP in (26b):

- (26) a. *The vikings saw each other.*
b. *Each viking saw the other.*

Such an analysis is attractive because the reciprocal meaning of (26a) could be said to arise compositionally from the interaction of the distributive pronoun with the pronoun 'other'. However, it is not at all clear how such a compositional analysis could ever describe the semantics associated with reciprocal constructions formed from converse bases such as in (27) and (28) below:

- (26) French (Nedjalkov, 2007:47)
Les deux compagnies se suivaient à une certaine de pas.
The two companies followed one after the other at a distance of 100 paces.
- (27) Nunggubuyu (Heath, 1984:391)
=*lhama-n'ji-*
“to beget each other”

Nedjalkov's typological work reveals that there is a tendency for the world's languages

18 English speakers, when asked about the felicity of such a sentence, overwhelmingly reject it. Nevertheless, its usage is widespread both in English, and also other languages (*e.g.*, see Nedjalkov 2007 and the discussion of converse bases there).

to describe asymmetric converse bases with a reciprocal construction, so perhaps these situations should be considered as part of reciprocal semantics. I will argue below (see section 1.4) that a better analysis of the semantics of many reciprocal constructions is along of the lines of Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) who use a reciprocal operator (RECIP) to indicate that two entities and a relation should be considered as being a reciprocal situation:

(29) $RECIP(they, \lambda x.\lambda y.follow(x,y))$

This formalism separates the logic of symmetry entailed by a symmetric situation from the verbal predicate. The RECIP operator they define could then be extended to include situations that are not strictly symmetric, such as those associated with converse bases above such as (27) and (28).

Finally, both Evans and Nedjalkov discuss the effect reciprocal constructions have upon valency. For example, a simple verbal reciprocal construction (*i.e.*, one that gathers the participants into a single NP), like sociative constructions, would usually be analysed as having its valency decreased (see Nedjalkov, 2007:40), although certainly there are exceptions. For example, Evans (2005:39) points out that Xaragure has a verbal reciprocal marker, but clearly no change in the resulting transitivity, as shown by the presence of two plural pronouns in the reciprocal construction:

(30) Xaragure (Moyses-Faurie 2004)

a. *nyärä pu-kégai nyärä.*
 3PL REC-pinch 3PL
 “They are pinching each other.”

b. *nyärä kégai nyärä.*
 3PL pinch 3PL
 “They pinch them.”

I will return to the issue of the valency of verbal reciprocal constructions in detail when examining Malagasy in chapter 3 where I argue that this verbal reciprocal construction, despite having an apparent change in valency, in fact remains syntactically transitive.

The issue of valency and reciprocal constructions has also been explored extensively by Evans, Gaby & Nordlinger (2007) who found that reciprocal constructions can often give mixed signals with respect to their valency. For example, in Kuuk Thaayorre, a seemingly intransitive clause contains ergative case marking on the subject of the reciprocal construction (ergative marking elsewhere only occurs with transitive clauses):

(31) Kuuk Thaayorre (Evans, Gaby & Nordlinger 2007:19)

parr-n peln ii waarin-rr.

kid-ERG 3PL.ERG there chase-REC

“All the kids are chasing each other.”

Sentence (31) demonstrates the uncomfortable relationship reciprocal constructions have with transitivity and understanding why this relationship exists is one issue this thesis addresses (see comments in section 1.1, also chapters 3 and 6).

I have highlighted the major typological issues with respect to the world's reciprocal constructions. Reciprocal constructions can be marked in any number of ways (*e.g.*, verbally via the application of morphology or a clitic, phrasally via a reciprocal pronoun or nominal *etc.*). However, with the exception of the dyadic reciprocal constructions, all the participants of the symmetric event are overwhelmingly gathered together into a single grammatical function (prototypically, the NP functioning as subject). Alongside this research into the structural typology of reciprocal constructions, there has been much work on their associated semantics. In section 1.4 below I explain how this research has affected our understanding of just what situations are described using reciprocal constructions and hence, exactly what constitutes reciprocal semantics and how this semantics should be analysed within a formal framework.

1.4 RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTIONS AND RECIPROCAL SEMANTICS

This thesis is primarily concerned with the syntax of reciprocal constructions rather than their semantics. However, as we will see, there is often a relationship between a reciprocal construction's reciprocation strategy and its resultant semantic behaviour so

in this section I will outline the development of the current theories of reciprocal semantics, as they apply to my research.

The study of reciprocal semantics encompasses two key domains. The first is what sort of situations should be thought of as being part of the logic of reciprocity – and how are they related. To answer this question, different approaches have been taken; Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) for example, identify the logically possible distinct types of symmetry and discuss the relationships between them. Alternatively, if we could identify a construction that is used to express prototypical symmetric situations in various languages and then, from a cross-linguistic perspective, study the types of situations it is used to encode we could study what constitutes the semantics of symmetry from a different perspective. This is the aim of the edited volume by Evans, Gaby, Levinson & Majid (2011), who find that the situations encoded by reciprocal constructions commonly extend beyond those that are simply prototypically symmetric to chaining situations as well as certain asymmetric events (such as chasing). They also stress the importance of viewing reciprocity as being based in the social sphere related to relationships, gift giving and trade (for example, see König, 2011). Interestingly, they find a strong family resemblance in the sorts of situations encoded by a reciprocal construction from language to language, but note that many of the specific classifications of symmetric situations identified below do not arise as part of a linguistic universal, but rather are the result of “a recurrent but not inevitable chain of polysemies” (Evans *et al.* 2011:23).

The second domain of study revolves around the mechanisms by which reciprocal constructions are formed. Typically the major distinction has been between argument and verbal reciprocals. An argument reciprocal is one where the verb's number of “arguments” does not change when it is reciprocated whereas verbal reciprocals are those whose expression is formed via a morpheme applied to the verb.¹⁹ The argument based analysis of reciprocal semantics finds its origins in trying to understand the English reciprocal pronoun “each other”.

In section 1.4.1 below, I show how theorists have (for the most part) moved from a semantically formal understanding of *each other* as being formed compositionally from the application of *each* to *other* (e.g., Heim, Lasnik & May, 1991a,b), to an operator

¹⁹ Note that use of “argument” here would typically refer to an NP or PP sub-categorised by the verb. LFG offers a more precise, and useful, definition of this term – see section 1.5 below, and chapter 3.

based understanding using a reciprocal quantifier which allows for a more general understanding of symmetry (e.g., Dalrymple *et al.* 1998, also see discussion in Asudeh, 1998). The second approach examined in section 1.4.2 is situated around reciprocal constructions that are formed from the verb (either through the application of reciprocal morphology or a clitic). These approaches also started by being closely tied to the syntax of the reciprocal construction as either: being formed from two arguments mapping to one grammatical function (e.g., Alsina, 1996); or through the synthesis of two thematic roles (my interpretation of Siloni, 2011). In this section, I will briefly review the literature on the semantics of reciprocity, discussing the major issues in the topic and identifying those areas that are going to be relevant more generally to the syntax of reciprocal constructions.

1.4.1 Reciprocal semantics and the English reciprocal construction

The first issue that any research on reciprocal constructions must grapple with is what exactly is reciprocal semantics? That is to say, which situations would we want to say are part of the logic of reciprocity, which situations are related to it, and which have nothing to do with it? To begin, note that the semantics involved in situations described by reciprocal constructions can be surprisingly complex – although the semantics of prototypical examples is straightforward. Consider (32) below:

(32) *Mary and John love each other.*

The phrase “each other” in example (32) is used to describe a situation where each participant shares the same relationship with every other participant in the group. Langendoen (1973:179) describes sentences like (32) above as having the property of “Strong Reciprocity” – this means that every entity in some set (*i.e.*, Mary and John in the set above) engages in a relation (that of *love* in the example above) with every other entity, but never themselves. Formally, he defines strong reciprocity as (33) below (modified to reflect the notation used in this thesis):

(33) $(\forall x, y \in A)(x \neq y \rightarrow R(x, y))$

In English, the formalism above says that for some group of entities (called set A –

Mary and John in (32) above), every one of those entities will be in a relationship (e.g., love in (32) above) with every other one of those entities (and optionally with themselves). Langendoen's definition of strong reciprocity gives the correct truth conditions for strongly symmetric situations like (32) above with the following propositions which match our real world understanding of the event. So, for example, (33) when applied to "Mary and John love each other" gives:

$$(34) \quad \textit{love}(\textit{Mary}, \textit{John}) \wedge \textit{love}(\textit{John}, \textit{Mary})$$

Although this definition captures the truth conditions for any prototypical reciprocal event – on closer inspection, we find that the phrase "each other" is used in many semantically diverse situations – situations where the definition above does not hold. In fact, as we saw earlier, reciprocal constructions are commonly used to describe events that fall on a continuum from the strictly symmetrical (or strongly symmetric to use Langendoen's terminology) such as (35a) below, to the somewhat symmetrical (35b, 35c) and to the asymmetrical (35d, 35e):²⁰

- (35) a. *John and Mary visited each other.*
 b. Picture showing a pyramid of cups captioned: *Disposable glasses stacked on each other.*²¹
 c. *A **Bucket brigade** refers to a method of firefighting ... whereby firefighters would pass buckets to each other to extinguish a blaze.*²²
 d. *Two new screens will be housed on top of each other ...*²³
 e. *...a motorboat (a real one) comes in behind Bond and begins a pursuit... The boats chase each other through the canals, finally coming across a gondola occupied by two lovers.*²⁴

If the definition of reciprocity in (33) were applied to sentence (35d) it would give the

20 Note that although the examples above come from English, many other languages will use reciprocal constructions to describe similar non-prototypically "symmetrical events" (see Nedjalkov, 2007:46)

21 <http://www.inmagine.com/pan005/pan005066-photo>

22 http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bucket_brigade (27/10/2009)

23 http://www.bbc.co.uk/tyne/content/image_galleries/tyneside_cinema_redevelopment_gallery.shtml?17

24 <http://www.agonybooth.com/moonraker/default.asp?Page=4> (27/11/06)

following propositions:

$$(36) \quad \textit{housed_on_top_of}(\textit{screen}_1, \textit{screen}_2) \wedge \textit{housed_on_top_of}(\textit{screen}_2, \textit{screen}_1)$$

However, the correct proposition for a situation like (35d) must be that of (37) below:²⁵

$$(37) \quad \textit{housed_on_top_of}(\textit{screen}_1, \textit{screen}_2) \wedge \neg \textit{housed_on_top_of}(\textit{screen}_2, \textit{screen}_1)$$

That is to say, only one screen can actually be housed on top of the other screen. Formal linguists are well aware of these problems and have tried to address them in different ways. Fiengo and Lasnik (1973) for example allow only two types of reciprocal semantics, *each-the-other* relationships and *each other* relationships (see Fiengo and Lasnik, 1973:39, 13-16). The *each-the-other* relationship is simply the strong reciprocal relationship defined above.²⁶ However, the *each other* relationship is more complex – it also describes situations where the set of entities within the reciprocal relation can be divided into subsets, each of which is engaged in a strong reciprocal relation. Take for example a situation where the Chinese and British Olympic teams are competing in a ping pong tournament, in which there are many tables with two players each. This would be an *each other* relationship only if it were described as “the Chinese and British teams are competing against each other”. Following Langendoen (1978), I will refer to Fiengo and Lasnik's *each other* relationship as “partitioned strong reciprocity”. Fiengo and Lasnik then attempt to address the question of how a listener knows which type of reciprocal semantics is used (*i.e.*, *strong reciprocity* vs *partitioned strong reciprocity*). They do this by claiming that stative predicates are not able to engage in *partitioned strong reciprocity* relationships.²⁷

Examples such as (35b) and (35c) above do not fit into either of Fiengo and Lasnik's definitions of reciprocal relations. They do discuss these types of relationships, naming them “linear configurational”. Although they formally define the relationship

25 Sentences like (35d) where stacks of two objects are described using a reciprocal construction abound in English. Many factors influence the acceptability of a reciprocal construction in sentences like these – one of which is the similarity of the participants. Contrast the acceptability of the following two sentences: “I left two sacks of flour piled on top of each other in the kitchen” with “I left a sack of flour and a can of beans piled on top of each other in the kitchen”.

26 “Each man saw the other” exemplifies an *each-the-other* construction.

27 Langendoen (1978:182, footnote 10) provides a counterexample originally cited in Chomsky (1975,150): “John's grandparents hate one another”. Clearly this relationship doesn't have to be strongly reciprocal, and could be interpreted as an example of partitioned strong reciprocity, yet it does use a stative predicate.

between the entities for examples such as (35c), they reject these types of situations as being part of reciprocal semantics saying “...when a reciprocal sentence is used to describe a linear configuration, there is not real reciprocity, in the sense we have defined it.” (Fiengo and Lasnik, 1973:44).

Heim *et al.* (1991a,b) demonstrate that the *each-the-other* relationship identified by Fiengo and Lasnik can be understood as arising from the compositional application of the operator *each* as applied to the appropriately defined pronoun *other* (*i.e.*, it is an instance of the compositional reciprocation strategy). By treating *each* as quantifying an antecedent in logical structure, they predict that the truth conditions associated with a reciprocal construction should be that of strong reciprocity (see (33) above). This analysis has the advantage of anchoring the semantics of reciprocal constructions in a predictable manner to the interaction of *each* and *other*. Furthermore, by treating *each* as belonging to the antecedent in logical structure, they can use the same analysis for regular “each other” constructions. However, it suffers from the same problems Fiengo and Lasnik encountered – reciprocal constructions are commonly used to describe situations that are not strongly reciprocal.²⁸

This brings us back to the central question of reciprocal semantics – which situations would we want to say are part of the logic of reciprocity, which situations are related to it, and which have nothing to do with it? Excluding linear configurations (or chaining situations) from the logic of reciprocal semantics would be straightforward if English were the only language to use a reciprocal construction to describe such events. But, many languages use reciprocal constructions to describe just these situations – *e.g.*, Lichtenberk (1985:25-26) gives examples of six languages that represent chaining using a reciprocal construction, namely English, Japanese, Manam, Menomini, Zulu and Hungarian and several more are identified in Evans *et al.* (2011).

Langendoen (1978) attempts to address this issue by defining another four schematisations for the truth conditions of reciprocal constructions – with the goal of

28 Hurst & Nordlinger (2011) survey the use of reciprocal constructions by speakers to describe a variety of situations – and their findings support Fiengo and Lasnik's (1973) that *each-the-other* constructions describe strongly symmetric events. However, although this might typically be the case, there are many exceptions, *e.g.*, “American nurse Helen Boylston wrote of the lines of men staggering back from the front, eight or 20 blind boys each leading the other.” (The Sydney Morning Herald - Apr 22, 1984). Furthermore, a compositional reciprocal construction was the main means by which symmetry was expressed in Old Icelandic – yet the range of situations expressed was not limited to strong reciprocity encompassing *mêlée* and intermediate reciprocity as well (see appendix C, section c, examples 5, 15 and 16).

finding a single set of truth conditions that can describe the semantics associated with all reciprocal constructions. These more complex definitions capture the truth conditions for other events that are commonly encoded using a reciprocal construction in the world's languages. One of these schematisations (what Langendoen calls *weak reciprocity* – see (38) below) is broad enough to capture the chaining situations above.²⁹

(38) Weak Reciprocity (WR) – from Langendoen (1978:179), notation standardised

$$(\forall x \in A)(\exists y, z \in A)(x \neq y \wedge x \neq z \wedge R(x, y) \wedge R(z, x))$$

The sense of (38) is that if we have a set of entities in a relation R (of passing something for example), then for every entity in the set of participants the following is true: if *e* is an entity, then it will pass something to someone, and will have had someone pass something to it. Note that the definition of weak reciprocity is a generalized instance of all the other types of reciprocal semantics – that is as well as being able to describe situations such as chaining, it is also compatible with other situations such as strong reciprocity and partitioned strong reciprocity. Implicitly then, Langendoen is seeking to include situations such as chaining as part of the logic of reciprocity. In fact, Langendoen analyses all sentences with the phrase “each other” / “one another” (what he calls “elementary reciprocal sentences”) as contributing to the logic of reciprocity.

In trying to describe a set of truth conditions that can capture the semantics of nearly all elementary reciprocal sentences (*i.e.*, those sentences containing *each other* in English), Langendoen considers the relation of reciprocal semantics to the logic of plurality.³⁰ He begins by noting that reciprocal relations are really just a special case of plural relations. Langendoen makes the following definitions:

(39)

a. Elementary plural relational sentence (EPRS) (Langendoen 1978:184)

A R B (*i.e.*, the men (=A) saw the horses (=B))

where A, B are sets containing at least two entities

29 Although it provides no insights into why sentences like (35d) and (35e) can be described by a reciprocal construction. For although his description can accommodate chains, in both (35 d,e) there is an entity which does not act upon any other entity.

30 Sentences such as (35e) above which also use a reciprocal construction are not captured by any of the schematizations Langendoen describes. This is one of the motivations for a new description of reciprocal semantics - see discussion below.

b. Elementary reciprocal sentences (ERS)

A R r (e.g., the men saw each other)

where r is the reciprocal element (e.g., each other, one another)

Langendoen (1978:185) argues that the truth conditions for elementary plural relational sentences are given by:

$$(40) \quad (\forall x \in A)(\exists y \in B)(R(x, y)) \wedge (\forall w \in B)(\exists x \in A)(R(z, w))$$

The definition above can be understood as making the following claim about the semantics of EPRS's: "Each member of set A must bear the relation R to some member of set B. And each member of set B must have the relation R borne to it by some member of the set A." Langendoen (1978:185). I have illustrated the intent of (40) above using three figures below:

Table 1.2 Illustration of truth conditions for elementary plural relational sentences

The final diagram is not consistent with (40) because not *every* element of A sees some element of B. As part of his discussion, Langendoen raises the possibility of using EPRS's in contexts which are not described by the schematization above. For example, talking of sentence (41) below, Langendoen notes that this sentence could be used to describe a situation where "one woman in the set denoted by *the women* was not involved in releasing the prisoners at all." Langendoen (1978:185):

(41) Langendoen (1978:185)

The women released the prisoners.

The schematisation given in (41) above cannot capture the truth conditions of these types of situations. As a result, Langendoen (1978:185) notes that the truth of (41) is not literally being asserted – that is to say, the truth of the assertion in (41) needs to be pragmatically weakened in order to capture the reality of the situation. Langendoen then uses the definition for the truth conditions of EPRS in (40) above to shed light on reciprocal semantics by noting that in a reciprocal situation, *r* (in (39b) above) is taken to be identical to set A (*i.e.*, in the examples above, this just means that set A is the same set B). Therefore (40) can be rewritten as:

(42) Langendoen (1978:186)

$$(\forall x \in A)(\exists y, z \in A)(R(x, y) \wedge R(z, x))$$

By including the constraints associated with a reciprocal construction (that is, that each entity engages in a relation with another entity), (40) can be rewritten as (43). This is important because (43) below is exactly the definition given in (38) for weak reciprocity which was formulated purely as a description of various events associated with the reciprocal construction:

$$(43) \quad (\forall x \in A)(\exists y, z \in A)(x \neq y \wedge x \neq z \wedge R(x, y) \wedge R(z, x))$$

This argument is interesting not only from the perspective of showing how a very general form of reciprocal semantics can be derived from the logic of plural semantics with appropriate constraints, but also because it introduces into the discourse the notion of imprecision or non-literal usage of sentences – a concept which Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) discuss at length in their paper “Reciprocal expressions and the concept of reciprocity”.

Dalrymple *et al.* (1998:167) identify both pragmatic weakening and pragmatic strengthening as possible means by which some (but not all) reciprocal statements may be used to describe situations that are not strictly symmetric. Pragmatic weakening of a reciprocal statement (that is, a “loose interpretation” of it) occurs when the finer details

of a statement are irrelevant to its ultimate truth value. For example, the sentence “The starving dogs ate each other” cannot logically represent a strong reciprocal situation under a strict interpretation of reciprocity. Nevertheless, a reciprocal construction is used in this sentence because the fact that one dog was not completely eaten is an unimportant detail to the speaker and hearer.

In their discussion of pragmatic weakening, Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) argue that all instances of partitioned strong reciprocity (as defined by Langendoen, 1978 and Fiengo and Lasnik, 1973) are in fact pragmatically weakened strong reciprocity. For example, a pragmatically weakened interpretation of (44) means that not every man must hit every other man:

(44) Dalrymple *et al.* (1998:167)

The men were hitting each other.

They note that, in its strict sense, this sentence is interpreted as being strongly reciprocal (and this becomes evident when considering smaller groups such as “The four men were hitting each other”). However, Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) conclude that pragmatic strengthening or weakening cannot account for the truth conditions of all situations described by a reciprocal construction. For example, Intermediate Reciprocity (the truth conditions associated with chains) cannot be an instance of pragmatically weakened strong reciprocity:

(45) Dalrymple *et al.* (1998:185)

The freeway exits are spaced five miles from each other.

The difficulty here is that the truth conditions behind (45) cannot be understood by varying the saturation of the quantification over the individuals within the set, because the required quantification needs to be over *pairs* of individuals. Having shown that pragmatic strengthening of weak reciprocity or pragmatic weakening of strong reciprocity cannot account for the logic of all reciprocal situations, Dalrymple *et al.* (1998:186) proceed to parametrize the differences between the various definitions of reciprocity. They ultimately identify six possible, non-equivalent, types of reciprocal semantics. These definitions form a hierarchy, with Strong Reciprocity at the top –

entailing all other types of reciprocal semantics and Inclusive Alternative Ordering at the bottom (e.g., one way chains such as “the coins were stacked on top of each other”):

Figure 1.2 Reciprocity hierarchy – adapted from Dalrymple *et al.* (1998)³¹

Dalrymple *et al.* (1998:189) then show that under certain conditions, such as a relation being intrinsically symmetric, some of these definitions of reciprocity are equivalent. These six types of reciprocity are associated with a quantifier called RECIP. Its quantifier nature is demonstrated by its ability to change scope – thus (46) below has two readings (though only the (b) reading where each person thinks that he is taller than the others is sensible):

(46) Dalrymple *et al.* (1998:183)

Tom, Dick and Harry think they are taller than each other.

- a. think({T,D,H}, RECIP({T,D,H}, λxy.taller(x,y)))
= “Tom, Dick and Harry think 'we are taller than each other'”

³¹ Examples are paraphrased from Dalrymple *et al.* (1998). Note that Beck (2001) argues that intermediate alternative reciprocity is not part of the logic of reciprocity and so does not include them as part of survey of reciprocal sentences. In other respects, her list of interpretations follows figure 1.2 above.

- b. $\text{RECIP}(\{T,D,H\}, \lambda xy.\text{think}(x,\text{taller}(x,y)))$
 = “Each of Tom, Dick and Harry thinks he is taller than the others”

Having argued that *each other* is a quantifier, the final question Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) address is how hearers know which type of reciprocal semantics should be applied in any particular instance – that is to say, which one of the six types of reciprocal situations defined in figure 1.2 should be used for in any particular instance. To do this, they define a procedure called the Strongest Meaning Hypothesis – SMH (Dalrymple *et al.* 1998:193). To paraphrase their definition, this procedure states that the strongest definition of reciprocity (*i.e.*, the definition that is highest in the entailment hierarchy in figure 1.2) should be used that is consistent with the hearer's knowledge of the event. To illustrate the SMH, consider the following example from Dalrymple *et al.* (1998:193-194):

- (47) Dalrymple *et al.* 1998:194
 The children followed each other into the church.

Because the relation between the children (*follow into the church*) is asymmetric, Strong Reciprocity must be rejected – and so the next strongest definition of reciprocity is considered. Ultimately, there are two possible definitions of reciprocity that could be applied to (47) above – depending on whether there is one, or more than one, door in the church. If there is more than one door, Inclusive Alternative Ordering (multiple one way chains) is used. If there is only one door, then the semantics associated with Intermediate Alternative Reciprocity (*e.g.*, a single one way chain) is used.

One construction type not discussed in detail in these papers is that of one-way asymmetric situations described using a reciprocal construction such as (35e) above (renumbered as (48) below):

- (48) “...a motorboat (a real one) comes in behind Bond and begins a pursuit... The boats chase each other through the canals, finally coming across a gondola occupied by two lovers.”

The existence of asymmetric events being described using a reciprocal construction provides another possible extension to reciprocal semantics. In this understanding of symmetry, the relationship between the participants is not so much described by the verb, but rather by its associated pragmatics. Perhaps the reciprocal interpretation above is possible because of the extent that Bond is an active participant in the situation described. That is to say, while Bond does not actually chase the motorboat, he is still an active participant in the state of affairs, constantly aware of the motorboat, trying his utmost to escape. In this way, a verb like *chase* can be seen as being metaphorically similar to the converse base verbs identified by Nedjalkov (2007).

This branch of the investigation into reciprocal semantics started by investigating just what events are encoded using reciprocal morphology, and what they have in common. Initial research in the area tried to answer this question by considering reciprocal semantics as being formed either compositionally, through the application of the quantifier *each* to the indefinite pronoun *other* (e.g., Heim *et al.* 1991a,b) or through the semantics of plurality with the caveat that no entities may engage in a relationship with themselves (e.g., Langendoen, 1978). However, Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) showed that the reciprocal construction in English was used to describe situations that could not be described by this analysis – even allowing for pragmatic weakening or strengthening. As such, they proposed a reciprocal operator RECIP that is applied to a proposition – and this operator, through the application of the strongest meaning hypothesis provides an account of the semantics of reciprocal constructions. In terms of reciprocation strategies, the analysis of these argument reciprocal constructions has changed from a compositional to an operator based strategy. In chapter 2 I will examine the Icelandic reciprocal construction and show that both strategies can coexist, even as one becomes more dominant.

1.4.2 Semantics and verbally marked reciprocal constructions

Above, I described work that arose from trying to understand what events should be described as symmetric. Ultimately, the analysis I follow for the Germanic languages is that put forward by Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) who argue for the existence of a reciprocal operator. However, within the area of verbally marked reciprocal constructions there are other ways of envisaging of the formation of symmetric events.

Alsina (1996) argues that the Romance reciprocal/reflexive clitic construction is

formed by two arguments in a-structure being mapped to a single grammatical function (this mechanism is called the argument unification reciprocation strategy here). In her discussion of reciprocal semantics, Siloni (2011) provides a compatible semantic interpretation of these constructions where a single grammatical function now carries two thematic roles. For example, in (49) below, Siloni maps both thematic roles of the verb *voir* – “see” to the subject NP “Jean et Marie”:

- (49) French (Siloni, 2011:23)
Jean et Marie se voient.
Jean and Marie_{RR} see
“Jean and Marie saw each other.”

Siloni (2011:24) notes that “Since each individual is assigned two distinct roles, the roles can be either associated with two distinct sub-events... or with the same sub-event, thus resulting in a reflexive interpretation.” This general notion of an inwardly directed event is exactly that which Gaby identifies for reciprocal/reflexive events in Kuuk Thaayorre (Gaby 2008:280):

“What distinguishes them [reciprocal/reflexive interpretations]... is the fact that each participant encoded as a reflexive subject is both Actor and Undergoer of the same subevent, whereas reciprocal subject participants are Actors and Undergoers of different subevents.”

Gaby and Siloni depart, though, in how they view the implications of this double thematic role mapping. Siloni provides a formula for determining which participant is mapped to which thematic role that is very similar to the formalism proposed by Langendoen above. Gaby, however, proposes a more general inwardly directed action whose specific properties (reflexive or reciprocal) are disambiguated by preceding context and background knowledge as well as various morphosyntactic cues (Gaby 2008:284). This approach has strong parallels to the development of the RECIP operator described above, one that also acknowledges that context is required to disambiguate different types of symmetry. When viewed from Gaby's perspective, an INWARD

operator might be an appropriate way of viewing these inwardly directed events. This INWARD operator would have the same functions as RECIP but also encapsulate the semantics of reflexives. As to which analysis is to be preferred, more data needs to be collected. However the view that reciprocal/reflexive semantics should be associated with a more abstract operator is given support when we consider that languages with very different reciprocal constructions (*e.g.*, phrasal and verbal) tend to express the same types of situations with reciprocal constructions. For example, Evans *et al.* (2011) examine the semantics of reciprocal constructions across 20 languages whose reciprocal constructions have a wide range of different morpho-syntactic expressions and conclude that reciprocal constructions, whether coded verbally or as arguments have very similar semantic properties (Evans *et al.* 2011:51). I think this point is best illustrated not by proto-typical or near proto-typical uses of reciprocal constructions, but rather, by examining the less obvious extensions to the logic of reciprocity. For example the asymmetric converse bases, which Nadjalkov (2007) identifies, are associated with reciprocal constructions time and time again in very diverse language groups, strongly implying that the semantics of reciprocal constructions are only loosely linked to their morphosyntactic expression:

(50) Kuuk Thaayorre (Gaby 2008:275)

pam-al ulp nhunh paanth ulp koorr waak-rr-ø nhul.
 man-ERG DEM.APRX 3SG.ACC woman.ACC DEM.APRX behind follow.REC.NPST 3SG.ERG
 “That man is following along behind that woman.”

(51) French (Nadjalkov 2007:47)

Les deux compagnies se suivaient à une certaine de pas.

The two companies followed one after the other at a distance of 100 paces.

Finally, symmetric semantics can be inferred using an altogether different mechanism in which an asymmetric lexeme becomes symmetric in its interpretation through the synthesis of two of its thematic roles (a reciprocation strategy I call theta-role synthesis). Siloni (2011) describes such a mechanism for lexical reciprocals and in chapter 4 I develop this mechanism in LFG and argue that it explains the highly productive process whereby asymmetric verbs take on a symmetric interpretation.

1.4.3 Concluding remarks

In this section I have examined key research on the logic of reciprocity. Fiengo and Lasnik (1973) defined two types of situations as being reciprocal situations (strong reciprocity and partitioned strong reciprocity) and rejected other situations which could be described with a reciprocal construction (such as one-way chaining) as not contributing to the logic of reciprocity. Langendoen (1978) argued that the stative/active distinction of verbs that Fiengo and Lasnik used to discriminate between strong reciprocity and partitioned strong reciprocity situations could not be maintained for all verbs. He examined a multitude of reciprocal sentences in English and presented a formal schemata that gave the correct truth conditions for six distinct reciprocal situations. He showed how the most general of these schemata (weak reciprocity – see (38) above) could be formulated from the semantics of plurality with appropriate constraints. Thus, he provided a theoretical account for why reciprocal constructions in English can be used to describe chaining situations as well as strongly symmetric situations. The work of Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) is important, because it provides a complete picture of how reciprocal semantics for English could be considered. Their analysis started by considering that reciprocal semantics can be pragmatically weakened or strengthened – and that these pragmatic effects can be used to describe some reciprocal situations which had been previously considered as distinct. For example, they consider Langendoen's Partitioned Strong Reciprocity to be pragmatically weakened Strong Reciprocity. However, they point out that pragmatic effects cannot account for the semantics of all reciprocal situations and so by parametrizing the differences between types of reciprocal situations (such as Strong Reciprocity and Weak Reciprocity) they arrive at six types of logically distinct reciprocity. These six types of reciprocity are then arranged on an entailment hierarchy (for example, the truth conditions associated with a strongly reciprocal situation will also include the truth conditions associated with one-way chain, but not vice versa). The most important contribution by Dalrymple *et al.* (1998) though is the Strongest Meaning Hypothesis (SMH) – a formalized procedure based upon their hierarchy of reciprocal semantics and a hearer's knowledge of the world which allows a hearer to determine which type of reciprocal semantics should be employed in any particular situation.

I will return to some of the concepts discussed here when examining the interaction

between reciprocal syntax and semantics in the following chapters and also in appendix A where I present fully worked examples of reciprocal sentences in LFG and how, formally, reciprocal semantics should be associated with them using the glue logic approach as presented in Dalrymple (2001).

1.5 LEXICAL FUNCTIONAL GRAMMAR

The theoretical framework used in this thesis is Lexical Functional Grammar (LFG) (Bresnan, 2001; Falk, 2001 and Dalrymple, 2001). Central to LFG is the idea that grammatical structure is best represented by a system of parallel structures. Each of these structures represents a different aspect of grammar and they are linked together by principles of correspondence. The key syntactic structures are c-structure (constituent structure), f-structure (functional structure) and a-structure (argument structure). C-structure encodes linear order and constituency and an understanding of the c-structure of a language helps identify phrasal dominance, phrasal positioning, adverb placement and so on. The f-structure represents both the grammatical functions of a clause and the relations between the grammatical functions through the use of argument structure. A-structure encodes the thematic roles associated with various predicates. Usually, the a-structure of a predicate does not change, rather, its various thematic roles are mapped (or suppressed – see chapter 2) to various arguments in the f-structure via a set of mapping principles known as Lexical Mapping Theory (LMT). However, in some situations, the a-structure of a predicate can be fundamentally changed (as for example in the case of morphologically formed causative constructions).

There are several advantages of LFG over transformational theories of syntax. I will discuss some here to illustrate how these parallel syntactic structures differ fundamentally from the deep and surface structures of government and binding (for example). The first advantage is that any lexeme in c-structure can contribute information to a grammatical function in f-structure without having to be in the same phrasal constituent. Consider *each* in the sentences below:

- (52) a. *[Each man] will buy three shirts.*
 b. *[The men] will each buy three shirts.*
 c. *[The men] will buy three shirts each.*

- d. **[The man] will buy three shirts each.*

The quantifier *each* in these sentences quantifies the subject as is evidenced by the ungrammaticality of (52d) where *each* requires a plural antecedent (*c.f.*, (52b) and (52b)). However, in sentences (52b) and (52c) *each* is not syntactically part of the subject NP. In government and binding theory, this is handled by allowing that *each* originated in the subject NP, and was moved to the VP (leaving a trace). Under this analysis, because the quantifier originated in the subject NP, *each* should not be able to co-occur with other quantifiers in the subject:

- (53) *Both men / each man / *both each man/men will buy three shirts.*

However, for many speakers, sentences such as (54) below are perfectly acceptable:

- (54) *Bill will share the award with Dr. William Kervin of Emmanuel College, and both men will each receive a cash prize of \$5000.*³²

LFG allows any lexeme to contribute information to any f-structure without the requirement that the lexeme be in, or have originated from, a particular phrasal node or constituent. As will be seen in chapter 2, this is accomplished using various functional descriptors which link information contained within a lexeme to a particular part of the f-structure. This means that in example (54) above, *each* can contribute information to the subject's f-structure even though it is not part of the subject NP.

Another advantage parallel syntactic structures offer is related to binding. Within government and binding theory, binding must ultimately occur at the level of c-structure – that is to say, in the phrasal domain. LFG offers more possibilities than this. Binding may occur at c-structure, f-structure or even a-structure (see chapter 3).³³ By allowing binding to occur at the level of f-structure (the level at which grammatical functions are defined) we can provide a straightforward analysis of topicalised anaphoric expressions in English. For example, the grammaticality of (54) would be surprising if we required

³² <http://www.queensu.ca/theology/spages/News.shtml>

³³ As this thesis studies the formation of reciprocal constructions rather than their binding, discussion on this topic is limited. However, see chapter 3.7 for brief comments regarding the binding of the Malagasy reciprocal construction.

that *each other* find its antecedent in c-structure, as the antecedent (*they*) occurs later in the sentence:

(55) *But with time, and each other's support, they got through the crisis...*³⁴

In LFG though, we could imagine a simplified binding theory that requires only that *each other* find its antecedent as the subject grammatical function – regardless of linear order in the clause.³⁵ Having introduced the basic concept of parallel syntactic structures in LFG, I will move to the specifics of how these structures are linked in section 1.5.1 below.

1.5.1 F- and C-structure

The f-structure represents both the grammatical functions of a clause and the functional relations between the grammatical functions. The c-structure and abbreviated f-structure for the Malagasy sentence in (56) are given below:

(56) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:70)

M-i-jaly *Rabe.*
 PRES-ACT-suffer Rabe
 “Rabe suffers.”

As the f-structure above demonstrates, (56) contains one grammatical function – a subject, and a verb *mijaly* – “suffer”, whose argument structure specifies that it requires a subject. Note that an f-structure consists of attributes (*e.g.*, SUBJ, TENSE among

34 http://www.therapist.com/Trent_Dr_Notes.html
 35 This binding rule is simplified but nevertheless captures one of the advantages of LFG.
 36 The f-structures and lexical entries that appear throughout this thesis have been abbreviated to include only those features that are relevant to the analysis at hand.

others) and values. A value may be an atomic value (such as “PRES”), a set or another f-structure.

1.5.2 Mapping between F- and C-structure

Equations called f-descriptions (functional-descriptions) are associated both with lexical entries as well as with nodes in the c-structure. These equations provide the mapping between f- and c-structure. The f-descriptions associated with c-structure nodes are generated from annotated phrase structure rules, and mostly follow from x-bar theoretic principles (see Bresnan, 2001). For example, the annotated phrase-structure rules for (56) (and other sentences as well) are below:

$$\begin{array}{lcl}
 (57) & \text{IP} & \longrightarrow & \begin{array}{l} \text{I}' \quad \text{NP} \\ \uparrow = \downarrow \quad (\uparrow \text{SUBJ}) = \downarrow \end{array} \\
 & & & \\
 & \text{I}' & \longrightarrow & \begin{array}{l} \text{I} \quad \text{VP} \\ \uparrow = \downarrow \quad \uparrow = \downarrow \end{array} \\
 & & & \\
 & \text{VP} & \longrightarrow & \begin{array}{l} \text{V} \\ \uparrow = \downarrow \end{array}
 \end{array}$$

The specific nature of such phrase structure rules are defined on a language by language basis. The Principle of Economy of Expression (see Bresnan, 2001:91; Falk, 2001:34) allows phrase structure nodes that are not associated with lexical items or required by independent principles, such as completeness, coherence and semantic expressivity, to be omitted from c-structure as with I' in (56) for example.

The vertical arrows in (57) refer to f-structures. \downarrow refers to the f-structure associated with the current node, while \uparrow refers to the f-structure that is associated with the mother of the current node (See Bresnan 2001:53, Falk 2001:71, Dalrymple & Kaplan 2000:761). The annotations in (57) can therefore be read as:

- (58) $\uparrow = \downarrow$ The f-structure associated with this node in the c-structure is the same as the f-structure associated with the node of its mother.
- $(\uparrow \text{SUBJ}) = \downarrow$ The f-structure associated with my mother's node has an attribute “SUBJ”. This attribute has a value that is the f-structure associated with my node.

Recall that in LFG, f-descriptions are associated with both lexical information and

phrasal annotations. The f-descriptions associated with the lexical items in (56) are listed below:

- (59) *Rabe*, NP (↑ PRED) = 'Rabe'
Mijaly, V (↑ PRED) = 'Suffer<(↑SUBJ)>'
(↑ TENSE) = PRES
(↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE

Thus the f-structure for (56) receives f-descriptions from two sources, lexical (in italics) and phrasal:

The c-structure annotations show that all of the lexical information from the verb must refer to the outermost f-structure – and this is reflected in the f-structure of the sentence (see above). The lexical information for the N *Rabe* requires that its mother's node's f-structure has a PRED feature. However, instead of referring to the outermost f-structure, it refers to the f-structure associated with the SUBJ – because the value of the SUBJ attribute corresponds to the node that is the N's mother.

1.5.3 Constraints in LFG

It is the constraints in LFG that make it a syntactic theory rather than a description. There are two types of constraints in LFG, those that are related to the mapping between structures, and those that are internal to a particular structure. Unification (see 1.5.3.1 below) is a constraint on how information may be combined in f-structure, whereas coherence (1.5.3.3) and completeness (1.5.3.2) are constraints that apply to f-structure.

1.5.3.1 UNIFICATION

If we consider an English sentence in present tense, the verb says something about its subject. That is to say, the verb has some lexical information as part of its definition that defines some values in the f-structure associated with its subject. For example, in (61) below, the verb “yawns” has information about the number and person of its subject and this is reflected in its lexical entry. In order for a sentence to be grammatical, the features and values that the various lexemes define must unify (*i.e.*, be compatible and have no values that are contradictory). The lack of unification explains why (61) is ungrammatical.³⁷

(61) **I yawns.*

<i>I</i> ,	NP	(↑ PRED) = PRO (↑ PERS) = 1 (↑ NUM) = SG
<i>yawns</i> ,	V	(↑ PRED) = 'yawn<(↑SUBJ)>' (↑ SUBJ PERS) = 3 (↑ NUM) = SG (↑ TENSE) = PRES

Among other information, the pronoun *I* contains the following information in its lexical entry: (↑ PERS) = 1 (*i.e.*, the fact that it is a first person pronoun). This

³⁷ Unification is described in detail by Dalrymple (2001:104).

information is contributed to the f-structure associated with the NP – in this case the SUBJ f-structure. On the other hand, the verb contributes the following information: (\uparrow SUBJ PERS) = 3. This functional rule captures the fact that verbs in English can say something about their subject's number. Formally, the rule says that the clause's f-structure contains a SUBJ which has an attribute called PERS, whose value is 3. So, we have a situation where two parts of the clause are saying contradictory things about the person property of the subject. Since f-structures are constrained by unification, there is no mechanism in LFG whereby one lexical entry may overwrite another, (61) is ungrammatical because two differing values are being assigned to the PERS feature. However, if the two values were compatible, then they would unify and the resulting sentence would be grammatical. PRED features have an additional constraint that disallows them from even participating in unification. If two PRED values, even if apparently identical, are constructed in the same f-structure, the resulting sentence is ungrammatical.

1.5.3.2 COMPLETENESS

One of the key tests for a sentence to be grammatical is that its associated f-structure must be both Coherent and Complete. For an f-structure to be complete, every function designated by a PRED must be represented in the f-structure. Furthermore, if that function is an argument function (SUBJ, OBJ, COMP), then it must also include a PRED feature (Bresnan, 2001:63). For example, in (56) above, the verb *mijaly* has the following lexical entry:

- (62) *Mijaly*, V (\uparrow PRED) = 'suffer<(\uparrow SUBJ)>'
 (\uparrow TENSE) = PRES
 (\uparrow VOICE) = ACTIVE

This means the f-structure that contains the PRED feature of *mijaly* will also be required to contain a SUBJ function. Looking again at the f-structure in (56) (repeated below) we see that it does:

- (56) $\left[\begin{array}{ll} \text{SUBJ} & \left[\text{PRED 'Rabe'} \right] \\ \text{PRED} & \text{'suffer}<(\uparrow \text{SUBJ})>' \\ \text{TENSE} & \text{PRES} \\ \text{VOICE} & \text{ACTIVE} \end{array} \right]$

If the SUBJ function were not present in the f-structure, or did not have a PRED value associated with it, then the f-structure would violate the principle of completeness, and therefore be ungrammatical.

1.5.3.3 COHERENCE

For an f-structure to be coherent, every argument function (such as SUBJ, OBJ, etc.) in the f-structure must be designated by a corresponding function in a PRED (see Falk, 2001:61). The ungrammatical sentence below illustrates an incoherent f-structure using the intransitive verb *mijaly* 'suffering':

(63) Malagasy
**M-i-jaly an-Rabe Rakoto.*
 PRES-ACT-suffer ACC.Rabe Rakoto
 “*Rakoto is suffering Rabe.”

Rabe,	NP	(↑ PRED) = 'Rabe' (↑ CASE) = ACC
Mijaly,	V	(↑ PRED) = 'suffer<(↑SUBJ)>' (↑ TENSE) = PRES (↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE
Rakoto,	NP	(↑ PRED) = 'Rakoto' ³⁸

38 Nouns do not inflect for case in Malagasy, although there is an accusative form of proper names. For simplicity I have not assigned a (default) case value of NOM to proper names functioning as subject.

The configuration of the c-structure above, and its associated f-descriptions, places 'Rabe' into an object function. In the f-structure above the SUBJ function is licensed by the main PRED, however, the OBJ function is not. As a result, the f-structure is incoherent and the sentence is ungrammatical.

1.5.4 Argument structure

Argument structure (a-structure) is an intermediary structure that sits between the semantics of a clause and the syntax. The argument structure encodes the predicate argument structure of a verb. Both Bresnan (2001:304-307) and Dalrymple (2001:197-200) give an overview of the development of a-structure and observe that there are two main conceptions of a-structure – one stemming from the work on proto-roles by Dowty (1991) and another arising from work on Conceptual Semantics by Jackendoff (1990). Jackendoff's work analyses predicates as being composed of primitives (such as GO, TO *etc.*) that act as operators on various entities and ultimately, these entities are mapped to their respective grammatical functions. However, within the work on reciprocal constructions, conceptions based upon Dowty's work on a-structure have been utilised and it is these I will ultimately extend. Within this understanding of a-structure there are two key notions. The first is, how we define which arguments a verb selects, and the second is how these arguments map to various grammatical functions. Dowty (1991) provides the theory for the first part – deciding which thematic roles a predicate selects. He classifies only two thematic roles – proto-agent and proto-patient. These are prototypical categories centred around four separate notions each:

Contributing properties for the agent proto-role:

- a. volitional involvement in the event or state
- b. sentience (and/or perception)
- c. causing an event or change in state in another participant
- d. movement (relative to the position of another participant)

Contributing properties for the patient proto-role:

- a. undergoes change of state
- b. incremental theme
- c. causally affected by another participant
- d. stationary relative to movement of another participant (Dowty, 1991:572)

The proto-agents and patients are ranked according to how many of properties listed above they have. For example, an argument containing all four proto-agent properties (such as *Mary* in *Mary built the house*) would be ranked higher than one with only one (such as *John* in *John fears Mary*)³⁹, also, proto-agents are ranked higher than proto-patients. Finally, Dowty allows some arguments to be neither proto-agents or proto-patients.⁴⁰ By conceiving of thematic roles as being prototypical in nature, Dowty also allows that some arguments can have both agent and patient-like properties (for example, see his discussion on psychological predicates: Dowty, 1991:section 8.3).

1.5.4.1 MAPPING BETWEEN A-STRUCTURE AND F-STRUCTURE: LMT

The standard set of rules for the mapping of arguments to grammatical functions in LFG is known as “Lexical Mapping Theory” (LMT) and it is detailed in Bresnan (2001:308) and is described in Bresnan and Kanerva (1989). The rules I describe here were developed by Ackerman (1992) and they are his interpretation of Bresnan's work, but they incorporate an interpretation of a-structure which utilises Dowty's concept of proto-roles.⁴¹

Firstly, arguments are intrinsically classified by assigning them one of two possible syntactic role features, [-r] or [-o]. These arguments are classified by the following principles:

- (1) The argument with the most heavily weighted proto-patient properties is intrinsically classified as [-r].
- (2) The argument with the most heavily weighted proto-agent properties is intrinsically classified as [-o].
- (3) All other arguments are intrinsically classified as [-o].

Ackerman (1992:64)

Secondly, arguments are assigned a default classification where the highest ranking argument receives a [-r] feature and all other arguments receive [+r], unless they have already received an intrinsic classification of [-r]. The arguments are then mapped to

³⁹ See Dowty (1991:572-573) for more examples.

⁴⁰ Rákosi (2008) utilises this possibility in his analysis of naturally symmetric reciprocal constructions (see chapter 4).

⁴¹ Rákosi (2008) provides a very clear summary of the important features of Ackerman's (1992) work, some of which are repeated here.

grammatical functions according to the standard principles of *function-argument bi-uniqueness* and the *subject condition* (see Bresnan, 2001:311 and the references contained within). Having been assigned syntactic role features, each argument can be mapped to a grammatical function using the following table:

(64) Feature Decomposition for Argument Functions (Bresnan 2001)

	-r	+r	
-o	SUBJ	OBL _θ	
+o	OBJ	OBJ _θ	

For example, the verb *push* is associated with two individual thematic roles, a pusher, and a pushee.⁴² The pusher is a proto-agent (volitional, sentient *etc.*) and the pushee is a proto-patient (causally affected by another participant *etc.*). As such, the a-structure of *push* has two arguments (a proto-agent and a proto-patient) and using the mapping theory described by Ackerman above, we see that they map to a subject and object grammatical function:

(65) *push* – associated with an entity which pushes, and an entity which is pushed.

a-structure:	push<[P-A][P-P]>
intrinsic classification:	[-o] [-r]
default classification:	[-r]
f-structure:	push<SUBJ,OBJ>

Finally, LMT has an additional tool available to it whereby an argument may be suppressed – in this situation an argument is not mapped to f-structure at all. Argument suppression provides a straightforward analysis of passive constructions – one that requires no modification of existing mapping rules or f-structure as it follows from the general principles of LMT. The discussion of passives is delayed until chapter 3.

⁴² Individual thematic roles are different for every predicate. However, some features of these roles affect grammar. Dowty's classification of proto-agent and proto-patient properties is his attempt to identify and categorise these features.

1.5.5 Conclusion

In this section I have given a brief account of the complexities and constraints that lie behind the different structures represented within LFG. This introduction provides enough background information to understand the different analyses presented in chapters 2 to 5. However, should the reader require a more comprehensive introduction to LFG, I recommend Dalrymple (2001), Bresnan (2001) and Falk (2001).

1.6 OVERVIEW OF THESIS

Reciprocal constructions in the world's languages vary wildly in their expression and are associated with highly unusual syntactic behaviour. By utilising the syntactic theory of LFG, I show that a host of seemingly unconnected properties associated with reciprocal constructions cross-linguistically are in fact different facets of a cohesive whole. In particular, I show that the dominant factor dictating reciprocal constructions' syntactic behaviour is not their morphosyntactic expression, but rather their underlying reciprocation strategy. I have chosen three languages to illustrate this argument; Icelandic, Malagasy and Swahili. Icelandic and Malagasy have completely different morphosyntactic expression, yet they behave in wider syntactic contexts, almost identically. In contrast, the Malagasy and Swahili reciprocal constructions are both formed from verbal affixes – however, these constructions have very different syntactic behaviour. My analysis is also informed by other languages (for example French and Hungarian) and by other researchers – and these will be introduced in later chapters.

In chapter two I provide an analysis of the Icelandic reciprocal construction that explains how its unusual case assignment is related to the various word orders associated with this construction (e.g., (2)). However, what makes this discussion particularly important to this thesis is not the syntactic analysis *per se*, but rather that the unusual syntactic behaviour associated with this construction has to be understood as resulting from more general mechanisms concerning its underlying formation. Briefly, the compositional reciprocation strategy of the Germanic languages comes about from the interplay of the distributive quantifier (e.g., *each*) with an indefinite pronoun (e.g., *other* in “*Each saw the other*”). I show that the peculiar syntactic behaviour of the Icelandic reciprocal construction arises because there has been underlying change in its reciprocation strategy from compositional to pronominal.

The relevance of these underlying reciprocation mechanisms is further explored in the analysis of the reciprocal construction in Malagasy. As this reciprocal construction is verbal, I examine previous analyses of apparently similar constructions, beginning with Alsina's (1996) work on the reciprocal construction in Catalan. He identifies a reciprocation strategy where a symmetric event can be formed by two thematic roles in a-structure being mapped to a single argument in f-structure (a mechanism which I call "argument unification" here). Alsina analyses the reciprocated predicate as having one fewer grammatical functions in f-structure than in a-structure. This is accomplished by mapping two arguments to a single grammatical function and gives both agent and patient-like properties to the grammatical functions in the symmetric relation. Although this analysis is appealing, I will show that Alsina's analysis cannot be extended to the Malagasy reciprocal construction. Instead I argue that the Malagasy reciprocal construction is best understood as being a covert instance of the pronominal operator reciprocation strategy. Using LFG, I show how a reciprocal pronoun may exist in f-structure, but not appear as a constituent in c-structure. This explains not only why the Malagasy reciprocal construction behaves syntactically like its Icelandic counterpart (they are both formed via an underlying pronominal strategy), but also why the Malagasy reciprocal construction has ambiguous indications regarding its valency.

To further highlight the disconnect between the surface morphosyntactic expression and the syntactic behaviour of reciprocal constructions, in chapters 4 and 5 I examine the verbally marked reciprocal construction in Swahili. Unlike the Malagasy reciprocal construction, it cannot co-occur with object possession and has a dyadic alternative – which more closely aligns it with intrinsically symmetric verbs (such as *quarrel* or *brawl*). I find that both Alsina's analysis for Catalan and Mchombo's analysis (1991) for Chicheŵa (another Bantu language whose reciprocation strategy utilises argument suppression – see chapters 3 and 4) is unable to explain the syntax of the Swahili reciprocal construction. Instead, I argue that symmetry can be formed via another mechanism, which I call theta-role synthesis (an analysis that is informed by Siloni's (2011) categorisation of verbal reciprocals into lexical and syntactic reciprocals – see discussion in chapter 4). Under this analysis, two thematic roles of a predicate are synthesised (meaning that the reciprocated predicate has one less argument in a-structure) and the resulting verb is interpreted as being symmetric. Unlike the argument unification and reciprocal operator mechanisms, theta-role synthesis occurs within the

lexicon. This has implications regarding both the semantic and syntactic behaviour of the construction, explaining its similarity to intrinsically symmetric verbs. Furthermore, this reciprocation strategy explains why only some verbally marked reciprocal constructions have a dyadic alternate.

I draw together these arguments in chapter 6 to show that these reciprocation strategies are responsible for the unusual phenomena that are so commonly associated with reciprocal constructions cross-linguistically and that it is a reciprocal construction's underlying reciprocation strategy that most strongly determines its syntactic (and to an extent, its semantic) behaviour. This thesis has ramifications for typologies of reciprocal constructions; if we want to capture their syntactic behaviour, they should be categorised by their reciprocation strategy rather than their surface expression because identical-looking reciprocal constructions can arise from different reciprocation strategies – each of which has different implications regarding the construction's syntactic behaviour.

2 THE ICELANDIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The Icelandic bipartite reciprocal construction is formed from two words: *hvor* (or *hver* for antecedents with more than two participants) and *annar*, which in its feminine singular accusative form is realised as *aðra* below:⁴³

- (1) *María og Lilja sáu hvor aðra.*⁴⁴
Maria.F.NOM and Lilja.F.NOM see.3PL.PST each.F.SG.NOM other.F.SG.ACC
“María and Lilja saw each other.”

Hvor/hver serves as a quantifier akin to “each” in English and *annar* is an indefinite pronoun meaning “other”. Distributional evidence suggests that *hvor aðra* in (1) above

43 See table 2.1 – 2.3 on pages 70-71 for the full declensions of *hvor*, *hver* and *annar*.

44 The Icelandic examples below come from a variety of sources – Icelandic literature, Icelandic websites (newspapers such as Morgunblaðið (<http://www.mbl.is>), various other commercial websites), an online survey on this construction (see section 2.6) and from data elicited in a series of interviews (both face-to-face and via email) with Ms Sigríður Ólafsdóttir, Ms Inga Árnadóttir and Mr Andri Snæbjörnsson. All three speakers are native to Iceland with Ms Sigríður Ólafsdóttir working privately as an Icelandic teacher, Ms Inga Árnadóttir working in Melbourne Australia as the Honorary Consul-General for Iceland and Mr Andri Snæbjörnsson studying history at the University of Iceland, Reykjavik. Although Ms Inga Árnadóttir and Ms Sigríður Ólafsdóttir have lived in Melbourne for more than ten years both have regular contact with speakers of Icelandic through extended family, local cultural groups and/or their professions.

is an NP. For example, it may be substituted for a regular object NP (as it has been in (2)) or optionally may serve as an indirect object (*e.g.*, (3)):

- (2) *María og Lilja sáu bíomynd.*
 Maria.F.NOM and Lilja.F.NOM see.3PL.PST movie.F.SG.ACC
 “María and Lilja saw (a) movie.”

- (3) *Þær gáfu honum / hvor annarri*
 they.F.PL.NOM give.3PL.PST him.M.SG.DAT / each.F.SG.NOM other.F.SG.DAT

bækur-nar.

book.F.PL.ACC-the

“They (María and Lilja) gave him/each other the books.”

Furthermore, the reciprocal construction is able to participate in nominal syntactic processes such as possession:

- (4) *Jón og María heimsóttu hvort annars*
 John.M.SG.NOM and María.F.SG.NOM visit.3PL.PST each.N.SG.NOM other.N.SG.GEN

foreldra.

parent.M.PL.ACC

“John and María visited each other's parents.”

All of this evidence points towards a treatment of *hvor/hver annar* as a NP. Indeed, based on similar distributional evidence, this is the analysis put forward by Evans, Gaby & Nordlinger (2007:10) for English. However, if we examine the case assignment of the reciprocal construction, we see some very unexpected behaviour: in (1) *hvor annar* has been assigned two different cases – *hvor* receives nominative case and *annar* (realized as *aðra*) receives accusative case. For a single NP to be assigned case in this way is contrary to all theoretical models of case assignment where relational case is assigned just once to a NP.⁴⁵ Furthermore, with respect to word order, the reciprocal construction

⁴⁵ Note that NPs can occur with more than one case marker - for example in case stacking (see

also exhibits unexpected behaviour. When the reciprocal construction occurs with a preposition, *hvor/hver* can occur either inside or outside the prepositional phrase. Consider the following two examples – the first is from *Morgunblaðið* (an online version of one of the main daily papers in Iceland), the other is from a blog. Both of these examples use the phrase *taka tillit til* – “to take something into account” or “to show consideration to someone”:

- (5) a. *Tryggingamenn virðast taka mikið tillit*
 Insurance_people seem_to take.3PL.PRES much regard.M.ACC.SG
- hver til annars í samkeppninni.*⁴⁶
 each.M.SG.NOM to other.M.SG.GEN in competition
 “Insurance people in competition seem to show much consideration to each other.” (*i.e.*, they keep a close eye on each other).
- b. *Allir taka tillit til hvers annars.*⁴⁷
 All take.3PL.PRES regard.M.ACC.SG to each.M.GEN.SG other.M.GEN.SG
 “All show consideration for each other.”

In (5a), *hver* appears outside of the PP *til annars* – “to each other” whereas in (5b), *hver* appears inside the PP and, like *annar*, its case is governed by the preposition *til* which requires its dependants to be in genitive case.

The syntactic analysis developed here needs to accomplish two things: (i) it must explain why an apparent NP can be assigned two different cases, and how these cases are assigned to *hvor/hver* and *annar* and (ii) it must give an explanation as to why we see reciprocal constructions with different word orders. I will show that both these phenomena are related to the reciprocal construction's underlying reciprocation strategy – in particular, a transition from the compositional reciprocation strategy to the pronominal (operator) strategy. I identify four similar looking, but syntactically distinct,

Nordlinger, 1998) or when in a possessive construction. However, the Icelandic reciprocal construction is formed from two words, each independently assigned a different case from outside of the NP.

46 http://www.mbl.is/mm/gagnasafn/grein.html?grein_id=226798

47 http://www.helviti.com/punknurse/2001_09_09_dagbokold.htm

types of reciprocal construction in Icelandic. Each of these constructions reflects a distinct step in the progression of the reciprocal construction's underlying form from compositional to pronominal.

My analysis necessarily begins with a thorough understanding of the nature of the reciprocal construction. However, within the linguistic literature we find that discussion of this construction is sparse – even in the most recent grammar of Icelandic (Thráinsson, 2007) it is relegated to a footnote. Icelandic grammars indicate that *hvor* or *hver* should have the same case as its antecedent (see Svavarsdóttir & Jónsdóttir, 1998:178; Glendening, 1986:48; Einarsson, 1949:131,147):

“The words *hvor* or *hver* which decline like the corresponding question pronouns are the same in gender and case as the word to which they refer. ... On the other hand it is the verb or preposition which governs the case of *annar*.”

Svavarsdóttir & Jónsdóttir (1998:178)

Note that only Svavarsdóttir & Jónsdóttir state this explicitly – Glendening (1986) and Einarsson (1949) giving only a brief example. An immediate problem with these descriptions is that they are inadequate insofar as they do not reflect how the reciprocal construction is used in both day to day speech and even in relatively formal writing such as an online newspaper:

(6) ...*til þess að þeir gætu elskað*
 so that.N.SG.GEN to they.M.PL.NOM able.3PL.PST.SUBJ love.PPL

hver annan og unnið saman.
 each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC and work.PPL together.

*Ekki til þess að drepa hvorn annan.*⁴⁸
 Not so that.N.SG.GEN to kill.INF each.M.SG.ACC other.M.SG.ACC

“[God created man and woman] ...so that they can love each other and work together. Not in order to kill each other.”

48 <http://www.mbl.is/mm/frettir/erlent/frett.html?nid=1175372>

In this instance, the reciprocal construction is used twice in sequential sentences – each time with the same antecedent. In the first sentence, the case of *hvor* matches that of its antecedent (*þeir* – “they” in nominative case) but in the second sentence it has the same case as *annar* (accusative). This difference in the form of the construction has been noted by both Thráinsson (1979) and Everaert (1991). Everaert (1991:282-283) calls the first construction in (6) above “the Split Case reciprocal” and the latter construction “the Like Case reciprocal”. These labels are descriptive and suitable for a typology, however, for my purposes I will opt for the theoretical descriptions of “antecedent case reciprocal construction” and “phrasal reciprocal construction” respectively and I argue for these descriptions in section 2.8.

Additionally, although scholars (notably Plank, 2008 and Everaert, 1991) have observed that the reciprocal construction may have two word orders when combined with a prepositional phrase, neither writer properly characterises its relation with case. For example, Plank (2008) notes that:

“...an inflectional dilemma is created when the quantifier [i.e., hvor] unorthodoxically gets into a prepositional phrase: outside its case is determined by agreement with the subject, but inside it is in the domain of prepositional case government, just like the alterity word [i.e., annar] always was. As seen ... the latter wins out in contemporary Icelandic.”

Plank (2008) – my comments in square brackets.

The analysis put forward by Everaert (1991) is the same – he identifies only two of the following four possible word order/case combinations of the reciprocal construction as being grammatical:⁴⁹

- (7) Everaert (1991:282)
- | | | | | | |
|----|------------|----------|-------------|-------------|--------------|
| a. | <i>NP</i> | <i>V</i> | <i>hvor</i> | <i>prep</i> | <i>annan</i> |
| | | | [NOM] | | [ACC] |
| b. | <i>*NP</i> | <i>V</i> | <i>prep</i> | <i>hvor</i> | <i>annan</i> |
| | | | | [NOM] | [ACC] |

⁴⁹ Everaert adds in a footnote that some of his speakers would accept sentences like (7b).

capture the transitional forms of the reciprocal construction as it moves from a compositional reciprocation mechanism to a pronominal one.

This story begins with a discussion of two aspects of the reciprocal construction which are uncontroversial, although complex (gender and number), and I present my analysis of them in sections 2.2 – 2.5 before returning to a more central discussion on case in section 2.6.

2.2 ICELANDIC GRAMMAR

Icelandic is a Germanic language spoken by about 300,000 people in Iceland. Iceland was colonized in A.D. 874, and since the 12th century the language has changed relatively little – the Icelandic sagas written in the 12th and 13th centuries are still accessible to speakers of today (Glendening, 1986). As a result, Icelandic still retains many of the linguistic features of early Germanic and Old Norse, such as the use of three genders (masculine, feminine and neuter), four cases (nominative, accusative, genitive and dative), strong/weak verbs and it even retains a dual number distinction in some indefinite and interrogative pronouns (*e.g.*, *hvor* – whichever or which (of two), *hver* – whoever or who (of many)). In terms of dialects, Icelandic is fairly homogeneous, with only minor differences in pronunciation between different regions and age groups.⁵¹ This section is not intended to be a comprehensive introduction to Icelandic; rather it supports the analysis of the various reciprocal constructions made later in the chapter. For a generally accessible introduction to Icelandic (in English), see Einarsson (1949, reprint forthcoming) and for a more comprehensive source (in Icelandic), particularly with regard to reciprocals, see Svavarsdóttir & Jónsdóttir (1998).

2.2.1 Nominal morphology and the definite article

Icelandic nouns have singular and plural number and one of three grammatical genders; neuter, feminine or masculine. The gender of any particular noun is usually dependant upon the inflexional ending of the noun – although there are exceptions (Einarsson 1949:32). Icelandic makes use of four cases; nominative, accusative, genitive and dative.⁵² Case marking occurs at the end of the noun and may be grouped into a number of declensions, many of which have various exceptions. A detailed listing of the

⁵¹ See Gíslason & Thráinsson (2000).

⁵² See sections 2.6 – 2.7 for further discussion on case.

paradigms and their exceptions can be found in Einarsson (1949:32-48). Note that some classes of nouns lack any overt case marking in the accusative singular – nevertheless, they will be glossed as accusative in the examples below although I haven't explicitly included a null morpheme in the corresponding noun. In addition to the nominal morphology above, Icelandic has a definite article which is usually suffixed on to the end of a noun (Einarsson 1949:48).⁵³ The suffixed definite article declines for case, number and gender although in the examples below it will only be glossed as '-the'.

2.2.2 Adjectival Morphology

Adjectives in Icelandic agree with their nouns in number, gender and case. Furthermore, many adjectives also have separate declensions depending on whether the noun they modify is strong or weak. Beyond agreement with whether a noun is strong or weak, the strong/weak declensions are also used to indicate other linguistic features. For example, the strong declension is used when agreeing with an indefinite noun (even if that noun is a weak noun), or when the adjective and noun are in a predicative construction. The weak paradigm is used when the adjective is modifying a definite noun (Einarsson 1949:50).⁵⁴

2.2.3 Verbal Morphology

Verbs in Icelandic are inflected for tense, mood, voice, number and person. There are numerous different conjugations – primarily depending on whether a verb is strong or weak. From this point unless otherwise glossed, verbs will be assumed to be active indicative. Icelandic verbs inflect for two tenses; present and past (glossed as PRES and PST below). Other tenses are formed with auxiliary verbs. These compound verb constructions will be introduced as required.

Icelandic has three moods; the indicative, subjunctive and imperative. When combined with tense, these three moods can express a very wide range of meanings – many not predictable from the sum of their parts. For example, among other things, the past subjunctive is used to express potentiality in the present or future and the present subjunctive can be used as an alternative to the imperative in the second and third

53 There is also a free definite article, but its use is limited to co-occurrence with an adjective and it is not commonly used in ordinary speech.

54 There are further uses and complexities in whether the strong or weak adjectival declension is used when agreeing with a noun. See Einarsson (1949:50-60).

person. However, generally the indicative is used to express facts, the subjunctive is used to express wishes, admonitions, exhortations and indirect speech (with a different subject in the lower clause) while the imperative is used to express commands. For more details see Einarsson (1949:135-180). Verbs are marked for either singular or plural number, depending on the number of their subjects. For example:

- (9) a. *María sá Lilju.*
 María.F.NOM see.3SG.PST Lilja.F.ACC
 “Maria saw Lilja.”
- b. *María og Lilja sáu Pál.*
 María.F.NOM and Lilja.F.NOM see.3PL.PST Paul.M.ACC
 “Maria and Lilja saw Paul.”

Icelandic makes use of three persons; first, second and third. This distinction exists in both the indicative, subjunctive and partially in the imperative (Einarsson, 1949:74). There are three voices in Icelandic; active, passive and middle (or mediopassive). Verbs only inflect for active and middle voice – passive voice is formed in combination with the verb “to be” – *vera* and the past participle of the verb being conjugated. Of particular interest is middle voice. Middle voice in Icelandic can be used to indicate reflexive, reciprocal or passive semantics (Einarsson, 1949:147). It is formed by adding the morpheme *-st* to the end of a vowel final conjugated verb. If the verb is consonant final, a more complex process occurs resulting in the verb's ending being modified before the addition of the *-st*.⁵⁵ The three uses of the middle voice are listed below:

1. Reflexive Use.

Glendenung (1986:48) lists this use of the middle voice as the most common:

- (10) Glendenung (1986:48) – my gloss
Rödd hans lognaði-st út af.
 voice.N.NOM his.M.SG.GEN quieten.PST-MV out down
 Lit. “His voice quietened itself down.” or “His voice died away.”

⁵⁵ These changes are detailed in Anderson (2000) and Einarsson (1949:100) but are outside the scope of this thesis.

2. Reciprocal Use

- (11) a. *Þeir hittu Lilju.*
They.M.PL.NOM meet.3PL.PST Lilja.F.ACC
“They met Lilja.”
- b. *Þeir hittu-st.*
They.M.PL.NOM meet.3PL.PST-MV
“They met each other.”

3. Passive Use

Einarsson (1949:147-148) introduces the following sentence as an example with a passive interpretation:

- (12) Einarsson (1949:147-148)
Ekkert heyri-st fyrir foss-inum.
nothing hear.3SG.PRES-MV for waterfall.M.SG.DAT-the
“Nothing is heard on account of the waterfall.”

The reflexive use of the middle voice morpheme *-st* is to be expected because the morpheme originated from *sik*, the old Icelandic reflexive pronoun which still exists as *sig* (Glendenung 1986:48). However, the interpretation of a verb's middle voice is somewhat idiosyncratic – while some verbs do fall exclusively into one of the three categories above, many verbs do not (see Anderson, 1990). For example, a number of verbs only appear in the middle voice (in other words, they do not have a non *-st* verb counterpart). This is especially surprising given that some of these verbs would otherwise be ideal candidates for reflexive/reciprocal semantics. For example the verbs *nálgast* – “approach”, and *óttast* – “fear” only exist in the middle voice (that is, they do not have their non-middle voice counterparts, *nálga* and *óttu*). In addition, there are many *-st* verbs which, while having a non *-st* verb counterpart, are not semantically linked to that counterpart. For example Anderson (1990:254) lists (among others), *fara* – 'go' and *farast* – 'perish' as well as *eygja* – 'see from afar/discern' and *eygjast* – 'become porous'. Furthermore, many *-st* verbs exhibit complex semantics that are not simply limited to any one of the three uses above. For example, in (13b) below, the

middle voice ending on the verb doesn't require a reflexive interpretation, although one is certainly available:

(13) Anderson (1990:252)

a. *Jón meiddi sig.*
John.M.NOM hurt.3SG.PST REFL
“John hurt himself.”

b. *Jón meiddi-st.*
John.M.NOM hurt.3SG.PST-MV
either “John hurt himself” or perhaps more accurately “John got hurt”.

2.2.4 Word Order

Basic word order in Icelandic is SVO.⁵⁶ By default, nominative case is assigned to the subject of the verb, and accusative case to the object:

SVO for transitive verbs

(14) a. *Lilja sá Pál.*
Lilja.F.NOM see.3SG.PST Paul.M.ACC
“Lilja saw Paul.”

b. *Páll sá Lilju.*
Paul.M.NOM see.3SG.PST Lilja.F.ACC
“Paul saw Lilja.”

SV for intransitive verbs

(16) *Páll svaf.*
Paul.M.NOM sleep.3SG.PST
“Paul slept.”

56 Like many other Germanic languages (not including English), Icelandic exhibits the “verb-second phenomenon” where the verb and subject are inverted for topicalised sentences (for example). See Rögnvaldsson & Thráinsson (1990) and the references contained within.

S-V-IO-O for ditransitive verbs selecting two objects

(17) Jónsson (2000:72)

Hann gaf litla barni-nu
He.M.SG.NOM give.3SG.PST little.N.SG.DAT child.N.SG.N.DAT-the

bók-ina.

book.N.SG.ACC-the

“He gave the small child the book.”

Note that there are actually five double object case patterns in Icelandic, all with the subject in nominative case. The majority pattern like the ditransitive verb above, with dative case for the indirect object and accusative case for the direct object (see Jónsson 2000:73 for discussion on this topic more generally). It is possible under certain conditions to invert the IDO/O order. Compare (17a) and (17b) below from Falk (1990:85):

(17) a. Unmarked order

Ég gaf/sýndi/sendu honum bók-ina.
I.NOM gave/showed/sent him.DAT book.ACC-the

b. Inverted order

Ég gaf/sýndi/sendu bókina einhverju bókasafni.
I.NOM gave/showed/sent book.ACC-the some library.DAT

However, this change in word order is not productive – for example, the IDO needs to be both stressed and non-pronominal (Falk 1990).

2.2.5 Conclusion

This concludes the overview of Icelandic grammar. The middle voice reciprocal construction is discussed in more detail in chapters 4 and 5. For further reference on syntax, phonology and morphology, any of the grammars previously mentioned would be suitable – in particular Einarsson (1949).

2.3 THE BIPARTITE RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION IN ICELANDIC

We saw in section 2.1 that there is more than one account of the bipartite reciprocal construction in Icelandic. For example, Everaert (1991) identifies two types of reciprocal construction based on word order – and in this chapter I identify a further two based upon case (see (19) and (20a-c) below for an example of each variant). The fact that these various forms exist contemporaneously strongly suggests that there are a number of variants of the reciprocal construction that need to be understood. As it is my aim to provide a syntactic account of these constructions, my first goal must be to describe the differences and similarities of these different variants. So, in this section I first outline the uncontroversial aspects of the bipartite reciprocal construction – features which most speakers of Icelandic agree upon. In the following sections I explore the reciprocal construction with respect to gender (section 2.4) and number (section 2.5). These features have relatively little variation with respect to the different variants of the reciprocal construction. In section 2.6 I discuss the results of a survey I conducted to provide an in-depth examination of the construction and its relation to case – where there is the most amount of disagreement and uncertainty regarding how the construction is formed (*e.g.*, see example (7) above). This survey is designed to answer two questions – what variation there is in the case marking of the bipartite reciprocal construction, and what factors might lead speakers to prefer one form over another.

Given that there is more than one realisation of the reciprocal construction, it may reasonably be assumed that they are historically related and any syntactic analysis I make must be sensitive to this fact. In section 2.7 I undertake a survey into the origins of the Icelandic reciprocal construction by examining how the reciprocal construction was formed in the sagas – 12-13th century Icelandic literature. Understanding the origins and development of the Icelandic bipartite reciprocal construction informs my analysis of the construction in section 2.8. This analysis addresses the following issues:

1. Why there is more than one form of the bipartite reciprocal construction.
2. How these forms of the reciprocal construction are related (both historically and through synchronic analysis).
3. What the connections are between the reciprocal constructions and grammatical functions as understood through case.

2.3.1 Uncontroversial aspects of the formation of the bipartite reciprocal construction

We saw that at its simplest, the bipartite Icelandic reciprocal construction is formed by combining the entities involved in a symmetric relationship into a single or conjoined noun phrase with the words *hvor annar* or *hver annar* appearing after the verb. For example:

- (18) a. *Köttur-inn sá hund-inn.*
 cat.M.SG.NOM-the see.3SG.PST dog.M.SG.ACC-the
 “The cat saw the dog.”
- b. *Hundur-inn sá kött-inn.*
 dog.M.SG.NOM-the see.3.sg.pst cat.M.SG.ACC-the
 “The dog saw the cat.”
- c. *Köttur-inn og hundur-inn sáu*
 cat.M.SG.NOM-the and dog.M.SG.NOM-the see.3PL.PST

hvor/n annan.
 each.M.SG.NOM/ACC other.M.SG.ACC
 “The cat and dog saw each other.”

The choice of *hvor* or *hver* is dictated by the number of entities in the subject NP – for two, *hvor* is used, for more than two *hver* is used (see section 2.5 for further discussion). Note that the case of *hvor* in (18c) above can be either nominative or accusative. Using the terminology introduced in the previous section, these two forms of the reciprocal construction will be called the antecedent case reciprocal construction and the phrasal reciprocal construction. There is in fact another bipartite reciprocal construction in Icelandic not mentioned by any of the grammars where *hvor* or *hver* functions as the subject of the clause and *annar* (realised as *öðrum* below) serves in some grammatical function selected by the verb:

- (19) ... *þar sem hver klappar öðrum á bak-ið*.⁵⁷
 where as each.M.SG.NOM pat.3SG.PRES other.M.SG.DAT on back.N.SG.ACC-the
 lit. “... whereas each pats the other on the back.”

These constructions are common in old Icelandic, but still occur occasionally in modern Icelandic. Because the symmetrical semantics of constructions like (19) can be made from the composition (or interaction) of the quantifier *hver/hvor* – “each” with the pronoun *annar* – “other”, I call constructions like this “compositional” (after the compositional reciprocation strategy). This is in contrast to the fixed form reciprocal constructions (20b), and the phrasal reciprocal construction (20c).⁵⁸

- (20) Antecedent (*hver/hvor* share the same case as their antecedent)
- a. *Ég kynnti mennina hvorn fyrir öðrum*
 I introduce.1SG.PST man.M.PL.ACC each.M.SG.ACC for other.M.SG.GEN
 “I introduced the men to each other.”

Fixed form reciprocal construction (*hver/hvor* are always nominative)⁵⁹

- b. *Elskhuga-na dreymdi hvorn annan.*
 lover.M.PL.ACC-the dream.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “The lovers dreamt of each other.”

Phrasal reciprocal construction (*hver* and *annar* have case governed by the verb)

- c. *Bræður-nir sáu hvorn annan.*
 brother.M.PL.NOM-the saw.3PL.PST each.M.SG.ACC other.M.SG.ACC
 “The brothers saw each other.”

57 [https://vgnt1.vegagerdin.is/vefur2.nsf/Files/Vidhorfskonnunverktakar2004/\\$file/Vegag_080-verkt.pdf](https://vgnt1.vegagerdin.is/vefur2.nsf/Files/Vidhorfskonnunverktakar2004/$file/Vegag_080-verkt.pdf)

58 As we will see the antecedent case reciprocal construction (e.g., (20a)), despite having very different morphosyntactic expression to the compositional reciprocation construction in (19), is also formed from the compositional reciprocation strategy.

59 In most contexts, the antecedent case reciprocal construction (where *hver/hvor* has the same case as its antecedent) and the fixed form reciprocal construction (where *hver/hvor* always appear in the nominative) look identical. However, *dreymdi* - “dreamt” is an irregular verb in Icelandic which assigns accusative case to both subject and object. Hence the fixed case of *hver* is apparent. Determining the syntax and the relationships between these constructions is central to this chapter. More broadly, this investigation accords with the main theme of this thesis – that reciprocal constructions need to be understood not by their morphosyntactic expression, but rather by their underlying reciprocation strategy.

Pl. nom.	<i>hverjir</i>	<i>hverjar</i>	<i>hver</i>
acc.	<i>hverja</i>	<i>hverjar</i>	<i>hver</i>
dat.	<i>hverjum</i>	<i>hverjum</i>	<i>hverjum</i>
gen.	<i>hverra</i>	<i>hverra</i>	<i>hverra</i>

Table 2.2 Declension of *Hver*

	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter
Sg. nom.	<i>annar</i>	<i>önnur</i>	<i>annað</i>
acc.	<i>annan</i>	<i>aðra</i>	<i>annað</i>
dat.	<i>öðrum</i>	<i>annarri</i>	<i>öðru</i>
gen.	<i>annars</i>	<i>annarrar</i>	<i>annars</i>
Pl. nom.	<i>aðrir</i>	<i>aðrar</i>	<i>önnur</i>
acc.	<i>aðra</i>	<i>aðrar</i>	<i>önnur</i>
dat.	<i>öðrum</i>	<i>öðrum</i>	<i>öðrum</i>
gen.	<i>annarra</i>	<i>annarra</i>	<i>annarra</i>

Table 2.3 Declension of *Annar*

For the purposes of this study of reciprocal constructions, *hver/hvor* and *annar* can be understood as being similar to the English words “each” and “other” respectively and will be glossed as such in the following examples. For example, the use of *hver* below gives a distributive interpretation to the sentence, while one of the many uses of *annar* is equivalent to the English word “other”:

- (22) a. *Hver maður fyrir sig verður að leita lausnar.*⁶¹
 each.M.SG.NOM man.M.SG.NOM for refl.ACC must.3SG.PRES to search.INF solution.F.SG.GEN
 “Each man for himself must search for a solution (*i.e.*, find the right answer).”
- b. *Hann og sumir aðrir.*⁶²
 He.M.SG.NOM and some.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.NOM
 “He and some others.”

61 http://www.helviti.com/punknurse/2001_06_24_dagbokold.htm

62 Einarsson (1949:130)

- c. *Aðrar orðabækur.*⁶³
 Other.F.PL.NOM word-book.F.PL.NOM
 “Other dictionaries (in the series).”

I next examine the reciprocal construction with respect to gender.

2.4 HVER/HVOR ANNAR AND GENDER

Correctly analysing the gender concord of the Icelandic reciprocal construction is not entirely straightforward – however I am fortunate to be able to make use of an existing work in LFG by Dalrymple & Kaplan (2000).

The reciprocal construction itself is conventionalised insofar as both *hver/hver* and *annar* must share the same gender – usually that of their antecedent. Sentences such as (23) are regarded as completely ungrammatical by most speakers because the genders of *hvert* and *annan* do not match:

- (23) **Bræður-nir sáu hvert annan.*
 brother.M.PL.NOM-the saw.3PL.PST each.N.SG.NOM/ACC other.M.SG.ACC
 “The brothers saw each other.”

However, there is disagreement between some speakers with respect to whether the gender of the reciprocal construction should be assigned grammatically or semantically (see discussion below). For the most part though, the gender of Icelandic bipartite reciprocal construction follows the same conventions as adjectival gender agreement. Icelandic has three genders, masculine, feminine and neuter. Adjectives agree in gender (as well as in number and case) with the nouns they modify:

- (24) a. *Stelpa-n er löng.*
 Girl.F.SG.NOM-the is.3SG.PRES tall.F.SG.NOM
 “The girl is tall.”

63 Hilbertsson (1990:End Cover).

- b. *Strákur-inn er langur.*
 Boy.M.SG.NOM-the is.3SG.PRES tall.M.SG.NOM
 “The boy is tall.”

- c. *Barn-ið er langt.*
 Child.N.SG.NOM-the is.3sg.pres tall.N.SG.NOM
 “The child is tall.”

Like other languages that exhibit such gender concord, there is a convention for assigning gender to predicative adjectives when the NP which they modify has mixed gender. In Icelandic, this convention is straightforward. If a NP is made from several nouns or noun phrases of differing gender, then the gender of the NP as a whole is considered neuter with respect to concord. Otherwise, the gender of the NP matches that of all its constituents. For example:

- (25) a. *Stelpa-n og strákur-inn eru löng.*
 Girl.F.SG.NOM-the and boy.M.SG.NOM-the be.3PL.PRES tall.N.PL.NOM
 “The girl and the boy are tall.”

- b. *Stelpa-n og móðir hennar eru*
 Girl.F.SG.NOM-the and mother.F.SG.NOM her.F.SG.GEN be.3PL.PRES

langar.

tall.F.PL.NOM

“The girl and her mother are tall.”

- c. *Strákur-inn og bróðir hans eru*
 Boy.M.SG.NOM-the and brother.M.SG.NOM his.M.SG.GEN be.3PL.PRES

langir.

tall.M.PL.NOM

“The boy and his brother are tall.”

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- d. *Stelpa-n* *og* *barn-ið* *eru* *löng.*
Girl.F.SG.NOM-the and child.N.SG.NOM-the be.3PL.PRES tall.N.PL.NOM
“The girl and the child are tall.”

In terms of gender concord between phrases, this agreement has been summarised by Dalrymple & Kaplan (2000) as :

(26) Dalrymple & Kaplan (2000:790)

Masc + Masc = Masc

Fem + Fem = Fem

Neut + Neut = Neut

Masc + Fem = Neut

Masc + Neut = Neut

Fem + Neut = Neut

The reciprocal construction (in all of its forms) nearly always follows this convention. For example, in a survey of 504 people (see section 2.6) I asked the participants to tell me the appropriate form of a reciprocal construction for a given antecedent. Although there was much variation in their replies, none of it related to gender which was consistently realised in the manner described in (26). For example, in (27) speakers were asked to give the form of the reciprocal construction they would use (or hear others use) for a sentence with a masculine, feminine and neuter antecedent. Over 99% of the answers respected the case assignment previously discussed:

(27) Sec A, Q ii – 99.23% of respondents

- a. *Bræður-nir* *sáu* *hvor/n*
brother.M.PL.NOM-the see.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM/ACC

annan.

other.M.SG.ACC

“The brothers saw each other.”

Sec A, Q iii – 99.41% of respondents

- b. *Konur-nar* *sáu* *hver/a* *aðra*.
 woman.F.PL.NOM-the see.3PL.PST each.F.SG.NOM/ACC other.F.SG.ACC
 “The women saw each other.”

Sec A, Q i – 99.80% of respondents

- c. *Maður-inn* *og* *kona-n* *sáu*
 man.M.SG.NOM-the and woman.F.SG.NOM-the see.3PL.PST

hvort *annað*.⁶⁴
 each.N.SG.NOM/ACC other.N.SG.ACC
 “The man and woman saw each other.”

Note that neuter forms in Icelandic are often syncretic between the nominative and accusative. For this reason *hvort* in (27c) is glossed as being in either nominative case or accusative case. Dalrymple and Kaplan (2000) have proposed an analysis in LFG which easily captures gender concord for Icelandic – which I will briefly introduce here. Their key insight is that the three genders in Icelandic can, in terms of analysis, be understood as sets which are formed from various combinations of masculine and feminine elements. They use the following definition for each gender:

(28) Gender concord (Dalrymple and Kaplan, 2000:790)

MASC	{M}
FEM	{F}
NEUT	{M, F}

When two NPs are combined, the resulting gender of the superordinate NP can be understood as the set union of the gender attribute of each of the constituent NPs. For example, in the table below, treating the combination of genders as a set union operation correctly accounts for the gender of the resulting NP:

64 In (27c) above, one respondent chose *hver aðra* (the feminine antecedent case reciprocal construction) for a mixed gender antecedent. Such a response is clearly exceptional.

(29) Gender concord resolutions (Dalrymple and Kaplan, 2000:790)

$$\begin{aligned} \{M\} \cup \{M\} &= \{M\} \\ \{F\} \cup \{F\} &= \{F\} \\ \{M, F\} \text{ (i.e., NEUT)} \cup \{M, F\} &= \{M, F\} \text{ (NEUT)} \\ \{M\} \cup \{F\} &= \{M, F\} \text{ (NEUT)} \\ \{M\} \cup \{M, F\} &= \{M, F\} \text{ (NEUT)} \\ \{F\} \cup \{M, F\} &= \{M, F\} \text{ (NEUT)} \end{aligned}$$

Formally then, all that is required is a way of implementing this operation in LFG. Dalrymple and Kaplan provide just such a device by using a NP rule for coordinated NPs which creates sets containing these gender features:

(30) Simplified from Dalrymple and Kaplan (2000:788)

$$\text{NP} \rightarrow \begin{array}{c} \text{NP} \\ \uparrow \in \downarrow \\ (\downarrow \text{GEND}) \subseteq (\uparrow \text{GEND}) \end{array} \text{ CNJ } \begin{array}{c} \text{NP} \\ \uparrow \in \downarrow \\ (\downarrow \text{GEND}) \subseteq (\uparrow \text{GEND}) \end{array}$$

For example, in (31) below, the subject NP has neuter gender – as evidenced by the adjectival agreement. In order to see how the rule above captures the gender of the resulting NP, examine the simplified c- and f-structures for the subject NP below:

(31) *Stelpan* *og* *strákur-inn* *eru* *löng.*
 girl.F.SG.NOM-the and boy.M.SG.NOM-the be.3PL.PRES tall.N.PL.NOM
 “The girl and the boy are tall.”

How then does the gender concord between the reciprocal construction and the

antecedent NP work? Consider (31) above. In this example, each of the conjoint NPs is headed by a noun which has been assigned a gender. These genders are construed as sets ($\{F\}$ for *stelpa* – “girl” and $\{M\}$ for *strákkur* – “boy”). The phrase structure rule for coordination includes the following feature assignment: $\downarrow\text{GEND} \subseteq \uparrow\text{GEND}$. This can be understood as the requirement that the gender value of the superordinate NP be a superset that contains the gender of the conjoint. So for *stelpa* (which is assigned a gender value of $\{F\}$), the superset must be either $\{F\}$ or $\{M,F\}$. The other conjoint requires its superordinate NP to have a gender feature of (at least) $\{M\}$. The only gender value of the superordinate NP which can satisfy both of these requirements is $\{M,F\}$ – which is neuter. Functionally, each of the different gender forms of *hvor/hver* and *annar* can be understood as having different constraining equations with respect to their antecedent's gender:

- (32) *hvor/hver/annar*: $\text{ANT GEND} =_{\subseteq} \{M\}$
hvor/hver/önnur: $\text{ANT GEND} =_{\subseteq} \{F\}$
hvort/hvert/annað: $\text{ANT GEND} =_{\subseteq} \{M,F\}$

These constraining equations do not assign gender features to the antecedent. Instead they require that the antecedent have a particular gender. For example, *annar* above requires that the antecedent has a gender value of $\{M,F\}$. I will delay a full discussion of the definition of *hver/hvor* and *annar* until section 2.8. However, until then, ANT can be considered as a shorthand way of referring to the f-structure of the antecedent NP to which the reciprocal construction refers. This means that the ungrammaticality of (33) below is predicted because *hvor annan*, as part of its lexical definition, requires an antecedent with the gender feature $\{M\}$ – however, as we saw above, the gender feature of the antecedent NP is $\{M,F\}$:

- (33) **Stelpa-n* *og* *strákur-inn* *sáu* *hvor*
 girl.F.SG.NOM-the and boy.M.SG.NOM-the see.3PL.PRES each.M.SG.NOM

annan.

other.M.SG.ACC

“The girl and the boy saw each other.”

Note that my survey (see section 2.6) reveals some interesting new data with respect to gender concord. Some speakers will allow the gender of the reciprocal construction to be semantically based rather than grammatically based. For example, in section d, question (i) of the survey (see appendix B below) speakers were asked to choose various forms of the reciprocal construction for a sentence with the antecedent NP *elskhugarnir* – “the lovers”. Grammatically *elskhugarnir* is a typical masculine plural noun in Icelandic. However, several participants in the survey noted that their preferred form of the reciprocal construction for this antecedent would be *hvort annað* (the neuter form of the reciprocal construction) – presumably based on their knowledge that the lovers were likely to be a male and female. Unfortunately, my survey was not able to reveal how widespread this semantic assignment of gender actually is – only that for some speakers it is preferable over grammatically based gender concord.

In the following section I examine the reciprocal construction's interaction with the number of its antecedent and find that the notion of grammatical number needs to be expanded in order to account for the number agreement data related to this construction.

2.5 *HVER/HVOR ANNAR AND NUMBER*

The number marking system of the Icelandic reciprocal construction is complex and has its origin in the oldest variant of the reciprocal construction (see section 2.7). In this section I detail how the Icelandic reciprocal construction is related to number.

2.5.1 *Hvor vs. Hver*

One of the many uses of *hvor* and *hver* is as an interrogative pronoun.⁶⁵ According to Einarsson (1949:127-128) the difference between *hvor* and *hver* when used as interrogative pronouns is that *hvor* is used to question groups with two entities (34b) and *hver* is used to question groups with three or more entities (34a):

⁶⁵ See Einarsson (1949:127) for more details.

(34) Glendening (1986:75)⁶⁶

- a. *Hver drengja-nna braut það?*
 Which.M.SG.NOM boy.M.PL.GEN-the break.3SG.PST it.3SG.N.ACC
 “Which of the boys broke it?”

Einarsson (1949:128)

- b. *Hvorn eið-inn á ég að rjúfa?*
 Which.M.SG.ACC oath.M.SG.ACC-the have.1SG.PRES I.1SG.NOM
 to break.INF
 “Which of the (two) oaths have I to break?”

This dual and plural distinction made in the interrogative pronominal forms is maintained when *hver* and *hvör* are used as quantifiers. For example, in the text below *hvör* refers to the fact that there are two books being spoken of:

“*Malla fer í leikskóla og Malla fer í sund eftir Lucy Cousins fjallar um Möllu mús sem börnin þekkja úr sjónvarpinu.... **Hvör** bók er 16 bls.*”⁶⁷

“Malla goes to kindergarten” and “Malla goes swimming” by Lucy Cousins deals with Malla mouse whom the children will be familiar with from television... Each book has 16 pages. (my translation)

To refer to more than two books, *hver* is used:

- (35) *Hver bók er í kringum*
 Each.F.SG.NOM book.F.SG.NOM be.3SG.PRES about

*500 blaðsíður.*⁶⁸

500 page.N.PL.NOM

“Each book is about 500 pages long.”

66 Note Glendening adds: “*Hver* is used when there are more than two to choose from...”

67 http://www.mbl.is/mm/gagnasafn/grein.html?grein_id=568364

68 <http://www.althingi.is/altext/117/O4/r07120026.sgml>

As might be expected, this distinction also exists in the corresponding reciprocal constructions. For example, in (36a) below, *hvor* refers to an antecedent with two entities and in (36b), *hver* refers to an antecedent with three entities:

- (36) a. *Þessir tveir meginþættir skulu*
 these.M.PL.NOM two.M.NOM main-factors.M.PL.NOM must.3PL.PRES
*styðja hvor annan.*⁶⁹
 support.INF each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “These two main factors must support each other.”
- b. *Mennir-nir þrír sáu aldrei*
 Man.M.PL.NOM-the three.M.NOM see.3PL.PST never
*hver annan eða aðra.*⁷⁰
 each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC or other.M.PL.ACC
 “At no time did the three men see each other or any others.”

The above distinction in number is all that is made in the grammars and language guides to Icelandic (Glendening (1986), Einarsson (1949), Svavarsdóttir & Jónsdóttir (1998), Thráinsson (2007)). However, in modern spoken Icelandic, there are a number of exceptions and additions to this description. The first of these is straightforward – speakers will often use *hver* (rather than *hvor*) to refer to an antecedent with only two entities. For example:

- (37) *Hjón geta elskað hvert*
 married-couple.N.PL.NOM be-able-to.3PL.PRES love.PPL each.N.SG.NOM/ACC
annað meira en systkini þó þau
 other.N.SG.ACC more than sibling.N.PL.NOM yet they.N.PL.NOM

69 <http://vefur.khi.is/sidur/kennslusk200405/1kafli.pdf>

70 http://www.amnesty.is/media/Frettabrefid/Amnesty_juni_200642.pdf

*séu ekki skyld.*⁷¹
 are.3PL.SBJ.PRES not related.N.PL.NOM

“(A) married couple are able to love each other more than siblings (can) yet they are not related.”

Thráinsson (2007:472) notes that the use of *hver* is probably generalising in this sense so that for many speakers *hver annan* can refer to an antecedent of two or more. However, of far more interest is that there is a further distinction in number which can be made using the singular and plural morphology of *hvor* and *hver* – one that has been in use for at least 700 years.

2.5.2 Morphological number

Hver and *hvor* have a singular/plural number distinction when used as interrogatives. Compare the morphologically singular and plural forms of *hver* in (38a) and (38b) below:

(38) a. Q. *Hver bilanna er bilaður?*
 which.M.SG.NOM car.M.PL.GEN is.3SG.PRES out-of-order.M.SG.NOM
 “Which of the cars is out of order?”

A. *Þessi bill.* / This car.

b. Q. *Hverjir bilanna eru bilaðir?*
 which.M.PL.NOM car.M.PL.GEN are.3PL.PRES out-of-order.M.PL.NOM
 “Which of the cars are out of order?”

A. *Þessir.* / Those ones.

Hver - “which” is pluralised when it refers to a plural entity and it means “which ones (of many)”. Likewise consider *hvor* below in (39). Initially it is not clear why a word which means “each (of two)” or “which (of two)” should require a plural form. However, Icelandic has a few collective nouns – some of which are singular (39a), and

71 <http://www.malefnin.com/ib/index.php?showtopic=11670&mode=threaded&pid=313832>

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others having only a plural form (39b). In the example below, *samtök* – 'association' is a noun which is grammatically plural. In situations like this, the morphologically plural form of *hvor* is used. Note the contrast between the singular and plural nouns :

- (39) a. *Í hvoru félaginu ertu?*
In which.N.SG.DAT company.N.SG.DAT are-you
“In which company are you?” (of two companies)
- b. *Í hvorum samtökunum ertu?*
In which.N.PL.DAT association.N.PL.DAT are-you
“In which association are you” (of two associations)

Finally, *annar* also has a morphologically plural form when used as a determiner:

- (40) a. *Ég sá aðra menn.*
I.1SG.NOM see.1SG.PST other.M.PL.ACC man.M.PL.ACC
“I saw other men.”
- b. *Ég sá annan mann.*
I.1SG.NOM see.1SG.PST other.M.SG.ACC man.M.SG.ACC
“I saw another man.”

As seen in (38), (39) and (40) *hver*, *hvor* and *annar* can appear with either morphologically singular or plural number agreement. This means that when *hvor/hver* are used in reciprocal constructions, there are, in terms of number, potentially two forms which can be used. As will be seen below, by far the most common form is the singular – and this raises the first question that needs to be addressed: why is it that the morphologically singular forms of *hvor/hver* are used at all in reciprocal constructions given that the antecedent to which they refer is both semantically and grammatically plural? If we consider that some aspect of the number of *hvor/hver* *annar* is assigned semantically rather than grammatically, the fact that the number of *hvor* and *hver* is singular can be explained straightforwardly. Recall that *hvor* and *hver* are quantifiers that take a proposition related to a group and apply it to each of the individuals in that group:

- (41) a. *Nunnur-nar gáfu barni-nu gjöf.*
 Nun.F.PL.NOM-the give.3PL.PST child.N.SG.DAT-the gift.F.SG.ACC
 “The nuns gave the child a gift.”
- b. *Hver nunna gaf barni-nu gjöf.*
 Each.F.SG.NOM nun.F.SG.NOM give.3SG.PST child.N.SG.DAT-the
 gift.F.SG.ACC
 “Each nun gave the child a gift.”

The difference between (41a) and (41b) is in the number of gifts the child received. In (41a), the nuns may have combined their efforts into one joint gift to give to the child, whereas in (41b), each nun gave their own gift to the child. That the proposition associated with *hver/hvor* must be able to be applied to each individual can be demonstrated by considering the acceptability of the following sentences:

- (42) a. *Eftir bardaga-nn, dreifðu strákar-nir sér.*
 After fight.M.SG.ACC-the disperse.3PL.PST boy.M.PL.NOM-the REFL
 “After the fight, the boys dispersed.”
- b. **Eftir bardaga-nn, dreifði hver strákur sér.*
 After fight.M.SG.ACC-the disperse.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM boy.M.SG.NOM
 REFL
 “After the fight, each boy dispersed.”

The verb *dreifa* – “disperse” requires a plural group as its subject. However, the use of *hver* in (42b) forces this proposition to apply to each member of the group – and so the sentence is unacceptable.

Given then that the *hver* and *hver* are operators that apply semantically to single entities within a group, their singular case marking should come as no surprise – their

number is singular because it corresponds to each entity within the group, not to the group as a whole.

However, although this argument can explain the singular case marking for *hvor/hver*, it does not provide any insight into why *annar* should be marked with singular number when referring to groups with more than two entities. For example, (43a) is acceptable and not (43b):

- (43) a. *Konur-nar hlupu hver frá annarri.*
 woman.F.PL.NOM-the run.3PL.PST each.F.SG.NOM from other.F.SG.DAT
 “The women ran away from each other.”
- b. *#Konur-nar hlupu hver frá öðrum.*
 woman.F.PL.NOM-the run.3PL.PST each.F.SG.NOM from other.F.PL.DAT
 “The women ran away, each from the others.”

Sentence (43b) is a logically possible sentence which describes a group of women running away from each other – however, in this sentence *annar* does not share the same number as *hvor/hver*. For the speakers I interviewed the only reading of (43b) is that there are two groups of women, and each woman in the first group is running away from all the women (or in fact, people, as *öðrum* has the same form for all genders) in the second group. In the absence of any other reason, it appears that the number of *annar* is simply constrained to be the same as *hvor/hver* – that is, that *hvor/hver annar* is a construction with conventionalised number insofar as *hvor/hver* and *annar* must agree with each other in number (hence the term “semi-conventionalised”). The number of *annar* will be discussed in more detail in section 2.7 which looks at the historical development of the reciprocal construction in Germanic languages in more detail.

In any case, the number that is assigned to *annar* becomes the number of the NP. For example, in sentence (44c) below, the adjective *rauður* “red” must agree in number with the NP it modifies, and not with its antecedent.

- (44) a. *Pétur og Jón máluðu hús-ið/hús-in*
 Peter.M.SG.NOM and John.M.SG.NOM paint.3PL.PST house.N.SG/PL.ACC-the

rautt/rauð.

red.N.SG/PL.ACC

“Peter and John painted the house red / houses red.”

- b. **Pétur* *og* *Jón* *máluðu* *hús-ið*
 Peter.M.SG.NOM and John.M.SG.NOM paint.3PL.PST house.N.SG.ACC-the

rauð.

red.N.PL.ACC

“Peter and John painted the house red.”

- c. *Pétur og Jón máluðu* *hver* *annan*
 Peter and John paint.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC

*rauðan / *rauða*

red.M.SG.ACC / RED.M.PL.ACC

“Peter and John painted each other red.”

Sentences like (44c) clearly establish that even though the number might be semantically assigned to the reciprocal construction, once established, regular number concord exists between it and any modifiers.

Having argued that some aspect of number in the reciprocal construction is semantically assigned, we might expect it to be amenable to various extensions and indeed this is the case. The combination of a morphological singular/plural number distinction and a dual/plural number distinction between *hver* and *hver* gives speakers of Icelandic four possible ways of indicating number. In practice, the distinction between the choice of *hver* and *hver* is used to indicate how many groups and or entities are involved in the antecedent, and the singular/plural morphological distinction can be used to indicate whether the entities in the antecedent are groups or individuals. For example, the sentence below (which comes from the website of the Icelandic Prime Minister) talks about two groups:

- (45) *Enn þann dag í dag kalla Norðmenn og*
 Still today call.3PL.PRES Norwegian.M.PL.NOM and
Íslendingar hvorir aðra frændur
 Icelanders.M.PL.NOM each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.ACC cousins
*eða bræður svo náin eru tengslin milli þjóðanna.*⁷²
 or brothers so close be.3PL.PRES connections between nations

“Still today, Norwegians and Icelanders call each other cousins or brothers, so close are the connections between the nations.”

In the example above, *hvor* (as opposed to *hver*) has been used to reflect that the subject contains two entities, while the plural masculine form of *hvor*, *hvorir*, has been used to indicate that each of the two conjoined entities is a group. As the example below attests, only one of the conjoined NPs needs to be a group in order to use the plural form of *hvor*:

- (46) *Jól-in eru sá tími þegar Guð og*
 Xmas.N.PL.NOM-the be.3PL.PRES one time.M.SG.NOM when God.M.SG.NOM and
*mennir-nir skilja hvorir aðra.*⁷³
 man.M.PL.NOM-the understand.3PL.PRES each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.ACC
 “Christmas is the one time when God and mankind understand each other.”

With three entities (with at least one being a group) *hverjir*, the plural form of *hver*, can be used:

- (47) *Norðmenn, Svíar og Danir geta þó*
 Norwegian.M.PL.NOM Swede.M.PL.NOM and Dane.M.PL.NOM can.3PL.PRES still

72 http://for.stjr.is/nordurlandaskrifstofa/Siv_Fridleifsd/nr/982

73 <http://tru.is/postilla/2005/12/jolin-eru-komin/>

skilið *hverjir* *aðra...*⁷⁴
understand.PP each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.ACC

“Norwegians, Swedes and Danes are still able to understand each other...”

Although this four-way distinction in number is not documented in the formal literature, speakers are either aware of it, or at least receptive to its use.⁷⁵ Some websites have commented upon it – the example below comes from Ólafur Oddsson, an Icelandic teacher, who has produced a document called “Gott Mal – Ábendingar um algengar ritvillur og hnökra á máli og stíl” or “Good Language – advice about common mistakes and flaws in speech and composition”.⁷⁶ In this document he writes:

Flt.-myndirnar eru hvorir og hverjir, eftir því hvort rætt er um tvo eða fleiri hópa. Athuga þarf þau orð, sem vísað er til, en hvorir (tveir hópar) og hverjir (fleiri en tveir hópar) eru yfirleitt í sama falli og kyni og þau: Nemendur og kennarar skólans virða hvorir aðra, og: Þeim er vel hvorum við aðra. – Fleiri en tveir hópar: Njósningar allra stórveldanna óttuðust hverjir aðra, og þeim var heldur illa hverjum við aðra.

The plural forms [of *hvor* and *hver*] are *hvorir* and *hverjir*, depending on whether one talks about two or more groups. *Hvorir* (two groups) and *hverjir* (more than two groups) are generally in the same case and gender as their antecedent. For example: “The school's students and teachers respect each other” [*hvorir aðra* – *i.e.*, plural form of *hvor* used], and “They like each other” [once again, the plural form of *hvor* is used]. (For) when there are more than two groups (use examples like): “All the spies of the superpowers feared each other and they rather disliked each other” [*hverjir aðra* – *i.e.*, plural form of *hver* used]. (My translation)

There is some evidence to suggest that the singular form of *hver* is now becoming a

74 http://tea.fernuni-hagen.de/Iglo/Install/kurs/text_without_exercises_56065.htm

75 This distinction in singular/plural morphology is mandatory in Old Norse (see section 2.7 below).

76 <http://www.mr.is/sel/isl/OIOGottm.pdf>

default form because both in reciprocal constructions and when *hver* is used solely as a quantifier (such as in sentences (34b) and (35) above), it can be used in place of *hver* in casual speech. That is to say, in casual speech (and writing) speakers are observed to use *hver/hvern annan* in each of the different situations above, but the converse never occurs. For example, *hver annan* may be used in a sentence with an antecedent containing just two individuals, but *hver annan* cannot be used in a sentence with an antecedent containing three groups. Furthermore, speakers can optionally use the singular forms of *hver* or *hver* in sentences like (45) above, but the plural forms of the quantifiers are not used when the antecedent contains only individual entities. Note that this distinction between singular and plural forms of *hver/hver* in the sagas (Icelandic literature, 13-15th century – see section 7 below) was apparently mandatory.

We might speculate on why *hver* in the singular is becoming the default form of the reciprocal construction. One possibility is that the need for a default form of the reciprocal construction might arise from speakers using a fixed form of the reciprocal construction. For example, as we will see *hver/hver* no longer receives case for some speakers – perhaps indicating that *hver annan* is slowly becoming analysed as a single constituent (*c.f.*, eachother in English).⁷⁷ As such, it may be that the number feature is also reverting to the default, unmarked form as well.

Another possibility revolves around how the reciprocal construction interacts with pronominal antecedents:

- (48) *Þeir* *sáu* *hver* *annan*.
 They.3PL.NOM see.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “They saw each other.”

The extensions to number discussed above can be understood intuitively with antecedents being conjoined NP's representing groups or individuals. However, whether the subject pronoun in (48) is considered to now represent a single group or, through context, a number of groups and/or individuals is more difficult to decide and it is possible that speakers simply use the default singular forms of *hver* and *hver* in these situations.

⁷⁷ For example the search term “saw eachother” on Google 24/2/12 lists about 270,000 results compared to 29 million for “saw each other”.

2.5.3 Analysis

As demonstrated above, there is a four way distinction in the way number can be described in Icelandic reciprocal constructions. These forms are (assuming case is constant):

(49)	All entities individuals	At least one entity a group
2 entities engaged in a symmetric relationship	“The boy and the man” 2 NP's, both singular <i>hvor annar (m.sg form)</i> <i>hvor önnur (f.sg form)</i> <i>hvort annað (n.sg form)</i>	“The boy and the men” 2 NP's, at least one plural, <i>hvorir aðrir (m.pl form)</i> <i>hvorar aðrar (f.pl form)</i> <i>hver önnur (n.pl form)</i>
3+ entities engaged in a symmetric relationship	“The boy, the man and the horse” >2 NP's, all singular <i>hver annar (m.sg form)</i> <i>hver önnur (f.sg form)</i> <i>hvert annað (n.sg form)</i>	“The boy, the men and the horse” >2 NP's, at least one plural <i>hverjir aðrir (m.pl form)</i> <i>hverjar aðrir (f.pl form)</i> <i>hver önnur (n.pl form)</i>

Table 2.4 Summary of number and the Icelandic reciprocal construction

The first thing to note is that the choice of using *hvor* or *hver* in a reciprocal construction is not the same as a grammatical dual/plural number distinction. For example, consider two groups conjoined in a single NP: [[Peter and Mary] and [Eric and Joan]]. This NP contains four entities and so would be marked with plural rather than dual number. However, a reciprocal construction referring to this group uses the plural form of *hvor*. Furthermore, the distinction in number between the singular and plural forms of *hvor* and *hver* is not a distinction in the grammatical number of the antecedent NP, but rather one that comes from the grammatical number of the entities which make up the antecedent NP.

In terms of analysis, the key question to consider is whether this distinction in the grouping of participants is semantic or syntactic. If syntactic, we have to capture these distinctions using concord in f-structure. However, these distinctions cannot be captured using standard concord attributes such as number. For example, recall (37) (repeated as (50) below) where the antecedent to the reciprocal construction is *hjón* – “married

couple”. Here the antecedent has plural morphology, but the reciprocal construction appears in the singular:

- (50) *Hjón* *geta* *elskað* *hvert*
 married-couple.N.PL.NOM be-able-to.3PL.PRES love.PPL each.N.SG.NOM/ACC
annað *meira en systkini* *þó þau*
 other.N.SG.ACC more than sibling.N.PL.NOM yet they.N.PL.NOM
séu *ekki skyld.*⁷⁸
 are.3PL.SBJ.PRES not related.N.PL.NOM
 “(A) married couple are able to love each other more than siblings (can) yet they are not related.”

Contrast this with (46), repeated below, where the antecedent NP is also plural (being formed from the conjoint of God (SG) and mankind (PL)), but where the reciprocal construction now has plural number:

- (46) *Jól-in* *eru* *sá tími* *þegar Guð* *og*
 Xmas.N.PL.NOM-the be.3PL.PRES one time.M.SG.NOM when God.M.SG.NOM and
mennir-nir *skilja* *hvorir* *aðra.*⁷⁹
 man.M.PL.NOM-the understand.3PL.PRES each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.ACC
 “Christmas is the one time when God and mankind understand each other.”

As the above demonstrates, the distinction in the number of the reciprocal construction is independent of the number of its antecedent.⁸⁰ Although we could capture the reciprocal construction's number agreement in syntax, it would require the invention of new syntactic attributes that have little utility elsewhere in Icelandic, or indeed in other languages. As such, the view I follow here is that the choice between *hver* and *hver*, and

78 <http://www.malefnin.com/ib/index.php?showtopic=11670&mode=threaded&pid=313832>

79 <http://tru.is/postilla/2005/12/jolin-eru-komin/>

80 Historically, Icelandic also had dual (DU) number. It might be possible that we could analyse the sg/pl distinction in *hver annar* as being sensitive to the number (DU/PL) of the antecedent NP. However, dual number is not usually considered as being assigned to NPs in Icelandic and the sg/pl distinction in *hver annar* cannot be explained using this analysis.

the number assigned to *hvor* and *hver* (whether singular or plural) is semantic – and follows the rules described in (49) above. A semantic treatment of this number distinction is beyond the scope of this thesis, therefore, in terms of number, the only grammatical concord between the reciprocal construction and its antecedent is that the antecedent be plural. We can capture this using existing LFG formalism (e.g., see Dalrymple (2000:156)) which treats the NUM feature of a set as being *nondistributive* – that is, the coordinate NP can have a different number (in this case PL) compared to its individual conjoints (which have singular number). This is captured using a phrase structure rule for coordination which assigns plural number to the coordinating NP, and updating the lexical entries for *hvor*, *hver* and *annar* to require that their antecedent have plural number:

- (51) NP → NP CNJ NP
- $\begin{array}{c} \uparrow \in \downarrow \\ (\downarrow \text{GEND}) \subseteq (\uparrow \text{GEND}) \end{array}$
 $\uparrow \text{NUM} = \text{PL}$
 $\begin{array}{c} \uparrow \in \downarrow \\ (\downarrow \text{GEND}) \subseteq (\uparrow \text{GEND}) \end{array}$
- | | | |
|-----------------------|-------------|--------------------------------|
| <i>hvor, hvorir</i> | <i>det,</i> | ANT NUM = PL
ANT GEND = {M} |
| <i>hver, hverjir,</i> | <i>det,</i> | ANT NUM = PL
ANT GEND = {M} |
| <i>annar, aðrir</i> | <i>pro,</i> | ANT NUM = PL
ANT GEND = {M} |

Using these lexical definitions, we can now correctly predict the grammaticality of Icelandic reciprocal construction with respect to number, and gender. For example, the c- and f-structures for the antecedent NP in (52) are given below (note that only features relevant to this discussion are included):

- (52) *Stelpa-n* *og* *strákur-inn* *sáú*
- girl.F.SG.NOM-the and boy.M.SG.NOM-the see.3PL.PST
- hvort* *annað.*
- each.N.SG.ACC/NOM other.N.SG.ACC
- “The girl and the boy saw each other.”

The lexical entries for *hvort* and *annað* both require that the antecedent have

plural number and neuter (= {M,F}) gender:

hvort, *det*, ANT NUM = PL
ANT GEND = {M,F}

annað, *pro*, ANT NUM = PL
ANT GEND = {M,F}

The f-structure of the antecedent NP carries all features:

2.5.4 Conclusion

The relationship between an antecedent and the form of Icelandic reciprocal used to express symmetry is complex. We saw in (49) that there are four distinct forms of the reciprocal construction which are related to four different types of the antecedent. Syntactically, the reciprocal construction only requires that its antecedent be plural. However, there is a far richer system in semantics which is sensitive to the number of groups in the reciprocal relation (*hvort* is used when there are two groups in opposition, *hver* when there is more than two) and the grammatical number of those groups (when all the groups have singular number, the reciprocal construction has singular morphology, otherwise it is plural).⁸¹ We will see in section 2.7 that this complex system of “number” agreement is related to the historical origins of the construction where *hvort/hver* quantified the subject noun directly. Many speakers have extended their usage of *hver* to include situations where there are only two groups in opposition in the symmetric relation (that is to say, situations usually expressed using *hvort*). However the converse is not true, and so it seems that *hver* is slowly becoming the default form of the construction (see the analysis in section 2.8 for further discussion).

81 In the absence of a semantic treatment of the distinction between *hvort* and *hver*, both will be glossed as “each” in the examples below.

2.6 SURVEY ON *HVOR ANNAR* AND CASE

In sections 2.4 and 2.5 I considered gender and number. The feature of gender and its analysis was relatively simple both in its formation and analysis. However, the relationship the reciprocal construction has with respect to number morphology and the selection of *hvor* vs *hver* was complex and extended beyond simple syntactic concord.

Having dealt with these features, I now turn to the more complex issue of case. By understanding precisely how the reciprocal construction interacts with case we can identify the construction's reciprocation strategy and so begin to untangle its different variants and gain insight into its unusual syntactic behaviour. However, we saw earlier that there is disagreement between various sources as to how the construction should be formed, and much variation in how the construction is actually formed – both between speakers, but also in its usage by individual speakers. For example in (53) below, the same speaker can apparently use either of two forms of the reciprocal construction in the same context – the first where *hvor* has the same case its antecedent, and the second where *hvor* has the same case as *annar*:

(53) ...*til þess* *að þeir* *gætu* *elskað*
to that.N.SG.GEN to they.M.PL.NOM able.3PL.PST.SUBJ love.PPL

hvor *annan* *og unnið* *saman.*
each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC and work.PPL together.

Ekki til þess *að drepa hvorn* *annan.*⁸²
Not to that.N.SG.GEN to kill.INF each.M.SG.ACC other.M.SG.ACC

“[God created man and woman] ...so that they can love each other and work together. Not in order to kill each other”

We also saw that the reciprocal construction acts in different ways with respect to distribution and case in prepositional phrases. This is illustrated for example in (54) where *hver* appears in the nominative outside a PP, but in the genitive when inside it:

82 <http://www.mbl.is/mm/frettir/erlent/frett.html?nid=1175372>

- (54) a. *Tryggingamenn virðast taka mikið tillit*
 Insurance_people seem_to take.3PL.PRES much regard.M.ACC.SG

*hver til annars í samkeppninni.*⁸³
 each.M.SG.NOM to other.M.SG.GEN in competition
 “Insurance people in competition seem to show much consideration to each other.”
- b. *Allir taka tillit til hvers annars.*⁸⁴
 All take.3PL.PRES regard.M.ACC.SG to each.GEN other.GEN
 “All show consideration for each other.”

In order to understand these constructions, I needed to gather data to answer several questions regarding its case marking and distribution. For example, Everaert (1991) has claimed that speakers will not allow *hver* to appear inside a PP with antecedent case marking – but I will demonstrate that this is the preferred construction in some situations. This raises additional questions that need to be answered – for example, what motivates the use of one construction over another?

Answering these questions required examining the reciprocal construction in a multitude of different environments – some of which are very rare and unlikely to occur frequently in natural language. For example, the overwhelming majority of reciprocal situations will have the antecedent in nominative case – and so it is very difficult to unambiguously determine whether *hver* or *hver* is agreeing with the antecedent or simply unmarked with respect to case (that is, using the default form which is typically the masculine, singular nominative for accusative languages.). To answer these questions I designed a survey which ran from 2008 to 2009 and collected data from 504 participants. Due to the length of the survey (50 questions) my investigation was, for the most part, limited to the formation of the *hver annar* construction in relation to various syntactic environments and ignored the related *hver annar* construction. However, corpus searches on the usage of *hver annar* show that it has the same distribution as *hver annar* (subject to number restrictions), and so the results gained here can be safely

83 http://www.mbl.is/mm/gagnasafn/grein.html?grein_id=226798

84 http://www.helviti.com/punknurse/2001_09_09_dagbokold.htm

said to apply to *hver annar* as well as *hvor annar*.

After receiving ethics approval for the project from the University of Melbourne, I made the survey available online. This meant that all respondents required a computer and basic computer literacy in order to sign up for and complete the survey. However, by using an online survey, I was able to quickly gather responses from people across a wide variety of age groups and locations in Iceland. Participants were either personally invited to take part in the survey, or they could volunteer at the survey sign up web page. In either event, the participants were directed to the online survey where they could answer the questions. The respondents can be broadly divided into two groups – a group of about 140 older speakers (aged 50+) and about 350 younger students from the University of Iceland (Háskóli Íslands).

There were three types of questions in the survey; multi-choice, ranking and long answer questions:

A typical multi-choice question.

(ii) Bræðurnir sáu [??? ???] Merktu við sem við á
<input type="checkbox"/> hvort annað <input type="checkbox"/> hvor aðra <input type="checkbox"/> hvora aðra <input type="checkbox"/> hvorn annan <input type="checkbox"/> hvor annan

Here the participant is presented with a list of forms of *hver annar* (in the singular) – varied by case. They are asked to select any which they might hear used in the sentence “The brothers saw each other”.

A typical ranking question.

(iv) Raðaðu eftirfarandi setningum eftir því hvora er líklegra að þú notir sértu að skrifa í dagblað.	
Smelltu á atriði á listanum til vinstri. Veldu fyrst dæmið sem þér þykir eðlilegra/eðlilegast. Val: <div style="background-color: #add8e6; width: 150px; height: 15px; margin: 5px 0;"></div> Smelltu á skærin hægra megin til þess að fjarlægja síðustu færslu í niðurröðun.	Niðurröðun: 1. Vandamálið er að stjórnáamenn virða ekki hver annan. 1. Vandamálið er að stjórnáamenn virða ekki hvern annan.

Figure 2.1 Examples of Question Types

In the ranking question above, the participant is asked to rank two sentences in order

according to which sounds better in the context of a letter to the editor. The sentences here are the same (“The problem is that politicians don't respect each other”) – the difference being the case forms used in the reciprocal construction.

The third type of question was a long answer question. These questions were provided so that participants could add their comments regarding any of their responses to previous questions. Overwhelmingly, the comments received related to issues regarding the participant's opinion as to the “correct” forms of various constructions.

To prepare for the survey, I first created a pilot study with four participants. The key issue that needed to be addressed as a result of this trial was that of “correctness”. Many Icelanders are very literate with an interest in their language. As a result, some participants in the trial consulted Icelandic grammars and/or prescriptive language experts in order to provide the “correct” answer – even if at times these answers did not reflect the language they actually used. Talking with Icelanders, it became apparent that this might be a real issue in the final survey when opened to more people – particularly with respect to older speakers. I attempted to address this issue in three ways:

1. By emphasising to all participants that the survey was anonymous.
2. By telling participants that I was seeking to record what people actually say, and that I was not looking for the “correct answer”.
3. By allowing participants to record not only their responses to the questions but also “what they hear other people say”.

As a result, it is possible that my survey will record more forms of *hvor annar* than are in actual use. However, when comparing the results I have attained with searches on the internet – strong agreement is found between my survey and Google searches. A full translation of the survey and related materials (such as the sign up process *etc.*) is available in appendix B of this thesis.

Finally, although people had the option to record more than one response to the multi-choice questions, most declined to do so, presumably only recording the version of *hvor annar* they used or heard in day-to-day speech.

2.6.1 Discussion of statistics

In a survey of this kind, statistics are used to provide a measure of the confidence that

the results attained in the survey reflect those that would be attained if the entire population were surveyed. The accuracy of the survey is measured using two parameters – a *margin of error* and a *confidence level*. For a population of approximately 317,398 and a sample size of 504 these parameters are:⁸⁵

Margin of Error: 4.36%
Confidence Level: 95%

In order to understand these parameters examine the results from section A, question (ii) on the survey:⁸⁶

(ii) *Bræðurnir sáu [??? ???] / The brothers saw [each other].*

Answers ⁸⁷	Raw Count ⁸⁸	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i> M.SG.NOM M.SG.ACC	126	24.32%
<i>hvorn annan</i> M.SG.ACC M.SG.ACC	388	74.90%
<i>hvor aðra</i> F.SG.NOM F.SG.ACC	4	0.77%
<i>hvora aðra</i> F.SG.ACC F.SG.ACC	0	0.0%
<i>hvort annað</i> N.SG.NOM/ACC N.SG.ACC	0	0.0%

Table 2.5 Different forms of *hvor annar* for question 2, section A.

A margin of error of 4.36% means that if the question above were asked of the entire

85 The maximum margin of error for a confidence level of 95% is given by the following formula where P = 50 (representing the worse case situation (in a statistical sense) where respondents are evenly split in their answers to a question, n = sample size (504) and N = population size (300,000):

$$\text{Margin of Error} = \pm 1.96 \sqrt{\frac{(100-P)P}{n} \times \frac{(N-n)}{N-1}}$$

86 The respondents would select the forms of *hvor annar* from a list which they thought could appear in the place of the square brackets containing question marks.

87 The gender, number and case forms for *hvor* and *annar* represent the possible forms given context of the question. *Hvor*, for example, is the form used for both the masculine and feminine singular nominative. However given the context of the brothers seeing each other, the feminine interpretation can be ignored. See section 4 for further discussion on this point.

88 In many questions, respondents could pick more than one answer.

Icelandic population, we could expect the percentage of people selecting *hvor annan* to be in the range of 19.9% – 28.5%. Note that the margin of error becomes considerably smaller when considering results which nobody or just one or two people selected (such as with *hvor aðra* above). In these situations, the margin of error decreases to less than 0.5%. The confidence level reflects how sure we can be that the margin of error is correct. For example, in my survey of 50 questions, a confidence level of 95% would mean that if all 50 questions were asked of the entire Icelandic population, we could expect that in only 2-3 questions (*i.e.*, 5% of the questions), would the actual results fall outside of the 4.36% margin of error. For my purposes, it is enough to know that there are two ways which people form the reciprocal construction in the context above, *hvor annan* and *hvorn annan*. How these different constructions should be analysed is answered in section 2.8.

2.6.2 Syncretic forms of *hvor* and *annar*

Because *hvor* and *annar* have many syncretic forms (*e.g.*, the plural dative form of *hvor* - “*hvorum*” is the same in all genders), the glosses for each word will reflect their most likely forms given the context. This judgement is based on two well-founded assumptions:

- The number distinction between *hvor* and *annar* remains the same in the reciprocal construction (*i.e.*, both *hvor* and *annar* are singular or plural).
- The gender distinction between *hvor* and *annar* remains the same in the reciprocal construction (*i.e.*, both *hvor* and *annar* are masculine, feminine or neuter).

In other words, with respect to morphology, the only variation in the reciprocal construction occurs with respect to case and distribution and not number and gender. For example, *aðra* is both the feminine singular and masculine plural accusative form of *annar*. However, given its co-occurrence with a feminine singular form of *hvor* we can safely analyse *hvor aðra* as *hvor*:F.SG.NOM *aðra*:F.SG.ACC and not some other combination of number, case and gender. That this assumption is well-founded can be seen in the survey data collected and in corpus searches – the formation of reciprocal construction *never* occurs with different number and/or gender on *hvor* and *annar*.

2.6.3 Constructions Identified

The syntactic analysis of the survey results will be discussed in section 2.8. However in terms of how the construction is formed with respect to case, three separate constructions can be identified. As noted earlier, in all instances both within the survey and more generally, *hvor* and *annar* share the same number and gender. Furthermore, for nearly every participant surveyed, *annar* has its case governed by the verb or preposition which controls it. That is to say, while there is much variation in the case marking of *hvor*, there is very little or no (in most instances) variation in the case marking of *annar*. The three constructions identified are:

1. *The antecedent case reciprocal construction*: where *hvor* shares the same case as its antecedent, and *annar* has its case governed by the verb or preposition which controls it:

(55) Survey – section A, question ii: 74.90% of responses

- a. *Bræður-nir* *sáu* *hvor* *annan*.
 brother.M.PL.NOM-the see.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “The brothers saw each other.”

Survey – section B, question iv: 23.52% of responses

- b. *Ég* *kynnti* *menni-na* *tvo*
 I.1SG.NOM introduce.1SG.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the two.M.PL.ACC

hvorn *fyrir* *öðrum*.
 each.M.SG.ACC for other.M.SG.DAT
 “I introduced the two men to each other.”

Survey – section D, question vi: 64.55% of responses

- c. *Strákar-nir* *tveir* *björguðu*
 boy.M.PL.NOM-the two.M.PL.NOM rescue.3PL.PST

hvor *öðrum*.
 each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.DAT
 “The two boys rescued each other.”

This construction matches the traditional account of the reciprocal construction (see section 2.3.1). That *hvor* agrees in case with its antecedent is evidenced by sentences like (55a) and (55b) above. In (55a) *bræðurnir* – “the brothers”, is in nominative case and so is *hvor*. In (55b) *mennini tvo*, “the two men” is in accusative case – and so is *hvor*. Sentence like (55b) allow us to rule out the hypothesis that the case of *hvor* is (always) simply fixed to be nominative in this instance. Note in (55c), even when the verb assigns irregular case to its object (*björguðu* – “rescued” assigns dative case to its object), *hvor* can still appear in nominative case.

2. *The phrasal reciprocal construction*: where *hvor* and *annar* both share the same case – governed by the verb or preposition which controls *annar*. Consider (56a) and (56b) below:

(56) Survey – section A, question iii: 43.92% of responses

- a. *Konur-nar* *sáu* *hvora* *aðra*.
women.F.PL.NOM-the see.3PL.PST each.F.SG.ACC other.F.SG.ACC
 “The women saw each other.”

Survey – section D, question vi: 34.14% of responses

- b. *Strákar-nir* *tveir* *björguðu*
boy.M.PL.NOM-the two.M.PL.NOM rescue.3PL.PST
- hvorum* *öðrum*.
each.M.SG.DAT other.M.SG.DAT
 “The two boys rescued each other.”

In (56a), both *hvor* and *annar* appear in accusative case. In (56b), the verb assigns irregular case to its object – and once again, *hvor* and *annar* can share this irregular case.

3. *The fixed form reciprocal construction*: where *annar* has its case governed by the verb or preposition which controls it, while *hvor* remains fixed in the nominative form:

(57) Survey – section B, question iv: 7.49% of responses

a. *Ég kynnti menni-na tvo*
 I.1SG.NOM introduce.1SG.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the two.M.PL.ACC

hver fyrir öðrum.
 each.M.SG.NOM for other.M.SG.DAT

“I introduced the two men to each other.”

Survey – section B, question iv: 38.50% of responses

b. *Ég kynnti menni-na tvo*
 I.1SG.NOM introduce.1SG.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the two.M.PL.ACC

fyrir hver öðrum.
 for each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.DAT

“I introduced the two men to each other.”

Survey – section E, question ii: 13.16% of responses

c. *Elskhuga-na dreymdi hver annan.*⁸⁹
 lover.M.PL.ACC-the dream.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC

“The lovers dreamt of each other.”

Usually the fixed form of the reciprocal construction is hard to discern because the antecedent is typically in nominative and so it can't be distinguished from the antecedent case construction. However, in unusual syntactic constructions where the antecedent is marked with a non-nominative case, *hver* appears in nominative case in a significant number of responses. For example, in (57a) and (57b) above, the antecedent is the direct object – appearing in accusative case. Of the various reciprocal constructions which can be used to describe this event, 46% of respondents picked a construction with *hver* appearing with nominative case. Clearly then, this form of *hver* must be fixed, as it is certainly not agreeing in case with its antecedent – nor with *annar*. In (57c) the verb *dreymdi* assigns accusative case to its subject. Once again, a significant number of

⁸⁹ *dreymdi* (from *dreyma* - to dream) like many other experiential verbs in Icelandic is irregular, assigning accusative case to both its subject and object.

respondents used a reciprocal construction with *hvor* appearing in nominative case.

2.6.4 The distribution of *hvor* and PPs

Recall that Everaert (2001) identified 4 possible ways *hvor* could appear with a PP – and considered only two grammatical:

(58) Everaert (1991:282), labeled as (15) in his text.

- | | | | | | |
|----|-------------|----------|--------------|--------------|--------------|
| a. | <i>NP</i> | <i>V</i> | <i>hvor</i> | <i>prep</i> | <i>annan</i> |
| | | | [NOM] | | [ACC] |
| | | | | | |
| b. | * <i>NP</i> | <i>V</i> | <i>prep</i> | <i>hvor</i> | <i>annan</i> |
| | | | | [NOM] | [ACC] |
| | | | | | |
| c. | * <i>NP</i> | <i>V</i> | <i>hvorn</i> | <i>prep</i> | <i>annan</i> |
| | | | [ACC] | | [ACC] |
| | | | | | |
| d. | <i>NP</i> | <i>V</i> | <i>prep</i> | <i>hvorn</i> | <i>annan</i> |
| | | | | [ACC] | [ACC] |

According to Plank (2008), when *hvor/hver* appears inside a prepositional phrase its case agrees with *annar* (see section 5.1). However, although this is usually the case for common instances of the reciprocal construction (such as might occur with a masculine antecedent and a preposition which selects a complement with accusative case), this analysis is a generalisation at best for some prepositions. For example, in my survey respondents were asked to select the forms of *hvor annar* that they would use or would hear others use. Question iv, section C asked which of the following forms they would use to describe the sentence, “The two women talked about each other”:

(59) Survey – Section C, question iv

- | | | | |
|-----------------|--------------|---------------|----------------------|
| <i>Konurnar</i> | <i>tvær</i> | <i>töluðu</i> | <i>[??? ??? ???]</i> |
| woman.F.PL.NOM | two.F.PL.NOM | talk.3PL.PST | |

Responses

<i>um hvor aðra</i> (about each.F.SG.NOM other.F.SG.ACC)	241	43.04%
<i>um hvora aðra</i> (about each.F.SG.ACC other.F.SG.ACC)	116	20.71%
<i>hvor um aðra</i> (each.F.SG.NOM about other.F.SG.ACC)	197	35.18%
<i>hvora um aðra</i> (each.F.SG.ACC about other.F.SG.ACC)	6	1.07%

As the responses above show *hvor* can certainly appear in a PP with nominative case for at least 43% of speakers.⁹⁰ What then conditions where *hvor* will appear in a PP, and what its case will be? To answer these questions I asked the survey participants a series of questions similar to (59) above – changing the prepositions involved, and the gender of the antecedent. The choice of preposition (*um*, *frá* and *til*) was designed to test whether the case assigned to *annar* (accusative, dative and genitive respectively) affected the respondents choice of reciprocal construction. Likewise, the choice of an antecedent with differing genders was designed to see how gender might affect the participant's choice of construction. The sentences used in the examples appear below and can be seen in full in appendix B. Recall that respondents could choose any of the forms of the reciprocal construction that Everaert (2001) identifies in (58) above:

(60) *Strákarnir / Konurnar / Maðurinn og konan töluðu [??? ??? ???].*

The boys/women/man and woman talked about (*um*) each other.

Strákarnir / Konurnar / Maðurinn og konan hlupu [??? ??? ???].

The boys/women/man and woman ran from (*frá*) each other.

Strákarnir / Konurnar / Maðurinn og konan hlupu [??? ??? ???].

The boys/women/man and woman ran to (*til*) each other.

The results of this investigation are presented below in three tables, separated by gender:

⁹⁰ Recall that the margin of error for this survey is about 4% with 95% confidence.

Masculine Antecedent

<i>preposition</i>	<i>hvor</i> sharing case of antecedent		<i>hvor</i> and <i>annar</i> having same case	
	<i>hvor P annar</i>	<i>P hvor annar</i>	<i>hvor P annar</i>	<i>P hvor annar</i>
<i>um</i> (acc)	169 (30%)	55 (10%)	21 (4%)	310 (56%)
<i>frá</i> (dat)	216 (38%)	249 (44%)	2 (0%)	99 (18%)
<i>til</i> (gen)	157 (28%)	48 (9%)	14 (3%)	332 (60%)

Feminine Antecedent

<i>preposition</i>	<i>hvor</i> sharing case of antecedent		<i>hvor</i> and <i>annar</i> having same case	
	<i>hvor P annar</i>	<i>P hvor annar</i>	<i>hvor P annar</i>	<i>P hvor annar</i>
<i>um</i> (acc)	197 (35%)	241 (43%)	6 (1%)	116 (21%)
<i>frá</i> (dat)	197 (35%)	252 (45%)	2 (0%)	113 (20%)
<i>til</i> (gen)	246 (44%)	183 (33%)	6 (1%)	118 (21%)

Neuter Antecedent

<i>preposition</i>	<i>hvor</i> sharing case of antecedent		<i>hvor</i> and <i>annar</i> having same case	
	<i>hvor P annar</i>	<i>P hvor annar</i>	<i>hvor P annar</i>	<i>P hvor annar</i>
<i>um</i> (acc)	<i>see note below</i>			
<i>frá</i> (dat)	234 (41%)	253 (44%)	5 (1%)	81 (14%)
<i>til</i> (gen)	170 (31%)	48 (9%)	7 (1%)	326 (59%)

Table 2.6 Interaction of preposition selection and case

Note that the neuter singular nominative and accusative forms of *hvor* and *annar* are syncretic (*hvort* and *annað*) – and so no generalisations can be made about their distribution except that respondents will usually place the preposition first (67% of speakers choose the form *um hvort annað* as opposed to 33% choosing *hvort um annað*).

Several generalisations can be made from this data – the most striking of which is that if *hvor* appears before the preposition it invariably does so in nominative case and not in the case assigned to *annar*. Everaert's claim that *hvor* can't appear before a PP with a non-nominative case is well supported – typically less than 2% of respondents will allow such a construction. However, the situation is much more variable when considering *hvor* inside a PP. Overall, when *hvor* appears inside a PP, 47% of

respondents chose a form of the reciprocal construction with *hvor* appearing in nominative case (53% gave *hvor* the same case as *annar*). This result is at odds with Everaert's claim that *hvor* can't appear in a PP with nominative case. However, his data can be understood if we look more widely and consider the influence the antecedent's gender has on which constructions respondents are likely to choose. Examining the tables above, we see that when *hvor* occurs with a masculine antecedent (particularly in combination with a preposition selecting accusative case) speakers are much less likely to allow *hvor* inside the PP with nominative case.

The main factor in determining whether a speaker will select a construction where *hvor* and *annar* have the same case or not is related to the markedness of the construction. The masculine nominative form of *hvor/hver* is the least marked and it acts as the base morpheme. The dative and genitive forms of noun are typically more marked. For example, consider the singular forms of *hvor* below:

		Masculine	Feminine	Neuter
Sg.	nom.	<i>hvor</i>	<i>hvor</i>	<i>hvor-t</i>
	acc.	<i>hvor-n</i>	<i>hvor-a</i>	<i>hvor-t</i>
	dat.	<i>hvor-um</i>	<i>hvor-ri</i>	<i>hvor-u</i>
	gen.	<i>hvor-s</i>	<i>hvor-rar</i>	<i>hvor-s</i>

Table 2.7 Singular forms of *hvor*

Those constructions occurring with a preposition which selects accusative case for its complement are more likely to appear with *hvor* and *annar* in the same case, and those appearing with a masculine antecedent are also more likely to do the same.

2.6.5 Concluding remarks

Before a syntactic analysis can be made of these three constructions, we need to be aware of the relationship between each construction and their origin. These three constructions are clearly related, and so their respective analyses must also be related – that is to say that any analyses for these constructions must be historically plausible in how they could form from one another. So in section 2.7 I examine the reciprocal construction as it appeared in the Icelandic sagas.

2.7 THE RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION IN THE SAGAS

In section 2.6 I identified three reciprocal constructions based on different case marking strategies used for *hvor/hver*. These are:

1. *The antecedent case reciprocal construction*: where *hvor/hver* shares the same case as its antecedent, and *annar* has its case governed by the verb or preposition which controls it.

(61) Survey – Section A, question ii: 24.32% of responses.

Bræður-nir *sáu* *hvor* *annan*.
brother.M.PL.NOM-the see.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
“The brothers saw each other.”

2. *The phrasal reciprocal construction*: Where *hvor/hver* and *annar* both share the same case – governed by the verb or preposition which controls *annar*:

(62) Survey – Section A, question ii, 74.90% of responses.

Bræður-nir *sáu* *hvorn* *annan*.
brother.M.PL.NOM-the see.3PL.PST each.M.SG.ACC other.M.SG.ACC
“The brothers saw each other.”

3. *The fixed form reciprocal construction*: where *annar* has its case assigned by a verb or preposition, while *hvor/hver* remains fixed in the nominative form:

(63) Survey – Section E, question ii, 13.16% of responses.

Elskhuga-na *dreymdi* *hvor* *annan*.⁹¹
lover.M.PL.ACC-the dream.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
“The lovers dreamt of each other.”

As mentioned previously, to properly understand the relations between them, and ultimately what motivated this variation we need to first determine how they are related

91 *dreymdi* (from *dreyma* - to dream) like many other experiential verbs in Icelandic is irregular, assigning accusative case to both its subject and object.

diachronically. In this section I examine the *hvor/hver* reciprocal constructions as they are used in the *Íslendinga sögur* (the sagas of the Icelanders) because these texts preserve the older variants of the reciprocal construction. This survey reveals a fourth reciprocal construction (still in occasional use today) and that the usage of *hvor* and *hver* as both pronouns and determiners is by no means a modern innovation.

The Icelandic sagas are a collection of prose tales (some semi-historical) describing events occurring soon after Iceland was settled in late 9th century. These tales were first recorded in oral tradition before being written down some time in the 13th century (Sveinsson, 1958:12). The stories themselves are straightforward and remarkably unadorned. Typically they describe events and record what people said and did – the protagonists are usually both believable and consistent with their stated beliefs. This consistency of character might have been influenced by the extensive discussion of the sagas by the populace during the first centuries of settlement when the sagas were recorded orally. The sagas play an important role within Icelandic society, past and present, not only because they were much discussed and commented on by the populace in general, but because they formed the cultural heritage from which the Icelandic national identity rose during the 19th century (Einarsson, 1957:220-224).

2.7.1 The corpus

For the most part, this corpus comes from a collection of the sagas edited by Guðni Jónsson (Jónsson, 1946-1947, vol. 1-11). His collection is largely based upon the oldest extant manuscripts and preserves the spelling, grammar and word order of the originals. The twenty stories included in this corpus represent a significant portion of the commonly accepted canon and include the most famous of the sagas – Njál's saga or “The burning of Njall.” These sagas were chosen for a number of reasons, one of which was the availability of an electronic version of the text because this enabled me to search the corpus for reciprocal constructions relatively quickly. The list in appendix C details the name of each saga, its approximate length, and the approximate age of the manuscript or manuscripts Jónsson based his version on. Where available, I have included references to the English sources which have informed my own translations – but any errors remain mine.

2.7.1.1 NOTE ON LIST OF TEXTS MAKING THE CORPUS

It is important to note that the texts referenced below are of varying age. The earliest fragments of the sagas are from the 12th century, however, during the 13th and 14th centuries the sagas were transferred to vellum and rewritten (Nordal, 2006). It is these vellums that form the basis for most modern editions of the sagas and it is likely then that the reciprocal constructions found in this corpus for the most part come from texts that were written during the late 13th century into the 15th century. Although it is possible that the sagas written during this time preserve older linguistic forms, Sveinsson (1958:15) notes that the scribes who wrote down the tales were not particularly concerned with making a linguistically accurate transcription of each story. During the middle ages, many sagas were gathered together into single books. Three of these books (*Möðruvallabók*, *Flateyjabók* and *Hauksbók*) are from the 14th century and are the oldest existing copies of many of the sagas listed below – and where earlier copies of the same sagas do exist, these books are fairly faithful copies of the earlier versions (Sveinsson 1958). One such book, *Vatnshyrna*, was destroyed by fire in Copenhagen, 1728 and the sagas contained within it (*Laxdæla saga*, *Eyrbyggja saga*, *Vatnsdæla saga*, *Hænsa-Þóris saga* and *Flóamanna saga*) have been reconstructed from more recent sources. The word order and spelling in the example sentences below is probably reflective of that which was used between the 13th and 15th centuries in Iceland. As will be seen there are very distinct differences between the reciprocal constructions used in Old and Modern Icelandic. Note that the sagas as they appear in Jónsson use a standardised Old Icelandic spelling – a necessary device given the widespread use of abbreviations and different typological conventions used by the writers during the middle ages. The total corpus size is approximately 600,000 words.

2.7.2 Method of analysis

I searched the corpus for every instance of the different forms of *hvor* and *hver*. This search revealed a wide variety of symmetric situations, of which 93 instances were described by *hvor/hver annar* reciprocal constructions. For the purposes of simplicity, in this search I have ignored examples of symmetric situations which although reciprocal in nature and closely related to the reciprocal construction, are not strictly *hvor/hver annar* type constructions. For example, *hvárgi...annar* “neither – other” constructions (64a) and *hvárt-tveggja...annar* “both – other” constructions (64b) while appearing in

the corpus, they do not form of my analysis:

(64) Grettis saga: 36

a. *Voru dylgjur miklar með þeim*
 be.3PL.PST insinuation.F.PL.NOM heavy.F.PL.NOM with them.3PL.DAT

um vetur-inn en hvorigir
 during winter.M.SG.ACC-the but neither.M.PL.NOM

réðu á aðra.
 attack.3PL.PST at other.M.PL.ACC

“There were heavy insinuations between them during the winter, but neither attacked the other.”

b. Grettis saga: 62

... ok þótti þar hvártveggi vel
 and was-considered.3SG.PST there both.M.SG.NOM well

*gera við annan.*⁹²
 do.INF with other.M.SG.ACC

“and both there were considered to do well to the other.”

Note that although these related constructions are not included in my analysis, they do conform to the generalisations described below with respect to number and gender. From the 93 sentences containing a reciprocal construction, a further six were removed because the clause containing the reciprocal construction had an ellipited verb (e.g., (65) below):

(65) Hrafnkels saga:7

... ok hefir mér líkat vel til þín
 and have.3SG.PRES I.1SG.DAT like.PPL well to you.2SG.GEN

⁹² *að gera vel við s-r* - “to behave so that it is beneficial for someone”.

ok hvárum okkar til annars.
 and each.M.SG.DAT us.1PL.GEN to other.M.SG.GEN

“...and I have liked you well, as/and each of us (has liked) the other”

The ellipted verb in (65) is simply the repetition of the verb *hefir ... líkat* “have liked” from the first clause – although the reasons for supposing so are not immediately apparent. This can be seen because experiencer verbs such as “like” often have non-nominative subject case marking in Icelandic. These verbs are known as impersonal verbs – and their number agreement is frozen at 3rd person singular (hence the non-agreement in verb-subject concord above). And so, in (65) above, we see in the first clause the unusual case marking of the subject (*mér* in the dative instead of *ég* in nominative). The reciprocal construction has the same case marking with *hvárum* in the dative instead of the expected nominative form *hvárr*. Hence in (65), because of the unusual case marking of *hvárum*, we can be certain that not only is there an ellipted verb, but that the verb was *hefir ... líkat* “have liked”. While sentences such as these are perfectly acceptable, the lack of a verb makes it impossible to categorise the resulting reciprocal construction. This is because we need to know the number of the verb (see section 7.3 below for an explanation). For this reason, sentences like these have been removed from the corpus, leaving a total of 87 reciprocal constructions.

2.7.3 Analysis of results

In this section I categorize the remaining 87 reciprocal constructions into only two classes; compositional reciprocal constructions like (A) below, and antecedent case reciprocal constructions like (B). Note that there were no instances of the phrasal reciprocal construction:

A. *Compositional reciprocal construction (79 of 87 (or 91%) sentences)*

Gunnlaugs saga: 9

Sagði hvárr öðrum frá
 tell.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.DAT about

ferðum sínum.
 travel.F.PL.DAT refl-POSS.F.PL.DAT

“Each [*i.e.*, Gunnlaugr and Hrafn] told the other about their travels.”

B. Antecedent case reciprocal construction (8 of 87 (or 9%) sentences)

Hrafnkels saga:2

...en þó riðu þeir feðgar
 but still ride.3PL.PST they.M.PL.NOM father_and_son.M.PL.NOM

jafnan hvárir til annarra.
 always each.M.PL.NOM to other.M.PL.GEN

“but still, they, father and son, always rode to each other (to visit).”

The antecedent case reciprocal construction has already been identified in previous sections. Below I will argue that the compositional reciprocal construction (where *hvor/hver* is a pronoun acting as the subject of the verb) is the main reciprocal construction in Old Icelandic. However, the classification of these constructions is not at all trivial and a brief look at the 87 reciprocal constructions in appendix B is misleading. At first glance, it appears that the antecedent case reciprocal construction *hvor/hver annan* is widespread, but in fact closer examination reveals that this is not the case. For example, examine (66) below:

(66) Njáls saga:63

Síðan eggjaði hverr annan.
 Then egg_on.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC

“Then each egged the other on / each incited the other”

Hverr (the Old Icelandic form of *hver*) here appears next to *annar*, looking similar to Modern Icelandic reciprocal constructions such as (67) below:

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- (67) *Þeir sáu hver annan.*
 They.3PL.M.NOM see.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “They saw each other.”

However, there are several differences between these sentences. The first, if we assume an antecedent case reciprocal construction analysis, is that the verb *eggja* in (66) has no clear subject within the sentence. While it could be supposed that the subject has been ellipsed in this instance, the fact that the verb in (66) has singular agreement strongly suggests that *hverr* is actually the subject of the sentence. Under this analysis, the word order in (66) would be VSO. Given that the word order in the Modern Icelandic sentence in (67) is SVO – can this analysis be maintained? Word order in Old Icelandic has been much discussed in the literature and is not, as many early linguists thought, entirely unconstrained (Davies 2006). For our purposes though, it is enough to show that VSO word order in Old Icelandic was common and used in a variety of situations – especially when a sentence is introduced by an adverbial phrase. For example compare (68a) with SV word order to (68b):

- (68) SV word order – Njáls saga: 103

- a. *Þeir fóru í Hagi við*
 They.3PL.M.NOM go.3PL.PST to Hagi.M.SG.ACC with
 S V

sex tigu manna.

six ten man.M.PL.GEN

“They went to Hagi with 60 men.”

- b. VS word order – Njáls saga: 102

- Eftir það skildu þau Þangbrandr*
 After it.3SG.ACC depart.3PL.PST they.3PL.NEU.NOM Þangbrandr.M.SG.NOM
 V S

- ok Steinunn... ok fóru þeir vestr*
 and Steinunn.F.SG.NOM and go.3PL.PST they.3PL.M.NOM west
 V S

til Barðastrandar.

to Barðaströnd.F.SG.GEN

“After that they_i, Þangbrandr and Steinunn departed... and they_j went west to Barðaströnd.”

The VS word order is typical of Old Icelandic – and it can be seen in Modern Icelandic as well where there is a change in word order from SVO to VSO under similar circumstances:

(69) *Hann berst við Loka og*
 He.3SG.M.NOM fight.SG.PRES.MV with Loki.M.SG.ACC and
 S V

*fella þeir hvor annan.*⁹³
 kill.3PL.PRES they.M.PL.NOM each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 V S O

“He fights with Loki and they kill each other.”

So, given this change of word order, I interpret *hvor* in sentences like (66) as being the subject of the verb. Therefore, I propose that these sentences should be analysed as compositional reciprocal constructions where *hvor/hver* is the subject of the verb, and *annar* is either an object or an oblique. This means that the two reciprocal constructions in sentences (70a) and (70b) below are in essence the same – there is a difference in word order, but not in the functions each word has:

(70) Egils saga: 57

a. ...*ok áðr þeir mættust, þá skaut*
 and before they.3PL.M.NOM join.PL.PST.MV, then hurl.3SG.PST

93 <http://www.hi.is/~gardarg/edda/godin.html>

hvárr kesju at öðrum.
 each.M.SG.NOM halberd.F.SG.DAT at other.M.SG.DAT

“...and before they joined each other (in hand-to-hand combat), each hurled a halberd at the other.”

Njáls saga: 52

b. ...*hvárr rann eftir öðrum.*
 each.M.SG.NOM run.3SG.PST after other.M.SG.DAT

“each ran after the other.”

These sentences exemplify both the word orders. The reciprocal construction in (70a) is like (66) above with VSO word order. The second reciprocal construction has SVO word order, with *hvorr* on one side of the verb and *annar* on the other. In both cases, the reciprocal constructions are compositional reciprocal constructions where *hvorr/hverr* functions as the subject of the verb and *annar* functions as the object or oblique. In sentences like those in (70), we can be sure that the subject of both the reciprocal constructions is actually *hvorr* because of the singular agreement marking on the verbs. If there were an ellipsed subject (which would be plural) then the agreement marking on the verb would be plural. Using both the verbal marking and lack of an overt antecedent as evidence, in the 58 reciprocal constructions found in the corpus with singular forms of *hvorr/hverr*, nearly all (55 from 58 or 95%) are instances of the compositional reciprocal construction where *hvorr/hverr* acts as the subject of the verb.

However, there were 29 instances where plural forms of *hvorr* and *hverr* were used in the reciprocal construction. In these situations, the verbal agreement becomes plural also:

(71) Laxdæla saga: 59

*Fagna þar hvárir öðrum vel.*⁹⁴
 welcome.3PL.PRES there each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.DAT well

“Each greets the other well there”

94 Note the plural morphology of *hvorr*. As expected from the previous discussion on number, the antecedent is made from two entities greeting each other - one of them a group (a mother and her sons greet a man while riding).

For sentences with a plural reciprocal construction, the case for arguing that either of *hvor* or *hver* is actually the subject of the verb is less straightforward because the number of the verb also remains the same under the analysis where a plural pronoun in subject position has been ellipted. To clarify the issue here, consider the English sentence below:

(72) *Two groups of men entered the room and saw each other.*

In English, we would analyse the second clause as having an ellipted pronoun “they” – so (72) would read “Two groups of men entered the room and [they]_{ellipted} saw each other.” However, Icelandic also allows another possibility because it has (at least) two possible word orders, SVO and VSO. This means that the second clause in (72) could be read as either VSO word order as in “...saw each_{subj} the other_{obj}” or SVO order in “[they]_{ellipted} saw each_{obj}”. When *hvor/hver* are plural, the number agreement on the verb remains the same in either case, and so it is not immediately clear whether a plural reciprocal construction is an antecedent case reciprocal construction with an ellipted pronoun, or a compositional reciprocal construction with VSO word order.

In the corpus, 10 sentences with plural reciprocal constructions have *hvor/hver* separated from *annar* by the verb. This is strongly suggestive of SVO word order which occurred with the singular reciprocal construction. This means that *hvor/hver* should be analysed as the subject of the verb, and hence, these constructions are compositional reciprocal constructions. However, there are a further 19 examples with both *hvor/hver* and *annar* in plural and appearing after the verb. For instance, consider the following sentence:

(73) Eyrbyggja saga : 9

Griðum *varð* *engum* *á* *komit* *því at*
 truce.N.PL.DAT become.3PL.PST no.N.PL.DAT on come.PPL because

hvárgir *vildu* *þau* *selja* *ok* *hétu*
 neither.M.PL.NOM want.3PL.PST it.3PL.N.ACC sell.INF and promise.3PL.PST

hvárir *öðrum* *aðförum* *þegar því*
 each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.DAT attack.F.PL.DAT when it.3SG.N.DAT

mætti *við koma.*⁹⁵
 be_able.3SG.PST.SBJ with come.INF

Lit: “No truces could be made [became came] because neither would give mercy to/pardon them and promised each other attacks when possible”

“No truce could be struck because neither side would allow it and threatened to attack each other when it was possible.”

In Modern Icelandic, a likely reading for (73) above would be with an ellipted pronoun *þeir* – “they” acting as the subject of the second clause (*i.e.*, *they* threatened each other). However, there is a second interpretation where *hvórir* is the subject of the second clause, and so an alternative reading (available to both Icelanders and speakers of English) is: “... and each threatened the other”. The question is: how should these sentences be analysed in Old Icelandic? To begin, note that 9 of the 19 plural reciprocal constructions with VSO word order have only one clause, or the reciprocal construction is in the first clause and so it is unlikely that the verb in these cases has an ellipted pronoun as subject:⁹⁶

(74) Heiðarvíga saga: 21

Segja *hvórir* *öðrum* *tíðindi.*
 say.3PL.PRES each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.DAT news.N.PL.ACC

“Each told the other news”

(75) Víga-Glúms saga:27

Síðan eggjuðu *hvárir* *aðra* *atgöngu*
 Then challenge.3PL.PST each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.ACC attack.F.SG.GEN

95 *Selja* – Usually “sell”, but in the context of *grið* – “truce”, means to give mercy/pardon. *c.f.* *Hvorki selja grið né taka* - “neither give nor receive pardon”. *þegar því mætti við koma* - “when possible”

96 Further work would be required to make this a definitive judgement – ruling out the possibility that the ellipsis is allowed by discourse context for example.

ok skutu-st á ok börðust grjóti ok varð
 and cast.3PL.PST-MV and fight.3PL.PST.MV stone.N.SG.DAT and become.3SG.PST

*hörð hrið ok urðu margir sárir.*⁹⁷
 hard.F.SG.NOM battle.F.SG.NOM become.3PL.PST many.M.PL.NOM wounded.M.PL.NOM
 “Each side challenged the other and cast rocks and spears at each other and it
 was a hard battle and many became wounded.”

For sentences like (74) and (75) above, the most straightforward analysis is that *hver* is acting as the subject of the verb. In other examples, analysing the reciprocal construction as having an ellipped subject pronoun is unlikely because the ellipped pronoun would need to be formed from two antecedents. For example:

(76) Grettis saga:69

Hann_i heilsaði þeim_j ok spurðu hvárir_{i+j}
 He.M.SG.NOM greet.3SG.PST them.3PL.DAT and ask.3PL.PST each.M.PL.NOM

aðra_{i+j} að nafni.
 other.M.PL.ACC to name.SG.N.DAT

“He_i greeted them_j and each_{i+k} (*i.e.*, the man and the group) asked the other (their) name.”

In this sentence, there are two groups (one with one man, the other with more than one man) and the sentence is so phrased that the two groups ask each other a question. In Modern Icelandic an overt plural pronoun can optionally find as its antecedent two singular entities from different grammatical functions. However as (77d) demonstrates, ellipped pronouns do not have this option available to them:

97 *eggja atgöngu* – a verb and noun combination meaning “spur to attack” - translated here as “challenge”. *skjótast á* – a middle voice verb + particle meaning “to exchange shots”. *berja grjóti* – “to stone (someone)”

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(77) a.

Hann_i heilsar honum_i og hann_{i or j} fer.
He.3SG.M.NOM greet.3SG.PRES him.3SG.M.DAT and he.3SG.M.NOM leave.3SG.PRES
“He_i greets him_j and he_{i or j} leaves.”

b.

Hann_i heilsar honum_i og fer.
He.3SG.M.NOM greet.3SG.PRES him.3SG.M.DAT and leave.3SG.PRES
“He_i greets him_j and (he_{i/*j}) leaves.”

c.

Hann heilsar honum og þeir fara.
He.3SG.M.NOM greet.3SG.PRES him.3SG.M.DAT and they.3PL.NOM leave.3PL.PRES
“He_i greets him_j and they_{i+j} leave.”

d.

**Hann heilsar honum og fara.*
He.3SG.M.NOM greet.3SG.PRES him.3SG.M.DAT and leave.3PL.PRES
*“He_i greets him_j and (they_{i+j}) leave.”

It is likely that sentences like (77d) were also ungrammatical in Old Icelandic, although it would be difficult to show this definitively. If we allow that such forms were ungrammatical, then sentences like (76) could not be interpreted as having an ellipted pronoun in subject position.

So, how should the remaining plural forms of the reciprocal construction in Old Icelandic be analysed? Recall that the problem here is that because the reciprocal construction is plural, it is difficult to determine whether *hvorir* should be analysed as being the subject of the clause, or whether in fact there is an ellipted plural pronoun acting as the subject. This is because the number marking on the verb would be the same in either case. My analysis of these plural reciprocal constructions is the same as the one I made for their singular counterparts which is that the quantifier *hvor/hver* (whether singular or plural) must be acting as the subject of the verb. My reasons for

this are that in the 29 sentences I found which have plural reciprocal constructions, only two actually had an overt plural antecedent in nominative case – in other words, using the ellipted pronoun analysis for the plural reciprocal sentences above, requires that the pronoun nearly always be ellipted for plural reciprocal constructions, but not singular reciprocal constructions. Furthermore, in all but 7 of the 29 plural reciprocal constructions, the reciprocal is in a position where an ellipted pronoun would be unusual or ungrammatical (either because the reciprocal construction is in the first clause, or because the subject of the clause would need to be constructed from the entities serving in two different functions in a previous clause (see (75) above) or because *hvor/hver* appears with nominative case before the verb in regular subject position).

After examining 87 reciprocal constructions from the sagas (see appendix B), I have argued that in the 58 instances where a singular reciprocal appears, 55 (or 95%) must be analysed as compositional reciprocal constructions where *hvor* or *hver* acts as the verb's subject and *annar* serves in some other function. The other 3 instances (or 5%) are examples of the antecedent case reciprocal construction. When the reciprocal construction is in the plural (29 instances), then in 24 instances (or 83%), the reciprocal construction is a compositional reciprocal construction – the remaining 5 instances (or 17%) being examples of the plural antecedent case reciprocal construction. In 7 of the plural reciprocal construction examples, the reciprocal construction appeared in an environment where it is possible that there could be an ellipted pronoun acting as subject of the verb. In these situations, an analysis whereby the ellipted pronoun is treated as the subject of the verb (rather than *hvor/hver*) is possible, and as such, it could be argued that these sentences are examples of antecedent case reciprocal constructions. I believe the ellipted antecedent pronoun analysis to be unlikely not only for the reasons stated above, but also by analogy with their singular counterparts – ultimately there is no compelling reason to assume a different analysis of the plural reciprocal construction when compared to the singular one. Finally, of the 87 reciprocal constructions in the corpus, I found 6 (or 7%) which were antecedent case reciprocal constructions which used an overt plural NP as the subject of the verb, with both *hvor/hver* and *annar* appearing after the verb. In sections 2.7.4 and 2.7.5 below, I examine both the compositional reciprocal construction and the antecedent case reciprocal construction in more detail.

2.7.4 Further analysis – Compositional reciprocal construction

Having shown that *hvor/hver* is part of the subject of the verb, we can turn our attention to looking at this NP in more detail. Of the 79 compositional reciprocal constructions found in the corpus, they nearly all make use of *hvor/hver* as a pronoun acting as the subject of the clause with various dependents:⁹⁸

(78)	Number of Occurrences	Construction Type
	61 (77 %)	<i>hvor/hver</i> acting as bare pronoun. (see (74) and others above).
	13 (16 %)	<i>hvor/hver</i> with genitive pronoun (see (79) below).
	2 (2.5 %)	<i>hvor/hver</i> with genitive pronoun and repeated noun (see (80) below).
	2 (2.5 %)	<i>hvor/hver</i> in singular with singular noun (see (82) below).
	1 (1.2 %)	<i>hvor/hver</i> with oblique plural noun (see (81) below).
	Total: 79	

(79) Laxdæla saga: 59

...ok það hvárt þeirra annat vel fara.
 and bid.3SG.PST each.N.SG.NOM them.N.PL.GEN other.N.SG.ACC well go.INF
 “... and each bade the other farewell.”

(80) Laxdæla saga: 70

Verður hvárr þeirra bræðra
 become.3SG.PRES each.M.SG.NOM them.M.PL.GEN brother.M.PL.GEN
 öðrum feginn.
 other.M.SG.DAT happy.M.SG.NOM

Lit. “Each of them brothers become happy at (the sight of) the other.”⁹⁹

⁹⁸ Note that the NP in all the plural antecedent case reciprocal constructions consisted solely of *hvor/hver*.

⁹⁹ Translated as “The brothers greeted each other joyfully” in Press (1899).

(81) Gylfaginning: 34

En hverr ása-nna sá til annars...
 But each.M.SG.NOM god.M.PL.GEN-THE see.3SG.PST to other.M.SG.GEN
 “But each of the Æsir looked at the other...”

(82) Gylfaginning: 54

Ok eftir honum sagði hverr maðr
 And after him.M.SG.DAT say.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM man.M.SG.NOM

öðrum þessar sögur.
 other.M.SG.DAT this.F.PL.ACC story.F.PL.ACC
 “And after him, men told each other these stories.”

The subject NPs in these examples all vary. The most common construction uses *hver* or *hver* standing by itself, heading the NP which functions as the subject of the clause. However, two variations of this construction exist – the first allows a genitive plural pronoun to follow *hver/hver* and a second, less common variation follows *hver/hver* with the entity being quantified, also in plural genitive case (see (81)). Note though that in both Old and Modern Icelandic, it is possible to reiterate the antecedent after a pronoun, in the same case:

(83) Eiríks saga Rauða: 2

Þeir Þorbjörn ok Eyjólfur ok Styrr
 They.3PL.M.NOM Þorbjörn.M.SG.NOM and Eyjólfur.M.SG.NOM and Styrr.M.SG.NOM

fylgðu Eiríki út um eyjar-nar, ...
 accompany.3PL.PST Eric.M.SG.DAT out through island.F.PL.ACC-the
 “They, Þorbjörn, Styrr and Eyjólfur, took Eric out through the Islands, ...”

In sentences like those of (74, 79-82), *hver/hver* forms the head of the subject NP. This analysis is supported by the fact that both *hver* and *hver* can stand on their own (as they do in 77% of the constructions found) and also by the fact that the verb's number agrees with *hver/hver* and not with its optional genitive plural noun or pronoun (e.g., (79, 82

etc.)). For example, in (84) below, *hvor* is accompanied by the 2nd person plural pronoun in genitive *ykkar* (i.e., *hvárr ykkarr* – “Each of you”). Note that the person of the verb remains as 3rd person, singular:

- (84) Víga – Glúms saga: 21
hvárr *ykkarr* *mun* *ljósta* *annan...*
 Each.M.SG.NOM you.2PL.GEN will.3SG.PRES strike.INF other.M.SG.ACC
 “Each of you will strike the other...”

However, there is one variation that deserves further attention as it has relevance to the formation of the antecedent case reciprocal construction. The reciprocal construction in (82) is formed with a singular noun and morphologically singular form of *hvor* or *hver* and it is rare in the corpus (it appears only twice in the 90 reciprocal constructions found). However, this construction does occur on occasion in non-reciprocal contexts such as (85) below:

- (85) Egils saga: 57
 ...*at hverr* *maðr* *fari* *til skipa*
 that each.M.SG.NOM MAN.M.SG.NOM go.3SG.PRES.SUBJ to ship.n.pl.gen

sinna *ok fari* *heim.*
 poss.N.PL.GEN and go.3SG.PRES.SUBJ home
 “(I want) that each man go to his ship and go home.”

The most obvious analysis of the subject NP in (85) is to simply treat *maður* – “man” as the head of the phrase with *hver* functioning as a determiner of the noun. We will see in section 2.8.3 that the antecedent case reciprocal construction is formed via the application of this determiner to the f-structure associated with the subject NP, even though it does not form a constituent with it.

2.7.5 Antecedent case reciprocal construction

Of the 87 reciprocal constructions found, only eight were antecedent case reciprocal constructions (although see comments below). These sentences all have in common a

plural NP acting as subject to the verb, with *hvor/hver annar* appearing after this NP:

(86) Hrafnkels saga:2

- a. ... *en þó* *riðu* *þeir* *feðgar*
 but nevertheless ride.3PL.PST they.M.PL.NOM father/son.M.PL.NOM

jafnan hvárir *til annarra ...*
 always each.M.PL.NOM to other.M.PL.GEN

“(The roads were difficult) but nevertheless they, father and son, always rode to each other.”

Grettis saga:43

- b. *Engi* *frami* *er* *í því,* *at vit*
 No.M.SG.NOM fame.M.SG.NOM be.3SG.PRES in it.N.SG.DAT that we.1PL.NOM

drepum *verkmenn* *hvárr* *fyrir öðrum..*
 kill.1PL.PRES worker.M.PL.ACC each.M.SG.NOM for other.M.SG.DAT

“(There is) no fame in it, that we kill workers to the detriment of each other.”

Heiðarvíga saga:16

- c. ... *þessir* *eru* *nauðleytamenn*
 this.M.PL.NOM be.3PL.PRES near-kinsmen.M.PL.NOM

hverr *annars...*
 each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.GEN

“... (that) these are close relations of each other...”

Note that in (86b), the preposition *fyrir* – “for” takes a dative case complement instead of the normal accusative case. In these instances, the construction is a malefactive – and so the implied reading is that the two parties are killing each other's workers to harm one another.

Given the rarity of the antecedent case reciprocal constructions in the sagas, it is

possible that they did not appear in the older texts, and were only added in later copies. There is some evidence for this in the case of the antecedent case reciprocal construction in the *Grettis saga* (see 86b). In at least two seventeenth century copies of this saga (Manuscripts AM 478 and AM 150¹⁰⁰) the reciprocal construction in (86b) does not appear and instead a reflexive construction is used.¹⁰¹ This at least raises the possibility that the reciprocal construction may have been added more recently in order to clarify the meaning of the text. However, the antecedent case reciprocal constructions do appear in two manuscripts of *Hrafnkels saga* – also from the seventeenth century (AM 156 and AM 157e). Ideally, the oldest manuscripts could be checked for the presence of these antecedent case reciprocal constructions. Nevertheless, there is some evidence that the antecedent case reciprocal construction in *Hrafnkels saga* is of older origin than other examples. This construction is unusual insofar as it uses the plural form *hvárir* rather than *hvár* in the reciprocal construction. To describe two men visiting each other, the usual form used in Old Icelandic was the masculine singular form *hvárr*, for example, (87) below and many others:

- (87) *Gunnlaugs saga*: 9
*Sagði hvárr öðrum frá ferðum sínum.*¹⁰²
 tell.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.DAT about travel.F.PL.DAT refl-POSS.F.PL.DAT
 “Each [*i.e.*, Gunnlaugr and Hrafn] told the other about their travels.”

For one or more groups of people (here Barði is meeting his sister's sons), the plural form of *hver*, *hvárir*, is used:

- (88) *Heiðarvíga saga*: 21
Segja hvárir öðrum tíðindi.
 say.3PL.PRES each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.DAT news.N.PL.ACC
 “Each tells the other the tidings.”

100 These manuscripts can be viewed online at Saganet (<http://saga.library.cornell.edu/>) - a cooperative project by the National and University Library of Iceland and Cornell University.

101 AM 478 reads “(there) is no fame to kill our workmen”. AM 150 reads “(there) is no fame that we kill workmen” (my translations). These reflexive symmetric situations also occur in English. For example, one soldier could say to an enemy soldier, “There is no sense in us killing ourselves by fighting...”

102 The possessive determiner *sínum* agrees in case, number and gender with noun it possesses (in this case, *ferðum* – “travels”), not its antecedent.

The compositional reciprocal constructions in the corpus were remarkably consistent in their usage of singular and plural morphological forms of *hvor* and *hver* to reflect whether the entities taking part in the reciprocal relation were individuals or groups, although in some instances, a definitive judgement cannot be made as to the appropriateness of the number of the reciprocal construction. For example, Egils saga:27 ...*hvárir vissu löngum til annarra* “for a long time, each (of the two ships) was in sight of the other” – the plural form of *hvor* is being used because each ship contains many men. However, in both of the examples of antecedent case reciprocal constructions with two participants, the plural form of the reciprocal construction was used instead of the expected singular form (see (86a) above and (89) below):

(89) Njáls saga:97

...*en þó hafð þér hættumikit*
 but yet have.2PL.PRES you.2PL.NOM perilious.N.SG.ACC

*hvárir við aðra...*¹⁰³
 each.M.PL.NOM with other.M.PL.ACC

“...but yet, you have a great deal of peril (bad blood) with each other...”

The irregularity of sentences like (86a) and (89) can be explained if they are considered as an intermediate step between the older compositional reciprocal construction and the more modern antecedent case reciprocal construction. A possible path is sketched out below:

Step 1: The Compositional Reciprocal Construction

The antecedent case reciprocal construction found its origins in the compositional reciprocal construction used to describe divisible antecedents – these constructions had both a verb and *hvor/hver annar* marked for plural number. For example:

103 In this part of the story, Flosi is telling Njal that the relationship between Njal and Hoskuld is precarious because of a past, violent, history. Translated as “but the relation between you and Hoskuld is very precarious.” in Cook (1997:164). Note that the translation of this sentence is made difficult by the use of the word *hættumikit* – glossed as “perilous” above. This interpretation is problematic because *hafa* requires a NP rather than a AP as a complement. It is possible that in Old Icelandic, *hættumikit* could be used as a noun (meaning “peril”), or perhaps there is a missing neuter noun like *ástand* - “situation or circumstance” which would mean that the sentence should be translated as “you have perilous circumstances with each other”. Sigríður Ólafsdóttir points out that there is a parallel with this sentence and the modern *Þeir hafa gott hver af öðrum* - “They have got the better of each other” where the adjective *gott* (good) is treated similarly.

(88) Heiðarvíga saga: 21

Segja hvárir öðrum tíðindi.
 say.3PL.PRES each.M.PL.NOM other.M.PL.DAT news.N.PL.ACC
 “Each tells the other the tidings”

Step 2: Reanalysis of Subject

There are two main word orders available in Old Icelandic; VSO and SVO. At some stage speakers may have re-analysed VSO sentences like (88) above as being SVO with an ellipted subject and a quantifier that is no longer part of the subject NP. They then employed an overt NP in the new subject position. With this NP antecedent now being treated as the subject, the alternative VSO word order is also possible – but with both the antecedent NP and *hvor/hver* appearing in the clause:¹⁰⁴

(86) Hrafnkels saga:2

a. ... *en þó riðu þeir feðgar*
 but nevertheless ride.3PL.PST they.M.PL.NOM father/son.M.PL.NOM

jafnan hvárir til annarra ...
 always each.M.PL.NOM to other.M.PL.GEN

“(The roads were difficult) but nevertheless they, father and son, always rode to each other.”

Step 3: Intermediate Form

These new constructions as yet only existed with morphologically plural forms of *hvor/hver* and *annar*. Speakers were faced with a choice as how to analyse prototypical antecedents (such as when two individuals meet each other). Their choices were to simply use the morphologically plural form of the reciprocal construction in all instances, regardless of number of antecedent or to require that *hvor/hver* and *annar* appear morphologically singular by analogy with the compositional reciprocal construction. Both occur in the corpus (note that in (89), the antecedent refers to two

¹⁰⁴ The corpus doesn't contain an instance of the antecedent case reciprocal construction with SVO word order using morphologically plural forms of *hvor* and *hver*. However, given the rarity of the antecedent case reciprocal construction at this time, this is not surprising. The existence of such constructions is however likely given that their VSO counterparts occur in the corpus.

individuals and so the singular form of *hvor annar* would usually be used):

Antecedent case reciprocal construction with morphologically plural reciprocal

(89) Njáls saga:97

...en þó hafið þér hættumikit
 but yet have.2PL.PRES you.2PL.NOM perilous.N.SG.ACC

hverir við aðra...
 each.M.PL.NOM with other.M.PL.ACC

“...but yet, you have a great deal of peril (bad blood) with each other...”

Antecedent case reciprocal construction with case marking analogous to the compositional reciprocal construction:

(86) Heiðarvíga saga:16

c. ... þessir eru nauðleytamenn
 this.M.PL.NOM be.3PL.PRES near-kinsmen.M.PL.NOM

hverr annars...
 each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.GEN

“... (that) these are close relations of each other...”

Ultimately, speakers standardised the number marking to be the same as the compositional reciprocal construction. The outline above is speculation, and further study would be required to place it on firmer foundations. However, it has the advantages of both allowing for grammatical steps along the path from the compositional reciprocal construction to the antecedent case reciprocal construction, and also for being able to account for the unusual number marking of the reciprocal construction for sentences like (86a) and (89) above.

Having described the types of the reciprocal constructions as they were used in the 13-16th centuries, I will now turn to the reciprocal constructions used in *Piltur og Stúlka*, a 19th century Icelandic play, and document the types of reciprocal constructions used there with view to better understand their development.

2.7.6 Reciprocal constructions in *Piltur og Stúlka*

It is not until the 19th century that there was revival in Icelandic literature. By this time, the use of the antecedent case governed reciprocal construction was common. *Piltur og Stúlka* (Lad and Lass) by Jón Thoroddsen (1850) is considered to be the first Icelandic novel since the sagas. It makes use of a variety of reciprocal constructions; among them are copious examples of the antecedent case governed construction. For example:

(90) Thoroddsen (1850)

að þeir kysstu hvor annan og
 that they.3PL.M.NOM kiss.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC and

beiddu hvor annan fyrirgefningar;
 ask.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC forgiveness.F.SG.GEN

“(that) they kissed each other and (they) asked each other for forgiveness;”

Note that the first verb *kysstu* – “kissed” has as its subject the plural pronoun *þeir* – “they” and this can be confirmed by the plural inflection of the verb. The second clause cannot have *hvor* as its subject, because the verb *beiddu* – “asked” also has plural morphology and the quantifier *hvor* appears in the singular. In this case then, the most likely analysis is that the subject of the second clause is simply an ellipped pronoun. *Piltur og Stúlka* has also a variety of other reciprocal constructions including the compositional reciprocal construction that was so prevalent in the sagas:

(91) Thoroddsen (1850)

...og kallaði þá hvor annan signor
 and call.3SG.PST then each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC “signor”

í hverju orði.
 in every word.

“and then each called the other *signor* in every word (*i.e.*, all the time).”

From examining *Piltur og Stúlka* it is clear that the usage of the antecedent case

reciprocal construction was far more frequent in the 19th century when compared to the times of the sagas. Further work examining writing from the intervening centuries (such as religious or legal writing) might reveal further evidence about how the modern reciprocal construction came into being.

2.7.7 Related constructions

There are two other constructions I want to briefly discuss because they shed light on various functions the quantifiers *hvor* and *hver* can perform – functions that are important when considering the phrasal reciprocal construction in section 8.3. As mentioned earlier, *hvor/hver* can mean “each” or “every” when applied to a noun. In the sagas these expressions were formed by using *hver* with a plural pronoun or noun in genitive case. Note that *hver* has the case marking appropriate to its function (*i.e.*, nominative for subject, accusative for object *etc.*), while the oblique noun or pronoun is always in genitive case. Compare (92), (93) and (94) below:

(92) Grettis saga: 24

Hafði hverr þeira mikla
 have.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM them.M.PL.GEN large.F.SG.ACC

sveit manna.
 company.F.SG.ACC man.M.PL.GEN

“Each of them had a large company of men.”

(93) Færeyinga saga:37¹⁰⁵

Þórir mælti að þeir skyldi drepa
 Þórir say.3SG.PST that they.M.PL.NOM should.3SG.PST.SUBJ kill.inf

hvern þeira sem þeir næði.
 each.M.SG.ACC they.M.PL.GEN which they.M.PL.NOM obtain.3SG.PST.SUBJ

“Þórir said that they should kill each/everyone of them they could catch.”

105 Note that verb subject concord here is unusual – but consistent throughout the sentence.

(94) Gylfaginning: 34

En hverr ása-nna sá til annars...

But each.M.SG.NOM god.M.PL.GEN-the see.3SG.PST to other.M.SG.GEN

“But each of the Æsir looked at the other...”

In these constructions, the quantifier *hver* functions as the head of the noun phrase which contains it ((92), (94) show *hver* in a NP functioning as subject to the verb, and (93) shows *hver* in a NP functioning as an object). This is evidenced by the fact that the quantifier is obligatory, and that it carries the case assigned to the noun phrase. However, there is an alternative construction where both *hver* or *hver* share the same case as the noun they quantify. In these constructions, the noun's number is singular, and the quantifier shares the same number and gender as the noun it quantifies. Like the examples above, the case of the NP is dictated by the function the NP plays in the sentence (*i.e.*, subject in (95) and object in (96)) :

(95) Gylfaginning:52

Ok hafið þér áður sagt at hverr

And have.2PL.PRES you.2PL.NOM before say.PPL that each.M.SG.NOM

maðr skal lifa í nokkurum heimi

man.M.SG.NOM shall.3SG.PRES live.INF in some.M.SG.DAT world.M.SG.DAT

um allar aldir!

throughout all.F.PL.ACC age.F.PL.ACC

“And you have said before that each man must live in some world throughout all ages.”¹⁰⁶

(96) Njáls saga: 83

Hinn er annar at vér

the_other.M.SG.NOM be.3SG.PRES another.M.SG.NOM that we.1PL.NOM

106 Odin has been talking about how after the end of the world, every man will spend their afterlife in one of many worlds – some of which are pleasant, and others hellish.

munum sækja at yðr ok drepa hvern
 will.1PL.PRES attack.INF at you.2PL.DAT and kill.INF each.M.SG.ACC

mann er vér fám.
 man.M.SG.ACC which we.1PL.NOM catch.1PL.PRES

“... the other one (choice) / the other thing is / that we will fall upon you and kill each/every man which we catch”

Note that unlike the English equivalent sentences, it is possible for the noun to be definite as in *dyrustafinn* – “the door post” below:

(97) Grettis saga:45

Væta var úti mikil, ok því gekk
 rain.F.SG.NOM be.3.SG.PST outside much and therefore walk.3.SG.PST

hann eigi út ok held sinni hendi
 he.M.SG.NOM not out but hold.3SG.PST reflx-POSS.F.SG.DAT hand.F.SG.DAT

í hvárn dyrustaf-inn ok litast svá um.
 on each.M.SG.ACC door-post.M.SG.ACC-THE and look.MV so about

“It was raining hard outside, and so he didn't walk out, but he held a hand on each door post and so peered out.”

In sentences like (95-97), we see that *hvor/hver* can modify a noun directly. In these cases, it is the non-optional noun which forms the head of the phrase. Now, given that *hvor/hver* can modify a noun, it might be expected the *hvor/hver* can act as a quantifier to *annar* – “other” and as examples below show, this is the case. Note that in these examples, *hver annar* should not be understood as a reciprocal pronoun analogous to “each other” in English, instead it should be read as “each or every other (one)” as in “You and each/every other man here will receive a \$100 gift voucher!”:

(98) Grettis saga:56

en flest annat þykkumst ek reyna
 but most.N.SG.ACC other.SG.N.ACC consider.1PL.MV I.1SG.NOM attempt.INF

*mega við hvern annan óbreyttan mann.*¹⁰⁷
 can.INF with each.M.SG.ACC other.M.SG.ACC un-changed.M.SG.ACC man.M.SG.ACC

“But I think that for most other (deeds), I can compete with any other normal man.”

(99) Fljótsdæla saga:23

Vil ek þat ráð þér
 want.1SG.PRES I.1SG that advice.N.SG.ACC you.2SG.DAT

gefa sem hverjum öðrum...
 give.INF as every.M.SG.DAT other.M.SG.DAT

“I wish to give such advice to you, as I would wish to give it to everyone else...”

These constructions are interesting because they show that the quantifiers *hvor* and *hver* had two functions in both Old and Modern Icelandic. They could stand by themselves as pronouns able to head a noun phrase and take optional dependants. Or, alternatively, they can act as determiners to a noun heading a NP. This is interesting because the latter construction has parallels with one of the most recent usages of the phrasal reciprocal construction in Icelandic. This point will be returned to in section 2.8.3 and 2.8.4.

2.7.8 Concluding remarks

There are very clear differences between the reciprocal constructions which appear in the sagas when compared to the reciprocal constructions used in Modern Icelandic. In Old Icelandic, the reciprocal construction was formed using *hvor* or *hver* as a pronoun functioning as the subject of the verb and *annar* was placed in some non-subject function. For example:

107 Note *reyna...við* means “try/compete”. Note also that the phrase *þykkumst ek* “I consider (myself)” has unusual number concord.

(100) Njáls saga:63

Síðan eggjaði hvern annan.

Then egg_on.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC

“Then each egged the other on / each incited the other.”

Clearly, the compositional reciprocal construction is the oldest form as it is by far the most common in the sagas. Note that despite being compositional in nature, the reciprocal construction even in this early time was still conventionalised – in the 87 examples I found, every one had *hver/hver* and *annar* exhibiting the complex four-way number identified in section 2.5.5.

The antecedent case reciprocal construction (formed with the antecedent NP acting as the subject of the verb) was used in 8 of the 87 reciprocal sentences in the corpus, and in at least one instance might have been added later to clarify the text. In none of the reciprocal constructions collected was there an example of the phrasal reciprocal construction, or *hver/hver annar* appearing inside a prepositional phrase.

At some stage, speakers stopped using *hver/hver* in the subject NP and starting using it in other positions within the clause. At this point we could consider the resulting construction either the antecedent case reciprocal construction, or possibly an instance of the fixed case form of the reciprocal construction. I consider the former to be much more likely for two reasons:

1. Speakers still allow non-nominative case on *hver/hver* today. Given that this construction originated from the compositional reciprocal construction where the case of *hver/hver* was dictated by the function it served in the clause, it is likely that *hver/hver* initially retained this case marking when appearing in different places in the clause before the case marking became fixed to nominative.

2. The older respondents to the survey were more likely to use the antecedent case reciprocal construction than the fixed case form when compared to younger speakers. For example, question iv of section B in the survey disambiguates the various forms of the reciprocal construction used. Older speakers (56+) were more likely to use the antecedent case reciprocal construction (57.4%) than the fixed form construction (42.6%). On the other hand, younger speakers (18-30) were more likely to use the fixed

case reciprocal construction (65.3% compared to 34.7% who used the antecedent case reciprocal construction).¹⁰⁸

Although it could be argued that there are instances of the fixed form reciprocal construction in the sagas or works by Thoroddsen, such an analysis is unlikely given that there are no instances of a phrasal reciprocal construction, nor instances of *hvor/hver* appearing inside a PP. I conclude then that the antecedent case reciprocal construction appeared after the compositional reciprocal construction, but before the fixed case and phrasal reciprocal constructions. The exact ordering of the fixed case and phrasal reciprocal constructions was not determined – beyond the fact that they are the most recent constructions.

2.8 ANALYSIS

I have identified four reciprocal constructions and proposed a diachronic path by which they are related: the compositional reciprocal construction, the antecedent case reciprocal construction, and then the phrasal reciprocal and fixed case reciprocal constructions (either one after the other or at the same time) and all of these constructions are still used to varying extents by modern speakers. In this section I show how these variants can all be provided an informative analysis within LFG. This analysis further provides answers for why and how each member of a NP can receive a different relational case, why the case of *hvor/hver* can match either that of its antecedent or *annar* (e.g., (100a)), why there is variable distribution of *hvor/hver* within a clause (100b) and how the different forms of the reciprocal construction are related:

(100) Survey – Section B, question iv.

- | | | | | |
|----|--------------|------------------------------|------------------|--------------|
| a. | <i>Ég</i> | <i>kynnti</i> | <i>menni-na</i> | <i>tvo</i> |
| | I.1SG.NOM | introduce.1SG.PST | men.M.PL.ACC-the | two.M.PL.ACC |
| | <i>fyrir</i> | <i>hvorn / hvorum / hvor</i> | <i>öðrum</i> | |
| | for | each.M.SG.ACC / DAT / NOM | other.M.SG.DAT | |
- “I introduced the two men to each other.”

¹⁰⁸ These results are statistically significant. Both results have a confidence level of 95%; the results for the older speakers having a margin of error of 14.3%, with only a 6.5% margin of error for the younger speakers.

- b. *Ég kynnti menni-na tvo*
 I.1SG.NOM introduce.1SG.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the two.M.PL.ACC

hver / hvorn fyrir öðrum
 each.M.SG.NOM / ACC for other.M.SG.DAT

“I introduced the two men to each other.”

Pivotal to my analysis is that the relationship between these variants of the reciprocal construction in a diachronic sense is captured by a change in their underlying reciprocation strategy. That is to say, all of the issues raised above result from a transition in the Icelandic reciprocal construction's reciprocation strategy from compositional to pronominal. I will argue that the Old Icelandic reciprocal construction is formed from a compositional mechanism where the symmetric interpretation of the event comes from the interaction of *hver/hver* – “each” with *annar* – “other”. In contrast, the reciprocation strategy of the two modern forms of the reciprocal construction (phrasal and fixed form) is pronominal – that is to say, the symmetric sense of the event comes about from the application of a reciprocal operator (associated with the complex pronoun *hver/hver annar*) to the predicate.¹⁰⁹ The antecedent case reciprocal construction captures the transition between these variants of the reciprocal construction. It shares many c-structure properties with the pronominal constructions, but its reciprocation strategy is still compositional.

LFG is well suited to these analyses – perhaps uniquely so in the analysis of the antecedent case reciprocal construction because it maintains a distinction between functional information and constituent structure. Thus LFG can easily capture the antecedent case reciprocal construction's chimeric nature, while simultaneously providing a natural motivation for the development of the later pronominal constructions.

I am fortunate that there has been considerable work on the grammar of Icelandic within LFG. Work by Andrews (1990, 1982) and Zaenen, Maling and Thráinsson (1990) has provided a solid foundation upon which I can base my account of the Icelandic reciprocal construction. In this section, I will introduce the basic analysis of Icelandic sentences within LFG as put forward by Andrews (1990).

¹⁰⁹ See appendix A for an example of how the reciprocal operator is linked to syntax.

In terms of a theoretical account of Icelandic syntax, the principal difficulty is representing the case system. Well behaved sentences have easily predictable case – the subject appearing in nominative case and the object, if present, being in accusative case:

- (101) a. *Hundur* *sá* *hest.*
 dog.M.SG.NOM see.3SG.PST horse.M.SG.ACC
 “(A) dog saw (a) horse.”
- b. *Hestur* *sá* *hund.*
 horse.M.SG.NOM see.3SG.PST dog.M.SG.ACC
 “(A) horse saw (a) dog.”

Andrews (1990:188) calls the case assignment in situations like (94) above "functional or structural case". By this he means that case may be assigned to the various NPs by rules associated with phrase structure rules such that the SUBJ position is annotated to assign nominative case to its NP, and the OBJ position assigns ACC case its NP.

There are two other systems of case marking for Icelandic – lexical (see Andrews 1990,1982) and semantic (see Zaenen *et al.* 1990). Of these, lexical case marking is the more complex to represent in linguistic theory. At its simplest, lexical case marking requires only that various lexemes can assign case to their complements (such as prepositions do). However, this analysis is complicated by the existence of some verbs which assign non-standard case to their subjects as well and various theories have been put forward to account for these verbs (see Andrews, 1982, 1990).

As mentioned earlier, Icelandic has two common word orders, SVO and VSO. VSO word order in Icelandic is usually triggered by the presence of a sentence initial adverbial phrase. Because of the existence of VSO word order, it is debatable as to whether Icelandic actually has a VP. In Andrews (1982) he claims that “there is no real evidence for a VP node dominating the verb and following complements” and certainly the regular use of a VSO word order supports this analysis. However, Thráinsson (1986) argues for the existence of a VP – and Andrews (1990) supports this analysis. Given the existence of complex verbal elements in Icelandic, some sort of verbal phrase is plausible for SVO word order at least. For my own analysis of Icelandic, I will assume the existence of VP in SVO word order. However, whatever the situation regarding the existence of a VP in Icelandic, structural case assignment can easily accommodate it and

the details of the analysis below can be easily changed to accommodate various minor changes in the analysis of c-structure.

So then, using a standard model c-structure, we can easily represent a sentence like (101b) in LFG formalism using structural case assignment:

The key point here is that the case value for the subject and object is determined by unification in each instance since both the phrase structure rules and the NPs themselves contribute case information to the SUBJ and OBJ f-structures. Furthermore, the number and person marking on the verb requires the subject NP to be both singular and in the 3rd person. With this formalism in hand, we can now turn to the analysis of the compositional reciprocal construction.

2.8.1 The compositional reciprocal construction

Recall that a compositional reciprocal construction is one that is available to most languages – it is formed from the interaction between a distributive quantifier (*hvárr/hverr* – “each”) and an indefinite pronoun (*annar* – “other”). Evan's (2008:35) definition of a reciprocal construction (see section 1.2) requires that the expression of symmetric semantics not be wholly compositional. Although there is no doubt that the reciprocal construction in Old Icelandic was largely compositional, already one aspect of its formation was conventionalised in the requirement that *hvárr/hverr* and *annar*

have the same number. For this reason the analysis I present below treats *hvárr/hverr* and *annar* as part of construction rather than as simply two otherwise unrelated pronouns.

The basic analysis of structural case described by Andrews (1990) is all that is required to account for the compositional reciprocal construction. Unlike the three other forms of the reciprocal construction, in the compositional reciprocal construction, the pronoun *hvárr* or *hverr* is the head of the subject NP while *annar* appears as the object:

(102) Njáls saga:63

Síðan eggjaði hverr annan.

Then incite.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC

“Then each egged the other on / each incited the other.”

(103) Víga - Glúms saga: 21

hvárr ykkarr mun ljósta annan...

Each.M.SG.NOM you.2PL.GEN will.3SG.PRES strike.INF other.M.SG.ACC

“Each of you will strike the other...”

I argued in section 2.7.4 that in sentences like (102) and (103), *hvárr* and *hverr* form the head of the subject NP. This is because:

1. Either *hvárr* or *hverr* is obligatory in the NP.
2. Either can take optional dependants and these dependents are constrained to have plural number in genitive case.
3. When either *hvárr* or *hverr* appear with a dependent, the verb agrees with them in number, and not the dependent.

Below I show the LFG analysis of the compositional reciprocal construction in Old Icelandic. In this analysis, both *hvárr* and *annar* are treated as pronouns and I use the standard LFG analysis of NP's *etc.* (as described in Dalrymple 2001). The sentence I analyse is (104):¹¹⁰

110 For the purposes of clarity, I ignore the discourse particle *þá* - 'then'.

(104) Heiðarvíga saga:11

Þekkir þá hvárr annan.

know.3SG.PRES then each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC

“Then each knew (recognised) the other.”

The relevant lexical entries for the reciprocal construction are below:

- (105) *hvárr, pro* \uparrow PRED='PRO'
 \uparrow QUANTTYPE = RECIP
 \uparrow PERS=3
 \uparrow NUM=SG
 \uparrow GEN={M}
 \uparrow CASE=NOM
- annan, pro* \uparrow PRED='PRO'
 \uparrow NUM=SG
 \uparrow GEN={M}
 \uparrow CASE=ACC
 $(GF (GF^*) \uparrow) GF = \%ANT$
 $\neg(\rightarrow$ TENSE)
- $\%ANT GEN =_c \uparrow GEN$
 $\%ANT NUM =_c \uparrow NUM$
 $\%ANT QUANTTYPE =_c RECIP$

Whereas in sections 2.5.4 and 2.5.5 I was able to use a fairly loose definition of the reciprocal construction, I introduce here the lexical entries required to formalise it – the most important of which is:

- (106) $(GF (GF^*) \uparrow) GF = \%ANT$
 $\neg(\rightarrow$ TENSE)

This functional equation defines the domain where *annar* must find its antecedent by making use of inside-out functional uncertainty as defined by Dalrymple (2001). It captures that the antecedent to *annar* will be one of the grammatical functions specified by the verbal predicate. Typically this is the subject, but in ditransitive or semi-transitive verbs it may be another grammatical function specified by the verb. The use of the Kleene star allows *annar* to be buried arbitrarily deep within f-structure (for example, within a prepositional phrase) and still find its antecedent. The off path constraint in the definition, $\neg(\rightarrow$ TENSE), limits the search domain for the antecedent to be those f-structures defined by the verbal PRED and the grammatical functions it governs (see

Dalrymple 2001:283-286). This antecedent GF (usually the value of the SUBJ attribute) is defined locally as %ANT (the '%' just indicating that this is a local variable name). A local variable is needed because we need to ensure that the following constraints (%ANT QUANTTYPE *etc.*) are all referring to the same f-structure – and not to just any f-structure within the antecedent domain which happens to meet one or more of the constraints. For example, we need to ensure that the gender constraint (that the antecedent be masculine) is met by the same f-structure. In the lexical entries that follow, I will usually use the following shorthand to refer to the lexical entry above:

$$\text{AFS} = \%ANT, \text{ where AFS (antecedent f-structure) is } (GF (GF^*) \uparrow) GF \\ \neg(\rightarrow\text{TENSE})$$

The lexical entry $\uparrow\text{QUANTTYPE} = \text{RECIP}$ describes the distributive operator that *hvor/hver* has upon the event, as well as capturing the conventionalised aspects of this construction (see following comments on *annar*).¹¹¹ *Annar* has several lexical specifications that reference the antecedent through the use of %ANT. The lexical entry $\%ANT \text{ QUANTTYPE} =_c \text{RECIP}$ is a requirement that the antecedent be quantified by either *hvárr* or *hverr* (in Old Icelandic, *hvor/hver* in Modern Icelandic). This constraint is necessary because *annar* also functions as a regular pronoun that could, at least in principle, refer to entities other than those specified by *hvor/hver*. Constraining the antecedent of *annar* to carry the RECIP feature is a means to unambiguously identify that both *hvor/hver* and *annar* are interacting together to describe a symmetric event. The pronoun *annan* has two lexical entries concerning gender. First, *annar* has its own gender (masculine) specified by the lexical entry $\uparrow\text{GEN}=\{\text{M}\}$ (see section 2.5.2 examples (44a-c)). In addition to this rule however, is the lexical entry $\%ANT \text{ GEN}=\uparrow\text{GEN}$. This entry, and $\%ANT \text{ NUM}=\uparrow\text{NUM}$ *etc.* have been discussed in sections 2.5.4 and 2.5.5 respectively and control the number and gender concord of the reciprocal construction. Here $\%ANT \text{ GEN}=\uparrow\text{GEN}$ specifies that the gender attribute of the antecedent f-structure be the same as the gender attribute of the current f-structure (*i.e.*, the f-structure associated with *annar*). Equally, the requirement that *annar* and

111 Within the literature there are several different analyses of quantifiers (*e.g.*, Dalrymple, 2001; Dipper, 2005; Andrews, 2007), any one of which could be used in the analyses I provide here with only minor changes to the formalism. I have adopted a simple analysis of these quantifiers that is closest to the work of Andrews (2007), albeit modified so that it is compatible with complex reciprocal pronouns (see section 2.8.3).

In sentences like these *hverr* is acting as a determiner to the noun which heads the subject NP – and lexical entry for *hverr* needs to be adjusted so that it no longer carries a PRED feature (in the same manner as other quantifiers which can function as both pronouns and determiners such as *allir* – “all” etc). A lexical entry for determiner *hverr* in a reciprocal construction is:¹¹³

- (109) *hverr*; *det* ↑QUANTTYPE = RECIP
 ↑NUM= SG
 ↑CASE= NOM
 ↑GEN= {M}
 ↑PERS= 3

The f-structure to which the lexical entries above refer is that of the noun which *hverr* quantifies. For example the c- and f-structures for (110) are below:

- (110) *Þekkir* *hverr* *maðr* *annan*.¹¹⁴
 know.3SG.PRES each.M.SG.NOM man.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “Each man knows the others.”

113 Note that when *hverr* functions as a regular distributive determiner (such as in the Icelandic equivalent to “Each man fell asleep”), the QUANTTYPE feature changes to: ↑QUANTTYPE = DISTRIB.

114 Note that in this sentence the usage of *hverr* requires that there be more than two men.

To begin, first examine (112) below which illustrates that *hver* (and *hvor* and several other quantifiers) can be located in different places within a clause, while always quantifying its subject:

- (112) a. ***Hver*** *veiðimaður má veiða 30 fugla.*
“Each hunter can catch 30 birds.”
- b. ***Hver*** *veiðimannanna* (or *Hver af veiðimönnum*) *má veiða 30 fugla.*
“Each of the hunters can catch 30 birds.”
- c. *Veiðimennirnir mega hver_{ant} veiða 30 fugla.*
“The hunters can each catch 30 birds.”
- d. *Veiðimennirnir mega veiða 30 fugla hver_{ant}.*
“The hunters can catch 30 birds each.”
- e. *Þeir kosta hver_{ant} 40 dollara.*
“They are each \$40.”

We see that *hver* is related to its antecedent both semantically (it distributes the predicate over each of the members of the subject NP) and also syntactically with respect to case and gender. I treat the antecedent case reciprocal construction as being formed from the compositional reciprocation strategy (*c.f.* the compositional reciprocal construction), but like in (112) above, *hvor_{ant}* and *hver_{ant}* no longer have to appear adjacent to the noun they quantify.

The immediate concern in the analysis of the antecedent case reciprocal construction is how to analyse *hvor_{ant}/hver_{ant}*. We saw in (110) that *hvor/hver* can act as a determiner in a NP, quantifying its head noun. I argue that *hvor_{ant}/hver_{ant}* still has the exact same function but it can do so from outside of the NP. This requires a lexical entry for *hvor_{ant}/hver_{ant}* allowing it to find an antecedent within the clause, rather than just the NP with which it is associated. This is accomplished using the same formalism as is used for *annar* – a lexical rule which defines a domain where the antecedent must be found. Note that this lexical entry *hvor_{ant}/hver_{ant}* is also required to account for the

non-reciprocal sentences in (112) above – and is not motivated to simply account for the data at hand. Instead the analysis of antecedent case reciprocal construction is exactly the same as the compositional reciprocal construction discussed previously, only now it also captures that *hvor_{ant}* and *hver_{ant}* (like many other quantifiers both in Icelandic and other Germanic languages – see Plank (2008)) can appear in different positions within the clause. Compare the lexical entry for *hvor* as a determiner with *hvor_{ant}*:

- (113) *hvor*, *det* ↑QUANTTYPE = RECIP
 ↑CASE= NOM
 ↑GEN= {M}
 ↑NUM= SG
- hvor_{ant}*, *det* AFS = %ANT
 %ANT QUANTTYPE = RECIP
 %ANT CASE=_c NOM
 %ANT GEN=_c {M}
 %ANT NUM=_c PL

Apart from allowing *hvor_{ant}* to find its antecedent somewhere in the clause, the only difference in the treatment of *hvor* is that it now requires that its antecedent be plural in number. Likewise, an additional lexical entry for *annar* now requires a plural antecedent. For example, *annan*, below:

- annan*, *pro*, ↑PRED= 'PRO'
 ↑NUM= SG
 ↑CASE= ACC
 ↑GEN={M}
 AFS = %ANT
 %ANT GEN=_c ↑GEN
 %ANT NUM=_c PL
 %ANT QUANTTYPE=_c RECIP

2.8.2.1 WHERE DOES *HVOR_{ANT}*/*HVER_{ANT}* APPEAR IN C-STRUCTURE?

My analysis is that *hvor_{ant}*/*hver_{ant}* is part of the verb phrase (or daughter to S in the case where there is no VP), although with the restriction that it must appear after its antecedent. Under this analysis, I can make the following two predictions:

1. *hvor_{ant}*/*hver_{ant}* is not part of the subject NP.
2. *hvor_{ant}*/*hver_{ant}* cannot appear after a sentential adjunct.

That *hver_{ant}/hver_{ant}* is not part of the subject NP can be seen by examining (115) below. In (115a) we see that it is possible to coordinate two NP's – one quantified with pronominal *hver*; but that the same situation is not possible with *hver* elsewhere in the NP:

- (115) a. *Hver manna-nna og María æptu.*
 each.M.SG.NOM man.M.PL.GEN-the and Mary.NOM cry.3PL.PST
 “Each of the men and Mary cried.”
- b. **Mennnir-nir hver (og María) æptu.*
 man.M.PL.NOM-the each.M.SG.NOM (and Mary) cry.3PL.PST
 *“The men each and Mary cried.”

That *hver_{ant}* appears inside a VP is evident from sentences like (116), (117) and (118) below:

- (116) *Brúður-nar kosta hver um 14 milljónir króna...*¹¹⁵
 doll.F.PL.NOM cost.3PL.PRES each.F.SG.NOM about 14 million kronar
 “The dolls (crash test dummies) cost each about 14 million kronar.”

- (117) a. *Veðimennnir-nir veiddu 30 fugla hver*
 hunter.M.PL.NOM-the catch.3PL.PST 30 bird.M.PL.ACC each.M.SG.NOM
í gærkvöldi.
 last night
 “The hunters caught 30 birds each last night.”
- b. **Veðimennnir-nir veiddu 30 fugla*
 hunter.M.PL.NOM-the catch.3PL.PST 30 bird.M.PL.ACC
í gærkvöldi hver.
 last night each.M.SG.NOM
 *“The hunters caught 30 birds last night each.”

115 http://www.toyota.is/innovation/technology/safety/avensis_ncap_2003.aspx

- (118) *Veidimennir-nir mega hver veiða 30 fugla.*
 hunter.M.PL.NOM-the can.3PL.PRES each.M.SG.NOM catch.INF 30 bird.M.PL.ACC
 “The hunters can each catch 30 birds.”

In (116) we see *hver_{ant}* occurring between a verb and its complement, while in (117) we see that *hver_{ant}* can appear after a verb's complement but before a sentential adjunct, but not after a sentential adjunct – once again suggesting the *hver_{ant}* is inside the VP. Finally, in (118) *hver* appears in the middle of the verbal element. With reference to the antecedent case reciprocal construction, based upon substitutional information, when *hver* and *annar* are adjacent, they may be substituted by a NP. This information can be captured by treating *hver_{ant}/annar* as being in specifier position to the NP headed by *annar*. When *hver_{ant}/annar* appears before a preposition (such as in (119)) I will treat it similarly as being in specifier position to the PP:

- (119) Survey – section B, question iv: 23.52% of responses
Ég kynnti menni-na tvo
 I.1SG.NOM introduce.1SG.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the two.M.PL.ACC

hvorn fyrir öðrum
 each.M.SG.ACC for other.M.SG.DAT
 “I introduced the two men to each other.”

2.8.2.2 ANALYSIS

I now present my analysis for the antecedent case reciprocal construction. The c- and f-structures for (120) are presented below (note that the treatment of *hver* here is as *hver_{ant}* above):

- (120) *Maðurinn og presturinn sáu hvor annan*
 man.M.SG.NOM and priest.M.SG.NOM see.3PL.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “The man and the priest saw each other.”

	PRED	'see<SUBJ,OBJ>'
	TENSE	PST
		NUM PL
		GEND {M}
		QUANTTYPE RECIP
		CASE NOM
SUBJ		[PRED 'man'
		CASE NOM
		DEF +
		GEND {M}
		NUM SG]
		[PRED 'priest'
		CASE NOM
		DEF +
		GEND {M}
		NUM SG]
OBJ		[PRED 'PRO'
		CASE ACC
		NUM SG
		GEND {M}]

This analysis readily predicts the ungrammaticality of sentences like (121) below where *hvers* has genitive case marking:

- (121) **Bræður-nir* *sáu* *hvers* *annan*.
- brother.M.PL.NOM-the see.3PL.PST each.M.SG.GEN other.M.SG.ACC
- “The brothers saw each other.”

The lexical entry for *hvers* appears below:

hvers_{ans} det. AFS = %ANT

%ANT QUANTTYPE = RECIP

%ANT CASE=_c GEN

%ANT GEN=_c {M}

%ANT NUM=_c PL

In (121) there is no grammatical function in the clause (as defined by the search domain) which has been assigned genitive case – as such the assignment of %ANT CASE=GEN will cause a feature clash and the resulting sentence is ungrammatical.

Finally, this analysis also predicts the grammaticality of sentences (subject to c-structure restrictions) of reciprocal constructions where *hvorn_{ant}* (or *hver_{ant}*) appears inside a PP. For example, consider (122) below:

- (122) Við kynntum menni-na fyrir hvorn öðrum.
 We.NOM introduce.1PL.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the for/to each.M.SG.ACC other.M.SG.DAT
 “We_i introduced the men_j to each other_{j,*i}”

The lexical entry for *hvorn* appears below:

hvorn_{ant}, det. AFS = %ANT
 %ANT QUANTTYPE = RECIP
 %ANT CASE= ACC
 %ANT GEN= {M}
 %ANT NUM= PL

PRED	'introduce<SUBJ,OBJ,OBL _{GOAL} >'	
TENSE	PST	
SUBJ	PRED	'PRO'
	NUM	PL
	GEND	{M}
	CASE	NOM
	PERS	1
OBJ	PRED	'men'
	NUM	PL
	GEND	{M}
	CASE	ACC
	QUANTTYPE	RECIP
OBL _{GOAL}	PRED	'PRO'
	PCASE	OBL _{GOAL}
	CASE	DAT
	NUM	SG
	GEND	{M}

Note that the ambiguity in the English translation of (122) is avoided using this construction in Icelandic because *hvorn* can only find as its antecedent *mennina* – “the men” and not the subject NP because of the requirement that its antecedent's case be accusative.

2.8.2.3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This analysis of the antecedent case reciprocal construction answers many of the questions posed at the start of this chapter. The antecedent case reciprocal construction is made from two words, *hvor/hver* and *annar* – if adjacent, they form a phrase at the level of c-structure, but in terms of f-structure, *hvor/hver* is associated with the NP with which it shares the same case – just as it did in Old Icelandic. This explains the strange case marking of the reciprocal construction. *Hvor/hver* has the same case as its antecedent – behaving in all respects like other quantifiers in Icelandic that may appear in various positions within the clause but which are tied, both syntactically and semantically, to their antecedent. *Annar* on the other hand is a regular pronoun – and its case is assigned by the verb or preposition which selects it as a complement. Despite the fact that *hvor_{ant}/hver_{ant}* can be separated from *annar* by a preposition, for transitive reciprocal constructions *hvor/hver* and *annar* are adjacent and form a phrase – one with undeniably unusual case assignment. As we will see in the analyses of the phrasal (2.8.3) and fixed form reciprocal constructions (2.8.4), this aberrant construction has more recently been brought back in to the fold of regular case assignment.

2.8.3 The phrasal reciprocal construction

Recall that I defined phrasal reciprocal constructions as those where *hvor/hver* shares the same case as *annar*:

- (123) *Bræður-nir sáu hvern annan.*
 brother.M.PL.NOM-the see.3PL.PST each.N.SG.ACC other.M.SG.ACC
 “The brothers saw each other.”

I argue here that people have re-analysed *hver_{ant}* in the reciprocal construction as a regular determiner to *annar*. This analysis is plausible both on syntactic grounds (*hvor/hver annar* now has regular case assignment) but also has a precedent when considering the various uses of *hver/hvor* and *annar*. For example, *annar* is a pronoun which can take a determiner:¹¹⁶

- (124) *Ég sá alla aðra.*
 I.1SG.NOM see.1SG.PST all.M.PL.ACC other.M.PL.ACC
 “I saw everybody else / all (the) others.”

- (125) *Mér finnst sjálfsagt að minna-st á ýmsa aðra.*¹¹⁷
 I.1SG.DAT find.3SG-RFLX natural to mention-MV on
 certain.M.PL.ACC other.M.PL.ACC
 “It seems to me natural to mention certain others.”

Earlier we saw instances of *hver/hvor* acting as a regular determiner:

- (126) *Hver bók er í kringum 500 blaðsíður.*¹¹⁸
 Each.F.SG.NOM book.F.SG.NOM be.3SG.PRES about 500 page.N.PL.NOM
 “Each book is about 500 pages long.”

116 See also section 2.4.7 for examples of *annar* taking *hvor* as a determiner with a meaning of “every other (one)” rather than “each other”.

117 <http://fhingar.net/fullStory.php?id=328&action=next&p=pistlar>

118 <http://www.althingi.is/altext/117/O4/r07120026.shtml>

Because of this, I argue that speakers re-analyse *hver_{ant}/hvor_{ant}* as a determiner to *annar*. Syntactically there is also strong evidence for this re-analysis. In nearly all instances where *hvor* or *hver* shares the same case as *annar*, they appear next to one another. This is in contrast to the antecedent form of the reciprocal construction where *hvor/hver* can appear next to, but also separated from *annar*. For example, two questions from the survey are illustrative. In section C, question v, the respondents are asked to provide any of the possible forms of *hvor annar* for the sentence “The two women ran from each other”. The preposition *frá* – from requires its complement to be in dative case. The results are below:

(127) Possible Reciprocal Constructions for, “The two women ran from each other”

Section C, Question v: *Konurnar tvær hlupu [??? ??? ???]*

<u>Type of Reciprocal Construction</u>	<u>Form of reciprocal</u>	<u>Responses</u>	
a. antecedent case construction ¹¹⁹ :	<i>frá hvor annarri</i>	252	45%
b. antecedent case construction:	<i>hvor frá annarri</i>	197	35%
c. phrasal reciprocal construction:	<i>frá hvorri annarri</i>	113	20%
d. ungrammatical form:	<i>hvorri frá annarri</i>	2	0%

In (c) and (d) *hvorri* is the feminine singular dative form of *hvor*. We see that *hvor* can only have the same case as *annar* when it appears next to it. In (128) below, only 2% of respondents would allow that they used or had heard someone else use *hvor* with the same case as *annar* when separated by a preposition (note that in this usage, the preposition *fyrir* requires its complement to have accusative case):

(128) Possible Reciprocal Constructions for “I introduced the two men to each other”

Section B, Question iv: *Ég kynnti mennina tvo [??? ??? ???].*

¹¹⁹ It is likely that for some few speakers, *hvor* here actually represents the frozen case form of the reciprocal construction. However, see (128) below where *hvor* cannot be understood to be in such a construction.

- (131) *annan, pro*, ↑PRED= 'PRO_{rec}'
 ↑NUM= SG
 ↑CASE= ACC
 ↑GEN={M}
 ↑QUANTTYPE=_c RECIP
 AFS = %ANT
 %ANT GEN=_c ↑GEN
 %ANT NUM=_c PL

In (130), *hvern* adds its functional information to the f-structure associated with *annar*.

The syntactic structures for (129) appears below:

	[PRED	'see<SUBJ,OBJ>']
		TENSE	PST	
			[
			PRED	'brother'
			CASE	NOM
			NUM	PL
			DEF	+
			GEND	{M}
			PERS	3
]	
			[
			PRED	'PRO _{rec} '
			QUANTTYPE	RECIP
			CASE	ACC
			NUM	SG
			GEND	{M}
]	

In the c- and f-structures above, the standard phrase structure rule for determiners places the *hver* in the same grammatical function as *annar*, and so *hver* contributes its information to the same functional structure. Note that the QUANTTYPE feature is no longer associated with the antecedent, but with the f-structure associated with *hvern annan*. This reflects a change in the reciprocation strategy of the reciprocal construction

from compositional to phrasal. As *hvor/hver* is no longer linked to its antecedent, but rather to *annar*, I argue that we should consider *hvor/hver annar* as a single, complex, reciprocal pronoun. Thus, although the historical origins of the phrasal reciprocal construction are evident, the phrasal reciprocal construction is now formed via a new pronominal process. The severance of *hvor/hver* from the reciprocal construction's antecedent predicts an ambiguity in certain sentences. For example, in (132) the antecedent of the reciprocal construction can be variously identified as the subject (132a), the object (132b) or either (132c):¹²¹

(132) a. *Við kynntum menni-na hvor*
 we.1PL.NOM introduce.1PL.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the each.M.SG.NOM
fyrir öðrum.
 for other.M.SG.DAT
 “We_i introduced the men_j to each other_i.”

b. *Við kynntum menni-na*
 we.1PL.NOM introduce.1PL.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the
hvorn fyrir öðrum.
 each.M.SG.ACC for other.M.SG.DAT
 “We_i introduced the men_j to each other_j.”

c. *Við kynntum menni-na fyrir*
 we.1PL.NOM introduce.1PL.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the for
hvorum öðrum.
 each.M.SG.DAT other.M.SG.DAT
 “We_i introduced the men_j to each other_{ij}.”

Because *hvor* specifies the case of its antecedent in (132a) and (132b) there is no possible ambiguity in who is introducing whom. In (132a) nominative case on *hvor* means that the antecedent to the reciprocal construction is the subject, in (132b) the

121 Coindexing *hvor fyrir öðrum* with “men” is possible if speakers use the fixed form reciprocal construction.

antecedent must be the object. This is in contrast to (132c) where *hvor* acts as a determiner to *annar*. In this situation, the domain in which the reciprocal construction must find its antecedent has two possible candidates (the subject and object) – hence the ambiguity.

2.8.4 The fixed form reciprocal construction

In the fixed form reciprocal construction *annar* takes its case in the regular manner, but *hvor/hver* has its case fixed in the nominative – and this case doesn't change regardless of the case of its antecedent. For example, in every example in (133), the antecedent is in accusative case, but *hvor* appears in the nominative:

(133) Survey – section B, question iv: 7.49% of responses

a. *Ég kynnti menni-na tvo*
 I.1SG.NOM introduce.1SG.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the two.M.PL.ACC

hvor fyrir öðrum.
 each.M.SG.NOM for other.M.SG.DAT

“I introduced the two men to each other.”

Survey – section B, question iv: 38.50% of responses

b. *Ég kynnti menni-na tvo*
 I.1SG.NOM introduce.1SG.PST men.M.PL.ACC-the two.M.PL.ACC

fyrir hvor öðrum.
 for each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.DAT

“I introduced the two men to each other.”

Survey – section E, question ii: 13.16% of responses

c. *Elskhuga-na dreymdi hvor annan.*¹²²
 lover.M.PL.ACC-the dream.3SG.PST each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC

“The lovers dreamt of each other.”

122 *Dreymdi* (from *dreyma* - to dream) like many other experiential verbs in Icelandic is irregular, assigning accusative case to both its subject and object.

In the examples above, we can rule out the other construction types. Sentences (133a-b) can't be examples of the antecedent case construction because *hvor* is not agreeing with its antecedent which is marked in accusative case in each instance. We can rule out the phrasal case construction as *hvor* cannot possibly agree with *annar*, because *annar* is marked in dative or accusative case. Finally, because *hvor* does not appear in the NP which it quantifies, we can rule out the compositional reciprocal construction.

Everaert (1991:298) points out that there is some debate with respect to nominative case assignment – himself (and others) arguing that nominative case means “lack of case” (see Everaert, 1991; Andrews, 1982 for example). Everaert's argument is supported, if we take the long view that *hvor/hver* are being progressively bleached of their origins as quantifiers – and that the reciprocal construction is slowly becoming an idiomatic chunk (as has occurred in many other Germanic languages). The choice then of fixing *hvor/hver* in nominative case could be seen under these circumstances as the result of *hvor/hver* simply losing its case marking altogether – strongly supporting the analysis that *hvor/hver annar* should be analysed as a single (complex) pronominal. Note however, that this process is by no means complete – although it is true that the fixed case form of the reciprocal construction does not decline for case, it certainly still exhibits number concord (for some speakers) and gender concord (for all speakers). Furthermore, examining (133a) above, we see that the *hvor* can still be separated from *annar* for a minority of speakers.

Nevertheless, the analysis of this construction is straightforward. I will analyse the fixed case reciprocal construction in the same way as the phrasal reciprocal construction, although the constraint that *hvor/hver* and its antecedent have the same case is relaxed. Thus, the definition of *hvor* in this context is:

- (133) *hvor*_{frozen} ↑QUANTTYPE = RECIP
 ↑GEN= {M}
 ↑NUM= SG

In all other respects, the fixed form of the reciprocal construction behaves like the phrasal reciprocal construction in (2.8.3). We can speculate that if this bleaching of lexical specifications continues there might be a time when the construction is formed by a single word: *hverannar*. Although we can never be sure of such predictions, there are precedents for it both in Icelandic (e.g., *hvorutveggja* – from *hvor tveggja* (“each of

two”) which no longer declines for case) and in other Germanic languages (e.g., German: *einander* – “one another”). Certainly the loss of the case marker is a development in line with a prediction by Plank (2008) that *hvor/hver annar* eventually join other Germanic languages in having a reciprocal construction formed via a single word. Both the phrasal and fixed case variants of the Icelandic reciprocal construction use a reciprocal pronoun (and its associated operator, RECIP) to create a symmetric interpretation of an event. The details of how this operator is linked to syntax is demonstrated in appendix A.

2.9 CONCLUSION

I undertook two surveys of the Icelandic reciprocal construction and they revealed four variants of the construction; Compositional, Antecedent Case, Phrasal and Fixed Case as well as a rich system of number concord making a distinction between the number of protagonists and whether those protagonists were acting as groups or individuals. The oldest of the variants was the compositional reciprocal construction, and it showed that *hvor/hver* found their origin in the subject NP as quantifier pronouns. The next oldest construction is the antecedent case reciprocal construction (still used by many speakers today, and typically the only account of the Icelandic reciprocal construction given in grammars). This construction relies on the fact that quantifiers can have variable distributive within a clause – a process called “quantifier float” and one that Plank (2008) appeals to as an explanation for the origin of many Germanic reciprocal constructions. Although *hvor/hver* no longer appear in the NP they quantify, their function remains unchanged – they still distribute a relation over every entity within the set specified by their antecedent. The phrasal and fixed form reciprocal constructions are the most recent variations. The phrasal reciprocal construction has *hvor/hver* acting as a determiner to *annar* – and so agreeing within it in number, case and gender. The fixed form reciprocal construction is analysed similarly, although *hvor/hver* have lost their case feature and appear in their default form. What these constructions have in common is that they are no longer compositional in nature – instead *hvor/hver annar* is acting as a complex reciprocal pronoun. The loss of case agreement in the fixed form reciprocal construction suggests that this complex pronoun may be in the process of becoming a single word – which fits with Plank's (2008) observation that Germanic

bipartite reciprocal constructions generally form single morphological units.

Below I present diagrammatic explanation of the development of the Icelandic reciprocal construction from *þekkir hverr annan* (“each knows the other” in Old Icelandic) to *Þeir þekkja hver/n annan* (“they know each other” in Modern Icelandic):

- (134) *Þeir þekkja hver annan.*
 they.M.PL.NOM know.3PL.PRES each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “They know each other.”

Compositional Reciprocal Construction – Old Icelandic Antecedent Case Reciprocal Construction – Icelandic Pronominal Reciprocal Construction – Icelandic

(Note, in the diagram above, the subscripts below indicate where *hver/n* puts its functional information. For example, *hver_i* in the antecedent case reciprocal constructions adds the quantifier feature attribute of RECIP to the subject f-structure. Also, I use the term “pronominal reciprocal construction” to refer to both the fixed form reciprocal construction and the phrasal reciprocal construction. Both use a reciprocal

pronoun for the reciprocation strategy, differing only in whether *hver/hvor* still has a case feature.)

At the outset of this chapter I claimed that the unusual case marking and word order phenomena associated with the Icelandic reciprocal construction was best understood as arising from a change in the reciprocation strategy that underlies its formation. The theoretical framework of LFG allows us to clearly capture this process, especially the transitional nature of the antecedent case reciprocal construction. The antecedent case reciprocal construction's f-structure is almost unchanged from its Old Icelandic origins, but its c-structure reflects modern constituency structure. The ability of quantifiers like *hver* and *hvor* in Icelandic to appear in different places within a clause while still quantifying an antecedent meant that the change in Icelandic from a non-configurational to a configurational language could be accommodated while still preserving the existing compositional reciprocation mechanism. However, this came at the cost of requiring non-standard case assignment to the NP headed by *annar* and this may be the motivation for the recent phrasal and fixed form reciprocal constructions.

The analysis above reenforces one of the themes of this thesis – that the surface morphosyntactic expression of a reciprocal construction is not a good predictor of its syntactic behaviour. For example, *hver annan* in (134) could be formed by either a compositional or pronominal reciprocation strategy, either of which affects the case and distribution of *hver* in different ways.

3 THE MALAGASY VERBAL RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In the previous chapter we examined the Icelandic reciprocal construction and saw the development of an underlying pronominal reciprocation strategy as the means by which it expresses symmetry. I now turn to the Malagasy reciprocal construction and examine it with a view to explaining its behaviour in a variety of syntactic environments.¹²³ I will argue that despite the Malagasy reciprocal construction having very different morphosyntactic expression to the Icelandic reciprocal construction, it surprisingly uses the same underlying reciprocation strategy – and that only this strategy can explain its behaviour in different syntactic environments.

Sentence (1a) shows a typical Malagasy transitive sentence with VOS word order. The NP functioning as object, when it is a pronoun or a proper noun, receives an ACC case marker. The verb has two prefixes, a tense marker *N* and a voice marker *-an-*. In general, verbal morphology can also indicate aspect, reciprocity and causality. Sentence (1b) shows the corresponding reciprocal construction which is formed by a verbal prefix *-if-*, with all the participants in the relation appearing in the subject NP and a

¹²³ This chapter builds upon work first presented by Hurst (2003). An earlier version of this analysis was presented at LFG 2006 (see Hurst, 2006) and incorporates feedback from Ash Asudeh and others.

concomitant loss of the object NP:

(1) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:47)

a. Basic Sentence

<i>N-an-daka</i>	<i>an-dRabe</i>	<i>Rakoto.</i>
PST-ACT-kick	ACC-Rabe	Rakoto
verb	obj	subj

“Rakoto kicked Rabe.”

Reciprocated Sentence

b. <i>N-if-an-daka</i>	<i>Rabe</i>	<i>sy</i>	<i>Rakoto.</i>
PST-REC-ACT-kick	Rabe	and	Rakoto
verb	-----subj-----		

“Rabe and Rakoto kicked each other.”

Existing analyses for other verbally marked reciprocal constructions (including those offered by Alsina (1996) for Catalan and other Romance languages, Mchombo (1991) for Chicheŵa, Rákosi (2008) for Hungarian and Siloni (2011) for French – among other languages) all treat the reciprocated verb as being intransitive, or more precisely, as having lost a non-subject grammatical function. Certainly such analyses are appealing for the Malagasy reciprocal construction which also lacks an object NP. However, on closer inspection, this construction has some very surprising behaviour. For example, none of the previously mentioned verbally marked reciprocal constructions may co-occur with object possession – however, the Malagasy reciprocal construction does:

(2) Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001:52)¹²⁴

<i>M-if-an-ome</i>	<i>vola</i>	<i>zananaka</i>	<i>Raso</i>	<i>sy</i>	<i>Ravelo.</i>
PRES-REC-ACT-give	money	child	Raso	and	Ravelo

“Raso and Ravelo give money to each other's children.”

124 Most nouns in Malagasy do not make a distinction in number. So *zananaka* - “child” in (2) could equally be “children”.

Sentences such as these exemplify two of the key issues related to this construction. The first issue is the mixed signals this construction has with respect to transitivity: in (1b) the construction appears intransitive, but in (2) there is no immediately clear way of understanding the relationship Rabe and Ravelo share with each other's children without utilizing an object grammatical function. Second, the compatibility of the Malagasy reciprocal construction with object possession seems to relate it more closely to the Icelandic pronominal reciprocal construction than to other superficially similar verbal reciprocal constructions.

In fact, despite the strong similarities in the morphosyntactic expression of the Malagasy and Swahili reciprocation constructions (*c.f.*, (1) above with example (4) in chapter 1), there is a startling amount of variability in their resulting syntax. As I foreshadowed earlier in section 1.1, I explain these differences as arising as a consequence of the nature of the reciprocation strategy involved – and each of these strategies (the application of a pronominal operator, theta-role synthesis or argument unification) may be applied to verbally marked reciprocal constructions, resulting in differences in their syntactic and semantic behaviour.

I argue that existing analyses of other verbally marked reciprocal constructions are unable to explain the behaviour of the Malagasy reciprocal construction in wider syntactic environments. Rather, I argue it needs to be understood as a disguised instance of the application of a pronoun operator reciprocation strategy that results in a mismatch between the number of grammatical functions specified by the verb with the number of overt NPs or PPs.

We saw previously that the Icelandic reciprocal construction leaves the argument and functional structure of reciprocated verbs unchanged. That this must be the case was immediately apparent – a typically transitive verb such as *sáu* – “see” (see chapter 2 example (1b)) retains both its grammatical functions (*i.e.*, its subject and object) when reciprocated. The argument I am making for the Malagasy reciprocal construction is that its verb's argument and functional structure are likewise unaffected by the process of reciprocation. This results in a mismatch, because the claim that the verb retains all its grammatical functions is seemingly contradicted by sentences like (1b) above where the NP associated with the object is obviously missing. By using the parallel syntactic structures offered by the theory of LFG, I show that this mismatch between grammatical functions and constituent structure, far from being a problem, is the only way that

syntactic behaviour of these constructions can be understood.

The data in this chapter comes from three chief sources: Keenan and Razafimamonjy (2001) who wrote an extensive article on Malagasy reciprocals and Pearson & Paul (1996) and Paul (1998) who compiled two volumes entitled “The structure of Malagasy”. The latter two volumes contain sixteen papers related to the syntax of Malagasy. Where possible, I have supplemented their data with elicited examples from two language consultants (both first language speakers of Malagasy). During the course of this chapter, I introduce the details of Malagasy syntax where appropriate. However, for a general introduction to Malagasy, I recommend both Keenan & Ochs (1979) and Keenan & Polinsky (1998).

3.2 THE MALAGASY RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION

Malagasy is an Austronesian language spoken by over 14 million people in Madagascar. There are two main dialects spoken and the examples reproduced here from Keenan and Razafimamonjy (2001) are based upon the official dialect of Malagasy as spoken at and near the capital and used by government. Malagasy is known for a rich system of verbal marking that allows nearly any argument selected by the verb to be realised as subject. The Malagasy reciprocal construction is formed by adding a prefix *-if-* to the verbal root as shown in (1b) above. There exist two further allomorphs of the reciprocal affix: *-ifamp-* and *-ifanka-*. Their usage is conditioned by the active prefix:

-if- is used when the active prefix has the form *-aN-* or *-ana-*.¹²⁵

-ifamp- is used when the active prefix has the form *-i-*.

-ifanka- is used when the active prefix has the form *-a-* or *-aha-*.

Keenan and Razafimamonjy (2001) convincingly demonstrated that NP *Rabe sy Rakoto* in (1b) is actually a subject NP by showing that it may be relativised – an operation that is only available to subject NPs in Malagasy. Additionally, *Rabe sy Rakoto* can be substituted with the nominative pronoun *izy*, but not its accusative equivalent *azy*:

125 *-N-* means any nasalised consonant.

- (3) Relativisation of *Rabe sy Rakoto* (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:22)

Ny olona (izay) n-if-an-daka.

“The people (who) were kicking each other.”

Thus, it is uncontroversial that *Rabe* and *Rakoto* in (1b) are part of a single NP that is functioning as the subject of the verb.

The reciprocal construction in Malagasy is very productive, appearing with verbs with a variety of arities and in a variety of constructions. Below I list some examples to give an indication of the versatility of this construction. In (4a) below the semi-transitive verb *mandainga* – “lie” takes the prepositional phrase “to Ranaivo” as a complement. The reciprocal equivalent to (4a) optionally retains the preposition, but the NP it selected is now missing:

- (4) Semi-transitive Verb (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:49)

a. *M-an-dainga amin'i Be Ranaivo.*

PRES-ACT-lie to³ART Be Ranaivo

“Ranaivo lies to Be.”

b. *M-if-an-dainga (amin)'i Be sy Ranaivo.*

PRES-REC-ACT-lie (to)'ART Be and Ranaivo

“Be and Ranaivo lie to each other.”

In (4b), the article *i* attached to the preposition *amin* is adding definiteness information to the proper noun *Be*; for convenience it will be analysed as being part of the NP it specifies. The preposition *amin* – “to” in (4b) is optional – however for PPs which have semantically heavy prepositions (*e.g.*, *akaikin* – “near”), the preposition is obligatory.¹²⁶

In (5) below, the ditransitive verb *manome* – “give” may also be reciprocated. Note that even though the verb selects two objects, only the recipient may be passivised, so in this instance the OBJ (and not the OBJ₀) is missing.¹²⁷

126 See Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001:49) for discussion.

127 For further discussion, see Van Valin (2001:68).

(5) Ditransitive Verb (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:49)

- a. *M-an-ome vola an-dRabe Rakoto.*
 PRES-ACT-give money ACC-Rabe Rakoto
 V OBJ_θ OBJ S
 “Rakoto gives money to Rabe.”

- b. *M-if-an-ome vola Rabe sy Rakoto.*
 PRES-REC-ACT-give money Rabe and Rakoto
 V OBJ_θ S
 “Rabe and Rakoto give money to each other.”

Sentences (6) and (7) are examples of causative and circumstantial constructions – both of which can co-occur with the reciprocal construction:

(6) Causative Construction (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:67)

- a. *N-if-an-daka Rabe sy Rakoto.*
 PST-REC-ACT-kick Rabe and Rakoto
 “Rabe and Rakoto kicked each other.”
- b. *N-amp-if-an-daka an-dRabe sy Rakoto aho.*
 PST-CAUS-REC-ACT-kick ACC-Rabe and Rakoto 1SG.NOM
 “I made Rabe and Rakoto kick each other.”

(7) Circumstantial Construction (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:56)

- a. *N-if-an-tao farafara amin'ity vy ity*
 PST-REC-ACT-do bed with-this metal this

Rabe sy Rakoto.
 Rabe and Rakoto
 “Rabe and Rakoto made each other beds from this metal.”

- b. *N-if-an-tao-van-dRabe sy Rakoto farafara ity vy ity.*
PST-REC-ACT-DO-CIRC-Rabe and Rakoto bed this metal this
lit. “This metal was made by Rabe and Rakoto beds for each other.”
“This metal was made into beds for each other by Rabe and Rakoto.”

Within the LFG literature there are two analyses posited for verbally marked reciprocal constructions. In section 3.3 I outline these and investigate their implications regarding the construction's behaviour in a wider range of syntactic environments in sections 3.4 – 3.6 before presenting my own analysis in section 3.7.

3.3 LFG ANALYSES OF VERBALLY MARKED RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTIONS

Both of the analyses described below are instances of the reciprocation strategies discussed in this thesis. The argument suppression analysis in section 3.3.1 uses a reciprocal operator (RECIP) associated with a syntactic operation that suppresses an argument as the underlying means by which an asymmetric predicate is made symmetric. In section 3.3.2 I discuss argument unification reciprocation strategy in detail and its application to Malagasy. In this section I focus on the syntactic consequences of these analyses – and delay the discussion of their semantic consequences to chapter 4.3.5.

3.3.1 Argument suppression analysis of the reciprocal construction in Chicheŵa

Like other researchers in the area of verbally marked reciprocal constructions, Mchombo (1991) addresses the issue what happens to the object grammatical function when a transitive verb is reciprocated. His analysis of the reciprocal construction in Chicheŵa builds upon the standard LFG analysis of the passive construction (see below) by positing that an argument at the level of a-structure has been suppressed and so does not map to f-structure. I present his analysis in detail in chapter 4 where I discuss its application to Swahili. However, I will introduce his work below because of its relevance to the discussion at hand.

Consider first the analysis of the passive construction. Lexical mapping theory allows thematic roles which are negatively specified to be suppressed (Bresnan,

2001:310; Alsina, 1990). By suppressing the proto-agent thematic role, the proto-patient is in turn mapped to the subject using the system discussed in section 1.5.4.1. The example below involving *phika* – “cook” is from Mchombo (2004):

(8) Chicheŵa (Mchombo, 2004:91)¹²⁸

a. Active Voice

Kalulú a-ku-phík-á maúngu.
 hare 3SGS-PRES-cook-FV pumpkins
 “The hare is cooking pumpkins.”

b. Passive Voice

Maúngu a-ku-phik-idw-a (ndí kilúlu).
 pumpkins 3SGS-PRES-cook-PASS-FV (by hare)
 “The pumpkins are being cooked (by the hare).”

The standard analysis of the passive verb *akuphíkídwa* – “be cooked” is below (the structures are simplified to present only the relevant information):

(9)	<p>Active Voice <i>phík-a</i><[P-A] [P-P]></p>	↔	<p>Passive Voice <i>phík-idw-a</i><[P-A] [P-P]></p>
	<p>intrinsic: [-o] [-r]</p>		<p>intrinsic: [-o] [-r]</p>
	<p>default: [-r] -</p>		<p><i>-idw-</i>: Ø</p>
	<p>↓ ↓</p>		<p>↓</p>
	<p>GF SUBJ OBJ</p>		<p>GF SUBJ</p>
	<p>[SUBJ [PRED ‘the hares’] OBJ [PRED ‘the pumpkins’] PRED ‘cook<SUBJ,OBJ>’]</p>		<p>[SUBJ [PRED ‘the pumpkins’] PRED ‘be_cooked<SUBJ>’]</p>

The reciprocal construction in Chicheŵa is formed by suffixing *-an-* to the verb. Using a variety of tests (including the object comparison test – see section 3.4 and a nominalisation process that only occurs with verbs having an object – see chapter

128 The Bantu languages have a rich system of gender marking for nouns – these are irrelevant for the discussion at hand and so are ignored. The full interlinearisations are available in Mchombo (2004).

4.2.2). Mchombo (1991) convincingly demonstrates that reciprocated verbs in Chicheŵa are intransitive. In a manner very similar to the passive above, Mchombo captures this lack of object in syntax by suppressing the proto-patient theme when a verb is reciprocated:

(10) Chicheŵa (Mchombo, 1991) – Adapted to fit the notation used here.

“cook each other”	<i>phík-an-a</i>	<[P-A] [P-P]>
intrinsic:	[-o]	[-r]
-an-:		Ø
default:	[+r]	
	↓	
		cook _{rec} <SUBJ>

However, he notes that there is a difference between the passive and the reciprocal processes he describes since “in reciprocation, the suppressed role must actually be expressed as an oblique and be bound to the subject function, unless the subject noun denotes a group which can be construed as containing the suppressed role.” (Mchombo, 1991:16). In other words, although the patient argument is *syntactically* suppressed, it is thematically linked to the subject (and, under some circumstances, must be overtly expressed as an oblique – see discussion in chapter 4.2.2).

3.3.2 Argument unification analysis of the reciprocal construction in Catalan

The reflexive/reciprocal construction in Catalan (and other Romance languages) is formed via the application of a clitic to the verb with the loss of an object NP:

(11) Catalan (Hualde 1992:342)

<i>en</i>	<i>Joan</i>	<i>i</i>	<i>la</i>	<i>Maria</i>	<i>s'estimen</i> .
ART	John	and	ART	Maria	RR'love.3PL
“John and Mary love each other/themselves.”					

Alsina argues that reciprocal constructions in Romance languages allow two arguments to be mapped to the same grammatical function via a mechanism he called “a-structure

binding” (Alsina 1996:116).¹²⁹ This process provides a natural account of monovalent reflexives – the original predicate with two arguments (*wash* with an agent and a patient for example), can have both arguments mapped to the subject grammatical function and the resulting PRED becoming *wash-recip*. Diagrammatically this is represented as (12) below:

- (12) Argument unification analysis for Catalan reciprocal constructions
(Alsina, 1996:262)

Note that this analysis sits outside typical LFG theory insofar as it violates Bresnan's (1980) function-argument bi-uniqueness constraint which states that “Each a-structure role must be associated with a unique function, and conversely.” However, there is much to recommend this analysis – especially when applied to Romance languages. For example, it is in step with Siloni's (2011) more semantically focused analysis of the monadic constructions which also links two thematic roles to a single grammatical function (see chapter 4). Furthermore, it suits our intuitions that the entities in a reciprocal or reflexive construction like (11) above are acting as both initiators and endpoints to a relation and so can be thought of as being both proto-agents and proto-patients (*c.f.* chapter 1.4.2).

With respect to f-structure, both the argument suppression and the bi-argument functional mapping analysis of reciprocal constructions are equivalent – they produce a predicate that has no OBJ function, despite having a proto-agent and proto-patient in a-structure. As such, I will use the term “valency reducing” to refer to either of these analyses – but note that I am restricting the meaning of valency in this context to mean only the number of grammatical functions at the level of f-structure, and not the number of arguments in a-structure, nor the number of constituents in c-structure. Under a valency reducing analysis of the Malagasy reciprocal construction the analysis of a

¹²⁹ For clarity with the other strategies I identify as being involved in reciprocation – I will refer to argument structure binding as the “argument unification reciprocation strategy”

sentence like (1b) is seemingly straightforward:

(13) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:47)¹³⁰

N-if-an-daka Rabe sy Rakoto.

PST-REC-ACT-kick Rabe and Rakoto

nifandaka, v (↑ PRED) = 'kick_{rec}<(↑ SUBJ)>'

(↑ TENSE) = PST

(↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE

Furthermore, this analysis correctly predicts the ungrammaticality of sentences such as (14) below where the presence of an object renders the sentence ungrammatical. This is because the resulting f-structure is incoherent (that is there is a grammatical function in f-structure that is not selected by a PRED – see chapter 1.5.3):

(14) Malagasy (elicited)

**N-if-an-daka an-dRabe Rasoa sy Rakoto.*

PST-REC-ACT-kick ACC-Rabe Rasoa and Rakoto

*“Rasoa and Rakoto kicked each other Rabe”

¹³⁰ I am assuming that, for Malagasy, functional descriptors for the creation of SUBJ and OBJ grammatical functions are associated with the phrase structure rules. The functional contribution of coordinated NP's has been simplified in the given f-structures.

Above I presented two analyses of the verbally marked reciprocal constructions as they could be applied to Malagasy. These analyses describe two similar reciprocation strategies: argument suppression (where the P-P thematic role is suppressed in the mapping between a- and f-structure) and argument unification (where both thematic roles map to a single grammatical function – see discussion in chapter 4.2.) Both of these reciprocation strategies reduce the number of grammatical functions that the verb requires at the level of f-structure, and can adequately account for the basic syntactic behaviour of the Malagasy reciprocal construction. However, as we will see, it is only when we examine this construction's behaviour in wider syntactic environments that we gain a better understanding of the valency of the reciprocated verb.

Within the literature, the object comparison test is often used as an indicator of a verb's valency. In section 3.4, I discuss this test and summarise its results when applied to the Malagasy reciprocal construction – as described by Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001).

3.4 DETERMINING VALENCY: THE OBJECT COMPARISON TEST

Although the reciprocated verb in Malagasy has lost the NP associated with the object grammatical function, it is not clear whether or not the verb still requires an object at f-structure. In other words, we need to consider whether the reciprocal morpheme detransitivises the verb, or whether it functions as an incorporated pronoun, leaving the reciprocated verb's valency unchanged. Within the literature on reciprocal constructions (e.g., Dalrymple *et al.* 1994; Mchombo, 1991; Nakao, 2003; Keenan & Razafimamonjy,

2001) there is widespread use of Zec's (1985) “object comparisons” as a means of determining the transitivity of a verbally marked reciprocal construction. In this section, I will describe this test and discuss Keenan & Razafimamonjy's (2001) interpretation of it as applied to Malagasy.

Consider (15a) below – its meaning is in fact ambiguous, having two possible interpretations (15b) and (15c) respectively. (15b) is known as a subject comparison because it compares two subjects – how many fish the eagles (subject) and the bears (subject) caught. In sentence (15c), we have an object comparison because we are comparing how many fish (object) were killed with how many bears (object) were killed.

- (15) a. *Eagles kill more fish than bears.*
- b. Subject Comparison: *Eagles kill more fish than bears kill fish.*
e.g., **Eagles** kill 100 fish a year.
Bears kill 90 fish a year.
- c. Object Comparison: *Eagles kill more fish than they (the eagles) kill bears.*
e.g., Eagles kill 100 **fish** a year.
Eagles kill 1 **bear** a year.

An object comparison ought to be impossible with a verb that is missing an object. This is illustrated in (16) below where the object of *kill* is missing. In (16b), the subject comparison is available, but the object comparison in (16c) is not:

- (16) a. *Eagles kill more than bears.*
- b. Subject Comparison: *Eagles kill more than bears kill.*
i.e., The **eagles** killed 200 times.
The **bears** killed 100 times.
- c. *Eagles kill more (?) than they (the eagles) kill bears.
i.e., Eagles killed 100 ??
Eagles killed 90 **bears**.

The above demonstrates that a missing object disallows an object comparison. Mchombo (1991:9) notes that object comparisons are also disallowed for reciprocated verbs in Chicheŵa. In the examples below he is contrasting the availability of an object comparison for verbs with reflexive morphology in (17a) and reciprocal morphology in (17b):

(17) Chicheŵa (Mchombo, 1991:9)

- a. *Alenje a-ma-dzi-kond-a ku-posa asodzi.*
 2-hunters 2SM-HAB-REFL-LOVE-FV exceeding 2-fishermen
 “The hunters love themselves more than the fishermen.”
- b. *Alenje a-ma-kond-an-a ku-posa asodzi.*
 2-hunters 2SM-HAB-LOVE-REC-FV exceeding 2-fishermen
 “The hunters love each other more than the fishermen.”

Mchombo (1991:9) notes:

“Although these two sentences are only minimally different, they are interpreted non-uniformly. The second sentence, with the reciprocal, only means that the hunters love each other more than the fishermen love each other. Distinctly missing is the possible interpretation that the hunters love each other more than they love the fishermen, or more than the fishermen love them. These interpretations are not disallowed in the reflexive construction.”

Mchombo lists two interpretations of (17) above related to subject and object comparisons. The first, “that the hunters love each other more than the fishermen love each other”, is a subject comparison. The second, “(that) hunters love each other more than they love the fishermen” is the object comparison – and this interpretation is available to the reflexive construction, but not to the reciprocal construction. Mchombo argues that, because of this, the reciprocal morpheme decreases the valency of the reciprocated verb.

Keenan and Razafimamonjy (2001) apply the same tests to the Malagasy reciprocal construction and find that the data does not support such a clear cut analysis. Example (18) below sets up a comparison between two groups with a reciprocated verb. Like the previous Chicheŵa data, object comparisons in sentences with reciprocal constructions are disallowed:

(18) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:74)

M-if-an-aja *noho* *Raso*a *sy* *Ravelo* *Rabe* *sy* *Rakoto*.

PRES-REC-ACT-respect than [Raso

“Rabe and Rakoto respect each other more than Raso

Subject Comparison: Rabe and Rakoto respect each other more than Raso and Ravelo respect each other.

Object Comparison: *Rabe and Rakoto_i respect each other more than they_i respect Raso and Ravelo.

But as Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001:74) note, the situation in Malagasy is muddled by the fact that reflexives also disallow object comparisons. This would not be a problem if the Malagasy reflexives were incorporated into the verb, but in fact they are ordinary pronouns occurring in the usual object position:

(19) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:75)

M-an-aja *tena* *noho* *iano*a *Rabe*.

PRES-ACT-respect self than you Rabe

“Rabe respects himself more than you respect yourself.”

Object Comparison: *Rabe respects himself more than he respects you.

Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001:75) conclude “It would seem then in Malagasy an anaphorically bound object, regardless of how it is bound, precludes an object comparison reading.” In other words, the object comparison test (a key test for determining transitivity of verbs) is inconclusive when applied to the Malagasy reciprocal construction – and, furthermore, the universal applicability of Zec's (1985)

object comparison test as an indicator of transitivity is also challenged.

To determine the valency of the reciprocated verb in Malagasy we need to explore its behaviour in wider syntactic environments. The possession construction in (2) is an obvious candidate, as such constructions would usually be analysed as having an object (although see the discussion in section 3.6). However, first I will explore the interaction of the Malagasy reciprocal construction with functional control, as this environment is capable of revealing more information about a verb's valency at the level of f-structure.

3.5 THE VALENCY REDUCING ANALYSIS OF FUNCTIONAL CONTROL

I will argue that functional control constructions provide a means of determining the valency of reciprocal constructions in Malagasy. The argument I present here fundamentally depends upon the subject condition – a requirement that every clause has a subject. More specifically, in LFG this is a requirement that “[a]n f-structure with propositional content must include a subject (as one of its grammatical functions) and no f-structure may include more than one subject.” (Alsina, 1996:20).

In order to see how this test works, first consider the standard LFG analysis of functional control for the verb *believe* in English:

- (20) “David believed Chris to know the answer.” (reproduced from Dalrymple, 2001:314)

The subject condition requires that the lower verb *know* have a subject. In transformational theories, this is accomplished by positing that Chris is the subject of the lower verb in deep structure, but is subsequently raised to the matrix verb's object.

The LFG account for control constructions is fundamentally different (see Bresnan, 2001:270; Dalrymple, 2001:314; Falk, 2001:131). The subject condition is fulfilled by allowing a single NP to act as both the object of the main clause and as the subject of the lower clause. In (19) above, this means that *Chris* functions as both the object of the matrix verb *believe* and also as the subject of the lower verb *know*. In general, this is accomplished with a lexical rule (in bold) associated with a control verb that equates these two f-structures. In (21) below, this is illustrated for the verb *believe*:¹³¹

- (21) *Believe*, *v* (↑PRED) = 'believe <(↑SUBJ)(↑XCOMP)>(↑OBJ)'
 (↑XCOMP SUBJ) = (↑OBJ)

Using this theory of functional control, we can see how, in principle, these constructions can be used to determine the valency of a reciprocated verb. The shared grammatical function serves two purposes in the sentence, as the main verb's object as well as the lower verb's subject. Now, the valency reducing analyses of the reciprocal construction require that the verb lose a grammatical function at the level of f-structure. So, if a control verb were reciprocated and its object lost, then the lower verb would no longer have a subject and the resulting f-structure would be incomplete – and so the valency reducing analyses predict that reciprocated control verbs be ungrammatical.

3.5.1 Functional control in Malagasy

The key to this test is identifying functional control verbs in Malagasy – and this task is not trivial as many verbs may optionally use anaphoric control or optionally select full complements. However, Paul and Rabaovololana (1998) identify a class of verbs they call RTO verbs (*i.e.*, Raise to Object), in Malagasy and I will show below that these verbs should be analysed as functional control verbs in LFG.

Paul and Rabaovololana (1998) use several criteria to identify RTO verbs and, as they approach their analysis from a transformational point of view, I have reinterpreted their criteria in a form relevant to LFG:

131 Note that the PRED value of *believe* has the OBJ grammatical function outside the angled brackets. This indicates that the verb does not assign a thematic role to the shared grammatical function. However, as we will see, this is not the case of the lower verb.

1. The embedded clause appears in typical object position (as opposed to other complements and sentential adjuncts, which appear after the subject).
2. The embedded clause has atypical word order (SVO instead of VOS).
3. The complementizer *ho* is used instead of *fa*.

The standard word order in Malagasy is VOS. Keenan & Ochs (1979:133-137) note that full complements appear after the subject, and so in (22) we can distinguish between two types of construction:

(22) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:50-51)

RTO Construction

- a. *N-i-laza an-dRaso* *ho n-amboly vary Ravelo.*
 PST-ACT-say ACC-Raso Comp PST-cultivate rice Ravelo
 [V O [Comp V O] S]
 lit. “Ravelo said Raso to have cultivated rice.”
 “Ravelo said Raso has cultivated rice.”

Complement Construction

- b. *N-i-laza Ravelo fa n-amboly vary i Soa.*
 PST-ACT-say Ravelo Comp PST-cultivate rice Art Soa
 [V Subj] [Comp V Obj Subj]
 “Ravelo said that Soa cultivated rice.”

Both sentences in (22) have *Ravelo* as the subject of the main clause. However, the RTO construction in (22a) has the embedded clause (*ho namboly vary* – “to have cultivated rice”) between the subject and the verb. This is unlike (22b) where it occurs after the subject of the main clause. Note also the *ho* complementiser in (22a) which is characteristic of the RTO construction identified by Paul and Rabaovololana.

I argue that the verbs which Paul and Rabaovololana identify as hosting RTO constructions should be analysed in LFG as functional control verbs. This is evident from the special status of the shared NP (*Raso* in (22a) above). That this NP is linked to the main verb is demonstrated by it receiving accusative case. However, is there any evidence to support the analysis that this NP is also functioning as the subject of the

lower clause? First, consider (23) below. Subjects in Malagasy (and not objects) must conform to a general requirement that they be specific. For example, in (23) – if the subject NP is specific (*e.g.*, *i Bao* – “Bao”, *izy* – “he/she”, *ny zaza* – “the child” *etc.*), the sentence is grammatical, otherwise it is ungrammatical:

(23) Specific subject condition (Pearson, 2001:19)

*m-a-maky boky i Bao/izy/ ny zaza /ilay zaza/*olona/*zaza.*

PRES-ACT-read book Bao/3SG/the child/that child/person/child

“Bao/(s)he/the child/that child is reading a book.”

“*Some person/child is reading a book.”

Returning to the status of the accusative marked NP in RTO constructions, we see in (24) that, unlike regular objects, it too must conform to this specificity condition:

(24) Malagasy (Paul & Rabaovololona, 1998:55)

M-i-hevitra zanaka ho hendry aho.

PRES-ACT-think child COMP wise 1SG(NOM)

*“I think some child is wise.”

Reexamining (22a) then, we see that the construction that Paul and Rabaovololona identify as RTO has all the hallmarks of functional control – the accusative marked NP in (22a) has been assigned accusative case from the main verb *nilaza* – “say”, but it also must conform to the specific subject requirement from the lower verb *namboly* – “cultivate”. Thus its associated (simplified) f-structure is presented in (25) below:

(25) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:50-51)

N-i-laza an-dRaso ho n-amboly vary Ravelo.

PST-ACT-say ACC-Raso COMP PST-cultivate rice Ravelo

“Ravelo said Raso has cultivated rice.”

Given that such RTO verbs can be considered as functional control verbs, we can use them as a probe to determine the valency of the reciprocated verbs in f-structure. In particular, if the same valency reducing analyses described above can be applied to Malagasy, we would predict that these functional control verbs cannot also engage in a reciprocal construction. However, as is revealed in section 3.5.2, this is not the case.

3.5.2 Functional control and reciprocal constructions in Malagasy

As (26b) below demonstrates – functional control verbs can be reciprocated. Their structure is exactly the same as for the basic verbs in (1), (4) and (5) above – the main verb is marked with a reciprocal morpheme, the participants in the event appear in the subject NP, along with the loss of a non-subject NP:

(26) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:50-51)

- a. *N-i-laza an-dRaso ho n-amboly vary Ravelo.*
 PST-ACT-say ACC-Raso Comp PST-cultivate rice Ravelo
 [V O Comp V O S]
 “Ravelo said Raso has cultivated rice.”

- b. *N-ifamp-i-laza ho n-amboly vary Raso sy Ravelo.*
 PST-REC-ACT-say Comp PST-cultivate rice Raso and Ravelo
 [V [Comp V O] S]
 lit. “Raso and Ravelo said each other to have cultivated rice.”
 “Raso and Ravelo said of each other that s/he cultivated rice.”
 *“Raso and Ravelo said ‘we cultivated rice.’”

Note that the starred gloss above is called the “shared reciprocal reading” of (26b). This reading is one that Keenan & Razafimamonjy note is ruled out in Malagasy and I will discuss its implications below.

see this, consider (30) below where the subject of the lower clause has been co-referenced with the matrix subject:

- (30) *N-ifamp-i-laza [e_i] ho namboly vary Rasoa sy Ravelo_i.*
 PST-REC-ACT-say COMP PST-cultivate rice Rasoa and Ravelo
 “Rasoa and Ravelo said each other to have cultivated rice.”

Given the co-referentiality of the subject of the lower clause with the subject of the higher clause, the likely (and arguably only) interpretation of (30) would be: “[Rasoa and Ravelo]_i said of each other that [Rasoa and Ravelo]_i cultivated rice” – *i.e.*:

- (31) *Rasoa said that Rasoa and Ravelo (i.e., we, or, they two) have cultivated rice.*
Ravelo said that Rasoa and Ravelo have cultivated rice.

This shared reciprocal reading is one that Keenan & Razafimamonjy test for (26b) and find to be unavailable – the correct reading being:¹³²

- (32) *Rasoa said that Ravelo has cultivated rice.*
Ravelo said that Rasoa has cultivated rice.

The unavailability of the shared reciprocal reading also rules out another possible mechanism for saving this analysis. Instead of linking the subject of the lower clause with the matrix subject, we could posit the existence of an optional PRO as the subject of the lower clause (whose presence is allowed by some more general rule not described here):

- (32) *Nifampilaza v* (↑PRED) = “say_{rec}<(↑SUBJ)(↑XCOMP)>”
 (↑TENSE) = PAST
 (↑VOICE) = ACTIVE

132 See Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001:50-51) for further examples.

[PRED	‘say _{rec} <SUBJ,XCOMP>’]
	SUBJ	[PRED ‘Rasoa and Ravelo’]	
	XCOMP	[PRED ‘cultivate<SUBJ,OBJ>’]	
	SUBJ	[PRED ‘PRO’]	
	OBJ	[PRED ‘rice’]	

A PRO acting as the subject of the lower clause in (32) creates a complete and coherent f-structure – however, semantically, this analysis has the same problem as that described above: as the antecedent of PRO is the matrix clause subject, we would again predict the shared reciprocal reading to be available.

The valency reducing analysis of reciprocal constructions faces considerable challenges when trying to understand the grammaticality of sentences like (26b). In order to produce an f-structure that is complete and coherent, either the co-reference between the subject of the lower clause and the matrix clause object must change – or a PRO must be posited as residing in the lower clause subject. Both of these additions are somewhat *ad hoc* in nature and result in a sentence with a possible interpretation that is unavailable to Malagasy speakers. Before presenting an alternative analysis, I will first examine the reciprocal construction and possession.

3.6 THE VALENCY REDUCING ANALYSIS OF POSSESSION

Possession constructions can allow us to determine the valency of a reciprocated verb – and I will argue below that in the case of Malagasy, they unequivocally rule out any valency reducing analysis. To understand how this test works, first consider English – a language whose reciprocal construction does not affect the valency of the verb.¹³³ In (34) below, the verb *visited* still has a subject and object when in a reciprocal construction:

- (34) a. *Jane visited Vilhjálmur.*
 b. *Jane and Vilhjálmur visited each other.*

English (in common with many other languages – see Nedjalkov, 2007) allows object possession to occur concurrently with the reciprocal construction:

133 This view is uncontroversial, but for further discussion on the valency of the English reciprocal construction – see Evans, Gaby & Nordlinger (2007).

- (35) a. *Jane visited Vilhjálmur's parents.*
b. *Jane and Vilhjálmur visited each other's parents.*

The semantics of (35b) require that Jane visit Vilhjálmur's parents, and he visit hers. This interpretation is available by virtue of the fact that the reciprocal pronoun is able to enter into a possessor relation with another NP – and that both of these NPs function as a unit as the object of the main verb. Now consider what happens in (36) when the possessor relation occurs not in the object, but in the subject:

- (36) *Jane and Vilhjálmur's parents visited each other.*

Sentence (36) has a different meaning from that of (35b). Instead of Jane and Vilhjálmur doing the visiting, now their parents are. The object possession reciprocal construction in (35b) entails a particular type of symmetry that is not available to a subject possession construction. These reciprocated object possessor constructions are particularly interesting because they, and the particular semantics they entail, require that the verb maintain its object grammatical function when reciprocated.

If we were to assume a valency reducing analysis of the Malagasy reciprocal construction, we would not expect to be able to express the semantics associated with the object possession reciprocal construction in (35b) above. In section 3.6.1 below I first outline how possession is expressed in Malagasy before investigating whether these constructions may co-occur with reciprocated verbs.

3.6.1 Possession in Malagasy

Possession in Malagasy is formed by inserting the possessor to the right of the possessee:

- (37) Malagasy (Paul 1996:77)
orona + olona → *oron'olona*
nose person nose of a person / a person's nose

Note that the affected nouns undergo some fairly complex phonological changes (see Paul, 1996 for details) and this is particularly the case for proper names. For example,

the *Ra-* that occurs at the beginning of many Malagasy names is a marker of respect and in possessive constructions, it triggers the deletion of the final vowel and optional subsequent deletion of the final consonant from the noun possessed:

- (38) Malagasy (Paul, 1996:81)¹³⁴
tongotra + *Rakoto* → *tongotry Rakoto* / *tongo-dRakoto*
 foot Rokoto “the foot of Rakoto / Rakoto’s foot”

Within LFG, possession constructions are analysed at the level of f-structure using the grammatical function POSS. Nouns are understood to have available to them an optional lexical rule that creates an alternative lexical entry in which the noun now requires a POSS grammatical function (which acts as a possessor). For example, *vady* – “spouse” below has a lexical alternate, *vadin*, where it is interpreted as being in possessor relation as the possessee:¹³⁵

- (39) *vady*, *N* ↔ *vadin*, *N*
 (↑PRED) = 'spouse' (↑PRED) = 'spouse_of(↑POSS)'

An addition to the phrase structure rule associated with the NP is assumed which relates the possessor and possessed together in f-structure. The analysis below is somewhat simplified (it ignores the DP hypothesis and intermediate levels of structure for example) but it captures all the features of possession that are relevant to our investigation. Sentence (40) shows a simple transitive verb, *maka* – “take/ravish”, occurring with a NP functioning as the object. Note that root of the verb *maka*, (*-aka*) starts with *a*, and so is assumed by default classification to already be in active voice (recall that *-a-* is the morpheme to indicate active voice):

- (40) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:51)
 a. *M-aka* *ny vady* *Rakoto*.
 PRES-ACT.take the spouse Rakoto
 “Rakoto ravishes the spouse.”

134 The *-d* in *dRakoto* is the result of this phonological operation and is not a case marker.

135 Note the presence of the final *-n* in *vadin*. Some authors (e.g., Ntelitheos, 2010) treat *-n* as a linking morpheme.

- b. *M-aka ny vadin-dRabe Rakoto.*
 PRES-ACT.take the spouse.of-Rabe Rakoto
 “Rakoto ravishes the spouse of Rabe.”

The lexical entries, c- and f-structure for sentence (40b) are below:

<i>M-aka</i>	<i>v</i>	(↑PRED) = 'ravish<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)>' (↑TENSE) = PRES (↑VOICE) = ACTIVE
<i>Rabe</i>	<i>n</i>	(↑PRED) = 'Rabe'
<i>Rakoto</i>	<i>n</i>	(↑PRED) = 'Rakoto'
<i>Vadin</i>	<i>n</i>	(↑PRED) = 'spouse_of(↑POSS)'

[PRED	'ravish<SUBJ,OBJ>']			
[SUBJ	[PRED	'Rakoto']]	
[OBJ	[PRED	'spouse_of<POSS>']]
[TENSE	PRES]]		
[VOICE	ACTIVE]]		

3.6.2 Reciprocated possession constructions

The valency reducing analyses of reciprocal constructions, which have been so fruitful in their application to other languages, predict that reciprocal verbs in Malagasy should not be able to express symmetric situations that require the presence of an object.

However, as the sentences below demonstrate, such sentences are grammatical and appear to involve some type of object possession:

(41) Transitive verb (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:51)

a. *M-aka ny vadin-dRabe Rakoto.*
PRES-take the spouse.of-Rabe Rakoto
“Rakoto ravishes the spouse of Rabe.”

b. *M-ifamp-aka vady Rabe sy Rakoto.*
PRES-REC-take spouse Rabe and Rakoto
“Rabe and Rakoto ravish each other’s spouse.”

(42) Ditransitive verb (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:52)

a. *M-an-ome vola ny zanan-dRavelo Raso.*
PRES-ACT-give money the child.of-Ravelo Raso
“Raso gives money to the children of Ravelo.”

b. *M-if-an-ome vola zananaka Raso sy Ravelo.*
PRES-REC-ACT-give money child Raso and Ravelo
“Raso and Ravelo give money to each other's children.”

(43) Semi-transitive verb (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:52)

a. *M-an-dainga amin'ny vadin-dRakoto Rabe.*
PRES-ACT-lie to'the spouse.of-Rakoto Rabe
“Rabe lies to Rakoto’s spouse.”

b. *M-if-an-dainga amin-bady Rakoto sy Rabe.*
PRES-REC-ACT-lie to-spouse Rakoto and Rabe
“Rakoto and Rabe lie to each other’s spouses.”

(44) Functional control verb (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:52-53)¹³⁶

- a. *M-i-laza ny ray aman-drenin'i Rabe ho mamboly vary*
 PRES-ACT-say the parents'.ART Rabe COMP cultivate rice

i Rakoto.

ART Rakoto

lit. "Rakoto says the father and mother of Rabe to be cultivating rice."

"Rakoto says Rabe's parents are cultivating rice."

- b. *M-ifamp-i-laza ray aman-dreny ho mamboly vary*
 PRES-REC-ACT-say the parents COMP cultivate rice

i Rabe sy Rakoto.

ART Rabe and Rakoto

"Rabe and Rakoto say each other's parents are cultivating rice."

Note that the semantics associated with the reciprocated possession constructions above is the same as reciprocal object possessions identified in English in (35b). For example, the semantics of (42b) require that Rasoa gives money to Ravelo's children, and Ravelo gives money to Rasoa's children (and not that the children of Rasoa and Ravelo are giving money to each other). Syntactically, though, these sentences are interesting. Consider the differences between (41a) and (41b). The basic sentence has an object that holds a possessor relation between Rakoto (the possessor) and his spouse (the possessee). The reciprocated form of the sentence is missing the possessor, but retains the possessee. In the context of these possessor reciprocal constructions I will refer to this remaining possessee as the remnant. This possessee's or remnant's relationship to the verb is critical to our understanding of how the reciprocal construction is formed. In section 3.7.3 I discuss this relationship in detail by attempting to analyse the remnant within a valency reducing analysis of the reciprocated verb.

136 For clarity I have changed the names of the participants in these examples.

3.6.3 The valency reducing reciprocal construction and possession

The valency reducing analysis of the reciprocal construction requires that the reciprocated verb have one less grammatical function than its transitive counterpart at the level of f-structure (through some means – see sections 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 above). Thus in (41) above, we see the following change in the verb's lexical entry when it is reciprocated:

- (45) a. *M-aka* v (↑PRED) = 'ravish<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)>'
 (↑TENSE) = PRES
 (↑VOICE) = ACTIVE
- b. *M-ifamp-aka* v (↑PRED) = 'ravish_{rec}<(↑SUBJ)>'
 (↑TENSE) = PRES
 (↑VOICE) = ACTIVE

SUBJ	[PRED 'Rasoa and Rakoto']
???	[PRED 'Spouse']
PRED	'ravish _{rec} <SUBJ>'
VOICE	ACTIVE
TENSE	PST

Note that the resulting f-structure for (41b) now has a predicate (“spouse”) which is not associated with a grammatical function. The question I address in this section is given a valency reducing analysis of reciprocated verbs, how should this remnant be analysed? In other words because the construction is grammatical, if we are to pursue a valency reducing analysis of the reciprocal construction, this remnant must find its place within the syntactic description of Malagasy. Clearly it cannot be part of an object grammatical function, so in the following discussion I will examine, and reject, several ways the remnant might be property integrated into a grammatical sentence. There are two candidates which are more likely than the others and these are discussed before I examine the less likely options (see remarks in section 3.6.3.3). The first possibility involves analysing the remnant as belonging to the subject NP, and the second requires treating the remnant as being part of an external possession construction.

3.6.3.1 THE REMNANT AS PART OF A POSSESSOR RELATION WITH THE SUBJECT NP

Interpreting the remnant as being part of the subject NP is problematic, as we would expect that there be the phonological change that is characteristic of other possessor constructions. For example in (46a) below we see an example of a subject NP

containing a possessor construction with a reciprocated verb – it has the phonological change discussed in (38), (39). It also entails the situation we would expect of a reciprocal construction, with a possessor relation in the subject grammatical function, where only the head of the NP engages in the relation. In contrast, (46b) has the remnant phonologically unbound to the subject NP and the sentence carries a different interpretation:

(46) Malagasy (Keenan & Ralalaoherivony, 1998:84)

- a. *N-if-an-lainga ny vadin-dRavelo sy Rasoa.*
 PAST-REC-ACT-lie the spouse-of-Ravelo and Rasoa
 “The spouses of Ravelo and Rasoa lie to each other.”

Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:51)

- b. *M-ifamp-aka vady Rabe sy Rakoto.*
 PRES-REC-take spouse Rabe and Rakoto
 “Rabe and Rakoto ravish each other’s spouses.”
 *“Rabe and Rakoto’s spouses ravish each other.”

Although the remnant could be analysed as being part of the subject NP in other ways (e.g., by being in apposition), only by being in a possessor relation could we hope that the resultant semantics of the construction would be harmonious with the syntactic form – and even if this were the case, by being in the subject NP, the resulting meaning of the sentence is different from what is expected. As such, I conclude that the remnant is not part of the subject NP.

3.6.3.2 THE REMNANT AS BEING PART OF AN EXTERNAL POSSESSION CONSTRUCTION

An external possession construction (EPC) is one where a possessee may be incorporated into the verb. If this analysis could be applied to the remnant, it would provide a convincing explanation for its existence – both from a syntactic perspective, but also semantically as the reciprocated verb in (45b) would actually mean something like “ravish_each_other's_spouse”. The predicate would be formed by first linking *spouse* with the base verb *ravish* – to form a new bivalent predicate, and subsequently this new predicate is reciprocated:

(47) $x \text{ ravish } y \rightarrow x \text{ ravish-spouse } y \rightarrow x \text{ ravish-spouse}_{rec} y$
 Base verb External possession Reciprocal construction

Such an analysis may be possible because Malagasy is a language in which some verbs may host external possession. In this section I will discuss external possession and then show that despite looking like providing a promising account of the remnant, this analysis cannot be sustained.

Keenan and Ralalaoherivony (1998) list several properties that characterise external possession. Among them are:

- The loss of the determiner (see *ny* below).
- The newly formed verb+noun acts as a prosodic word – question particles and adverbs cannot be inserted between the verb and noun (for examples, see Keenan and Ralalaoherivony, 1998:76)
- A semantic shift where the subject in a external possession construction becomes more involved in the situation described.

For example, in (48) below, Keenan and Ralalaoherivony (1998:65) point out that, in the regular possession construction, Rabe may not be aware of the death of his spouse – however, it is entailed that Rabe is aware of his spouse's death in the EPC construction:

(48) Possession vs. External Possession in Malagasy
 (Keenan and Ralalaoherivony, 1998:65)

<p><i>Maty ny vadin-dRabe</i> [died [the spouse-of-Rabe]] “Rabe’s spouse died/is dead.”</p> <hr style="width: 80%; margin: 0 auto;"/> <p style="text-align: center;">Regular Possession</p>	<p>↔</p>	<p><i>Maty vady Rabe</i> [[died spouse] Rabe] “Rabe was widowed.” or “Rabe underwent spouse death.”</p> <hr style="width: 80%; margin: 0 auto;"/> <p style="text-align: center;">EPC</p>
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Keenan & Ralalaoherivony note that the likelihood of a verb hosting external possession decreases with the complexity of the clause. Ditransitive, semi-transitive and control verbs are unable to host external possession at all. Although intransitive verbs

undergo external possession productively, transitive verbs only do so in a limited fashion – frequently with idiomatic interpretations. They add:

“In almost all the excluded cases [of external possession] the Pn [predicate] is syntactically and semantically “complex”, where containing two or more content words counts as complex, as does *causative and reciprocal morphology*.”

Keenan & Ralalaoherivony (1998:82) – My emphasis.

However, under a valency decreasing analysis of reciprocation, a transitive verb becomes intransitive when reciprocated (and ditransitive becomes transitive *etc.*). As such I will rule out the possibility of the remnant being analysed as being in an external possession construction below.

When we compare the possessor raising construction above with a reciprocated possession construction, they do look very similar. For example, the remnant of (49b), *vady* – “spouse”, appears as if it may be in the same relation to the verb as *vady* is in (49b) – (examples repeated from above):

(49) Reciprocated possession construction

- a. *M-ifamp-aka vady Rabe sy Rakoto.*
PRES-REC-take spouse Rabe and Rakoto
“Rabe and Rakoto ravish each other’s spouse.”
- b. *Maty vady Rabe.*
dead spouse Rabe
“Rabe was widowed.”

However, the remnant cannot be engaging in an external possession construction because words can be inserted between the verb and remnant (meaning that the verb + remnant cannot be acting as a prosodic word). For example, in (50) we see the preposition *amin* – “to” has been inserted between the verb and remnant (underlined):

(50) Malagasy (from (43b) above)

M-if-an-dainga amin-bady Rakoto sy Rabe

PRES-REC-ACT-lie to-spouse Rakoto and Rabe

“Rakoto and Rabe lie to each other’s spouse.”

Likewise in (51) an entire NP (*vola* – “money”, functioning as OBJ₀) is between the verb and the remnant (*zananaka* – “child”):

(51) Malagasy (from (42b) above)

M-if-an-ome vola zananaka Rasoa sy Ravelo.

PRES-REC-ACT-give money child Rasoa and Ravelo

“Rasoa and Ravelo give money to each other's children.”

The presence of an NP between the reciprocated verb and remnant in (51) tells us that *zananaka* – “child” is not phonologically bound to the verb, and so the remnant cannot be understood to be in an external possession construction. Furthermore, Keenan & Ralalaoherivony (1998:84) note that RTS verbs do not participate in external possession. For example, they illustrate this with (52b) below where the possessee (*janka* – “child”) is unable to be attached to the verb:

(52) Regular control construction (Keenan & Ralalaoherivony, 1998:82)

a. *M-i-hevitra ny zana-Rakoto ho mpangalatra Rabe.*

PRES-ACT-think the child-of-Rakoto COMP thief Rabe

“Rabe thinks Rakoto's child is a thief.”

Ungrammatical external possession construction

b. **M-i-hevi-janka an-dRakoto ho mpangalatra Rabe.*

PRES-ACT-think-child ACC-Rakoto COMP thief Rabe

As we saw, this same class of verbs (analysed as functional control verbs in section 3.5 above) may be reciprocated – and in this case they also allow a possessee remnant:

(53) Functional control verb (from (44b) above – remnant underlined)

M-ifamp-i-laza ray aman-dreny ho mamboly vary
 PRES-REC-ACT-say the parents COMP cultivate rice

i Rabe sy Rakoto.

ART Rabe and Rakoto

“Rabe and Rakoto say each other's parents are cultivating rice.”

Furthermore, the remnant here is also accompanied by a determiner – another feature that is incompatible with the external possession construction. Based on this evidence, it is clear that the remnant cannot be part of an external possession construction.

3.6.2.3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Above I explored two possible accounts of the remnant when viewed from the perspective of a valency reducing analysis of reciprocal constructions. Namely, that the remnant is part of an external possession construction or that the remnant is part of the subject NP. I investigated these possibilities because they were the ones that respected the general semantic requirement that the core participants in the event be related to arguments selected by the predicate. This requirement rules out unlikely analyses such as treating the remnant as an adjunct for example. It also brings into focus another difficulty that the valency reducing analysis of reciprocation has with these possession constructions – one to do with the mapping between argument structure and f-structure. Recall that I used “valency reducing analysis” as shorthand to refer to two more specific analyses of reciprocal constructions: one which maps both arguments to the subject grammatical function (argument unification – see section 3.3.2 above) and another that works analogously to the passive, where one of the arguments is suppressed (the argument suppression analysis – see section 3.3.1). Both of these analyses result in the reciprocated predicate losing a grammatical function in f-structure:

In the figure above, in both cases the proto-patient argument is utilised – it is either mapped to subject, or it is suppressed entirely. However, consider (54) below:

- (55) Malagasy (repeated from (41a) above)
Maka ny vadin-dRabe Rakoto.
PRES-take the spouse.of-Rabe Rakoto
“Rakoto ravishes the spouse of Rabe.”

Here the possessee (*vadin* – “spouse”) is the patient of the verb *maka* – “take” or “ravish”, and using standard notions of LMT its presence in (55) can be understood straightforwardly. However, in terms of thematic roles, the remnant in (56) is behaving similarly as it is also the patient of the verb:

- (56) Malagasy (repeated from (41b) above)
M-ifamp-aka vady Rabe sy Rakoto.
PRES-REC-take spouse Rabe and Rakoto
“Rabe and Rakoto ravish each other’s spouse.”

The difficulty then for a valency reducing analysis of reciprocation is that the patient argument in a-structure is either suppressed or mapped to the subject grammatical function – leaving no natural account of the remnant. At the outset of this section, I claimed that the loss of grammatical function in a reciprocated predicate should disallow the existence of object possession constructions like those in English (see (35b)). However, the existence of reciprocated possession constructions confounds this prediction. In order to understand these constructions, the existence of the remnant needs to be explained and I found no syntactic nor semantic explanation of its presence was forthcoming when its analysis was situated in a valency reducing account of reciprocation. And so in section 3.7 I reexamine these constructions from the valency preserving perspective of reciprocal constructions.

3.7 THE VALENCY PRESERVING ANALYSIS

In this section I present a valency preserving analysis of the Malagasy reciprocal construction and demonstrate that it correctly predicts the grammaticality of the basic reciprocal constructions above (*e.g.*, (1), (4) and (6)). Recall that I am using valency to indicate the number of grammatical functions selected by the predicate at the level of f-structure. So under this valency preserving analysis the a- and f-structures of the verb remain unchanged when it is reciprocated – instead the reciprocal morpheme indicates the presence of a reciprocal pronoun, PRO_{rec}, in some non-subject grammatical function specified by the verb. Like PRO in the pro-drop languages, PRO_{rec} is not associated with any phonological material.¹³⁷ As a first approximation, this is accomplished by associating a new lexical rule with the reciprocal morpheme *-if-*:

$$(57) \quad -if- \quad (\uparrow [GF^* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'$$

This definition creates a reciprocal pronoun at the end of some arbitrary long chain of grammatical functions. Here GF* represents this chain (which can be of zero length) and it starts from the f-structure containing the verb. There is an additional requirement that the reciprocal pronoun not be in the matrix subject (see discussion after example (58) below). In a general sense, this chain of grammatical functions is mostly unconstrained, meaning that it may consist of any grammatical function(s) whatsoever.¹³⁸ However, in any particular instance of a grammatical sentence, the f-structure principles of completeness and coherence (Bresnan, 2001:63), and predicate uniqueness (Dalrymple, 2001:104) will require the grammatical function at the end of the chain to be one that is both designated by a PRED, but also one that does not already contain a PRED. To illustrate how this definition works, consider (58) below where I have provided the lexical entries and instantiated c- and f- structures for sentence (1b). At this point, the information associated with the lexical entry *-if-* has not been incorporated – and so the f-structure is incomplete:

137 See Bresnan (2001:144) for details on the analysis of pro-drop or pronominal incorporation in LFG.

138 Note that “GF* - SUBJ” in (57) represents all strings of grammatical functions except for the singleton string SUBJ. This notation was described to me by Dalrymple (personal communication, May 24, 2012). See section 3.7.1 for further discussion of this notation, its implications and limitations.

- (58) *N-if-an-daka Rabe sy Rakoto.*
 PST-REC-ACT-kick Rabe and Rakoto
 “Rabe and Rakoto kicked each other.”

n-if-an-daka, v, (↑ PRED) = 'kick<(↑ SUBJ)(↑ OBJ)>'
 (↑ TENSE) = PAST
 (↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE
 (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'

At this point, the OBJ grammatical function appears in the f-structure because it has been created by the predicate “kick”; however, it has not been associated with an f-structure. Now consider the lexical entry associated with *-if-* : (f₁ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'. GF is shorthand for any argument grammatical function (*e.g.*, SUBJ, OBJ, OBJ_θ, OBL, COMP, XCOMP) – and the Kleene star allows any combination of these grammatical functions to appear any number of times (including not at all).¹³⁹ For example, the following lexical entries are all generated by the definition of the reciprocal morpheme in (58) above:

- (59) *-if-* (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'
- a. (↑ PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'
 - b. (↑ OBL OBJ PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'
 - c. (↑ OBJ PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'
- etc...*

¹³⁹ The allowable grammatical functions are further refined in section 3.7.1.

The notation [GF* - SUBJ] describes a requirement that the grammatical function denoted by GF not be (nor be embedded within) the matrix subject. This requirement reflects the binding condition that reciprocal constructions in Malagasy require a matrix subject as an antecedent.¹⁴⁰

We can now turn to how the definition of *-if-* above correctly predicts the grammaticality of (1b). As we saw in (59), there are infinitely many possible lexical entries that satisfy the lexical entry in (57). If we consider just those given in (59) below, we can see how the principles of completeness, coherence and uniqueness will result in only one, correct, value for *-if-* that predicts a grammatically correct sentence. In (60) below, each of the lexical entries above has been incorporated into the f-structure of (58):

(60) *-if-* (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'

where GF = (a) nothing, (b) OBL OBJ, (c) OBJ.

a. f_1 PRED = 'PRO_{rec}'

$$f_1 \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{SUBJ} \quad [\text{PRED} \text{ 'Rabe and Rakoto'}] \\ \text{PRED} \quad \text{'PRO}_{\text{rec}} \\ \text{PRED} \quad \text{'kick} \langle (f_1 \text{SUBJ})(f_1 \text{OBJ}) \rangle \\ \text{VOICE} \quad \text{ACTIVE} \\ \text{TENSE} \quad \text{PST} \end{array} \right]$$

This f-structure is ungrammatical, because it places a PRED in the clausal f-structure that cannot unify with the PRED from the verb.

b. f_1 OBJ OBL PRED = 'PRO_{rec}'

$$f_1 \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{SUBJ} \quad [\text{PRED} \text{ 'Rabe and Rakoto'}] \\ \text{OBJ} \quad [\text{OBL} \quad [\text{PRED} \text{ 'PRO}_{\text{rec}}]] \\ \text{PRED} \quad \text{'kick} \langle (f_1 \text{SUBJ})(f_1 \text{OBJ}) \rangle \\ \text{VOICE} \quad \text{ACTIVE} \\ \text{TENSE} \quad \text{PST} \end{array} \right]$$

This f-structure is incoherent, because the OBL grammatical function is not selected by a PRED. As such, GF may not equal OBJ OBL.

140 Although see discussion in section 3.8.

(62) Semi-transitive Verb (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:49)

- a. *M-if-an-dainga* *i* *Be sy Ranaivo*
 PRES-REC-ACT-lie ART Be and Ranaivo
 “Be and Ranaivo lie to each other.”

i Be sy Ranaivo, NP “Be and Ranaivo”
Mifandainga V (↑ PRED) = 'lie<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBL_θ OBJ)>'
 (↑ TENSE) = PRES
 (↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE
 (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'

Resolving GF as OBL_θ OBJ gives a complete and coherent f-structure for (20a):

- b. *M-if-an-dainga* *amin'i* *Be sy Ranaivo*
 PRES-REC-ACT-lie to'ART Be and Ranaivo
 “Be and Ranaivo lie to each other.”

i Be sy Ranaivo, NP “Be and Ranaivo”
amin P (↑PCASE) = OBL_θ
Mifandainja V (↑ PRED) = 'lie<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBL_θ OBJ)>'
 (↑ TENSE) = PRES
 (↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE
 (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'

Once again, only GF = OBL_θ OBJ gives a complete and coherent f-structure:

Mifandainja
 (↑ TENSE) = PRES
 (↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE
 (↑ PRED) = 'lie<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBL_θ OBJ)>'
 (↑ OBL_θ OBJ PRED) = PRO_{rec}

SUBJ	[PRED 'Be and Ranaivo']
OBL _θ	[PCASE OBL _θ OBJ [PRED 'PRO _{rec} ']]
PRED	'lie<SUBJ,OBL _θ OBJ>'
VOICE	ACTIVE
TENSE	PST

(63) Reciprocated Ditransitive Verb (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:49)

M-if-an-ome vola Rabe sy Rakoto.

PRES-REC-ACT-give money Rabe and Rakoto

“Rabe and Rakoto give money to each other.”

Rabe sy Ranaivo NP “Rabe and Rakoto”
vola NP (↑ PRED) = 'money'
Mifanome V (↑ PRED) = 'give<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)(↑OBJ_θ)>'
 (↑ TENSE) = PRES
 (↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE
 (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'

Resolving GF as OBJ gives a complete and coherent f-structure for (63):

Above I demonstrated how the valency preserving analysis of the Malagasy reciprocal construction correctly predicts the grammaticality of verbs selecting various grammatical functions. This analysis also predicts that a reciprocal morpheme cannot be used in a regular non-reciprocal construction. In (64) below, the ungrammaticality of (14) is correctly predicted:

(64) Malagasy (elicited)

**N-if-an-daka an-dRabe Raso a sy Rakoto.*

PST-REC-ACT-kick ACC-Rabe Raso a and Rakoto

“Raso a and Rakoto kicked each other Rabe”

There is no possible value for GF in *nifandaka* above that can result in a grammatical f-structure. If GF is nothing (or the same as an existing grammatical function in the f-structure), then the f-structure fails because it cannot unify two PREDs for the clause (e.g., (60a) above). If GF is anything else, the f-structure is incoherent because there is a grammatical function(s) specified by GF which is not selected by a PRED (e.g., (60b)).

3.7.1 The domain of GF

The definition of the reciprocal morpheme above allows the reciprocal pronoun to be located in any non-subject grammatical function inside the co-argument domain defined by the matrix predicate. That is to say, the reciprocal pronoun may be located in any non-subject grammatical function defined by the PRED. For example, *give* below requires a SUBJ, OBJ and OBJ_θ – this means the reciprocal pronoun could be in either the OBJ or OBJ_θ

(65)

SUBJ	[PRED	‘Be and Ranaivo’]
OBJ _θ	[]
OBJ	[]
PRED		‘give<SUBJ,OBJ,OBJ _θ >’	
VOICE		ACTIVE	
TENSE		PST	

However, this definition for the location of the reciprocal pronoun is too broad. In this section the domain of the reciprocal pronoun is examined in more detail. In particular, we need to consider the binding domain of the reciprocal pronoun. Dalrymple (2001) identifies four binding patterns with cross linguistic relevance to anaphoric binding:

- (66) Different Binding Domains (Dalrymple, 2001:283 – see also Dalrymple, 1993)
- a. Coargument Domain
 - “minimal domain defined by a PRED and the grammatical functions it governs”
 - b. Minimal Complete Nucleus
 - “minimal domain with a SUBJ function”

- c. Minimal Finite Domain
“minimal domain with a TENSE feature”
- d. Root Domain
“f-structure of entire utterance”

The Malagasy reciprocal construction is interesting because different speakers use different binding domains. For example, consider (67) below:

(67) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:54)

- a. *M-ino Rabe fa mpangalatra Rakoto.*
PRES-believe Rabe [COMP thief Rakoto]
“Rabe believes that Rakoto is a thief.”
- b. *?M-ifamp-ino Rabe sy Rakoto fa mpangalatra.*
PRES-REC-believe Rabe and Rakoto [COMP thief]
?“Rabe and Rakoto each believe the other to be a thief.”

The questionable grammaticality of (67b) is important – Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001:54) note that some speakers find constructions like this to be acceptable, while others do not.¹⁴¹ For those speakers that do, the binding domain of the reciprocal pronoun must be the co-argument domain – because the reciprocal pronoun is able to find its antecedent in any grammatical function required by the verb carrying the reciprocal morpheme. However, for speakers who consider (67b) ungrammatical, the reciprocal pronoun must find its antecedent within the domain that contains a subject grammatical function (in other words, in (67b) above, the reciprocal pronoun must find its antecedent within the lower clause – which it cannot) Thus, the definition of GF

141 For readers familiar with binding theory, (67b) violates principle A – that a reciprocal pronoun needs to be bound within its minimally complete nucleus (*i.e.*, roughly speaking, its antecedent needs to be within the same clause). Violations of principle A occur not just in Malagasy, but are also widespread in English. For example: “the frustrating fact remains that both policymakers and the markets believe that each other are going to magically solve the Euro-crisis.” (<http://articles.businessinsider.com>, “The Financial World’s Expectations Are Threatening The European Union”). “They got into fights over e-mail because they both thought that each other was cheating while neither of them was.” (From comments as part of <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dVq8jTktXHM>). “When do Romeo and Juliet think that each other are dead?” (http://wiki.answers.com/Q/When_do_Romeo_and_Juliet_think_that_each_other_are_dead). See discussion on this subject in Uchiumi (2006).

needs to change to reflect whether speakers find sentences such as (64b) grammatical:

- (68) a. Antecedent within co-argument domain
 $GF \equiv \{SUBJ \mid COMP \mid OBJ \mid OBJ_0 \mid OBL \mid XCOMP \mid POSS\}$
- b. Antecedent within minimally complete nucleus
 $GF \equiv \{SUBJ \mid OBJ \mid OBL \mid OBJ_0 \mid XCOMP \mid POSS\}$

Using the definitions above (in conjunction with the restriction in (57) that disallows the presence of a reciprocal pronoun in the matrix subject f-structure) the binding domain of the reciprocal pronoun is specified not by defining where its antecedent may occur in structure, but rather by defining in which locations the reciprocal pronoun may reside. As pointed out by Dalrymple (personal communication, May 24, 2012), defining the location of the reciprocal pronoun using $(\uparrow [GF^* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'$ has the consequence of allowing the reciprocal pronoun to occur in arbitrarily long paths through f-structure. This is not problematic *per se* as the principles of completeness, coherence and predicate uniqueness require that these f-structures must already have been created through other means. However, should further investigation into the Malagasy reciprocal pronoun reveal that its distribution is more restricted (say to just one of the domains identified by Dalrymple, 1993) we can define the reciprocal pronoun using an off-path constraint instead.¹⁴²

The valency preserving analysis of reciprocal constructions I that have described above exploits the parallel structures in LFG, allowing a grammatical function to be present in f-structure that is not associated with a NP in c-structure. This creates a mismatch in the valency of the verb such that there is a single argument NP at c-structure but two core grammatical functions at f-structure. In the following sections I re-examine reciprocal constructions in the environments of functional control and possession, to demonstrate how this mismatch can account for the behaviour of the Malagasy reciprocal construction.

142 For example, if the distribution of the reciprocal pronoun were limited to the minimal complete nucleus, its definition would be given by: $-if- : (\uparrow \underset{\neg(-SUBJ)}{GF^*} PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'$. See Dalrymple (2001:284) for further details.

3.7.2 Reciprocated control constructions

Under the valency reducing analysis of reciprocation, functional control verbs lose an object when they are reciprocated. In section 3.5 I described how this would lead us to either assume that either functional control verbs cannot be reciprocated, or, if they could be, they would have a very specific interpretation – one that is disallowed in Malagasy. As we saw, functional control verbs may be reciprocated productively, and with an interpretation not predicted by the valency reducing analysis of reciprocation. However, the valency preserving analysis of reciprocal constructions provides a very natural account for the grammaticality of reciprocated control verbs. Under this analysis, the control verb keeps all its grammatical functions when reciprocated – and so the equation between the lower verb's subject and the matrix verb's object can be maintained.

Using the new definition of the reciprocal morpheme in (60), we can now analyse reciprocated functional control verbs. Below are the lexical entries, c- and f- structure for (26b), repeated here as (69):

- (69) *N-ifamp-i-laza ho n-amboly vary Raso sy Ravelo.*
 PST-REC-ACT-say COMP PST-cultivate rice Raso and Ravelo
 [V [Comp V O] S]
 “Raso and Ravelo said of each other that s/he cultivated rice.”

As part of the information associated with the main verb *nifampilaza*, note the contribution from in the reciprocal morpheme (in bold):

<i>Raso sy Ravelo</i>	NP	“Raso and Ravelo”
<i>nifampilaza</i>	V	(↑ PRED) = 'say<(↑SUBJ)(↑XCOMP)>(OBJ) (↑ TENSE) = PAST (↑ VOICE) = ACTIVE (↑XCOMP SUBJ) = (↑OBJ) (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO _{rec} '
<i>namboly</i>	V	(↑PRED) = 'cultivate<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)> (↑VOICE) = ACTIVE (↑TENSE) = PAST
<i>vary</i>	NP	(↑PRED) = 'rice'

Recall that the definition of the reciprocal pronoun requires that it must belong in some

non-subject grammatical function. However, the principles of completeness, coherence and uniqueness require that the grammatical function it belongs to is one that is both selected by a predicate (usually the verb), and one that does not already contain a PRED. The only grammatical function that conforms to these requirements (in this context) is the object subcategorised for by the main verb. Thus lexical entry for *-ifamp-* in (69) is effectively:

As the valency preserving analysis of the reciprocal construction does not affect the PRED of the reciprocated verb in f-structure, this analysis does not require the invention of new lexical rules to explain the grammaticality of sentences like (69) – their analysis

is unchanged. This is because lexical entry given for the reciprocal morpheme is flexible enough to accommodate control constructions without modification.

The analysis above is able to capture the grammaticality of reciprocal functional control verbs, as both their analysis and existence emerge as a natural consequence of the definition of the reciprocal morpheme in (60). This definition also formalises the notion of mismatch – there is a pronoun in f-structure that is not associated with an NP in c-structure. Such a condition, difficult to analyse in some syntactic theories, is easily accommodated in LFG.

Although both the valency reducing and valency preserving analyses of the Malagasy reciprocal construction are capable of explaining the syntax of relatively simple constructions, such as those formed from transitive verbs, an examination of reciprocated functional control verbs reveals clear differences between them. A valency reducing analysis of reciprocation would not predict this existence of reciprocated control verbs – so their existence is highly problematic. In contrast though, the valency preserving account of reciprocation that I present here provides a straightforward account of these verb's existence and their behaviour by utilising the notion of a mismatch between f-structure and c-structure. In section 3.7.3 below I once again contrast these two analyses of the reciprocal construction – but this time in conjunction with possession. It is in this environment that it becomes completely clear that only the valency preserving analysis of the reciprocal morpheme can explain the fuller behaviour of reciprocal construction in Malagasy.

3.7.3 Reciprocal possession constructions

The valency preserving analysis of reciprocal constructions readily predicts the grammaticality of reciprocated possession constructions – in fact the definition of the reciprocal morpheme previously given requires no modification to explain the syntax of reciprocated possession sentences, and it also provides a semantically plausible account of the remnant. In this section I am going to reexamine sentence (44b) below (relabelled as (70)) which exhibits functional control, reciprocation and possession:

(70) Malagasy (repeated from (44b))

<i>M-ifamp-i-laza</i>	<i>ray aman-dreny</i>	<i>ho</i>	<i>mamboly vary</i>
PRES-REC-ACT-say	the parents	COMP	cultivate rice

i Rabe sy Rakoto.

ART Rabe and Rakoto

“Rabe and Rakoto say each other's parents are cultivating rice.”

The valency preserving definition of the Malagasy reciprocal construction places a reciprocal pronoun in some grammatical function using the following lexical entry (repeated from (57) above):

(71) *-if-* (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'

Recall that GF* can represent any chain of grammatical functions, but that the principles of completeness, coherence and predicate uniqueness require that the PRED feature be in an f-structure that is selected by another PRED, and that the f-structure have no other PRED feature. In (72) below I list the relevant lexical entries associated with sentence (69) and sketch out the associated c-structure:

(72) *M-ifamp-i-laza ray aman-dreny ho mamboly vary*
 PRES-REC-ACT-say the parents COMP cultivate rice

i Rabe sy Rakoto.

ART Rabe and Rakoto

“Rabe and Rakoto say each other's parents are cultivating rice.”

<i>M-ifamp-i-laza</i>	<i>v</i>	(↑PRED) = 'say<(↑SUBJ)(↑XCOMP)>(↑OBJ) (↑XCOMP SUBJ) = (↑OBJ) (↑TENSE) = PRES (↑VOICE) = ACTIVE (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO _{rec} '
<i>mamboly</i>	<i>v</i>	(↑PRED) = 'cultivate<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)> (↑TENSE) = PRES (↑VOICE) = ACTIVE
<i>ray aman-dreny</i>	<i>NP</i>	(↑PRED) = 'parents_of<(↑POSS)>'
<i>vary</i>	<i>n</i>	(↑PRED) = 'rice'
<i>Rabe sy Rakoto</i>	<i>NP</i>	(↑PRED) = 'Rabe and Rakoto'

Note that this analysis follows the previous discussion of functional control sentences and possession. The remnant belongs to the OBJ grammatical function of the main verb, and still functions (via the assignment of a lexical rule) as the SUBJ of the lower verb. *Ray aman-dreny* – “the parents (of)” selects a possessor grammatical function. To better illustrate how the definition of the reciprocal morpheme works, in (73) below I have drawn the f-structure generated by (72) – temporarily ignoring the lexical contribution of the reciprocal morpheme:

(73) Incomplete f-structure for (72)

PRED	'say<SUBJ,XCOMP>OBJ'
SUBJ	[PRED 'Rabe and Rakoto']
OBJ	[PRED 'parents_of<POSS>']
	[POSS
	[PRED 'cultivate,OBJ>']
XCOMP	OBJ [PRED 'rice']
	TENSE PRES
	ASPECT ACTIVE
TENSE	PRES
ASPECT	ACTIVE

The contribution of the reciprocal morpheme creates a reciprocal pronoun as the PRED value of some chain of grammatical functions. However, there is only one chain that simultaneously conforms to the requirements of completeness, coherence and predicate uniqueness:

(74) GF = OBJ POSS,

and hence the lexical definition associated with *-ifamp-* in this context is:

(↑ OBJ POSS PRED) = 'PRO_{rec}'

This results in the final, complete and coherent f-structure for (72):

(75) Final f-structure for (72)

[PRED	‘say<SUBJ,XCOMP>OBJ’	
SUBJ	[PRED ‘Rabe and Rakoto’	
OBJ	[PRED ‘parents_of<POSS>’	
	POSS	[PRED ‘PRO _{rec} ’
		[PRED ‘cultivate,OBJ>’
XCOMP	SUBJ	—	
	OBJ	[PRED ‘rice’
	TENSE	PRES	
	ASPECT	ACTIVE	
TENSE	PRES		
ASPECT	ACTIVE]

The valency preserving analysis of the reciprocal constructions in Malagasy predicts the existence of reciprocated possession constructions, and it provides a straightforward analysis of them. Notably, no extensions to lexical rules or syntax have been required to accomplish this analysis. The remnant, whose presence was all but inexplicable under a valency reducing analysis of reciprocation, is now understood as being in a possession construction with the reciprocal pronoun – explaining both the presence of the remnant syntactically, but also where it appears in the clause.

In this chapter I have examined two different classes of reciprocation strategies. The valency reducing reciprocation strategies (*i.e.*, the argument unification or argument suppression processes) have been successfully applied to languages whose reciprocal constructions are, in terms of morphosyntactic expression, almost identical to the Malagasy reciprocal construction. As such, we might expect that their application to

Malagasy would be just as successful. On first inspection that does appear to be the case as the syntax of basic reciprocated verbs can be explained by either of these two valency reducing reciprocation strategies. However, to really determine how a reciprocated verb should be analysed we need to first gain a clearer notion as to its valency. For this purpose, I described two further syntactic environments which could be used as tests to probe the reciprocated valency in more detail – functional control and possession. These environments revealed that the verb must maintain all its grammatical functions when reciprocated. However, as reciprocated verbs have lost (typically) an object NP when compared to their base forms, this introduces a mismatch between f- and c-structure. This mismatch was resolved by taking advantage of the parallel but distinct levels of syntactic structure which LFG offers. The reciprocal morpheme was defined so that it introduced a reciprocal pronoun into the f-structure of the reciprocal construction. However, this reciprocal pronoun was not associated with an overt constituent in c-structure. Despite its absence in c-structure, this reciprocal pronoun acts like a regular pronoun in all other respects – as demonstrated by its ability to function as both an object and subject (to a lower clause) in a functional control construction and, its ability to engage in possession constructions with a possessee.

Having argued that the reciprocation strategy in Malagasy is realised in f-structure we can make a further prediction – that the reciprocated verbs should be compatible with other syntactic environments (with appropriate semantic considerations). As such, in 3.8 below, I turn to two more complex constructions; causativisation and nominalisation and examine their interactions with the reciprocal morpheme.

3.8 CAUSATIVES, NOMINALISATION AND RECIPROCATION

Above, I argued that reciprocated predicates in Malagasy are unchanged with respect to the grammatical functions they specify at the level of f-structure. This has implications within the broader domain of Malagasy grammar, because the presence of a reciprocal pronoun at the level of f-structure means that any PRED specifying more than one grammatical function can potentially host a reciprocal construction. Below I examine two complex constructions, reciprocated causative (and causativised reciprocal) constructions (3.8.1) and nominalised reciprocated constructions (3.8.2) to test the valency preserving analysis of the Malagasy reciprocal constructions.

(81) Causative construction of “kick” (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:67) – my a-structure.

- a. *M-an-daka an-Rabe Ranaivo.*
 PRES-ACT-kick ACC-Rabe Ranaivo
 “Ranaivo kicks Rabe.”

- b. *M-amp-an-daka an-dRabe an-dRasoa Rakoto.*
 PRES-CAUS-ACT-kick ACC-Rabe ACC-Rasoa Rakoto
 “Rakoto made Rasoa kick Rabe.”

In (81b), the predicate *kick* has been incorporated into the abstract predicate CAUSE and two of the arguments the P-P of *cause* and the P-A of *kick*, have been linked. When a transitive verb undergoes causativization, either of the non-subject NPs may be made into a subject by the application of the passive morphology (see Spencer & Zwicky (1998:603) for further discussion and the references listed there). As a result (and unlike the ditransitive verbs), both non-subject NPs function as objects, and this is reflecting in the mapping above. I will refer to OBJ₁ as the higher object and OBJ₂ as the lower object.

Interestingly, like their overt reflexive pronoun counterpart, the reciprocal pronoun cannot function as the higher object, although it can do so as the lower object (see (86b) for example). For example, consider (82b) and (83b) below where an overt reflexive and the reciprocal pronoun are in the higher object:

- (82) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:72)
- a. *M-amp-a-mono ilay omby Rakoto Rabe.*
 PRES-CAUS-ACT-kill that cow Rakoto Rabe
 “Rabe made Rakoto kill that cow.”
- b. **M-amp-a-mono ilay omby tena Rabe.*
 PRES-CAUS-ACT-kill that cow self_i Rabe_i
 “Rabe made himself kill that cow.”
- (83) a. *M-amp-an-daka an-dRabe an-dRasoa Rakoto.*
 PRES-CAUS-ACT-kick ACC-Rabe ACC-Rasoa Rakoto
 “Rakoto made Rasoa kick Rabe.”
- b. *#M-if-amp-an-daka an-Rabe Rakoto sy Ranaivo.*
 PRES-REC-CAUSE-ACT-kick ACC-Rabe Rakoto and Ranaivo
 #“Rakoto and Ranaivo made each other kick Rabe.”

The argument structure for (83b) is below – updated to reflect the ungrammaticality of having a reciprocal or reflexive pronoun functioning as the higher object:

- (84) Cause < [P-A] [P-P] Kick < [P-A] [P-P] > >
- | | | |
|----------------------|----------------------|------------------|
| | | |
| SUBJ | OBJ ₁ | OBJ ₂ |
| “Rakoto and Ranaivo” | *PRO _{rec} | “Rabe” |
| | *PRO _{refl} | |

Keenan and Razafimamonjy (2001:70) discuss (83b) – and note that although speakers consider it to be grammatical, they are unsure and inconsistent regarding its interpretation. However, Keenan and Polinsky (1998) do note that there are a few instances of transitive verbs which do undergo both causativization and reciprocation, such as *anatra* – “study” below:

(85) Malagasy (Keenan & Polinsky, 1998:607)

- a. *N-i-anatra zavatra betsaka izy.*
PST-ACT-study thing many he
“He studied many things.”
- b. *N-if-amp-i-anatra zavatra betsaka isika.*
PST-REC-CAUS-ACT-study thing many we (incl.)
“We taught each other many things.”

Given that both reflexive and reciprocal pronouns may not productively function as higher objects, it is likely that this restriction is due to binding. In making this suggestion I am in agreement with Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001) who came to a similar conclusion – although they do not argue for a pronominal analysis of the reciprocal construction. That binding is likely to be involved is further supported by the fact that both the higher and lower objects are both regular objects (*i.e.*, they can both be passivised). This means that we cannot appeal to a difference in the grammatical function of the higher and lower objects to explain why reciprocal and reflexive pronouns should be grammatical only when functioning as the lower object. Without further study into the specifics of the productivity of reciprocated causative expressions, the exact reason as to the ungrammaticality of (82b) and (83b) cannot be fully determined. For our purposes, the fact that the causativised transitive verb cannot be reciprocated, nor have an overt reflexive pronoun in the higher object grammatical function, provides further evidence for the pronominal nature of the valency preserving analysis of reciprocation. This is because both the overt reflexive pronoun and the covert reciprocal pronoun are behaving in the same manner with respect to these constructions.¹⁴³

No such restrictions apply, however, to the lower object. For the reciprocal pronoun to function as the lower object of a causativised transitive verb, the order of the reciprocal and causative morphemes needs to be reversed as in (86b) below:

143 See also the discussion of object comparisons on page 175, where again the reciprocal and reflexive pronouns behave similarly.

(86) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:67)

a. *N-if-an-daka Rabe sy Rakoto.*

PST-REC-ACT-kick Rabe and Rakoto

“Rabe and Rakoto kicked each other.”

b. *N-amp-if-an-daka an-dRabe sy Rakoto aho.*

PST-CAUS-REC-ACT-kick ACC-Rabe and Rakoto 1SG.NOM

“I made Rabe and Rakoto kick each other.”

This type of construction is characterised as being productive by Keenan & Razafimamonjy (2001), with the caveat that the main clause subject may not serve as antecedent.¹⁴⁴ The f-structure of (86b) is shown below where the predicate *nampifandaka* – “make kick” now specifies three grammatical functions:

(87)
$$\left[\begin{array}{ll} \text{PRED} & \text{'make_kick<SUBJ,OBJ}_1\text{,OBJ}_2\text{>} \\ \text{SUBJ} & \text{[PRED 'I']} \\ \text{OBJ}_1 & \text{[PRED 'Rabe and Rakoto']} \\ \text{OBJ}_2 & \text{[PRED 'PRO}_{\text{rec}}\text{'}} \\ \text{TENSE} & \text{PRES} \\ \text{VOICE} & \text{ACTIVE} \end{array} \right]$$

The valency preserving analysis of reciprocation ought to be compatible with not only other syntactic processes, but also the behaviour of other anaphoric pronouns. This was illustrated above, where the analysis of causativised reciprocal expressions followed straightforwardly from the existing definition of the reciprocal morpheme. The pronominal nature of the reciprocal construction for which I have argued here, was demonstrated by considering the reciprocation of causative constructions – constructions that are ungrammatical, whether they are reciprocated, or occur with an overt reflexive pronoun.

3.8.2 Nominalised reciprocal constructions

The nominalisation construction in Malagasy is formed by applying the prefix *mp-* or *f-* (depending on the phonological environment) to tenseless active verbs:

¹⁴⁴ *i.e.*, there is no equivalent to (86b) of “Rabe and Rakoto made each other kick Raso.”

- (88) Nominalisation (Keenan & Polinsky, 1998:612)
m-i-haino – “listen” → *mp-i-haino* “listeners”

The nominalised expression preserves the sub-categorisation of the verb (although, of course, without the subject). For example, a nominalised ditransitive verb still requires an object and indirect object, and in (89) below, the nominalised control verb still specifies an OBJ and a XCOMP. As nominalisation is a process generally understood to take place in a-structure (see Bresnan, 2001:319 and the references there), we would expect that semantically appropriate nominalised predicates would be compatible with the reciprocal construction. This prediction is borne out, as evidenced by (89) below:

- (89) Nominalised Reciprocal Construction (Keenan & Razafimamonjy, 2001:62)

M-if-am-angy matetika ireo mpifanantena zanaka
 PRES-REC-ACT-visit often these NMLZ-REC-ACT-hope children

ho salama ireo.

COMP healthy these

“Those people who hope(d) each other’s children were healthy visit each other often.”

In (89), the subject NP (underlined) contains the nominalised reciprocal expression *mpifanantena* – “hoppers” along with its arguments. The process of nominalisation is theoretically complex and not pursued here, but it is generally considered to be an operation that results in a modified predicate in f-structure. For our purposes, it is sufficient to consider nominalisation as a lexical process, which incorporates the highest thematic role into the meaning of the nominalised verb.¹⁴⁵ For example:

145 The grammaticality of sentences like (89) above (which contain a reciprocal pronoun) has implications for binding theory. Nominalised expressions have no subject NP, and in these situations it makes far more sense to consider that binding take place at the level of a-structure (where there is an available a-subject – à la Manning’s (1996b) analysis) rather than in f-structure, where it is not clear how the binding to the antecedent would be properly interpreted.

(90) Nominalisation Process

go<(↑SUBJ)>	→	one_who_goes
visit<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)>	→	one_who_visits<(↑OBJ)>
give<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)(↑OBL)>	→	one_who_gives<(↑OBJ)(↑OBL)>
and <i>mpifanantena</i> (one_who_hopes):		
hope<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)(↑XCOMP)>	→	hoper<(↑OBJ)(↑XCOMP)>

Therefore the predicate *mpifanantena* (from *manantena* – “to hope”, a functional control verb) can be analysed analogously.

The nominalisation process may also be applied to reciprocated causative expressions. The analysis of the reciprocal morpheme given in (57) needs no modification to account for the grammaticality of these very complex NP's such as *fifampianaran* – “the teaching (cause-study) of Malagasy to each other”:

(91) Malagasy (Ntelitheos, 2010:397)

<i>Ny f-if-amp-i-anara.n'</i>	<i>ny ankizy ny teny gasy.</i>
DET NMLZ.CAUS.REC.ACT-study-LNK	DET children DET language Malagasy
“The children's teaching of Malagasy to each other.”	

The head of the NP above is *f-if-amp-i-anara.n'* which takes *ny teny gasy* – “the Malagasy language” as an accusatively marked complement and this entire complex is in a possessor relation with *ny ankizy* – “the children”. In (88) below, I step through the contribution each of the morphemes make to the head verb *anara* – “study” to make *fifampianara.n'* – “(someone's) teaching (of something) to each other”:

(92) <i>anara,</i>	v	(PRED) = 'study<(SUBJ)(OBJ)>'
<i>i-anara,</i>	v	(PRED) = 'study<(SUBJ)(OBJ)>' (VOICE) = ACTIVE
<i>amp-i-anara,</i>	v	(PRED) = 'teach<(SUBJ)(OBJ ₁)(OBJ ₂)>' (i.e., cause_study) (VOICE) = ACTIVE
<i>if-amp-i-anara,</i>	v	(PRED) = 'teach<(SUBJ)(OBJ ₁)(OBJ ₂)>' (VOICE) = ACTIVE (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO _{rec} '

<i>f-if-amp-i-anara,</i>	<i>n</i>	(PRED) = 'teaching<(OBJ ₁)(OBJ ₂)>' (VOICE) = ACTIVE (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO _{rec} '
<i>f-if-amp-i-anara-n'</i>	<i>n</i>	(PRED) = 'teaching<(OBJ ₁)(OBJ ₂)(POSS)>' (VOICE) = ACTIVE (↑ [GF* - SUBJ] PRED) = 'PRO _{rec} '

Allowing GF = OBJ₂ (the only grammatical function not otherwise containing a PRED), the f-structure associated with (91) is:

PRED	'teaching<OBJ ₁ ,OBJ ₂ ,POSS>'
POSS	[PRED 'the children']
OBJ ₁	[PRED 'the Malagasy language']
OBJ ₂	[PRED 'PRO _{rec} ']
VOICE	ACTIVE

As the above analysis demonstrates, the definition of the reciprocal pronoun given in (57) correctly predicts the grammaticality of reciprocated nominalised expressions. This should come as no surprise as the nominalisation process occurs in a-structure, while reciprocation affects c-structure. Provided that the nominalised verb still selects a grammatical function in f-structure, we would expect that it could be reciprocated.

3.9 CONCLUSION

When considering basic reciprocal sentences in Malagasy, there was no reason at the outset to suppose that their analysis be any different from that which has been put forward in the literature to account for the verbally marked reciprocal constructions in other languages. In fact both of the analyses I consider here can adequately account for the grammaticality of these simple constructions. On closer inspection, however, the valency preserving and reducing analyses of reciprocation make different predictions regarding the grammaticality of reciprocated constructions in more complex syntactic environments. In particular, I have argued that any analysis of the Malagasy reciprocal construction that reduces the number of the grammatical functions for which the verb subcategorises is problematic, for two key reasons. The first reason is the lack of a convincing account of the missing subject of the lower clause in control verbs. The second is an inability of the valency reducing analyses to ascribe a syntactically plausible account of the remnant in possession constructions, and a fundamental

semantic incompatibility between the function of the remnant as a possessee and the suppressed (or otherwise mapped) patient argument.

Instead, I show that the reciprocal morpheme in Malagasy is essentially valency preserving – that is to say, the process of reciprocation does not change the argument structure of the predicate, and neither does it change its f-structure representation. By utilising the different levels of syntactic structure that LFG offers, we can analyse the reciprocal morpheme as creating a reciprocal pronoun in a grammatical function – one that exists in f-structure, but which is not associated with a NP constituent in c-structure (*cf.*, the analysis of pro-drop and related phenomena). This creates a mismatch between c- and f-structure in the analysis of the Malagasy reciprocal construction. However, unlike the valency reducing analyses which create a mismatch between a- and f-structure, this mismatch occurs between f- and c-structure. I have shown that this mismatch provides a simple and natural account of the syntax of these constructions, by allowing what appears to be an empty category or missing NP to engage in syntactic processes such as object possession and control. This particular reciprocation strategy is not limited to Malagasy. As (93) below demonstrates, the verbally marked reciprocal construction in Japanese behaves similarly – and it is probable that the same analysis argued here for Malagasy can be applied to it as well:¹⁴⁶

(93) Japanese

- a. *Taro-ga Jiro no hahaoya-o home-ta.*
 Taro-NOM Jiro-POSS mother-ACC praise-PST
 “Taro praised Jiro's mother.”

PRO_{rec} functioning as possessor (Nakao, 2003)

- b. [*Taro to Jiro*]-ga *hahaoya-o home-aw-ta.*
 Taro and Jiro-NOM mother-ACC praise-REC-PST
 “Taro and Jiro praised each other's mothers.”

¹⁴⁶ There is some argument in the literature as to whether functional control sentences (called ECM in Nishigauchi, 1992; Ishii, 1990) can be reciprocated in Japanese in the same manner that they can be in Malagasy. Ishii (1990) claims they can be, but Nishigauchi (1992) argues that apparent examples of reciprocated functional control sentences are actually instances of anaphoric control (to use the terminology here). This issue is ultimately related to binding (*i.e.*, can the reciprocal pronoun find its antecedent past a clause boundary). Nonetheless, my view is that the existence of the reciprocal pronoun is demonstrated by the object possession example above in (93).

One key feature of this analysis is that it highlights our notions of valency need to be expanded. Calling a verb transitive really needs to be qualified... do we mean in c- or f-structure? This idea is pursued in Manning (1996b) who investigates syntactic ergativity and shows that different aspects of syntax can be sensitive to different levels of syntactic structure. A very interesting area of further research would be to determine whether various morphosyntactic features taken to be indicative of transitivity for reciprocal constructions are in fact linked to either (or both of) the number of NP's associated with the verb in c-structure or the number of grammatical functions in f-structure. It is likely that the mixed signals regarding transitivity, that often accompany reciprocal constructions, could be in part explained by this type of mismatch.

More generally, because this analysis leaves the f-structure of the reciprocated verb unchanged, it has implications regarding the productivity of the reciprocal construction. For example, subject to various phonological criteria, binding and basic semantic requirements, a reciprocal construction should be compatible with other syntactic environments. This prediction is fulfilled in Malagasy, where we see that reciprocated verbs may participate in causative, circumstantial and nominalisation constructions.

The Malagasy reciprocal construction utilises an operator (pronominal) reciprocation strategy – just like the phrasal and fixed case reciprocal constructions in Icelandic. Although its morphosyntactic expression is entirely different, its f-structure analysis is essentially the same. By understanding the strategy that underlies the formation of the Malagasy reciprocal construction, initially surprising data, such as the ability of the construction to be compatible with object possession, are entirely predictable – we would expect the Malagasy and Icelandic phrasal reciprocal constructions to behave similarly in wider syntactic environments.

Thus far, we have seen three possible strategies that may underlie verbally marked reciprocal constructions – Alsina's (1996) argument unification strategy for Romance reciprocals, Mchombo's operator based argument suppression analysis (1991) for the Chicheŵa reciprocal construction and the pronominal operator analysis presented here for Malagasy. As we have seen, different reciprocation strategies can have different implications regarding the behaviour of a reciprocal construction in wider syntactic environments, yet despite these different strategies, the morphosyntactic expression of their corresponding reciprocal construction is little changed. This supports one of the key contentions of this thesis – that reciprocal constructions need to be understood

Chapter 3

primarily by their underlying reciprocation strategies, and not their surface expression. To further reinforce this point, in chapters 4 and 5 I examine the Swahili reciprocal construction and demonstrate that despite its similarity in expression to the Malagasy reciprocal construction, its reciprocation strategy (and hence, its syntactic behaviour) differs greatly – and in fact it is more closely related to intrinsically symmetric verbs (such as *fight* or *meet*) than to any of the reciprocal constructions discussed so far.

4 SWAHILI – THE MONADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

We have seen, so far, that reciprocal constructions are best analysed by determining their underlying reciprocation strategies. I have demonstrated that the variety of different Icelandic reciprocal constructions and their unusual case marking came about as a result of a transition in their underlying reciprocation strategy from the compositional to the pronominal/operator. One consequence of this transition is that two apparently identical reciprocal constructions, the fixed form and antecedent case reciprocal constructions, could have different underlying reciprocation strategies and as a result, different syntactic behaviour. Conversely, the verbally marked Malagasy reciprocal construction, despite having very different morphosyntactic expression to the phrasal and fixed case Icelandic reciprocal constructions, was shown to have the same underlying pronominal/operator reciprocation strategy – and consequently similar syntactic behaviour. In this chapter I examine the Swahili reciprocal construction (which like the Malagasy construction, is formed via the application of a reciprocal morpheme to a verb) and argue that an entirely different mechanism is responsible for its formation. This results in syntactic behaviour that is quite different from anything previously discussed in this thesis – behaviour that aligns this construction more closely

with that of intrinsically symmetric verbs (such as *meet*, *argue*, *chat* etc.). I will show that this strategy can usefully be applied to many other reciprocal constructions as well, such as those in Hungarian, Greek, Hebrew amongst others.

Many Bantu languages (*e.g.*, Swahili – Vitale, 1981; Luganda – McPherson, 2008; Ciyao – Mchombo & Ngunga, 1994 and Chicheŵa – Mchombo, 1991), are able to productively form two types of reciprocal constructions from a transitive base. In the case of Swahili both constructions are formed by marking the verb with the reciprocal morpheme *-an-*. The monadic reciprocal construction in (1b) below groups the participants of an event into the subject NP while losing the object NP. The dyadic reciprocal construction in (1c), so called because it is formed from two parts, creates a symmetric situation by placing one participant, or group of participants, into a subject NP and another in a comitative phrase (also with the corresponding loss of an object).¹⁴⁷

(1) Swahili – Basic transitive construction¹⁴⁸

- a. *Juma a-li-m-tekeny-a Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-3SGO-tickle-FV Halima
 “Juma tickled Halima.”

Monadic reciprocal construction

- b. *Juma na Halima wa-li-tekeny-an-a.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-tickle-REC-FV
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

Dyadic reciprocal construction

- c. *Juma a-li-tekeny-an-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-tickle-REC-FV COM Halima
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

147 Note that by using the terms *monadic* to refer to the basic reciprocal construction in (1b) and *dyadic* to refer to the reciprocal construction in (1c), I am following terminology introduced by Rákosi (2008). In the literature the dyadic construction is often referred to as the “discontinuous reciprocal construction” - however I do not want to make any implicit claims that the dyadic construction is formed from a discontinuous subject (see discussion in section 4.3 below).

148 Unless otherwise referenced, the Swahili language data was elicited during interviews with my language teacher, Mr Hillary Kissassy, a first language speaker of Swahili.

Note that there are subtle semantic differences between (1b) and (1c). In (1c), both Juma and Halima share roughly equal participation in the event of tickling. However, the default reading of (1c) is that Juma is usually the instigator of the event and Halima's participation does not have to match his – she may be a reluctant participant for example. Note that both (1b) and (1c) are ungrammatical if they appear with an object NP, or if object concord marking (*-m-* above in (1a)) appears on the verb. In (2a) and (2b) below, there is a further contrast in the partitioning of the participants in the symmetric event. In (2b), the reading is that the women tickled Halima, and she them, but the women did not tickle each other. However, this second reading is available to (2a):

(2) Monadic reciprocal construction with plural subject

- a. *Wa-nawake na Halima wa-li-tekeny-an-a.*
 PL-WOMAN and Halima 3PLS-PST-tickle-REC-FV
 “The women and Halima tickled each other.”

Dyadic reciprocal construction with plural subject

- b. *Wa-nawake wa-li-tekeny-an-a na Halima.*
 PL-WOMAN 3PLS-PST-tickle-REC-FV COM Halima
 lit. “The women tickled each other with Halima.”
 “The women mutually-tickled with Halima.”

The two Swahili reciprocal constructions in (1b,c) and (2a,b) above are in fact representative of a type of alternation that occurs amongst many, but not all, languages that have verbally marked reciprocal constructions. The productive alternation of a monadic and dyadic construction is a common feature amongst the Bantu languages but the alternation also exists in many diverse language groups of the world (albeit, not usually as productively). Examples are found in Icelandic (see chapter 5, example (71), Hungarian (Rákosi, 2008), Greek, Serbian, German (Dimitriadis, 2008), Dutch (Reinhart & Siloni, 2005), Hebrew (Siloni, 2008), Lao (Enfield, 2003) and many others. Even English has a similar alternation available to it for most intrinsically symmetric verbs:

- (3a) *Jane, Mary and Arthur quarrelled.*
(3b) *Jane and Mary quarrelled with Arthur.*

In an early analysis the dyadic construction in Ciyao (Mchombo & Ngunga, 1994) the comitative phrase in a dyadic construction was simply analysed as being part of a discontinuous subject. In other respects its treatment was the same as the monadic construction. At first glance, such an analysis is not without merit. Work by Stassen (2000) revealed that there is cross-linguistic evidence that comitative constructions can be used, in some instances, as part of a standard coordination strategy which introduce two arguments of equal syntactic status. Evidence for such disguised instances of basic coordination is: plural number agreement on the verb; the comitative phrase appearing next to the NP with which it is coordinated (in the case of SVO languages like Swahili); and/or a doubling of the comitative marker when used as a coordinator. Such constructions are possible in Swahili (see example (12) below) and other Bantu languages (see Stassen, 2000:28). However, constructions such as (1c) have none of these hallmarks – the verb retains its singular marking and the comitative phrase occurs after the verb rather than as part of the subject. In fact, when considering comitative phrases co-occurring with intrinsically symmetric verbs, for many languages (such as Hungarian, Hebrew *etc.* (Siloni, 2008; Rákosi, 2008) this approach has been abandoned, both on syntactic grounds (see section 4.2) but also because it does not provide an explanation as to why: from a cross-linguistic perspective, we find that dyadic constructions are usually formed from comitative phrases; and why the monadic and dyadic constructions have consistently different semantics with respect to the entailments of symmetry.¹⁴⁹ In fact, when viewed from a cross-linguistic perspective, the monadic/dyadic alternation of verbally marked reciprocal constructions is remarkable. That languages from so many different families should have an alternative way of expressing symmetry which is so similar with respect to its formation, its entailments regarding the relations between the participants and other more subtle semantic behaviour can only be explained by a mechanism which is common to them all.

What is needed for Swahili, the other Bantu languages, and in fact any language

¹⁴⁹ Note, that for some languages (such as Japanese – Nishigauchi 1992), the comitative phrase is argued to be part of a discontinuous subject. Equivalent English examples are “The boys, with the girls, threw snowballs at each other.” and “The man, with his wife, kissed.” Their analysis is straight forward and not pursued further here.

that has a productive alternation between a monadic and dyadic reciprocal construction is an account which explains their productive formation from a transitive base. My argument is that just two processes explain both the formation and semantic similarities of many of these verbally marked reciprocal constructions.

The first process relates to how the predicate gains a symmetric sense, and I will argue that this process in Swahili is fundamentally different from those that we have already examined. My argument is that Swahili, and possibly other languages which have a productive alternation between monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions employ a lexically based construal of symmetry – one where the symmetric sense of an event does not arise from the application of an operator, but is an intrinsic part of the meaning of the lexeme (see section 4.3). The second process follows from the first – that there is a syntactic operation, available only to symmetric predicates which gives rise to a dyadic construction (see chapter 5). I capture this phenomenon in LFG by building upon the work of two researchers: Rákosi (2008); and Webb (2008). In conception, my analysis is similar to the distinction Siloni (2008) makes between lexical and syntactic reciprocals, (see discussion in section 4.2 below). It is, apart from differences due to different theoretical frameworks, compatible with the conclusions she draws regarding the typology of these constructions.

As a consequence of this analysis, I provide an account of the alternation of the Swahili monadic and dyadic constructions above with respect to their transitive base. Additionally, this account explains why there are differences between the Romance and Swahili reciprocal constructions as well as the similarities between the Swahili reciprocal construction with intrinsically symmetric verbs in other languages (such as *fight, marry etc.*).

The analysis presented here is divided into two chapters. In this chapter I examine the monadic reciprocal construction and argue for an analysis that is centred around lexical symmetry. In chapter 5, I examine one of the consequences of this analysis and argue that there is a process available to symmetric lexemes, which allows for the formation of a dyadic construction.

4.2 THE MONADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION

One of the key issues in any analysis of monadic reciprocal constructions is how to

understand the apparent loss of the object grammatical function. In the previous chapter, I argued that the f-structure of the reciprocated verb in Malagasy was unchanged, despite the loss of a NP in c-structure. The reciprocal construction in Swahili also loses the NP associated with the object. For example, in (1b) the reciprocated verb *walitekenyana* – “tickle each other” appears without an object – yet it is formed from a verb that has two arguments (an agent and a patient). Under the usual syntactic processes, we would expect that both these arguments are mapped to a subject and an object respectively (as they are for the pronominal operator reciprocation strategy – see chapter 2).

Understanding the monadic reciprocal construction hinges upon two key issues that concern much of syntax more generally. The first is, how do we define which arguments a verb requires, and the second is, how to map these arguments to various grammatical functions. Recall, the data that needs to be addressed is how to relate a reciprocated verb with its transitive counterpart. In chapter 3 we saw that reciprocated verbs in Malagasy, despite losing a constituent, remain syntactically transitive – that is to say, the reciprocated verb is grammatically unchanged by the application of the reciprocal morpheme. This analysis can be ruled out for the Swahili reciprocal construction, which disallows object possession (without the application of an applicative morpheme), and also on other grounds to be discussed below. This analysis is contra Guthrie (1970:96), who takes the position that the reciprocal morpheme in Bantu languages can be considered as an object. Under his analysis, the valency of the verb remains unchanged and it is only the surface form of the construction that changes (*i.e.*, the object moves from its normal place in the sentence to become part of the verb). This analysis is refuted by Dalrymple *et al.* (1994), who show that under a variety of syntactic tests, the reciprocated verb in Chicheŵa patterns with other intransitive verbs in its behaviour.

4.2.1 Determining the valency of the Swahili monadic reciprocal construction

To determine the valency of reciprocated verbs in Chicheŵa, Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) examine the interaction of reciprocal morphology with nominalisation constructions. They begin by demonstrating that deverbal nominals lose their direct object. For example, the verb *sonkha* – “contribute” takes a direct object in (4a) below, but requires a PP in (4b):

- (4) Chicheŵa (from Dalrymple *et al.* 1994:153)
- a. *sonkh-a ndalâma*
 contribute 10money
 “contribute money.”
- b. *m-sonkh-o *ndalâma / wa ndalâma*
 NMLZ-contribute 10money / of 10money
 “contribution *money / of money.”

However, reciprocated expressions may be nominalised – showing that they cannot be associated with an object grammatical function:

- (5) Chicheŵa (from Dalrymple *et al.* 1994:154)
- a. *kõnd-a*
 “love”
- b. *kond-ăn-a*
 love-REC-FV
 “love each other.”
- c. *chi-kond-an-o*
 NMLZ-love-REC-FV
 “mutually love each other.”

As expected, the same argument that Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) developed for Chicheŵa works for Swahili.¹⁵⁰ Here too, nominalised verbs lose their object (see (6) below), but reciprocated verbs may be nominalised:

- (6) Swahili
- a. *pend-a*
 love-FV
 “love”

150 Note, in terms of valency, the analysis I present here for Swahili is in agreement with the analysis Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) describe for Chicheŵa. However, as will become clear, in other details our analyses diverge. These differences are described in section 4.3.6.

- b. *ma-penzi* **mama / la mama*
NMLZ-love mother /for mother
“the love for a mother.” / *“the love mother.”
- (7) a. *pend-an-a*
love-REC-FV
“love each other”
- b. *u-pend-an-o*
NMLZ-LOVE-REC-FV
“mutual love”

This test shows that the Swahili reciprocated verb cannot have an object at the level of f-structure, and that the analysis described for the Malagasy reciprocal construction in chapter 3 cannot be pursued here. Once we allow that the reciprocated verb has one fewer grammatical function at the level of f-structure, other analyses become available to us. Within the literature, they fall into two classes, both affecting the mapping between argument structure (which is unchanged) and f-structure (which has one less grammatical function when compared to its transitive counterpart):

1. Argument Suppression – where one of the arguments in a-structure is suppressed (e.g., Mchombo's 1991 analysis for Chicheŵa).
2. Argument Unification – where two arguments in a-structure are mapped to a single grammatical function in f-structure. For example, Alsina's (1996) analysis for Catalan.

Below I describe each of these analyses, but all of them are problematic when considering the monadic construction in Swahili, and so in section 4.3, I propose an alternative analysis, quite different in its conception. Note that the lexical mapping theory (LMT) that each author uses differs, but functionally they are very similar. For the sake of consistency, I will use the LMT rules described previously (see section 1.5.4.1).

4.2.2 Theories based upon argument suppression.

Firstly we recall Mchombo's analysis of the reciprocal construction in Chicheŵa (see chapter 3.3.1) He argues that this construction is formed by suppression of the P-P argument. For Swahili, Mchombo's analysis is capable of explaining some aspects of the construction – such as the lack of an object. Consider first the transitive verb *tekenya* – “tickle” in (1a) above. It has the a-structure given in (8), and under normal circumstances, we see the following mapping of arguments to grammatical functions via LMT:

(8)	a-structure:	<i>tekenya</i> <[P-A] [P-P]>
	intrinsic classification	-o -r
	default classification	-r
	<u>bi-uniqueness</u>	<u>SUBJ SUBJ/OBJ</u>
	f-structure	<i>tekenya</i> <(SUBJ)(OBJ)>

Under Mchombo's analysis of the reciprocal construction in Chicheŵa, when the reciprocal morpheme *-an-* is applied to the verb, the [P-P] argument is suppressed, and as a result the verb becomes intransitive and no longer specifies an object grammatical function. Example (9) illustrates the same process in Swahili:

(9)	a-structure	<i>tekeny-an-a</i> <[P-A][P-P]>
	arg. suppression	∅
	intrinsic classification	-o
	default classification	-r
	<u>bi-uniqueness</u>	<u>SUBJ</u>
	f-structure	<i>tekenyana</i> <(SUBJ)>

When this verb co-occurs with an object, the principle of coherence (see section 1.5.3) renders the resulting f-structure ungrammatical:

(10)	* <i>Juma na Halima wa-li-pig-an-a</i>	<i>Fatuma.</i>
	Juma and Halima	3PLS-PST-hit-REC-FV Fatuma
	“Juma and Halima hit each other Fatuma.”	

Alternatively, instead of suppressing the proto-patient argument, the proto-agent could

be suppressed, with much the same result.¹⁵¹

(11)	a-structure	<i>tekeny-an-a</i> <[P-A][P-P]>
	arg. suppression	∅
	intrinsic classification	-r
	<u>bi-uniqueness</u>	<u>SUBJ/OBJ</u>
	f-structure	<i>tekenyana</i> <(SUBJ)>

We see that the lexical entry for *tekenyana* (tickle each other) with the proto-agent suppressed also results in a verb that is intransitive at the level of f-structure: *tekenyana*<(SUBJ)>.

4.2.3 Argument unification theories

In section 3.3.2, I discussed Alsina's (1996) analysis of the clitic reciprocal construction in the Romance languages. In his analysis, both arguments in a-structure are mapped to a single grammatical function in f-structure. As in Mchombo's analysis for Chicheŵa above, this results in the loss of a grammatical function in f-structure, and hence the ungrammaticality of (10) above may be explained. The appeal of Alsina's analysis for Romance is that it simultaneously provides an account of the formation of the reciprocal and reflexive constructions. However, as we will see below, there are sound syntactic reasons why this analysis cannot be applied to Swahili – beyond the fact the reciprocal construction does not have a reflexive interpretation.

4.2.4 Discussion

On first inspection, either of the valency reducing analyses above can explain the detransitivisation of reciprocated verbs in Swahili. However, the existence of the dyadic construction shows that none of these analyses can be applied to Swahili. To see why this is the case requires, first, an understanding that the comitative phrase in these constructions is an argument – and not part of a discontinuous subject, nor an adjunct.

In previous work, Dimitriadis (2004) has convincingly argued that for some

¹⁵¹ In fact there are more subtle differences between these analyses revolving around whether the reciprocated verb should be understood as being unergative or unaccusative. I will ultimately reject both of these analyses, so I will not go into details here – but the interested reader can read a very accessible account of these differences in Rákosi, 2008.

languages the comitative phrase in a dyadic reciprocal construction is not part of a discontinuous subject and it is syntactically (and semantically) distinct from the subject NP. In the case of Swahili, despite the fact that the comitative preposition *na* is homophonous with the coordinator, the phrase *na Halima* – “with Halima” in (1c), can be shown to be distinct from the subject by verbal agreement. Verbs in Swahili agree in number with their subject – irrespective of whether the subject is discontinuous or not. So, unlike the dyadic construction, the discontinuous form of the monadic construction has plural subject agreement:

(12) Discontinuous form of the monadic reciprocal construction

- a. *Juma wa-li-pig-an-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3PLS-PST-hit-REC-FV and Halima
 “Juma and Halima hit each other.”

Dyadic reciprocal construction

- b. *Juma a-li-tekeny-an-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-tickle-REC-FV COM Halima
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

That (12a) is distinct from the dyadic reciprocal construction in (12b) is also demonstrated by the semantic differences between them. A dyadic reciprocal construction allows the two participants to have unequal participation in the event – however, (12a) above has the same meaning as the monadic construction in (1b), where both Halima and Juma are equal participants in the event.¹⁵²

Furthermore, we know that the comitative phrase in a dyadic reciprocal construction is an argument, because it is obligatory:

- (13) **Juma a-li-tekeny-an-a.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-tickle-REC-FV
 *“Juma tickled each other.”

152 Dimitriadis (2004) provides further evidence demonstrating the distinctness of the comitative argument in the Swahili dyadic reciprocal construction by examining causative constructions. See section 5.2.1.3 for more details.

The above example shows that the comitative phrase is distinct from the subject, and is a core argument of the verb – an analysis well supported in the literature for many other languages (see Dimitriadis, 2004 in particular for an in-depth discussion). Now, as a core argument of the verb, this means that the comitative phrase must have a counterpart in the a-structure of the verb. However, there is no mechanism in the three valency reducing analyses above that can allow both the formation of the monadic construction and subsequent formation of a dyadic reciprocal construction. Consider the problem – we have two reciprocal constructions and three possible ways in which they can be related to a transitive base:

1. basic verb → monadic construction → dyadic construction
2. basic verb → dyadic construction → monadic construction
3. basic verb $\begin{cases} \rightarrow & \text{monadic construction} \\ \rightarrow & \text{dyadic construction} \end{cases}$

In the first situation, there is no way the dyadic construction can be formed from its monadic counterpart. This is because the dyadic reciprocal construction needs to have two thematic roles in a-structure to explain why the comitative phrase is an argument. However, under either Alsina's analysis, or any argument suppression analysis, both arguments are already used (by being either mapped to one grammatical function, or, by one being suppressed). As a result, any comitative phrase would be incorrectly analysed as an adjunct.

The second and third possibilities both have the same problem – how can a dyadic reciprocal construction be productively formed from a transitive verb? Recall that it is thematic role assignment that ultimately dictates the mapping between arguments and grammatical functions. In the usual case, if the agent is mapped to subject, then the patient is mapped to object. However, if we argued that the dyadic construction was formed from the base transitive verb, this would mean that the patient must now map to an oblique. I can think of no possible mechanism that is able to simultaneously allow the proto-patient to be mapped to an object in one situation, and an oblique in another. The closest I have found would be the anti-passive – however there the entity represented by the patient is reintroduced into the clause as an adjunct rather than as an

argument.

For the dyadic construction in Hungarian, Rákosi (2008) proposes a possible solution for this dilemma using Alsina's idea (with some modification) of a-structure unification as part of his explanation of reciprocal verbs. He proposes that the dyadic reciprocal predicate is a primitive lexeme (*i.e.*, not derived from a transitive verb). This lexeme has two arguments, a proto-agent and a partner argument. The partner argument is unspecified for a thematic role – a possibility allowed for by Dowty (1991). This partner argument is represented by the empty square brackets in the argument structure for (14) below:

- (14) Rákosi (2008:444)
veszekedik quarrel_{dyadic} < [P-A], [] >

It is important to keep in mind that this argument is *unspecified* for a thematic role, and it is not the case that it should be thought of as some sort of generalized partner theme. Instead, the thematic role of the partner argument needs to be inferred from context – and, in the context of reciprocal constructions, its role is usually understood to be similar to that of the proto-agent.¹⁵³ This assignment of thematic roles to the arguments results in the partner argument being mapped to an oblique grammatical function using the mapping principles above:

- | | | |
|------|-------------------------------|--|
| (15) | a-structure | P _{rec,dyadic} <[P-A][]> |
| | intrinsic classification | -o -o |
| | <u>default classification</u> | <u>-r +r</u> |
| | f-structure | P _{rec,dyadic} <(SUBJ) (OBL)> |

Rákosi (2008:445) now uses a process very similar to Alsina's a-structure binding to form the monadic alternation of (15) in (16) below:

- | | | |
|------|-------------------------------|---|
| (16) | a-structure | P _{rec,monadic} <[[P-A][]]> |
| | intrinsic classification | -o |
| | <u>default classification</u> | <u>-r</u> |
| | | P _{rec,monadic} <(SUBJ)> |

¹⁵³ The partner argument is discussed in more detail in chapter 5.

Unfortunately this solution has real problems when applied to Swahili, or to any language with a productive dyadic reciprocal construction, because the dyadic lexeme cannot be understood as being basic – it is clearly formed from a transitive base through the application of the productive derivational affix *-an-*. Furthermore, although it suffices as a synchronic account of the monadic/dyadic alternation in Hungarian, it has no explanatory power in a diachronic context. For example, consider these two points: Rákosi (2003), treats the dyadic form of *veszekedik* – “quarrel” as a basic verb. However, he notes that this verb does contain reciprocal morphology – although it is no longer connected to its base form (*veszekedik* – from take.REC). Clearly, though, these two words were once related – and their counterparts still are in Swahili. This means that any analysis positing the dyadic reciprocated verb as basic, cannot be usefully applied to Swahili. Furthermore, Rákosi's analysis does not tell us why there are more monadic reciprocated verbs than dyadic ones. This fact requires that there be some other mechanism that creates monadic reciprocated verbs which do not have a dyadic counterpart. Finally, from a cross-linguistic perspective Rákosi's analysis provides no insight into why comitative phrases in particular (as opposed to obliques introduced by other prepositions) are so widespread in dyadic constructions.

Above I have outlined my reasoning as to why I think that none of the existing valency reducing theories of monadic reciprocal constructions can account for the set of Swahili reciprocal constructions. Below, I will offer one more consideration as well: there is typological evidence based upon the syntactic and semantic behaviour of these constructions to show that there is more than one possible mechanism for their formation from a cross-linguistic perspective. In other words, as different verbally marked reciprocal construction have quite different behaviours with respect to syntax, it is reasonable to expect that the manner of their formation differs as well. Ultimately, I will explain the origin of these differences, but I present some key differences here for consideration.

Dimitriadis (2004:2) demonstrates that languages with a verbally marked reciprocal construction differ with respect to licensing a dyadic alternation. He notes that “Discontinuous [called dyadic reciprocal constructions here] reciprocals are found in very many languages of the world, including Hebrew, Greek, German, Hungarian, Russian, Polish, Serbian, Sakha, Japanese, Lao and the Bantu languages including

Swahili, Chichewa, Kinyarwanda and Ciyao; but they are not found in Dutch, French, Italian or Spanish...”.^{154,155}

For example, note the contrast between German and Italian below where the Italian monadic reciprocal construction is formed via the addition of a clitic to the verb:

(17) German (Dimitriadis 2004)

- a. *Johann und Maria schlugen sich.*
Johann and Maria hit REC
“Johann and Maria hit each other.”
- b. *Johann schlug sich mit Maria*
Johann hit REC COM Maria
“Johann and Maria hit each other.”

(18) Italian (Dimitriadis 2004)

- a. *Giovanni e Maria si sono abbracciati.*
Giovanni and Maria REC are hugged
“Giovanni and Maria hugged each other.”
- b. **Giovanni si è abbracciato con Maria.*
Giovanni REC is hugged COM Maria
*“Giovanni hugged each other with Maria.”

Another difference is noted by Siloni (2002, 2008) – and is discussed extensively elsewhere. She demonstrates that languages with verbally marked reciprocal constructions can differ with respect to the countability of sub-events. To illustrate this, consider (19) below:

154 My comments in square brackets.

155 For the most part, the data suggests that these languages should be analysed similarly to the Swahili presented here – but there are exceptions, such as the Japanese comitative reciprocal construction discussed earlier.

(19) French (Siloni, 2011)

*Le laryngologue et le dentiste se sont examinés cinq fois.*¹⁵⁶

The laryngologist and the dentist_{RR} are examined 5 times

“The laryngologist and the dentist examined each other 5 times.”

How many events of examination were there?

Five or ten – possibly five by the laryngologist and five by the dentist.

In (19), the adverbial “five times” can be interpreted in two ways. It may refer to five instances of mutual examination, or ten (five by each person) instances of asymmetric examination. English and the Icelandic bipartite reciprocal construction pattern the same way. Interestingly, Swahili does not, even when the semantics of the situation would seem to require that sub-events be possible. Consider (20) below:

(20) *Juma na Halima wa-li-tembel-e-an-a mara tatu.*

Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-VISIT-APP-REC-FV times three

“Juma and Halima visited each other three times.”

The only interpretation of (20) is that there were three periods of mutual visiting – not that there were six asymmetric visits. Siloni (2008:495) observes that the property of sub-event countability is linked to whether or not a language allows a dyadic alternation. If a verbally marked reciprocal construction has a dyadic alternation – both it and the monadic construction will not have countable sub-events (and *vice-versa*).¹⁵⁷

That languages with a verbally marked reciprocal construction differ with respect to the allowability of a dyadic alternation, and to sub-event countability, at least raises the prospect that their reciprocal constructions are formed in different ways. These differences in behaviour are further explored in several papers by Siloni (2011 *etc.*) and Reinhart and Siloni (2005) who argue that differences seen above are related to the manner in which the reciprocal construction is formed.

156 Note that although the French clitic reciprocal construction appears as if it were transitive (for example, the clitic could be imagined as being a regular pronominal object) - it is uncontroversial that these constructions are in fact intransitive. I have not provided the argumentation here, however Siloni (2008) provides ample evidence to support this position.

157 This observation, and in fact this relationship, is actually predicted by the analysis I present below.

4.2.5 The Lexical-Syntax parameter

Works by Siloni (2001, 2002, 2008, 2011) and Reinhart and Siloni (2005) seek to understand the varying syntactic and semantic behaviour of verbal or clitic reciprocal constructions as arising from their locus of formation – either in syntax or in the lexicon. In earlier work, Reinhart and Siloni (2005:408) express this difference by creating a “lex-syn” parameter:

The lex-syn parameter

Universal Grammar allows thematic arity operations to apply in the lexicon or in the syntax.

In their analysis, a lexical reciprocal is one that is formed in the lexicon and enters the syntax already symmetric, whereas a syntactic reciprocal is one where the symmetric sense is formed in syntax.

By examining many different properties (the “I” versus “we” reading of embedded reciprocals, sub-event countability and the availability of a dyadic construction), Siloni ultimately designates the reciprocal constructions in her sample of 10 languages as belonging to either the class of syntactic or lexical reciprocals. My analysis of the Swahili monadic reciprocal construction fits neatly with this typology, being firmly in the lexical reciprocal category (as evidenced by sub-event counting and the availability of a dyadic construction). Note though that in chapter 1.4, I discussed symmetry formed through the application of a reciprocal operator to an asymmetric predicate (*e.g.*, RECI or INWARD). This type of symmetry is *not* the same as Siloni's syntactic reciprocals. Siloni considers reciprocals formed through the application of a reciprocal anaphor to be a different class to those formed via the *lex-syn* parameter (Siloni 2008:463). The syntactic reciprocals she describes are those formed in Romance languages through the application of an arity operation (*i.e.*, similar to the analysis which Alsina offers for Catalan). In other words, she describes a three-way typology of reciprocal constructions:

- Reciprocals formed in the lexicon via an arity operation (*e.g.*, Hebrew, Russian, Hungarian)

- Reciprocals formed in syntax via an arity operation (e.g., Romance, Czech clitics)
- Reciprocals formed via the application of a reciprocal operator (e.g., English – *each other*)

I will briefly examine Siloni's work as to why she made this three-way classification. In particular, I want to raise the possibility that the classification of syntax reciprocals that Siloni makes may in fact be an instance of the operator reciprocation strategy.

Siloni (2008) uses a series of tests to distinguish these three classes of reciprocals. The syntax reciprocals she identifies (such as French, Czech) and the operator reciprocals (such as those in English using *each other*) behave the same way with respect to these tests except in one instance: the embedding of reciprocal constructions within superordinate clauses. Siloni builds on the work of Higginbotham (1980), Heim, Lasnik, May (1991a, 1991b), Williams (1991) and Carlson (1998), by examining the ambiguity that arises when reciprocal constructions are embedded. As an example, consider the ambiguity in English when a reciprocal construction is embedded within a superordinate clause:

(21) *John and Paul said that they saw each other.*

This has two interpretations; an “I” reading and a “We” reading – the difference can be understood as arising from the scope of the reciprocal operator, whether wide or narrow:

(22) “I” reading (wide-scope):

John and Paul say different things:

John said “I saw Paul”, Paul said “I saw John”

$RECIP(\{John, Paul\}, \lambda x. say(x, \lambda y. see(x, y)))$

(23) “we reading” (narrow-scope):

both John and Paul say “we saw each other”.

$say(\{John, Paul\}, RECIP(\{John, Paul\}, \lambda x. \lambda y. see(x, y)))$

Armed with this terminology, Siloni (2011) then examines the contrast between French and English, when using self-contradictory reciprocal constructions (such as “defeated each other”). Consider first the logically impossible main clauses below (when restricted to a single event):

- (24) #*Peter and John defeated each other in the final.*
- (25) French (from Siloni, 2011)
 #*Pierre et Jean se sont vaincus à la finale.*
 Peter and John_{RR} are defeated at the final.
 #“Peter and John defeated each other at the final.”

Now, consider the felicity of these sentences when embedded into a main clause:

- (26) *Peter and John said that they defeated each other in the final.*
- (27) Siloni (2011)
 #*Pierre et Jean ont dit qu'ils se sont vaincus à la finale.*
 Peter and John have said that they_{SE} are defeated in the final.
 #“Peter and John said that they defeated each other in the final.”

The acceptability of (26) can be understood as a result of quantifier ambiguity – or, more precisely, the RECIP operator taking wide-scope (that is to say, scope over the entire clause):

- (28) “I” reading: $RECIP(\{Peter, John\}, \lambda x. say(x, \lambda y. (defeat(x, y))))$
i.e., John said “I defeated Peter” and Peter said “I defeated John”
- #“We” reading: $say(\{Peter, John\}, RECIP(\{Peter, John\}, \lambda x. \lambda y. (defeat(x, y))))$
i.e., John and Peter said #“We defeated each other”

Thus, it is the availability of two possible readings of embedded reciprocal constructions (only one being acceptable) that allows (26) to be grammatical, even

though the embedded clause is not on its own. However, as evidenced by (27), the equivalent French sentence is not acceptable and so the “I” reading cannot be available. Siloni understands the difference between the acceptability of the English and French sentences as arising from differences in how the constructions are formed (or to use my terminology, different reciprocation strategies). Her analysis of the French reciprocal construction treats it as being formed in syntax through two thematic roles being mapped to a single grammatical function. Under her analysis, the subject of *vaincus* receives two thematic roles (*cf.* Alsina's analysis of Catalan – chapter 3.3), and this means that the only semantically plausible reading of (27), the “I” reading, is unavailable. This is because the “I” reading requires each of the participants in the relation to receive only one thematic role (in this case, that of agent). As a result, the “I” reading is unavailable, the “we” reading is unacceptable – and so (27) has no acceptable interpretation.

An alternative possibility that is worthy of further study is that the Romance clitic reciprocal constructions (and others like them) may in fact still be formed via the application of a reciprocal operator rather than a thematic role operation. This operator (INWARD, *i.e.*, RECIP but also with reflexive semantics – see section 1.4) is unlike the Malagasy and English constructions because it is associated not with a pronoun, but rather with the verb. In this manner, the analysis of the Romance reciprocal constructions would be very similar to that which Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) put forward for Chicheŵa. Under this analysis, the syntactic behaviour of the reciprocal construction (caused by the loss of an object grammatical function) is divorced from its semantic behaviour which arises wholly as a result of an application of the reciprocal operator (be it RECIP or INWARD). As the operator is tied directly to the verb, it is possible that the operator cannot change scope, resulting in only one reading being allowable. If this were the case, then the reciprocal constructions in the Romance languages should behave very much like analytic or phrasal reciprocal constructions (subject to their being intransitive). This does occur when considering sub-event counting, productivity and non-availability of a dyadic alternation. If the INWARD or RECIP operator were unable to move from the verb it quantifies, then only the self-contradictory “we” reading would be possible – and this is also what is seen:

- (29) #“We” reading: $say(\{Pierre, Jean\}, RECIP(\{Pierre, Jean\}, \lambda x. \lambda y. (defeat(x, y))))$
i.e., #Pierre and Jean said “We defeated each other” – see (27) above.

Such work is beyond the scope of this thesis, but it would be enlightening to examine other verbal operators (possibly such as *ne pas*) to see if they too cannot change scope.

4.2.6 Comments

In the above I examined different analyses of monadic reciprocal constructions and showed that they cannot be applied to Swahili. The analysis presented for Malagasy could not be applied to the Swahili monadic reciprocal construction, because reciprocated verbs in Swahili lose a grammatical function in f-structure. Initially, analyses which decreased the valency of the reciprocated verb (whether by argument suppression (*c.f.* Mchombo, 1991) or argument unification (*c.f.* Alsina, 1996) appeared as if they might plausibly explain the monadic reciprocal construction. However, any analysis of this construction in Swahili must also explain the presence of the dyadic alternation – and the valency reducing analyses examined were unable to provide an account that related a transitive base with both the monadic and dyadic reciprocal alternates. Finally, I reviewed work by Siloni (2001, 2002, 2008, 2011) and Reinhart and Siloni (2005) on the “lex-syn” parameter. This is a parameter by which verbal reciprocal constructions are classified into one of two types: lexical or syntactic. Based upon this classification, the Swahili reciprocal construction is clearly “lexical”, and it is upon this categorisation that I build my analysis of the Swahili monadic reciprocal construction.

4.3 ANALYSIS OF THE MONADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION

In this section, I show how the monadic reciprocal construction in Swahili is built upon a different conception of symmetry from that used for other languages, such as English for example. As a consequence of this analysis, I will show how three features that characterise these constructions can be predicted.

4.3.1 Differing conceptions of the formation of symmetry

We saw in previous chapters that one way the symmetry of a reciprocal construction comes about is as a consequence of the application of a reciprocal operator to a predicate. This operator quantifies an asymmetric expression, giving rise to a symmetric interpretation of the event – and there is much evidence for this, such as quantifier ambiguity *etc.* In Icelandic, English and Malagasy, this reciprocal operator is associated with a corresponding reciprocal phrase (or morpheme in the case of Malagasy). For example, in (30) below the reciprocal operator is associated with the phrase *each other*:

(30) *Kate and Jean passed each other (their) glasses.*

The (simplified) f-structure below shows how the reciprocal pronoun in (30) is represented in a normal grammatical function:

$$(31) \begin{bmatrix} \text{PRED} & \text{'pass<SUBJ,OBJ,OBJ}_\theta\text{'}} \\ \text{SUBJ} & \text{[PRED 'Kate and Jean']}} \\ \text{OBJ} & \text{[PRED 'PRO}_{\text{rec}}\text{'}} \\ \text{OBJ}_\theta & \text{[PRED 'glasses']}} \end{bmatrix}$$

Associated with the lexical entry for PRO_{rec} is the quantifier RECIP. This acts just like any other quantifier insofar as it takes an expression, in this case the meaning constructor associated with the predicate, and quantifies it. The formalism associated with the meaning assembly here is quite complex, but ultimately it generates the following expression:¹⁵⁸

(32) $\text{RECIP}(\{\text{Kate, Jean}\}, \lambda x. \lambda y. \text{pass}(x, \text{glasses}, y))$

I describe symmetry that is formed via the application of an operator like that in (32) above as formed via the operator reciprocation strategy. This quantifier approach is used by Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) in their analysis of the Chicheŵa reciprocal construction. Their analysis is that the reciprocal morpheme suppresses the object (essentially detransitivizing the verb), and applies a RECIP operator to the antecedent. Although I agree that the Swahili reciprocal construction no longer has an object, this is not the approach I will take here. Instead I argue that languages can exploit a radically different mechanism to describe symmetric situations where the reciprocated verb is interpreted

¹⁵⁸ See appendix A for a full description of the meaning assembly of sentences like (30) above.

lips or a period of kissing (both of which have a sense of the symmetry of *tekenyana* above). As such, the nomenclature I use to describe derived symmetric verbs will be to use the basic form of the verb followed by the subscript indicating that it is now symmetric. To reiterate, the key difference between this analysis of reciprocation and the other reciprocation strategies previously described (argument suppression, argument unification and the application of a reciprocal operator) is that this analysis creates a symmetric lexeme that enters syntax as already symmetric. My claim that the Swahili monadic reciprocal construction is forming a new symmetric lexeme is testable by the several predictions it makes:

1. That the reciprocated verbs in Swahili should behave like other basic intrinsically symmetric verbs – both in Swahili but also cross-linguistically (section 4.3.2).
2. That as with other lexemes, these reciprocated verbs should be conceived of as being atomic events (section 4.3.3).
3. That these reciprocated verbs, as newly formed lexemes, will be prone to lexical drift (section 4.3.4).

Additionally, we will see in chapter 5, that only symmetric lexemes can act as a base for the dyadic alternation. Finally, having identified an additional reciprocation strategy, there is no reason in principle why a language should not utilise more than one of these strategies in their formation (such as both argument unification and the strategy described here). In section 4.3.5 I show how this possibility is realised in German.

4.3.2 Intrinsically symmetric verbs and the Swahili monadic reciprocal construction

Crucial to this analysis is that the lexeme in the monadic reciprocal construction is now symmetrical – and, as such, would be expected to exhibit the same behaviour as regular intrinsically symmetric predicates. This is indeed the case, both within Swahili and also when these derived symmetric verbs are compared to intrinsically symmetric verbs cross-linguistically. For example, in (36) below, I contrast *tekenyana* – “tickle_{sym}” (a verb that I claim is symmetric) with an intrinsically symmetric verb *onzea* – “chat”:

- (36) a. *Juma na Halima wa-li-tekeny-an-a.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-tickle-REC-FV
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”
- b. *Juma na Halima wa-li-onge-a.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-chat-FV
 “Juma and Halima chatted.”

In (37) we see that unlike typical verbs, both *tekenyana* and *ongea* have a dyadic alternation:

- (37) a. *Juma a-li-tekeny-an-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-tickle-REC-FV COM Halima
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”
 or: “Juma mutually tickled with Halima.”
- b. *Juma a-li-onge-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-chat-FV COM Halima
 “Juma chatted with Halima.”

Recall that this dyadic form is only available to some reciprocal constructions – for example, Swahili differs from the Romance languages where reciprocal constructions do not have a dyadic alternate. Note that the dyadic alternation is not just limited to intrinsically symmetric Swahili verbs – it occurs in many languages (*e.g.*, English – *chat*, French – *bavarder* (to chat), Icelandic – *skrafa* (to chat) *etc.*). This implies that there is a process common to the Swahili reciprocal construction and symmetric verbs (from any language) which licenses the dyadic construction. I will return to this process in chapter 5.

4.3.3 Atomic events and symmetry

Above, I claimed that, as the monadic reciprocal construction creates new symmetric lexemes (that is to say, a word that is symmetric before it enters syntax), then it should act like other basic lexemes. This is a point Siloni (2011) makes by building on work by

Carlson (1998). The basic claim is that “plural events are not part of the lexicon's inventory” (Siloni, 2011:14), or conversely, lexemes may only denote atomic events – and that their pluralisation comes from the application of an operator of some sort (such as EACH, but also RECIP *etc.*).

An atomic event is one in which the participants engage in a single event. For example, in (38) below there is one event of cooking, and Olaf is performing it:

(38) *Olaf cooked some fish.*

With a plural entity, we can often conceive of an event in two ways, as being atomic or non-atomic. For example, the event of cooking below can be either atomic (39a) or non-atomic (39b):

- (39) a. *Olaf and Sally cooked some fish together.*
b. *Olaf and Sally cooked some fish, Olaf in the morning and Sally in the evening.*

Now, when a RECIP operator is applied to a predicate, it takes an asymmetric event, and effectively pluralises it with a rearrangement of the participants described by the event:

(40) *John and Mary saw each other* → *see(John,Mary) and see(Mary,John)*

As the Swahili monadic reciprocal construction is formed via a lexical strategy that makes no use of a RECIP operator, it stays essentially atomic or singular in its conception. Below, I provide two pieces of evidence to support this view. The first relates to the countability of sub-events using tests described by Dimitriadis (2008) and Siloni (2008), and the second relates to the interpretation of events that would seemingly be non-atomic when reciprocated.

4.3.3.1 COUNTABILITY OF SUB-EVENTS

Dimitriadis (2004) and Siloni (2008) both use the countability of sub-events to make broad classifications of reciprocal constructions. To illustrate this test, let us first

consider English:

(41) *They kissed each other three times.*

Example (41) above can be interpreted in two ways. First imagine a situation where a knight kisses a queen on the hand, and she him on the forehead. If this occurred three times, we could say that there were six kisses. Now, interpreting this event as a collection of asymmetric sub-events in English is expected, because we have as a basis for the construction an asymmetric predicate to which a RECIP operator is applied. Siloni (2008) calls this type of construction syntactic (as opposed to lexical), whereas Dimitriadis would classify it as being non-irreducibly symmetric (as opposed to irreducibly symmetric). There is also another interpretation, in which there are just three kisses (such as between two lovers for example) – and Dimitriadis (2008) would characterise this type of event as being irreducibly symmetric.

Recall that languages with verbal reciprocal constructions can behave differently with respect to this test. In (19) above, we saw that French reciprocal construction is similar to English, in that the adverbial counting test is able to access the asymmetric sub-events. Previously, I have stated that the Swahili reciprocal construction is formed via a derived symmetric lexeme. As such, we can now explain the data in (20) – illustrated with the verb *walibusiana* – “kiss_{sym}” below:

(42) *Juma na Halima wa-li-bus-i-an-a mara tatu.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-KISS-APP-REC-FV times three
 “Juma and Halima kissed each other three times.”

As expected, the only interpretation of (42) is that there were three symmetric kisses – and this symmetric interpretation is the only one available for other reciprocally marked verbs in Swahili also. Additionally, note that as I am arguing that, as the Swahili monadic reciprocal construction is a derived symmetric lexeme, it should behave similarly to other symmetric lexemes with respect to sub-event countability, and this is the case. For example, *kiss* in English is intrinsically symmetric:

(43) *They kissed three times.*

How many kissing events were there? Three only.

Example (43) above, like its Swahili equivalent, can only have an irreducibly symmetric interpretation. This is the interpretation we expect from intrinsically symmetric lexemes as they may only denote atomic events.

4.3.3.2 COUNTABILITY OF SUB-EVENTS – NON IRREDUCIBLY SYMMETRIC VERBS

In (42) above, the likely interpretation is that the kisses were on the lips – and so it is understandable that there be only three kisses. This idea is one that Dimitriadis (2008) explores in his work, where he calls these types of simultaneous symmetric events “irreducibly symmetric”. That is that they:

- (a) express a binary relationship, but
- (b) have two arguments which have necessarily identical participation in any event described by the predicate.

(adapted from Dimitriadis 2008:378)

To illustrate this definition, consider the verbs “push” and “meet”. In (44) below, the transitive usage of “meet” is irreducibly symmetric – there is no way that Alfred can meet Ealhswith without Ealhswith also meeting Alfred. This kind of irreducible symmetry, which *requires* that the participants simultaneously participate in a single event, is called obligatory irreducible symmetry (Dimitriadis 2004:15):

(44) *Alfred met Ealhswith (#but Ealhswith didn't meet Alfred).*

Contrast this with (45), where we see that the verb “push” is asymmetric in its transitive use:

(45) *Sisyphus pushed the boulder (but the boulder didn't push Sisyphus).*

We can see why the Swahili reciprocal construction lends itself to irreducibly symmetric interpretations. As a derived symmetric lexeme, it only denotes atomic events, and an

irreducibly symmetric event interpretation of the verb preserves this atomicity. However, although the most likely interpretation of a monadic reciprocal construction is irreducibly symmetric, I have found that there are other possible interpretations that are also atomic in their conception – but which are not irreducibly symmetric. If monadic reciprocal constructions were required to be both irreducibly symmetric and atomic – we would not expect Swahili to allow the reciprocation of events that must necessarily be collections of asymmetric events. For example, consider the verb “visit” in (46) below:

- (46) *Juma a-li-m-tembel-a Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-3SGO-visit-FV Halima
 “Juma visited Halima.”

Should (46) be made symmetric, the visits cannot occur simultaneously, and so an irreducibly symmetric interpretation is forbidden. This means that, under the constraints put forward by Dimitriadis (2008), the reciprocal construction in (47) below should not be acceptable, whereas in fact it is both completely grammatical and acceptable:

- (47) *Juma na Halima wa-li-tembel-e-an-a mara tatu.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-visit-APP-REC-FV times three
 “Juma and Halima visited each other three times.”
 More accurately: “There were three periods, where in each period, Juma and Halima exchanged some number of visits.” In English this is perhaps best expressed as “Juma and Halima mutually visited thrice.”

I claim that, on closer inspection, the meaning of (47) is entirely compatible with an atomic (and therefore lexical) interpretation of the verb *walitembeleana*. The interpretation of (47) is that there were three periods of mutual visiting by Halima and Juma. To illustrate this point, consider the English verb “exchange” in (48) below:

- (48) *The parents exchanged gifts three times.*

In (48) we know that for each exchange, there must have been some indeterminate

number of gifts passed around, yet these sub-events (although logically present) are not accessible to the counting test. And so, as *walitembeleana* refers to a period of mutual visiting, the requirement that the event not have accessible sub-events via the counting test above is fulfilled. Note that the existence of these types of symmetric verbs is not predicted by Dimitriadis (2004), who predicts that all verbs with a dyadic alternate should be irreducibly symmetric. Similar verbs I have examined are *-pigana* – “hit each other”, which has two interpretations; an extended sense of mutual hitting and an irreducibly symmetric sense of “fight”. Similarly, *-shinda* – “defeat”, when reciprocated takes on the new irreducibly symmetric meaning of “struggle” rather than the logically impossible sense of “defeat each other”.¹⁶⁰

4.3.3.3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

By analysing the Swahili reciprocal construction as being formed from a symmetric lexeme, two predictions were made with respect to event countability:

1. That the construction be atomic in its conception (as opposed to reciprocal constructions formed via the application of an operator).
2. That the construction behave like other intrinsically symmetric lexemes.

Both of these predictions were borne out by the data above. As part of this investigation we also saw that at least some predicates in monadic reciprocal constructions need not be irreducibly symmetric. Additionally, as Siloni (2008) observes, we saw that monadic reciprocal constructions in different languages may behave differently with respect to event countability. For example, the French reciprocal construction in (24) allowed an interpretation that was non-atomic – meaning that it is not formed from a symmetric lexeme. This leads to the possibility that some languages may utilize more than one mechanism for the formation of the monadic reciprocal construction (see section 4.3.5 below.)

4.3.4 Lexical drift

As the monadic reciprocal construction is formed via a lexical strategy, we would expect that the reciprocated verb may undergo semantic drift – slowly diverging in

¹⁶⁰ See section 4.3.6 for further discussion.

meaning from the base from which it was formed. In many languages, this is just what is found. For instance, Seidl & Dimitriadis (2002:18) treat idiomatic meanings of monadic reciprocal constructions as being evidence that they are formed via a lexical strategy and give several examples of Swahili reciprocated verbs that have this property (e.g., *-pinda* meaning “bend or twist” and *-pindana*, “strive” etc.). This process is not just limited to Swahili either – it is evident in several other languages whose monadic reciprocal constructions are similar to the Swahili construction. For example, in Icelandic, the middle voice construction is formed by suffixing a verb with *-st* (itself an old form of the reflexive pronoun *sik*):

(49) Icelandic

- a. *Madonna sló Lady Gaga.*
 Madonna hit.3SG.PST Lady Gaga
- b. *Madonna og Lady Gaga slógu-st (í beinni)¹⁶¹*
 Madonna and Lady Gaga brawl.3PL.PST-MV live
 “Madonna and Lady Gaga brawled (live).”
 (*slógu-st* from *slógu*, the 3PL.PST form of *hit*.)

Note the change of gloss from *hit* to *brawl*. This reflects the change in meaning of the base verb (“hit”) has undergone when reciprocated – becoming “brawl”, not “hit each other”. This new meaning (“brawl”) has an extended sense of duration with no countable sub-events which conforms to the requirement that lexemes denote atomic events. These types of changes in meaning have been noted in the literature by Siloni (2008), Rákosi (2008), Dimitriadis (2008) (among others) for languages such as Hungarian, French and German. Further evidence for this semantic drift is that it is common to find examples where the morphologically formed dyadic reciprocal no longer has any connection to its base, or where the base form is entirely missing from the lexicon. See Anderson, (1990), for a comprehensive discussion of Icelandic middle voice verbs.

161 <http://www.dv.is/abendig/email/18361/>

4.3.5 Two possibilities for the formation of monadic reciprocal constructions

In section 4.2 of this chapter, I investigated two types of possible reciprocation strategies for the formation of intransitive monadic reciprocal constructions in Swahili. With respect to their application to Swahili, I found that neither Mchombo's analysis of the reciprocal construction in Chicheŵa, nor Alsina's (1996) analysis of the clitic reciprocal construction in Romance languages could be extended to the Swahili data. For example, neither provided an analysis of a syntactic process which would explain the formation of the dyadic reciprocal construction in Swahili. I have proposed a third analysis to account for the reciprocal construction in Swahili – one that makes different predictions from Alsina's regarding event countability, lexical drift and the availability of a dyadic reciprocal construction.

We have seen many similarly expressed verbally marked reciprocal constructions formed from very different reciprocation strategies. Given this variety, we might expect that the reciprocal construction in some languages can be optionally formed from one of two strategies. We saw this for the Icelandic reciprocal construction, where the phrase *hvor/hver annar* could be formed from either a pronominal or compositional reciprocation strategy. Similarly, I argue that the German clitic reciprocal construction can be formed from one of two different underlying reciprocation strategies.

The clitic reciprocal construction in German is made from the application of a clitic (non-pronominal) to a verb, with the resulting loss of an object. Consider (50) below – according to Dimitriadis, it has two possible interpretations:

(50) German (Dimitriadis 2004:4)

Johann und Maria schlugen sich.

Johann and Maria hit REC

“Johann and Maria hit/argued with each other.”

The first is simply a reciprocal interpretation of the asymmetric verb *hit*, and the other is idiomatic, meaning to *fight* or *argue*. These two interpretations behave quite differently with respect to the predictions above – only the “hit” interpretation has accessible sub-events:

- (51) *Johann und Maria schlugen sich fünfmal*
 Johann and Maria hit REC five times

In this situation there can be five or ten hits, but there may only ever be five arguments, and only the idiomatic sense of (51) may appear with the dyadic construction:

- (52) *Johann schlug sich mit Maria*
 Johann hit REC COM Maria
 *Johann and Maria hit each other
 “Johann fought/argued with Maria”

Note further that this idiomatic interpretation is both atomic and irreducibly symmetric, containing all the hallmarks of a symmetric lexeme. I believe that this evidence supports an analysis of the German monadic reciprocal construction as being formed from two strategies. The first is akin to Alsina's and is built upon an INWARD or RECIP operator being applied to an asymmetric base (see section 1.4.2). The second is the same mechanism I have described for Swahili (*i.e.*, theta-role synthesis), one built upon a symmetric lexeme with the resultant properties that such an analysis entails.

4.3.6 The Chicheŵa and Swahili reciprocal constructions

Chicheŵa and Swahili are both Bantu languages and so there is the possibility that their analyses might be similar. In terms of valency, the analysis put forward by Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) for Chicheŵa and my analysis for Swahili are equivalent – we both argue that the reciprocal constructions are intransitive at the level of f-structure. However, Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) pursue an analysis for Chicheŵa that applies a RECIP operator to an asymmetric predicate, while I argue that the Swahili reciprocal construction is formed via a strategy that turns an asymmetric lexeme into a symmetric one. The key reason for the RECIP analysis of the Chicheŵa reciprocal construction is to do with scope ambiguity. Recall that in section 4.2.5 we discussed the contrast in acceptability between (53) and (54):

- (53) *#Peter and John defeated each other in the final.*
 (54) *Peter and John said that they defeated each other in the final.*

This difference in acceptability was explained by the existence of two possible interpretations of (54), linked with whether the RECIP operator has wide or narrow scope. Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) found that the Chicheŵa equivalent to (54) is acceptable:

- (55) Chicheŵa (Dalrymple *et al.* 1994)
Anyamăta a-ku-gániz-a kutí a-na-gónj-éts-ăn-a.
 2boys SM-PRES-think-FV that 3PLS-PST-lose-CAUS-REC-FV
 “The boys think that they defeated each other.”

Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) interpreted the acceptability of (55) as evidence for a RECIP operator, because its likely interpretation (each boy thinks he defeated the other) requires a RECIP operator to take scope over the entire clause:

- (56) From Dalrymple *et al.* (1994)
 RECIP(BOYS, $\lambda x.\lambda y.$ THINK(x , DEFEAT(x,y)))

Interestingly, when testing similar sentences in Swahili, I found both similarities and differences. The Swahili verb *-shinda* has a range of meanings such as “defeat, beat, succeed, conquer, overcome, overpower” or “subdue”. When reciprocated, the resulting sentences are acceptable, but the reciprocated verb takes on a new meaning that is closer to “struggle, contend” or “fight”:

- (57) Swahili: Book of Judges – 11:25
Yeye a-li-shind-an-a na Israeli...
 he.3SG 3SGS-PST-defeat-REC-FV COM Israel
 “(did) he (ever) contend/strive with Israel...”

Note that the new meaning of this reciprocated verb is strikingly similar to what we might expect if a symmetric interpretation of *defeat* were required to be atomic in its conception. In the case of Swahili, then, the acceptability of sentences like (55) is not surprising – rather than requiring RECIP operator changing scope, the reciprocated verb itself changes its meaning. In other words, as the Swahili equivalent to “The boys defeated each other” is already grammatical (*walishindana* means something more like

struggle), the subsequent grammaticality of a sentence like (55) is expected. Based upon subtle meaning changes and reciprocal scope ambiguities, it would be difficult to definitively determine which analysis is correct, especially since different speakers could possibly employ either one of the analyses described above as their reciprocation strategy. However, there are sound reasons for thinking that the Swahili reciprocal construction is formed via a strategy which creates symmetric lexemes from asymmetric ones.

The first reason is that, unlike reciprocal constructions formed from the RECIP operator, the Swahili reciprocal construction is construed as being atomic (see section 4.3.3). This restriction is understood as resulting from the symmetric sense of the predicate being formed in the lexicon rather than syntax. The second reason is that, unlike reciprocal constructions formed via the application of the RECIP (or INWARD) operator, the Swahili reciprocal construction has a dyadic alternate that requires a symmetric lexeme as its base. Taken together, these properties align the Swahili reciprocal construction with intrinsically symmetric verbs (which share these properties) rather than reciprocal constructions formed via the application of a RECIP operator. As such, based on the data I have available, I will pursue a lexically based conception of symmetry for the Swahili reciprocal construction and note that the analysis put forward by Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) for Chicheŵa might not be applicable to all Bantu languages.

4.3.7 Analysis and formalism

The formalism I will use to reflect this strategy in LFG is straightforward; the application of the reciprocal morpheme *-an-* converts an asymmetric predicate into a symmetric one via theta-role synthesis where two of its theta-roles are joined together. This is represented at the level of a-structure using the following formalism:

$$(58) \quad P_{\text{asym}}\langle [\dots][\dots] \rangle \quad \rightarrow \quad P_{\text{sym}}\langle [[\dots][\dots]] \rangle$$

The outer square brackets of P_{sym} indicate that these two thematic roles are being synthesized and treated as one in the predicate. The 'sym' subscript indicates that the predicate P should now be understood as being symmetric. This symmetric predicate enters the syntax as a new lexeme and undergoes the typical mapping processes of LMT

without further modification. For example, consider *walitekenyana* – “tickle_{sym}” in (59) below:

- (59) *Juma na Halima wa-li-tekeny-an-a.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-tickle-REC-FV
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

The predicate is formed from the base verb *tekenya* – “tickle” via the application of the reciprocal morpheme *-an-* via theta-role synthesis:¹⁶²

- (60) *tekenya*<[P-A][P-P]> → *tekenyana_{sym}*<[[P-A][P-P]]>¹⁶³

Now, application of the LMT to the symmetric predicate reveals that the predicate selects only a subject grammatical function:

- (61) a-structure: *tekenyana_{sym}*<[[P-A][P-P]]>
 intrinsic classification -o
 default classification -r
bi-uniqueness SUBJ
 f-structure *tekenyana_{sym}*<(SUBJ)>

Thus the complete lexical entry for *walitekenyana* and f-structure for (59) is:¹⁶⁴

- (62) *walitekenyana, v*
 ↑PRED = tickle_{sym}<(SUBJ)>
 ↑TENSE = PST
 ↑SUBJ NUM = PL

[PRED	‘	tickle _{sym}	<	SUBJ	>’]
[SUBJ	[PRED	‘	Juma and Halima	’]
[TENSE	PST]]]]]

162 Given the productivity of this construction in Swahili, it appears that most verbs with two arguments may undergo theta-role synthesis.

163 Although both Rákosi (2008) and I use the same square brackets in our formalism – the analysis is different. Rákosi is indicating which arguments are being mapped to the same grammatical function. I am using them to indicate which arguments are been synthesized together – creating a symmetric predicate.

164 This f-structure has been simplified to only those features relevant to this discussion.

To reiterate the most important point of this analysis, the symmetric interpretation arises from the nature of the predicate being symmetric (in the same way that “exchange” has no need of a RECIP operator to explain its symmetry). There is no RECIP operator associated with the predicate, and this explains why the resultant sentences do not have accessible sub-events, and why they are biased towards an irreducibly symmetric interpretation.

There is one final note I would like to make regarding the formalism above. There is at least one other possible analysis, in which the synthesised arguments are simply reinterpreted as a single participant argument:

$$(63) \quad P_{\text{asym}}\langle[\dots][\dots]\rangle \rightarrow P_{\text{sym}}\langle[\dots]\rangle$$

In Swahili, I could find no way of formally distinguishing between these two analyses, and so for ease of explication I have used the former. However, in the cases of the verbally marked reciprocal constructions in Icelandic and Hungarian, there are instances of symmetric verbs containing reciprocal morphology but which have no transitive counterpart. For example, *nálgast* – “approach” or “draw near” in Icelandic is a regular symmetric verb, which participates in a dyadic construction. The *-st* ending is a middle voice marker which for other verbs can indicate a reciprocal construction (among other things). However, there is no verb *nálga* in Icelandic.¹⁶⁵ As speakers no longer productively link the reciprocated verb with a transitive counterpart, it is reasonable to analyse these verbs being formed from a single argument as they are entirely new lexemes that have drifted irrevocably far from their origins.

4.4 CONCLUSION

I have presented a new analysis of the monadic reciprocal construction for Swahili. It takes an asymmetric transitive predicate as being the basis for a new symmetric lexeme where the two arguments of the transitive verb have been synthesized together. Because the monadic construction forms a symmetric lexeme, this analysis predicts that the resultant verb be atomic in its event conception, and hence not have accessible sub-events. As a new lexeme, it should be prone to lexical drift – a feature common to these

¹⁶⁵ However, the verb *nálga* does exist in Old Norse, also meaning approach.

constructions. Finally, this new symmetric lexeme behaves like intrinsically symmetric predicates (*i.e.*, those that are symmetric but do not have overt reciprocal morphology such as *fight*, *chat* *etc.*), insofar as it has a dyadic alternation and a strong likelihood of having an irreducibly symmetric interpretation.

My analysis is broadly compatible with the distinction Siloni makes between lexical and syntactic reciprocal constructions. When used as a complement to the analysis Alsina (1996) puts forward for Romance languages, it also explains some unusual behaviour in the German monadic reciprocal construction in which idiomatic and non-idiomatic interpretations of these verbs behave differently in syntax with respect to having a dyadic alternation and sub-event countability.

Any one of the theta-role synthesis, argument unification, argument suppression or operator reciprocation strategies may underlie a verbally marked reciprocal construction. We have seen that these reciprocation strategies have different syntactic consequences for the wider syntactic behaviour of a reciprocal construction. Semantically, though, there are consequences as well. We can speculate that Alsina's argument unification reciprocation strategy will result in a construction that is polysemous between reciprocal and reflexive semantics – as both thematic roles are associated with a single grammatical function. Theta-role synthesis functions in a different way and is associated with distinctive semantic behaviour. This is a result of two thematic roles being synthesised in the creation of a new symmetric lexeme. Semantically, this results in a predicate whose interpretation is both symmetric and atomic – and one that does not have accessible sub-events for counting tests.

As both the monadic reciprocal construction in Swahili and intrinsically symmetric verbs have a dyadic alternation, I have offered this as evidence that monadic reciprocal construction be treated as being symmetric. However, in chapter 5, I will provide an account of the dyadic reciprocal construction that shows that this property is not just a coincidental feature of these constructions, but in fact requires a symmetric predicate as its basis.

5 SWAHILI – THE DYADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Central to my approach to the Swahili dyadic reciprocal constructions (and many other dyadic reciprocal constructions) is that they are formed from symmetric predicates. We have seen some that predicates (such as *chat*) are intrinsically symmetric – meaning that the symmetric relationship between the participants in the subject comes not from some sort of operation, but simply is part of the meaning of the verb. In chapter 4, I argued that the Swahili reciprocal construction was formed via the strategy of theta-role synthesis: a derivational process that creates symmetric lexemes. In this chapter, I propose a new and general mechanism whereby a comitative phrase in conjunction with a symmetric predicate (whether intrinsically symmetric or formed via theta-role synthesis) may be reanalysed as being a core argument of the predicate.

A comitative phrase is an argument-like phrase which adds an optional entity to an event. This entity is unusual because, unlike entities introduced by adjuncts, it typically takes part in the event by causally acting upon a patient (if available).¹⁶⁶ As such, comitative phrases have varying degrees of acceptability or felicity depending on the context in which they appear – they are particularly effective when attached to verbs which are likely to require a partner and to verbs where they can act upon a patient. This

¹⁶⁶ For further discussion, see section 5.3.1.1. Also, see causal chains in Croft (2012), section 6.3.2.

is exemplified in (1a) and (1b) below:

- (1) a. *She built the house with Eric.*
b. *She sighed with Eric.*

Symmetric predicates provide a rich environment for comitative phrases because they require at least two participants, and both participants are agent-like insofar as they participate in the event in a causal-sense (see section 5.4 below). I will argue that because these predicates require two participants (instead of implying them), speakers come to understand the comitative phrase as being a core argument of the predicate. I capture this phenomenon in LFG by building upon the work of two researchers, Rákosi (2008) and Webb (2008).

As a consequence of this analysis, I provide an account of the alternation of the above Swahili monadic and dyadic constructions with respect to their transitive base. In addition, in section 5.3, I show how this analysis in fact predicts several intriguing cross-linguistic properties of these constructions, including:

1. Why the dyadic construction is formed so similarly across such a diverse set of languages and, in particular, why the oblique argument is nearly always formed identically to the comitative construction.
2. Why these constructions have subtly different semantics with respect to the participation of the entities in the symmetric relation.
3. Why the clitic marked reciprocal construction in Romance languages, and periphrastic reciprocal construction in English (*i.e.*, *they saw each other*), are not able to form the dyadic reciprocal construction.
4. Why there exists in English a small set of so called “naturally symmetric” verbs (such as *dance*, *argue*, *fight etc.* – see Kemmer, 1993) which, despite not being marked with reciprocal morphology, still allow the formation of a dyadic construction.

5.2 EXISTING THEORIES OF DYADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTIONS

Our understanding of dyadic reciprocal constructions has developed in three main stages. Early work for the most part focussed on their relation to monadic reciprocal constructions. A significant number of these constructions are now uncontroversially considered to be syntactically intransitive, and their analysis has been described in chapter 4.2.1. However, it is only in the last decade or so that researchers began to appreciate the importance of the dyadic reciprocal construction's place in the understanding and analysis of verbally marked reciprocal constructions, and so the next step in our understanding of verbally marked reciprocal constructions is centred on the dyadic reciprocal construction. As data for these constructions was collected, it became apparent that some explanation would be required for the alternation between dyadic reciprocal constructions and their monadic counterparts.

Initially, researchers (*e.g.*, Mchombo & Ngunga, 1994; Siloni, 2001 – but not later work) investigated approaches that would preserve their analyses of the monadic reciprocal constructions. They did this by treating the oblique argument of the dyadic alternation as belonging to the subject (*e.g.*, as part of a discontinuous subject where one of the conjuncts has been extraposed in a comitative construction), or by being a verbal adjunct. Under these analyses, the monadic reciprocal construction is basic, and the dyadic reciprocal construction is formed from it without any fundamental changes to the reciprocated verb's argument structure and syntax. This means the reciprocal constructions in (2a) and (2b) are analysed in the same way – because Halima in (2b) is still analysed as being in (or connected to) the subject grammatical function:

(2) Monadic reciprocal construction

- a. *Juma na Halima wa-li-tekeny-an-a.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-tickle-REC-FV
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

Dyadic reciprocal construction

- b. *Juma a-li-tekeny-an-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-tickle-REC-FV COM Halima
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

However, as research continued, it started to appear doubtful that dyadic reciprocal constructions could be understood as being syntactically neutral alternations of their monadic counterparts (although in specific languages, this may be the case – see the discussion of the Hungarian reciprocal construction in section 5.4.2 below). The reason for this was that it became clear that for many languages, the dyadic reciprocal construction must be formed from two arguments – both represented in a-structure and related to two grammatical functions in f-structure. For example, Dimitriadis (2004) argues from semantic grounds that the subject and oblique grammatical functions are separate syntactic and semantic arguments because they entail a more expressive reciprocal semantics.¹⁶⁷ This analysis leads to the possibility that the argument structure of the dyadic reciprocal construction is richer than its monadic equivalent – an insight that is central to Rákosi's (2008) analysis of the Hungarian verbal reciprocal constructions. However, this treatment of the dyadic reciprocal construction, as being “semantically more expressive” than its monadic counterpart, takes us to some surprising places. Both Dimitriadis (2004, 2008) and Rákosi (2008) treat the dyadic construction as basic, with the monadic construction being formed from it. Rákosi goes even further, treating the verb in the dyadic reciprocal construction as a primitive lexeme (*i.e.*, as existing in the lexicon in its own right and not being derived from another lexeme). His analysis clearly cannot be applied to Bantu languages, where the dyadic and monadic reciprocal constructions are productively formed from transitive verbs (because the dyadic construction cannot be considered basic if it is derived via some process from a transitive verb).

In the most recent work on verbal reciprocals, researchers have focussed on the relations between the two or three of the transitive, monadic and dyadic constructions (illustrated by the German sentences below):¹⁶⁸

167 I discuss his arguments below, and although I take issue with some of them, I support his contention that the dyadic reciprocal construction has two arguments in a-structure. See discussion in section 5.2.

168 *Sich* is analysed to be a clitic attaching to the verb rather than a separate phrase by Siloni (2002) – although see discussion in König and Kokutani (2006).

(3) German (Dimitriadis, 2004)

Basic Transitive Use:

a. *Johann schlug Maria.*

John hit Maria

“John hit Maria”

Monadic Reciprocal Construction:

b. *Johann und Maria schlugen sich*

John and Maria hit REC

“John and Maria hit each other”

or “John and Maria fought”

Dyadic Reciprocal Construction:

c. *Johann schlug sich mit Maria*

John hit REC COM Maria

“John fought with Maria”

The asymmetric interpretation of *schlug* in (3a) is the most basic sense of the verb, *x hit y*. In the monadic reciprocal construction in (3b) Dimitriadis (2004) notes that there are two possible meanings: an irreducibly symmetric sense, where both participants are engaging in a single event with indistinct sub-events (the second reading in (3b) above), and another sense in which the symmetry of situation is understood to be a collection of asymmetric sub-events (the first reading). With respect to the collection of asymmetric sub-events, it is only when these events are considered as a set that we can consider the event as a whole to be symmetric. For example, if Maria hit John on the shoulder, and John hit Maria on the hand, then this event could be described using the monadic reciprocal construction in (3b) above. Under the irreducibly symmetric sense, the verb has undergone a meaning change to mean something like fight/argue. In this idiomatic sense, the two participants equally engage in the same event. Note that in the dyadic construction of (3c), Dimitriadis claims that only the irreducibly symmetric sense is available.

Using this concept of “irreducible symmetry”, Dimitriadis (2004, 2008) for the most part explores the semantic relationship between the monadic and dyadic reciprocal

constructions (simple and discontinuous reciprocal constructions in his terminology). Rákosi (2008) also studies the relation between these two constructions by positing the dyadic reciprocal construction as being a basic lexeme – this allows him to analyse the monadic reciprocal construction as being derived from the dyadic construction (an arguably correct analysis synchronically for Hungarian, but one that provides no insight into the relationship of these reciprocated verbs with their transitive counterparts). Finally, Siloni (2011, 2008, 2002) and Rienhart and Siloni (2005) consider the relationship between the two reciprocal constructions as stemming from a difference in whether reciprocals are formed in the syntax or in the lexicon (a contrast that can be loosely thought of as being equivalent to the difference between f- and a-structure in LFG). As we will see, this distinction is one that aligns closely to Dimitriadis' semantic notion of irreducible symmetry. These researchers (among others listed below) all bring different ideas and theoretical approaches to their studies of these constructions – and for the most part, their ideas are broadly compatible. In the sections below I outline the strengths and weakness of these theories, and how they relate, before presenting my own analysis in section 5.4 which provides a more general understanding of verbally marked reciprocal constructions that is able to accommodate this data.

5.2.1 Theories positing that the monadic construction is formed from a more basic dyadic construction

Both Rákosi (2008) and Dimitriadis (2004, 2008) argue that the monadic reciprocal construction is formed from a dyadic base. I previously discussed Rákosi's work in chapter 4.2 – in particular noting that it cannot be usefully applied to the Swahili data. Dimitriadis takes a different approach to Rákosi and has identified *irreducible symmetry* as the key concept that relates certain dyadic reciprocal constructions with their monadic counterparts. Using this concept in conjunction with “semantic expressiveness” (see section 5.2.1.4 below), he argues that the monadic reciprocal construction must be formed from the dyadic construction. His proposal is that:

- (4) Dimitriadis (2004:34)¹⁶⁹
- a) The function of the core reciprocalization operation is to create an irreducibly symmetric predicate. The roles of two participants in an event

169 My comments in square brackets.

become necessarily identical, but the participants remain distinct.

- b) Non-discontinuous (“simple”) [*i.e.*, monadic] reciprocals are derived by application of an additional operation, which causes the two semantic arguments of the reciprocal to be identified.

In the terminology I have used, Dimitriadis is proposing that, (a), the basic lexeme is dyadic with the additional requirement that both participants in that construction have identical, but distinct, participation in the relation, and (b), that the monadic construction is formed from the dyadic construction. This finding is at odds with my own research, so in this section I am going to discuss two aspects of his work, both with respect to Swahili, but also more generally. These aspects are: that irreducible symmetry is the core function of reciprocation, and the claim that the dyadic reciprocal construction is more basic than its monadic equivalent. I will argue that, although irreducible symmetry is strongly associated with the monadic/dyadic reciprocal alternations in European languages, it is not necessarily entailed by a dyadic construction – that in fact one of the motivations of the dyadic construction may be to background or lessen the degree of agency of one of the participants in the relation. In section 5.2.1.4 I argue that, from a diachronic perspective, it seems unlikely that the monadic reciprocal construction was formed from a dyadic base – although such an analysis may be justified synchronically for some languages (such as Hungarian – see section 5.4.2).

5.2.1.1 IRREDUCIBLE SYMMETRY

What exactly is irreducible symmetry, and why does Dimitriadis believe it so important to our understanding of the relationship between monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions? Dimitriadis (2008:378) defines a predicate as being irreducibly symmetric if:

- (5) a. it expresses a binary relationship, but
- b. its two arguments have necessarily identical participation in any event described by the predicate.

To illustrate this definition, consider the verbs “push” and “meet”. In (6) below, the

transitive usage of “meet” is irreducibly symmetric – there is no way that Alfred can meet Ealhswith without Ealhswith also meeting Alfred. This kind of irreducible symmetry which *requires* that the participants simultaneously participate in a single event is called obligatory irreducible symmetry (Dimitriadis, 2004:15):

(6) *Alfred met Ealhswith (#but Ealhswith didn't meet Alfred).*

Contrast this with (7) where we see that the verb “push” is asymmetric – in its transitive use Sisyphus pushes the boulder, but the boulder does not push Sisyphus:

(7) *Sisyphus pushed the boulder (but the boulder didn't push Sisyphus).*

Within the semantic domain of symmetry there is another type of symmetry which can be thought of as a collection of asymmetric events. For example in (8) below, the most likely interpretation is that two asymmetric events have occurred:

(8) *Arthur and Lancelot visited each other.*

The situation described in (8) is not irreducibly symmetric because it is a collection of two asymmetric events, although it is nevertheless still a symmetric situation. Finally, some verbs are polysemous with respect to the kind of symmetry they encode. For example, Dimitriadis (2004:15) discusses the verb *kiss* where its transitive usage can be thought of as being irreducibly symmetric or asymmetric. Consider (9) below.¹⁷⁰

(9) *It's finally happened! Last night I saw Alfred kissing Ealhswith!*

Depending on the context, the meaning of *kiss* when used transitively can be either irreducibly symmetric (the most likely meaning of (9) above) or asymmetric in the instance of a chaste kiss on the forehead for example. Note that the symmetric meaning of *kiss* above is a property of the predicate, rather than some type of pragmatic imprecision. This can be seen by considering (10) below, where the symmetric

¹⁷⁰ I chose these examples because I think they best illustrate his discussion. For more details see Dimitriadis (2004:15).

interpretation is never available:

(10) *It's finally happened! Last night I saw Arthur hitting Lancelot!*

As the examples above show, irreducible symmetry need not be linked to reciprocal morphology – nor even the dyadic construction. Another example in English is “touch” – this verb has an irreducibly symmetric interpretation but does not contain reciprocal morphology nor participate in the dyadic construction:¹⁷¹

(11) *John and Mary touched* (but not **John touched with Mary*).¹⁷²

Even the verb “to see” in Shakespearian English had an irreducibly symmetric interpretation (see Potter, 1953, 34:252-257; cited in Evans, 2008:38):

(12) Henry VIII, I, i. 1-2
*Good morrow, and well met. How have ye done
Since last we saw in France.*

Given that irreducible symmetry does not have to co-occur with reciprocal morphology, it is my view that it is a property of some predicates and is not entailed by reciprocity (although clearly, they are related domains). However, Dimitriadis uses the concept of irreducible symmetry to explore the semantics of monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions, and makes the following claims:

- (i) that the entities in a dyadic reciprocal construction must participate in an irreducibly symmetric relation (Dimitriadis, 2004:20).
- (ii) that the entities in the dyadic reciprocal construction are semantically distinct (with respect to partitioning) and syntactically distinct (Dimitriadis, 2004:5,41).

171 Note that the verb “marry” is seemingly in the same category, but it does have a dyadic alternate using the preposition “to”: They are married / she is married to him.

172 The transitive form (“John touched Mary”) would usually be interpreted as being an asymmetric event also.

- (iii) that the dyadic reciprocal construction is basic insofar as the monadic reciprocal construction is formed from it (Dimitriadis, 2004:1,34).

The first claim states that unlike, typical reciprocal constructions which allow a symmetric interpretation to be formed from a collection of asymmetric events, the participants in a dyadic reciprocal construction must both share the same role in a single event (and presumably also receive the same thematic role). This point has two parts: that the entities participate in a single event, and that they have the same role in that event. I discuss these claims in section 5.2.1.2 below.

Having argued that the two terms in the dyadic reciprocal construction have exactly the same relationship to the predicate, his second claim is that in another sense they must be semantically distinct. This claim is based on the observation that the two terms in the dyadic reciprocal construction partition participants differently from monadic reciprocal constructions. On this point, I am in close agreement with Dimitriadis, and his observation is well supported cross-linguistically (see section 5.2.1.3 below for further discussion).

The final claim, that the dyadic reciprocal construction is basic and that the monadic construction is formed from it, is ultimately built upon the second claim above regarding the partitioning of participants. His idea is that, in terms of partitioning, the situation described by a dyadic reciprocal construction cannot be generalised to characterise the situation described by a monadic reciprocal construction (see section 5.2.1.4). The view I take for the dyadic construction in Swahili (and for other languages which have the monadic/dyadic reciprocal alternation) is contrary to Dimitriadis (2004, 2008) and Rákosi (2008) – I will argue that the dyadic reciprocal construction is formed from the monadic construction (see section 5.4).

Having outlined Dimitriadis' claims and terminology, in the following sections I will discuss each of these claims in turn. Contra Dimitriadis, I conclude that the concept of irreducible symmetry cannot be used to understand the alternation between monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions. However, Dimitriadis' point that irreducibly symmetric events are strongly associated with monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions needs to be addressed (see below).

5.2.1.2 THAT THE ENTITIES IN A DYADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION MUST PARTICIPATE IN AN IRREDUCIBLY SYMMETRIC RELATION.

I start with an objection to the claim Dimitriadis makes that the entities in a dyadic reciprocal construction must obligatorily participate in an irreducibly symmetric relation. Consider the verb *collide* – an irreducibly symmetric predicate:

- (13) a. *The car collided with the tree.*
 b. *#The car and the tree collided.*
 c. *##The tree collided with the car.*

It has been noted by many authors (*e.g.*, Dowty, 1991; Gleitman *et al.* 1996; Rákosi, 2008), including Dimitriadis himself, that sentences like (13 b,c) potentially throw doubt upon any analysis in which the entities in the subject grammatical function (“the car” in (13a)) and oblique grammatical function (“the tree” in (13a)) must participate identically in the predicate. To put it simply, if both participants were receiving identical thematic roles from the predicate, we would expect that the participants could be swapped in (13a) with little or no change in meaning – and clearly that is not the case (*c.f.*, 13c).

Dimitriadis argues that the differences in meaning between (13a) and (13c) are not caused by the two arguments being assigned different thematic roles, but because of “structural differences between the two argument positions” (Dimitriadis, 2004:37). The evidence he uses to support this view comes from Gleitman *et al.* (1996) who argue that, even for predicates which must logically assign the same thematic roles to two participants, there are still differences in interpretation which seem dependent upon structural factors. For example, consider the predicate “be similar to” in (14) below:¹⁷³

- (14) From Dimitriadis (2004), based upon examples from Gleitman *et al.* (1996)
 a. *China is similar to North Korea.*
 b. *North Korea is similar to China.*

Here, the “ground” (the oblique argument) is the source of comparison, and the figure (the subject) is compared to it. For example, in (14b) North Korea might be similar to

173 Given the different domains of grammar and logic, I can see no *a priori* reason why a predicate such as “be similar to” or even “be the same as” need assign identical thematic roles to both arguments.

China insofar as, like China, it has a communist government.

Although structural effects (and their relation to figure and ground) might play some role in the contrast in meaning between two structurally distinct arguments, the change in acceptability of irreducibly symmetric verbs like *collide* above is sensitive to agency – *i.e.*, it is a thematic distinction. Consider again the contrast in meaning between (13a) and (13c). Dowty (1991) points out that changes in context change the admissibility of the sentences. For example, imagine the following contexts: the tree has been torn from the ground by a hurricane and slams into a stationary car, or, the tree is animate (such as in a children's story) and while running through the forest, trips over an unseen car. In these contexts, (13c) is now the appropriate description of the event. Examining the contexts in more detail we see that the acceptability of (13c) is dependent upon the subject NP moving and/or being animate. These are both properties that Dowty argues contribute to the characterisation of an agent proto-role (Dowty, 1991:572). As such, my contention is that in (13a) “the car” is agentive whereas “the tree” is not, and so I think that the two arguments in a dyadic reciprocal construction receive different thematic roles. In turn, this means that they cannot be understood as having (necessarily) identical participation in the event. This is also the view taken by Rákosi (2008) in his analysis of the dyadic and monadic reciprocal constructions in Hungarian. He provides additional evidence that the two grammatical functions do not have to participate in the relation in the same way – namely that the symmetry of some “irreducibly symmetric events” can be cancelled:

(15) Hungarian (Rákosi, 2008:423)

Én num veszeked-t-em János-sal ő veszeked-ett vel-em.

I not quarrel-PST-1SG John-COM he quarrel-PST COM-1SG

“I was not quarrelling with John, he was quarrelling with me.”

Initially, reliance on his example could seem overly pedantic, but on further inspection it is shown to have some cross-linguistic validity – this same pattern is also seen in other languages which allow the formation of the dyadic reciprocal construction (such as Swahili (see example (75) and discussion), Icelandic and English:

(16) Icelandic

Pétur reif-st við Orlandó, en Orlandó reif-st ekki við Pétur.
 Peter quarrel-MV COM Orlando, but Orlando quarrel-MV not COM Peter
 “Peter quarrelled with Orlando, but Orlando didn't quarrel with Peter.”

That the symmetry of the dyadic constructions in these languages can be cancelled means that unlike their monadic equivalents, the symmetry is implied, not entailed. In turn, this means that comitative cannot be seen as simply being part of the subject. Finally, and as Dimitriadis readily acknowledges, the dyadic reciprocal construction need not be irreducibly symmetric in Bantu languages (Dimitriadis, 2004:24).

I reject Dimitriadis' claim that both participants in dyadic reciprocal construction must participate in an irreducibly symmetric relation. This is for two reasons: first, because the symmetry of the event is only implied and not entailed, and second, because the two grammatical functions behave differently with respect to agency – the subject grammatical function is required to be more agent-like than the oblique, strongly suggesting that the participants engage in the event differently. These different participations are listed under (17) below. Although this sentence could be used to describe two people tickling each other, a more fitting description of the situation is that Juma is actively engaged in the tickling (he planned it, initiated it and does most of the tickling), whereas Halima is only a reluctant participant in the event:

(17) Swahili

*Juma a-na-tekeny-an-a na Halima.*¹⁷⁴
 Juma 3SGS-PRES-tickle-REC-FV COM Halima
 “Juma and Halima: there is tickling between them.”
 “Juma and Halima: there is tickling in the air.”
 “Juma and Halima: tickling is going on.”

However, it is undeniable that irreducible symmetry is closely associated with the dyadic reciprocal construction. Recall chapter 4.3.3 and the discussion of atomic events. My analysis of the monadic reciprocal construction in Swahili is that the reciprocated predicate is a derived symmetric lexeme and so has the properties of other lexemes –

¹⁷⁴ To be sure of the assertion I make here, a large corpus based study would need to be undertaken.

such as the requirement that the event described be atomic. We saw previously that this requirement can be fulfilled in various ways (for example, the Swahili verb *-tembeleana* – “mutually visit”), but by far the most common way is to conceive of the event as being irreducibly symmetric – that is, that the entities in the symmetric event participate in the event in the same way at the same time. The dyadic alternation of the monadic construction still requires that the entities engage in an atomic event, but relaxes the requirement that they participate in the event in the same way.

5.2.1.3 THAT THE ENTITIES IN THE DYADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION ARE SEMANTICALLY DISTINCT (WITH RESPECT TO PARTITIONING) AND SYNTACTICALLY DISTINCT.

I now turn to Dimitriadis' claim that the entities in the dyadic reciprocal construction are semantically and syntactically distinct. Syntactically, what is at issue is how to consider the comitative phrase – whether as an adjunct, as part of the subject NP (albeit in some sort of discontinuous form), or whether it should be considered as a separate grammatical function associated with an argument. In other words, should both the subject NP and PP in (18) below be considered as arguments required by the predicate, or only the subject NP?

(18) Swahili

Juma a-li-pig-an-a na Halima.

Juma 3SGS-PST-hit-REC-FV COM Halima

“Juma and Halima were hitting each other.”

To complicate matters, in many languages (including Swahili) the comitative preposition is polysemous with a coordinator.¹⁷⁵ Dimitriadis (2004) provides overwhelming evidence for the comitative phrase to be considered as an oblique grammatical function (that is, a grammatical function associated with a verbal argument – a phrase that is distinct from the subject NP syntactically, and one that is linked to a distinct argument in a-structure).

He first dismisses the adjunct analysis by showing that the semantics of the dyadic reciprocal constructions are more specific than that of a typical comitative adjunct (Dimitriadis 2004:26). For example, he gives the sentences below and examines the

175 Such polysemy is not coincidental – Stassen (2000) argues that there is a cross-linguistic tendency for comitative markers to take on the role of basic coordinators.

contrast in meaning between them:

(19) Dimitriadis (2004:26)

- a. *John and Mary rode to the store together.*
- b. *John rode to the store with Mary.*

In (19a), by whatever means John rode to the store, Mary did as well. However, as (19b) shows, the entity in a typical comitative adjunct does not have this requirement – Mary could equally have run alongside John.¹⁷⁶ Consider the contrast with dyadic reciprocal constructions. Here the participant introduced by the comitative phrase is much more closely linked to the predicate and their participation is usually understood as being similar to that of the entity introduced by the subject. For example, in (20) below, Halima must also meet Juma:

(20) Swahili

Juma a-li-kut-an-a na Halima.

Juma 3SGS-PST-meet-REC-FV COM Halima

“Juma met with Halima.”

That the comitative phrase is an argument can also be seen by the fact that it is obligatory. (20) above is ungrammatical without the PP, *prima facie* evidence for the PP being an argument required by the verb.

Additionally, Dimitriadis draws on early work by Rákosi (2003), who shows a further distinction between regular comitative adjuncts and the comitative phrase associated with dyadic reciprocal constructions in Hungarian. Whereas only one comitative adjunct may appear in a clause (see (21a) below), the comitative phrase of a dyadic reciprocal construction and a regular comitative adjunct can co-occur:

(21) Hungarian – Two comitative adjuncts (Rákosi 2003:3)

- a. **Péter-rel (együtt) ritkán fut-ott-am Kati-val.*

Peter-COM together rarely run-PST-1SG Kate-COM

*“I rarely ran with Kate with Peter.”

¹⁷⁶ Although see additional discussion in section 5.3.1.1.

Comitative adjunct and comitative argument

- b. *Péter-rel (együtt) ritkán veszeked-t-em Kati-val.*
 Peter-COM together rarely quarrel-PST-1SG Kate-COM
 “I rarely quarrelled with Kate, together with Peter.”

The same contrast is illustrated in English below, where two comitative phrases may be stacked only if one is an argument (22b):¹⁷⁷

- (22) a. **Sarah caught a film with Erin with Rachel.*
 b. *On the case side, I met with my lawyer with my father.*¹⁷⁸

Dimitriadis (2004:27) also examines arguments for and against treating the comitative argument in dyadic reciprocal construction as being part of a discontinuous subject. Such a discussion is required because this analysis would explain why the entity in the comitative phrase's activity is so similar to that of the subject's. For example, if Halima in (20) were simply part of a discontinuous subject, then we can understand why her participation is the same as Juma's.

The initial proponents of this analysis are Mchombo & Ngunga (1994), who were investigating Ciyao (a Bantu language related to Swahili). Their analysis is motivated by the lack of default noun class for coordinated NPs formed from nouns of different declinations. As a result, there is a problem with verbal agreement:

- (23) Ciyao (Mchombo and Ngunga, 1994)
 **Diguluve ní n'óombe ?-kú-wúlág-an-a.*
 5-pig and 9-cow ?-PRES-kill-REC-FV
 “The pig and cow killed each other.”

They argue that the extra position made available in the dyadic construction solves this morphological tangle:

177 Note that the adverb “along” can be used to test whether a comitative phrase is acting as an argument or adjunct: *Pete and I went driving (along) with Al.* vs *I met (*along) with Al.*

178 <http://weeklyinjuryreport.blogspot.com.au/2005/01/this-past-week-was-really-bad.html>

- (24) Ciyao (Mchombo and Ngunga 1994)
Diguluve di-kú-wúlág-an-a ní n'óombe.
 5-pig 5S-PRES-kill-REC-FV COM 9-cow
 “The pig and cow killed each other.”

Dimitriadis (2004) points out that, although the dyadic construction is undeniably useful for solving this problem, it need not be its primary function. Furthermore, without further analysis, the Ciyao data above could be interpreted as supporting the argument that the subject and the comitative phrase are distinct grammatical functions, because the verbal agreement marker in (24) is only agreeing with the subject NP.

To support the view that comitative phrase is semantically distinct from the subject NP, Dimitriadis examines causativisation in Swahili. The causative construction in Swahili is formed via the application of a morpheme to a verb. For example:

- (25) Swahili (Comrie, 1976)¹⁷⁹
- a. *Msichana a-li-(u-)fungu-a mlango.*
 girl 3SGS-PST-O-open-FV door
 “The girl opened the door.”
- b. *Mwalimu a-li-m-fungu-zish-a msichana mlango.*
 Teacher 3SGS-PST-O-open-CAUS-FV girl door
 “The teacher made the girl open the door”

Dimitriadis gives an illuminating example of a causativisation construction applied to a dyadic reciprocal construction:

- (26) Swahili (Dimitriadis, 2004:28)
- a. *Ni-li-shind-an-a na Mike Tyson.*
 S-PST-defeat-REC-FV COM Mike Tyson
 “I competed/struggled with Mike Tyson.”

179 Comrie (1976) analyses the final vowel as an indicative marker – an analysis not followed here.

- b. *A-li-ni-shind-an-ish-a na Mike Tyson.*
 S-PST-O-defeat-REC-CAUS-FV COM Mike Tyson
 “He made me compete/struggle with Mike Tyson.”

Note that (26b) cannot mean “He made me and Mike Tyson compete” – that is to say, only the subject NP of the verb is causativized, not the participant in the comitative phrase as well. This demonstrates that, for causative constructions at least, the comitative phrase in Swahili is certainly distinct from the subject NP.

Dimitriadis argues persuasively that the comitative phrase in a dyadic reciprocal construction is distinct from the subject NP. He rejects the adjunct analysis on semantic grounds, and then on syntactic grounds based on work by Rákosi (1993) and causativization in Swahili. Based on his analysis, as well as the semantic arguments I put forward in chapter 4.1, I agree with his conclusion that, for Swahili as well as for many other languages, the comitative phrase in a dyadic reciprocal construction can be shown to behave as an argument – one that is distinct from the subject grammatical function.

5.2.1.4 THAT THE MONADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION IS FORMED FROM THE DYADIC CONSTRUCTION
 Dimitriadis (2008, 2004) makes the claim that the monadic reciprocal construction is formed from a more basic dyadic construction. Deciding which construction is more basic is central to any analysis of verbally marked reciprocal constructions, and so I will discuss his work in some detail before ultimately rejecting its application to Swahili.

For semantic reasons, Dimitriadis believes that the monadic reciprocal construction is formed from its dyadic equivalent. The reasons he gives for this are that the events described by the dyadic reciprocal are more “specific” and “expressive” (Dimitriadis, 2004:4) than their monadic counterparts. This observation revolves around how the participants are packaged in a dyadic construction which Dimitriadis illustrates using Greek, although this behaviour is remarkably consistent in other languages that allow the formation of the dyadic reciprocal construction:

- (27) Greek (Dimitriadis, 2004:4)
 a. *O Yanis, o Nikos kje I Maria tsakothikan.*
 the John the Nick and the Maria argued.REC
 “John, Nick and Maria argued.”

- b. *O Yanis kje o Nikos tsakothikan me ti Maria.*
 the John and the Nick argued.REC COM the Maria
 “John and Nick argued with Maria”

In both Greek and English, there is a distinction in meaning between these two sentences. In (27a) there are at least two meanings possible. It is possible that John and Nick acted as a group, arguing with Maria, or alternatively, each one of them might have argued with the others. However, in (27b) there is only one possible meaning – the former one where John and Nick argue with Maria (ignoring the possibility in which Nick argues with Maria, and then John argues with Maria).¹⁸⁰

(27a) *J and N and M argued.* (27b) *J and N argued with M.*

<p>can mean: $argue(\{J,N\},M)$ or $argue(J,\{N,M\})$ or $argue(J,N) \wedge argue(J,M) \wedge$ $argue(M,N)$ <i>etc.</i></p>	<p>can mean only: $argue(\{J,N\},M)$¹⁸¹</p>
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In this sense, the meaning of (27b) is more specific than that of (27a) – in other words, the meaning of (27b) is not “semantically reducible” to that of (27a), because it only encodes one potential set of relations, whereas (27a) can describe more.

Dimitriadis (2004:34) takes the position that, because the dyadic reciprocal construction is more semantically specific than the monadic construction, the monadic construction must be formed from it. I believe this data can be explained by another process that allows meanings to change. For example, one of the accepted types of semantic change is known as “semantic narrowing” where the meaning of a lexeme can change to be more specific. Bloomfield (1933:426) illustrates this process using *mete* – “food” in Old English which narrows its meaning to be just “edible flesh” as it is used

180 Note that these English examples reflect the same differences in semantics as seen in languages with the monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions.

181 For the purposes of best illustrating Dimitriadis' argument, I will ignore meanings such as $argue(J,M) \wedge argue(N,M)$ and senses where J and N argue with M, but M doesn't argue with J and N.

today. Semantic narrowing is based upon a change in meaning of a lexeme – and not a construction. So to argue that this type of semantic change causes the difference in meaning between (27a) and (27b) requires that there be two different lexemes, one associated with the monadic construction and one associated with the dyadic construction. This is, in fact, the analysis I present for monadic/dyadic alternation in section 5.4, where I argue that many other features of the dyadic lexeme (such as its propensity to gain idiomatic interpretations) comes about precisely because it is a lexeme distinct from its monadic counterpart (see section 5.4.1 for further discussion).

An additional difficulty with Dimitriadis' analysis lies in the relative productivity of monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions. In all the languages I have examined, the dyadic reciprocal construction is either less productive or as productive, but never more productive, than its monadic counterpart. This supports the view that the dyadic construction is formed from the monadic construction. If we were to follow Dimitriadis' (and Rákosi's) analysis, then there must be two mechanisms to form the monadic reciprocal construction – one that allows their formation from a dyadic base, and another to allow for their formation more generally when the dyadic base is not available. I think this is an unlikely historical path for the formation of monadic reciprocal constructions – a simpler and more natural analysis would be either that both the monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions are formed from a transitive base, or, as I will argue below for Swahili, that the dyadic reciprocal construction is formed from its monadic equivalent.

5.2.1.5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Dimitriadis has identified “irreducible symmetry” as a key feature associated with the dyadic reciprocal construction. Based on the semantics of this notion, he argues that the entities associated with the subject and oblique grammatical functions are selected by the verb in their own right (*i.e.*, they are both arguments of the verb, and the comitative phrase is not part of an extra-posed subject). I agree with this analysis, although ultimately I believe that his argument that these two grammatical functions participate in the relation identically is not supported by the data on two grounds; the symmetry of these events can often be cancelled and semantic tests indicate that the subject grammatical function is more agent-like than the oblique.

Building upon the concept of semantic expressivity, Dimitriadis argues that the

dyadic reciprocal construction must be basic (meaning that the monadic construction is formed from it). I reject this argument, because there is a precedent of semantic narrowing (which could explain the process whereby the semantics associated with the monadic construction are narrowed when in a dyadic construction), but also because it appears to be historically unlikely – the monadic reciprocal construction being more productive than the dyadic construction. Nevertheless, Dimitriadis' point about how these two constructions differently package their participants in symmetric events is well made – and any analysis that seeks to understand how these constructions are related will need to address the question of how the meaning of the dyadic reciprocal construction can have a more specialised sense than its monadic counterpart (see section 5.4.1 below). Having examined (and rejected) analyses which posit that the monadic reciprocal construction is formed from the dyadic base, I will now discuss an alternative analysis put forward by Siloni (2011).

5.2.2 Siloni's analysis of dyadic reciprocal verbs

The approach Siloni (2011) takes towards the analysis of the dyadic construction differs from that of both Rákosi and Dimitriadis. Like the analysis I offer here, she argues that a symmetrical lexeme is required as the basis for the dyadic construction, and that this lexeme may be intrinsically symmetric (such as is the case for verbs like *exchange* or *fight*), or formed via the addition of a morpheme – with the provision that this occurs in the lexicon, before entering syntax. Her conception of the lexicon is such that “plural events are not part of the lexicon's inventory” (Siloni 2011:14). This is based on work by Carlson (1998) on the individuation of events, and means that predicates (such as *hit*, *exchange*, *etc.*), as basic lexical entries, can only describe singular events. To indicate a plurality of events, some sort of syntactic operation is required. For example, consider the two uses of the verb *kiss* in (28) below. In (28a), with an intransitive form of *kiss*, there can only be one kiss, whereas in (28b) with the transitive version of the verb *kiss*, there can be two:¹⁸²

- (28) a. *They kissed.*
 (e.g., a symmetric kiss on the lips – one kiss, or one session of kissing only)

¹⁸² *c.f.*, chapter 4.3.3.1 – Differing conceptions of the formation of symmetry.

- b. *They kissed each other.*
 (e.g., potentially, a ceremonial exchange of kisses allowing for an interpretation where there were two kisses.)

This contrast is explained by the two different forms of *kiss*. The intransitive form of *kiss* is intrinsically (and irreducibly) symmetric – it is a predicate whose lexical form denotes a symmetric situation.¹⁸³ Like other basic lexemes, unless pluralised in syntax, it is singular in nature. So, in (28a), there is only a single kiss. In (28b), however, we see the asymmetric transitive form of *kiss* (such as “the mother kissed her child”). The application of the RECIP operator to this asymmetric sense of *kiss* pluralises it, allowing for an interpretation where there were two asymmetric kisses. The Swahili monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions pattern with the intrinsically symmetric verbs, and Siloni interprets this data as demonstrating that monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions are formed in the lexicon because they can denote only singular events.

Siloni analyses the monadic construction as being formed via two thematic roles being assigned to one argument (in turn linked to the subject). Her analysis of the dyadic construction is the same as the monadic, but that the additional comitative phrase is associated with an argument that “lacks thematic content”. This results in two lexical entries for a reciprocal verb:

- (29) From Siloni (2011:45)
- a. Monadic: $V_{\text{SYM}} [\text{Ag-Th}]$
 - b. Dyadic: $V'_{\text{SYM}}[\text{Ag-Th}], [\emptyset\text{-WITH}]$

Like Rákosi, she discusses at length the implications of an argument lacking thematic content (by which she means, an argument not associated with a thematic role). She follows Reinhart (2002) in assuming that theta-roles are composed of two atomic features: $\pm c$ – a causal feature and $\pm m$ – a mental state feature. These features may be valued as [+], [-], or simply left unspecified. Her analysis of the argument associated with a comitative phrase is that it is entirely unspecified:

183 Contrast *kiss* with *compete* - another intrinsically symmetric predicate, but one that is not irreducibly symmetric.

(30)	Siloni (2011:46)	
	Agent	[+c][+m]
	Theme	[-c][-m]
	Ø-WITH	[Ø]

And, being unspecified, she makes the assumption that any entity belonging to this thematic role has its participation in the event defined by context alone. Along with Rákosi, this is the analysis I follow below – but for systems that allow a richer universe of thematic roles, we might consider the benefits of defining a new role called PARTNER.¹⁸⁴

Siloni's analysis focuses mainly on thematic roles and how they are assigned to the various participants. She claims that the dyadic verb is associated with two underlying events of the same type, so that the entities associated with the subject are assigned the agent and theme thematic roles (crucially, one at a time), and the comitative phrase entity's participation is then inferred (*i.e.*, assigned theme when the subject gets agent, and agent when the subject gets theme). I am in agreement with the broad tenets of her analysis – that the dyadic construction is formed from the monadic construction, and that both the dyadic and monadic constructions are formed in the lexicon. In the sections that follow, I detail my analysis of this construction with a view to understanding it within the theoretical framework of LFG. I fill in the details of how exactly a comitative phrase may be interpreted as a core argument of the verb, and consequently, why we see a weakening of the symmetric entailments related to the dyadic construction. More broadly, my analysis of the dyadic reciprocal construction in Swahili also addresses the question of why these constructions are associated with comitative phrases cross-linguistically and why they pattern so closely with intrinsically symmetric verbs.

5.3 COMITATIVE PHRASES AND THE DYADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION

As noted earlier, the most striking feature of dyadic reciprocal constructions from a cross-linguistic perspective is their formation from a comitative phrase. In fact, as we

¹⁸⁴ A PARTNER thematic role could be used with predicates like *be similar to* as well (*e.g.*, China is similar to North Korea).

will see below, many of the unusual properties that dyadic reciprocal constructions share in the world's languages actually arise as a consequence of their relationship with comitative phrases. I show how these phenomena can be understood as a consequence of a comitative phrase which when associated with a symmetric predicate is newly interpreted as one of its core arguments. In this section, I first present my analysis of comitative phrases in LFG, before turning to the analysis of the Swahili dyadic reciprocal construction in section 5.4.

5.3.1 Comitative phrases

A typical comitative phrase adds an optional entity to an event. This comitative entity participates in the event in a manner very similar to another participant in the event. For example, in (31) below, the PP “with Abel” is a comitative phrase, and Abel participates in the event of *catching* in a manner similar to that of Cain:

(31) *Cain caught fish with Abel*

The terminology I use here is that the comitative entity (Abel above) is *semantically linked* to another participant in the event. In this case, Abel is linked to Cain and his participation in the event is similar to that of Cain's.

5.3.1.1 A-ADJUNCTS

I analyse (most) comitative phrases as a-adjuncts – and the analysis which I present here parallels Webb's (2008) work on instrument phrases (another type of a-adjunct). Comitative phrases straddle what has sometimes been analysed as a divide between arguments and adjuncts. Like adjuncts, they are usually optional participants in the event – not specifically selected by the verb:

(32) *I ate noodles [with Elise]* Optional comitative phrase

And like regular adjuncts, the existence of a comitative participant is not implied or presupposed by the meaning of the verb. For example, consider the contrast between (33) and (34) below:

- (33) a. *Eric ate [spam] earlier.*
 b. *Eric ate earlier.*
- (34) a. *Eric ate noodles [with Ben] earlier.*
 b. *Eric ate noodles earlier.*

Although in (33b) the patient does not appear in the sentence, its existence is presupposed – we know that Eric ate something, whereas the verb *eat* in (34b) implies nothing about eating with someone. For a phrase to be both optional and also to not have its existence being presupposed by the verb are the hallmarks of adjuncts.

However, comitatives also share properties with arguments. For example, comitatives participate in the event described by the verb – (typically) as partners to the entity described carrying the highest thematic role (although optionally, without the same degree of agency). For example:

- (35) a. *John ran with Sally.*
 b. *Sally underwent surgery with John.*
 c. *Sally went fishing with John.*

Both John and Sally run in (35a) as agents, and undergo surgery in (35b) as patients. In (35c), it may not be strictly necessary that John catch any fish – he could assist Sally in some other way, but he is still acting with a high degree of agency with respect to the event.¹⁸⁵

The sense that these comitatives should be considered as arguments is captured by Croft (2012) in his work on the argument structure of verbs. In this work, he analyses the force-dynamic relations between participants in an event as being tied to argument realisation. In particular, he identifies comitatives as being *antecedent obliques* – a term he uses to describe entities which not only participate in the event described by the verb,

185 In some instances, the entity introduced in a comitative phrase can actually be more “active” than other entities in the clause. For example, say Mary is invited to a party, and her partner John comes along with her. This could be described as “John is going to the party with Mary”, even though Mary is the principal person invited. It is difficult to determine whether the more active participant is in fact more (thematically) agentive, or whether this notion of activity comes from the domain of discourse-pragmatics. Consider John in “John accompanied Mary to the shops”. He is more agentive insofar as he is doing the accompanying, but Mary is the person who controls the event of shopping.

but which in a causal sense occur in the event before the entity described by the object (this is opposed to *subsequent obliques* which occur – causally – after the entity specified by the object). To illustrate this idea of force-dynamic relations (represented by the arrows below), consider (36). Here the initial participant in the event (and also a canonical argument) is Sue. She uses a hammer (another participant related to the event via possession rather than through transfer of force), which itself causally affects the coconut (the final participant in the event – and another argument) by breaking it.¹⁸⁶

(36) Croft (2012:7.2.1)

Sue broke the coconut for Greg with a hammer.

Sue	→	hammer	→	coconut	- - -	→	Greg
S		A.OBL		OBJ			S.OBL
AG		INSTRM		PT			BENE

Likewise in (37), the entity identified by the comitative phrase participates in the event, causally affecting the entity specified by the object:

(37) Croft (2012:7.2.3)

Howard wrote the textbook with Tim.

For this reason, comitative phrases have an important property of arguments – they detail participants who take an active involvement in the event described by the verb, occurring inside the event frame. This then causally affects the entity specified by the object (if present).

Comitative phrases are also like arguments in that their number is constrained by the verb. Whereas any number of (semantically harmonious) adjuncts can occur with a verb, only one comitative phrase may. For example, in (38) below, two temporal adjuncts can be stacked after the verb, but in contrast, arguments (in this case objects) may not be in (39):

¹⁸⁶ The dashed arrow linking the coconut and Greg indicates that Greg is a participant outside of the verbal profile. As we are examining participants inside the verbal profile, it may be ignored for our purposes. For more details, see Croft (2010), section 5.6.3.2.

- (38) *I like to go dancing in February in the evenings.* Two adjuncts stacked
(39) **I ate a hamburger some spam.* Two arguments stacked

Comitatives behave like arguments in this respect:¹⁸⁷

- (40) **I ate with Ophelia with Hamlet.*

In summary, comitatives are phrases whose existence, like adjuncts, are not entailed by the meaning of verb, but which, like arguments, take part in the event described by the verb and whose number are constrained. In other words, comitatives have both adjunct- and argument-like properties which can be summarised as:

Adjunct properties

- Comitative phrases are optional, and their presence is not part of the verb's meaning. In “*Cain ate (spam) (with Abel)*” the patient's meaning is implied, even if not present, whereas the comitative's meaning is wholly optional.

Argument properties

- Comitative phrases participate in the event described by the verb – acting with another entity, and upon another entity, if present. For example, in “*Cain caught fish with Abel*”, Abel has very similar participation in this event to Cain.
- Comitative phrases are restricted in their number – unlike adjuncts.

5.3.2 Analysis of comitative phrases in LFG

As comitative phrases share properties of both adjuncts and arguments, how should they be analysed? In fact, an analysis of phrases that sit in the middle of the argument/adjunct continuum has been explored by many linguists but most notably by Grimshaw (1990). She defines the term “a-adjunct” (argument/adjunct) as a phrase which has an intermediate status between an argument and an adjunct and analyses it as:

187 Recall however (22) where two comitative phrases could be stacked. The difference is that only one comitative phrase was an argument in that instance. See the analysis below for further discussion.

(41) A-Adjunct Properties (adapted from Grimshaw 1990:108)

- (i) not being assigned a theta-role by the verb.
- (ii) being licensed by the argument structure of the verb.

Grimshaw's first property accounts for the existence of comitatives not being presupposed by the verb when they are not present (and hence their adjunct-like optionality). Her second property accounts for why the number of comitatives is restricted.

The way I analyse comitative a-adjuncts in LFG is built upon the work of two researchers (with various modifications described below): Rákosi (2008) and Webb (2008). Webb's work is an analysis of instruments and argument structure, and I will extend his analysis to incorporate comitative a-adjuncts.

Webb implements Grimshaw's account of a-adjuncts in LFG for instruments. I will outline the basics of his analysis below because with very little modification it can be used for comitative a-adjuncts as well. Crucially, a-adjuncts require the existing conception of argument structure in LFG to be extended to include two tiers – the first tier is for arguments whose presence is entailed by the meaning of the verb (such as the patient for the verb *eat* in (32) above), and the second tier is reserved for a-adjuncts:

(42) A-adjunct analysis (from Webb, 2008):

<i>I opened the door</i> <hr style="border: 0; border-top: 1px solid black;"/> <i>open</i> – 1 st tier <[P-A][P-P]>	<i>I opened the door with a key</i> <hr style="border: 0; border-top: 1px solid black;"/> <i>open</i> – 1 st tier <[P-A][P-P]> 2 nd tier <[P-A]>
---	--

The second tier of argument structure captures the argument and adjunct behaviour of a-adjuncts. By being defined in argument structure, their argument-like properties such as restricted number and participation in the event are explained. However, the second tier is also used to describe entities whose participation in the event is not required (nor inferred if they are absent).

I propose that comitative phrases are also usually a-adjuncts and so should be analysed in a manner parallel to Webb's analysis of instruments. The mapping from a-structure to f-structure occurs via the standard mapping rules (described by Ackermann, 1992), but with the provision that the arguments in the first tier are mapped before any

of the a-adjuncts in the second tier. For example, in (43) below, the 1st tier argument structure has two slots for the two thematic roles selected by the verb *catch*. However, an optional 2nd tier of argument structure is also defined for the a-adjuncts:

- (43) *Cain caught fish with Abel*
catch: 1st tier < [P-A][P-P] > 2nd tier < [] >

Note that, in Webb's analysis, the instrument a-adjunct receives the theta-role of agent. However, I follow Grimshaw (1990) in supposing that comitative a-adjuncts are not directly assigned a theta-role (hence the empty square brackets above).

This analysis of a comitative entity, as having an argument description of [], is equivalent to that which Rákosi gives for a *partner* thematic role in his analysis of the dyadic reciprocal construction in Hungarian (see Rákosi, 2008:424 and the references contained within). Siloni (2011) uses this in her analysis of the dyadic reciprocal construction (see discussion in section 5.2.2). The implication of this analysis is that the comitative phrase specifies an entity whose participation in the event is inferred contextually. Consider (44) below, where the comitative a-adjunct may be linked with either the subject or object (and consequently, either thematic role) depending on context:¹⁸⁸

- (44) *Jack saw Sally with his wife.*
 (i) *Jack and his wife saw Sally.*
 (ii) *Jack saw Sally and his wife.*

From a syntactic perspective, the mapping from argument structure to functional structure occurs via the standard mapping rules described above, but with the provision that the arguments in the first tier are mapped before any of the a-adjuncts in the second tier:

188 See Rákosi (2006:107-112) for further discussion.

(45)	a-structure	<i>catch</i>	1 st tier < [P-A] [P-P] >	2 nd tier < [] >
	intrinsic classification		-o -r	-o
	default classification		-r	+r
	<u>bi-uniqueness</u>		<u>SUBJ SUBJ/OBJ</u>	<u>OBL</u>
	f-structure		SUBJ OBJ	OBL _{a-adj}

Below, I outline some of the predictions this analysis makes. These will have relevance to my analysis of dyadic reciprocal constructions.

5.3.2.1 COMITATIVE PHRASES AS ARGUMENTS

Above, I analysed comitative phrases as being associated with an a-adjunct which is unspecified for a thematic role. As an a-adjunct, it is related to an entity who participates in the event, but whose participation is not presupposed by the verb. The first implication of this analysis is that we might expect to find verbs which select a comitative phrase as an argument, rather than as an a-adjunct. In other words, these verbs would select a comitative phrase as a core argument – one whose participation in the event is required and presupposed. I analyse these verbs as selecting an argument unspecified for a thematic role, as in (45) above, but with the modification that the comitative entity is part of the verb's first tier of argument structure – making it a prototypical argument. This is the analysis Rákosi (2008) proposes for intrinsically symmetric verbs in Hungarian which, if occurring with a singular subject, require the presence of the comitative phrase.

Central to Rákosi's analysis is that the monadic construction is formed from the dyadic one. Such an analysis is possible because, unlike the Swahili data, the dyadic constructions in Hungarian typically have no transitive counterpart: this means that either the monadic or dyadic construction may be treated as being basic. By choosing the dyadic construction as being basic, he is able to assign them an a-structure which includes a partner thematic role as a core argument. Rákosi (2008) gives the example of *vesz-ekedik* – “quarrel”: as having a lexical base of “take” followed by the reciprocal morpheme and offers the following analysis of its a-structure:

(46)	Rákosi (2008:444)
	<i>veszekedik</i> quarrel <[P-A], [] >

Although he treats these verbs as being basic (an entirely plausible analysis given that they have no transitive counterpart), they (and their monadic counterparts) do carry reciprocal morphology. The analysis I offer for Swahili can also be applied to Hungarian and most other languages with an irregular dyadic construction, with only a minor modification. I will return to this point in section 5.4.2 below.

Rákosi's analysis also raises the possibility of comitative phrases appearing as both a first tier argument and a second tier a-adjunct. Rákosi (2003) observes that verbs that treat the comitative phrase as being an argument allow an optional comitative a-adjunct as well – a possibility that is not available to verbs that do not select a comitative phrase as an argument:¹⁸⁹

(47) Rákosi (2003:3)

a. **Péter-rel (együtt) ritkán fut-ott-am Kati-val.*

Peter-COM together rarely run-PST-1SG Kate-COM

*“I rarely ran with Kate with Peter.”

b. *Péter-rel (együtt) ritkán veszeked-t-em Kati-val.*

Peter-COM together rarely quarrel-PST-1SG Kate-COM

“I rarely quarrelled with Kate, together with Peter.”

Under this analysis of comitative phrases, the verb *veszekedtem* – “quarrel” in (47b) now selects a comitative entity in both first and second tier argument structure:

(48)	a-structure	<i>veszekedtem</i>	1 st tier < [P-A] [] >	2 nd tier < [] >
	intrinsic classification		-o -o	-o
	default classification		-r +r	+r
	<u>bi-uniqueness</u>		SUBJ OBL	OBL
	f-structure		SUBJ OBL _{arg}	OBL _{a-adj}

The treatment of a comitative phrase as a core argument of a verb is by no means limited to Hungarian – it is likely that the majority of languages have verbs that

¹⁸⁹ *c.f.*, (22) above: *I met with my lawyer with my father.*

subcategorise for comitatives as core arguments. For example, *chat* in English and *ongea* (=chat) in Swahili both license a comitative phrase as an argument.

5.3.2.2 UNEQUAL PARTICIPATION IN THE EVENT

In the analysis of comitative phrases above, we see that the comitative entity does not receive the same thematic role as that of the entity to which it is linked. This means we would expect the comitative entity to be able to engage in the event in a manner different from that of its linked entity. This behaviour is observed in the day-to-day usage of comitative phrases. For example, consider Maria's participation in the event in (49) below:

(49) *Maria selected photos for the gallery with Mark.*

Although it is possible Maria and Mark have identical participation in the event, my understanding is that Mark is more likely to be providing assistance to Maria – perhaps looking over her shoulder. Fortunately, we do not need to rely on intuition alone to argue that there are differences between these comitative entities and the entities to which they are linked – for a restricted set of verbs, these intuitions can be formalised. Consider the a-structures for *collide* and *struggle*:

- (50) a. collide <[P-A] []>
 b. struggle <[P-A] []>

These a-structure definitions map, via the regular process described above, to a predicate that selects a subject and an oblique complement. Ideally, the subject NP is a prototypical agent (*i.e.*, it would be volitional, sentient, causal and moving), but there is no such requirement of the comitative phrase. Now recall the earlier discussion in section 5.2.1.2 of irreducible symmetry where I argued that the differences in acceptability of sentences like (51a) and (51b) were due to the fact that the two entities in the relation do not receive identical thematic roles:¹⁹⁰

190 Also *dance* – “Don danced with the broomstick”, *fight* – “The fishermen fought with the elements”, *struggle* – “Eric struggled with the flu”.

- (51) a. *The car collided with the tree.*
b. *##The tree collided with the car.*
- (52) a. *Eric struggled with the flu.*
b. *##The flu struggled with Eric.*

This contrast is predicted by the analysis above: the subject NP may have a different participation in the event than that of the partner because the partner is not assigned a thematic role. Speakers consciously make use of these different thematic roles when describing symmetric events that necessarily require two participants, but where the one of the participants (the comitative entity) is not agentive. For example, the following was offered by a news reporter to describe an alleged rape:

- (53) *She was asleep when he started having sex with her.*¹⁹¹

Compare the contrast in the meaning of (53) with the monadic version in (54) where the more likely assumption is that they are lovers:

- (54) *She was asleep when they started having sex.*

The lover interpretation of (54) is more likely because both participants are assigned the same thematic role.

5.3.3 Concluding remarks on the comitative construction

The analysis of comitative phrases presented above parallels that of Webb's analysis of instruments. The typical comitative phrase is an a-adjunct, which is unspecified for a thematic role by the verb but whose presence is licensed in a second tier of argument structure. This means that like an argument, it can't be stacked and takes part in the event described by the verb. However, like an adjunct, its participation in the event is wholly optional. With respect to the analysis of the dyadic reciprocal constructions, two properties of this analysis are of particular importance:

191 A.B.C. News – Melbourne, Australia, 13/7/2011

1. That some predicates can select a comitative phrase as an argument rather than an a-adjunct. This requires that the comitative entity be selected in the first tier of argument structure rather than the second.
2. That the comitative entity need not have identical participation in the event as that of the entity to which it is linked. This is as a result of the comitative entity not being assigned a thematic role. As such, the nature of its participation in the event is inferred contextually.

5.4 ANALYSIS OF THE DYADIC RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTION IN SWAHILI

I propose that in Swahili (and other languages), under suitable semantic conditions, a comitative a-adjunct may be promoted to the first tier of argument structure, becoming a comitative argument.¹⁹² Specifically, I claim that verbs whose meaning is symmetric, are particularly likely to allow this lexical change. The motivation for this process is straightforward. First, consider the usual role of the comitative entity:

- It adds to the event a participant that typically engages in the same activity as the subject.
- This participant engages in the same event as the other participants (*i.e.*, its addition makes for a collective interpretation of the event, rather than distributive).

For example, in “Diana hunted deer with Eric”, Eric is a participant in the hunt, although he need not have the same degree of agency as Diana. Additionally, they must be hunting together in the same atomic event, and they cannot hunt at different times – an interpretation that is compatible with the requirement that lexemes denote singular events.

Now consider the semantics of verbs whose default interpretation is symmetric. Once again, we have two participants engaging in the same event with very similar participation. For example, in “John and Mary fought” both John and Mary have

¹⁹² Such an analysis fits with work by Dowty (2003) who claims that “... a complete grammar should provide a DUAL ANALYSIS of every complement as an adjunct, and potentially, an analysis of any adjunct as a complement.”

identical thematic participation in the event; they are both fighters, and they are both being fought. The key difference is that the semantics of a symmetric verb *requires* that there be two participants.

Finally, consider the situation when a comitative phrase is applied to a symmetric predicate. We know comitative phrases are already used to describe situations in which two entities have the same or similar participation in a single event (*e.g.*, (35) above). We know that speakers already analyse some comitative phrases as first tier arguments (*c.f.*, the discussion of comitatives as arguments in section 5.3.2.1). And we know that symmetric verbs require at least two participants. In this environment, speakers may optionally interpret the comitative phrase as being a core argument of the verb. In theory, this is reflected by an alteration in a-structure where the comitative entity is understood as being in the first tier of a-structure rather than the second.¹⁹³ This process can be demonstrated with the Swahili verb *tembelea* – “visit”. Recall that Swahili speakers productively form the monadic reciprocal construction from a transitive base:

$$(55) \quad \text{Transitive } \underline{\textit{visit}} \qquad \qquad \qquad \underline{\textit{visit}}_{\text{sym}} \\ \textit{tembelea} < [\text{P-A}][\text{P-P}] > \quad \rightarrow \quad \textit{tembeleana} < [[\text{P-A}][\text{P-P}]] >$$

A verb in a monadic construction, like other verbs, can take a comitative a-adjunct. For example, in (56) the comitative phrase *na Daktari* – “with the doctor” is an a-adjunct and the a-structure of the verb *tembeleana* – “visit_{sym}” is given below.¹⁹⁴

$$(56) \quad \textit{Juma na Halima wa-li-tembel-e-an-a} \quad \textit{na Daktari.} \\ \text{Juma and Halima} \quad 3\text{PLS-PST-VISIT-APP-REC-FV} \quad \text{COM} \quad \text{doctor} \\ \text{“Juma and Halima visited each other, with the doctor.”} \\ \textit{i.e.}, \text{ Juma visited Halima, accompanied by the doctor and } \textit{vice versa}.$$

193 To illustrate the process, consider the example below in English using the intrinsically symmetric verb “meet”:

<i>meet</i> <[P-A]>	“Churchill and Stalin met at the HQ.”
<i>meet</i> <[P-A]> <[]>	“Churchill and Stalin met (at the HQ) (along) with their bodyguards.”
<i>meet</i> <[P-A] []>	“Churchill and Stalin met (*along) with their bodyguards.”

194 Unless given a specific context, the a-adjunct reading of (56) is now dispreferred in favour of the argument reading of the comitative phrase where the doctor visited Juma and Halima, and they visited the doctor.

Monadic $visit_{sym}$ with a-adjunct

tembeleana: 1st tier < [[P-A][P-P]] > 2nd tier < [] >

Symmetric and lexically derived reciprocal verbs have an interpretation that is very similar in its entailments – two entities engage in an event with the same participation. However, as noted previously, because reciprocal verbs are symmetric, the verb now *requires* the presence of a partner. As such, these verbs allow for the possibility of a comitative a-adjunct being understood as an argument in the first tier of argument structure:

(57) Monadic $visit_{sym}$ with a-adjunctDyadic $visit_{sym}$

tembeleana: 1st tier < [[P-A][P-P]] > → 1st tier < [[P-A][P-P]] [] >
2nd tier < [] >

Now that the comitative entity is an argument of the verb, the subject NP no longer requires two participants, and the symmetric relation occurs between the subject NP and the comitative phrase:

(58) *Juma a-li-tembel-e-an-a na Halima.*

Juma 3SGS-PST-VISIT-APP-REC-FV COM Halima

“Juma mutually visited with Halima.”

or “Juma and Halima visited each other.”

This representation of reciprocal verbs in Swahili was built upon the notion that speakers can reanalyze a comitative a-adjunct in a monadic construction as being an argument. The argument status of the comitative phrase is demonstrated in (59) below where its omission is either ungrammatical, or (at best) presupposed:

(59) */# *Juma a-li-tembel-e-an-a.*

Juma 3SGS-PST-VISIT-APP-REC-FV

*/# “Juma mutually visited.”

The resulting form of the dyadic reciprocated verb correctly predicts the syntax of these constructions. For example, the a-structure of the dyadic verb *pigana* – “hit_{sym}” in (60) correctly maps the comitative entity to an oblique argument:

- (60) *Juma a-li-pig-an-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-hit-REC-FV COM Halima
 “Juma and Halima hit each other.”
 lit. “Juma hit_{sym}/fought with Halima”

Dyadic *pigana* – “hit each other with”

a-structure	<i>pigana</i> :	< [[P-A][P-P]] [] >
intrinsic classification		-o -o
default classification		-r +r
<u>bi-uniqueness</u>		<u>SUBJ OBL</u>
f-structure		hit _{sym} <(SUBJ),(OBL)>

[PRED	‘hit _{sym} <SUBJ,OBL>’
SUBJ	[PRED ‘Juma’]
OBL	[PRED ‘Halima’]
TENSE	PST

5.4.1 Partitioning of participants in symmetric relations

As noted earlier, there is a difference between the dyadic and monadic reciprocal constructions with respect to how the participants in the event are partitioned. I will illustrate this using *piga* – “hit” in Swahili, but the same observations apply to the other languages studied here. In (61) below, all of the participants might be fighting with one another, or perhaps Juma and Halima are fighting with the child (among other readings):

- (61) *Juma na Halima na mtoto wa-li-pig-an-a.*
 Juma and Halima and child 3PLS-PST-hit-REC-FV
 “Juma and Halima and the child are hitting each other/fighting.”

However, in (62), the partitioning is such that the only reading is that Juma and Halima are fighting together with the child:

The limitation of this account is that it cannot (nor seeks to) explain the origin of the dyadic verb, and why it has a reciprocal morpheme. The analysis I present here shows how this situation comes about. Recall that the reanalysis of a comitative phrase, as being an argument, must occur at the level of the lexeme. From a purely formal point of view, the dyadic reciprocation operation takes a symmetric lexeme as its input and from it creates a new lexeme, one which selects a comitative entity as an argument:

$$(66) \quad \text{Verb}_{\text{sym,monadic}} \text{ 1}^{\text{st}} \text{ tier} < [[P-A][P-P]] > \rightarrow \text{Verb}_{\text{sym,dyadic}} < [[P-A][P-P]] [] > \\ \text{2}^{\text{nd}} \text{ tier} < [] >$$

Examining the a-structure of the dyadic verb above, we see that the complex structure of the first argument slot is a good candidate for simplification during a process of lexicalisation, as it is associated with only one grammatical function in syntax:

$$(67) \quad \text{Verb}_{\text{sym,dyadic}} < [[P-A][P-P]] [] > \rightarrow \text{Verb}_{\text{sym,dyadic,lexicalised}} < [P-A] [] >$$

This final analysis of lexicalised dyadic verbs is precisely that which Rákosi gives for dyadic verbs in Hungarian. Verbs formed in this manner are *bona fide* new lexemes, whose new a-structure reflects the fact that speakers no longer consider them productively formed from a transitive base. As new lexemes, they may undergo lexical drift, and their relationship to their original transitive bases may be lost. Furthermore, once this new lexeme has been created, it may undergo argument unification to form the monadic construction as described by Rákosi (2008).

5.5 CROSS-LINGUISTIC IMPLICATIONS

In the previous section, I have argued that a comitative a-adjunct attached to a reciprocated verb be interpreted as an argument. This reanalysis stems from the fact that a reciprocated verb meets all the preconditions for productive formation with a comitative entity, but with the additional condition that there are two participants in the event. In these constructions the comitative phrase may be understood by speakers as being an argument. I have extended the work of Rákosi (2008) and Webb (2008) to capture this phenomenon, and I have shown that this analysis correctly predicts the

syntax of the monadic and dyadic reciprocal constructions, and the relationship they have with their transitive base. However, the process I have described above is not specific to just Swahili. Below, I examine the implications this analysis has from a cross-linguistic perspective, and show that many properties of dyadic reciprocal constructions can be now understood.

5.5.1 Dyadic reciprocal constructions and comitative phrases

The analysis of dyadic reciprocal constructions presented above is built upon the notion that a comitative a-adjunct may be understood as an argument in the environment of a symmetric predicate. Under this analysis, we would expect that a similar operation could occur in different languages. More specifically, though, it predicts that the dyadic reciprocal construction will be formed from a comitative phrase and overwhelmingly, this is the case:

- (68) Greek (Hellenic) – Dimitriadis (2004:25)

O Yanis filithike me ti Maria.

the John kissed-REC COM the Maria

“John and Maria kissed (each other).” lit. “John kissed each other with Maria.”

- (69) Hebrew (Afro-Asiatic) – Siloni (2008)

Ha-yeladim hitnaešku im ha-yeladot.

the-boys kissed.REC COM the-girls

lit. “The boys kissed each other with the girls.”

“The boys and girls kissed each other.”

- (70) Hungarian (Uralic) – Rákosi (2008:443,444)

A katoná-k veszeked-t-ek az őrmester-rel.

the soldier-PL quarrel-PST-3PL the sergeant-COM

“The soldiers quarrelled with the sergeant.”

- (71) Icelandic (Germanic – elicited)

Þeir börðu-st við víkinga.

They.3PL.M.NOM fight.PL.PST-MV COM viking.M.PL.ACC

“They fought (from *berja* – ‘hit’) with the vikings.”

As a matter for further research, it would be useful to gain a greater appreciation of just how widespread is the formation of the dyadic construction using a comitative phrase. All available evidence is that this formation is the norm cross-linguistically, but an examination of any exceptions may be revealing.

5.5.2 That the dyadic reciprocal construction is formed from the monadic construction

Dimitriadis (2008, 2004) and Rákosi (2008) argue that the monadic reciprocal construction is formed from its dyadic equivalent, whereas the analysis above predicts the opposite. In the literature I have examined, the monadic reciprocal construction is either more prevalent than its dyadic counterpart, or equally prevalent. For example, in German and French, the monadic (verbal clitic) reciprocal constructions are relatively productive when compared to the dyadic constructions. Furthermore, there are languages whose monadic constructions disallow the dyadic alternation, but, as far as I am aware, the converse situation does not commonly occur.

Given that both the dyadic and monadic constructions contain reciprocal morphology, and given that monadic constructions are more widespread and more productive than dyadic ones, any analysis that posits that the dyadic construction is the base of formation for the monadic construction needs to do more. It needs to provide an additional mechanism to account for the existence of the monadic constructions that have no dyadic counterpart. I think that this is an unlikely historical path for the formation of monadic reciprocal constructions. However, should the dyadic construction become lexicalised, and no longer linked to a transitive base, then there is a possibility that the monadic construction could be formed from it via grammatical functional unification, as in Rákosi's analysis (see section 5.4.2 above).

5.5.3 Weakening of symmetric semantics

In this section, I discuss the implications the above analysis of dyadic reciprocal constructions has on their associated semantics. In particular, I contrast the predications made by this analysis with Dimitriadis' (2004) work on irreducible symmetry, and show that some unexpected data revealed by Rákosi (2008) can be explained by the analysis presented here.

Revisiting Dimitriadis' notion of irreducible symmetry and its relation to dyadic

reciprocal constructions, we can interpret irreducible symmetry as one way of conforming to the requirement that a symmetric event be conceived of as atomic, and that the symmetry be absolute, insofar as the entities are required to have identical participation within the event. For example, for the predicate *kiss* to be irreducibly symmetric, both participants must kiss in the same way in a single event. Situations where one participant has a different participation in the event are ruled out, as are situations which are only symmetric when seen as a collection of events (*e.g.*, Henry kissed Sally on the hand at night, and Sally kissed Henry on the cheek at dawn).¹⁹⁶

Under the analysis I presented here, the dyadic construction arises from a reanalysis of a comitative a-adjunct as a comitative argument. What semantic features might we expect in the resulting construction, and to what extent are they compatible with Dimitriadis' conception of irreducible symmetry? Comitative constructions introduce an entity that participates in the same event as the entity to which it is linked, but often with a less active participation. The implications such an analysis has on our understanding of the formation of dyadic reciprocal constructions revolve around two concepts, atomic events and symmetry.

The first point is that the addition of an entity in a comitative phrase to a predicate requires an atomic conception of the event – that is he or she takes part in the same event as their partner. For example, the addition of the comitative phrase in (73) precludes a non-atomic interpretation of the event, whereas (72) does not:

(72) *Olaf and Sally cooked some fish, Olaf in the morning and Sally in the evening.*

(73) *#Olaf cooked some fish with Sally, Olaf in the morning and Sally in the evening.*

With respect to reciprocity, unlike analytic (or phrasal) reciprocal constructions, monadic reciprocal constructions describe atomic events because they are formed at the level of the lexicon. Lexemes usually denote atomic events (recall chapter 4.3.3 and Carlson's (1998) conception of the lexicon being restricted to describing singular events). The addition of a comitative entity is entirely compatible with this requirement

196 There are other interpretations of events which are atomic, but not irreducibly symmetric. For example, Sally and Henry could kiss in greeting by kissing each other on the cheek. However, these types of kisses are still conceived of as being part of an atomic event as they are not accessible to the counting test.

because it introduces an entity to the event who must participate in the same event. In other words, we would expect the dyadic reciprocal construction to denote a singular event and this view is in line with Dimitriadis (2008, 2004) and Siloni (2011, 2008).

My second point is that symmetric participation occurs when every participant in a relation acts as both the initiator and endpoint of that relation. For example, we can say that Olaf and Sally have symmetric participation in the event of *seeing* if we can say: “Olaf saw Sally and Sally saw Olaf”. Symmetric participation is independent of whether the event is atomic or not. For example, if Olaf saw Sally in the morning, and Sally saw Olaf in the evening, their participation in the relation of seeing is still symmetric. Given my analysis of comitative entities, how might symmetry be affected in dyadic reciprocal constructions? I have argued above that comitative entities do not need to have identical participation in the event with the entity to which they are linked – and often have less agentive properties. Therefore, we might expect dyadic constructions to have weaker symmetric entailments between the two participants. This predication is at odds with Dimitriadis (2008, 2004), who argues that participation of the two entities in a dyadic construction must be identical. However, my prediction is in line with the data, where we do see this weakening of symmetry – even to the point of allowing the symmetry to be cancelled. For example, Rákosi (2008:423) illustrates this very clearly with the following example:

(74) Hungarian (Rákosi 2008:423)

Én num veszeked-t-em János-sal ő veszeked-ett vel-em.

I not quarrel-PST-1SG John-COM he quarrel-PST COM-1SG

“I was not quarrelling with John, he was quarrelling with me.”

I have found similar examples for the Icelandic middle voice construction (*slást* – “brawl” from the middle voice of *slá* – “hit”), and this pattern is particularly clear in Swahili, where the symmetry can be cancelled for some verbs in a dyadic reciprocal construction. For example:

(75) Swahili – elicited¹⁹⁷

Juma a-na-pend-an-a na Halima,

Juma 3SGS-PRES-love-REC-FV with Halima

lakini Halima ha-m-pend-i Juma

but, Halima NEG-3SGO-love-FV Juma

“Juma loves each other with Halima, but Halima does not love Juma.”

To be clear – the default interpretation of the dyadic construction is symmetric. However, because the comitative entity is not assigned a thematic role, and its activity in the event is inferred, the symmetric sense of the event can be mitigated or even cancelled under some circumstances. In fact, one of the motivations for the preservation of these constructions might be that speakers need a way of expressing unequal participation of entities within a symmetric event. With respect to whether the situation should be seen as an atomic event, or as a collection of events, the analysis I present is in line with work by Dimitriadis (2008), in predicting that dyadic reciprocal constructions be atomic. Note, though, that the strict entailments of irreducible symmetry are not required by this analysis. I believe that Dimitriadis' requirement of irreducibly symmetry actually comes about as a result of the predicate being singular or atomic in its conception. In other words, the strict sense of irreducible symmetry (*i.e.*, the requirements that both entities participate in the same event in the same way at the same time – *e.g.*, “they met.”) arises because a symmetric lexeme can only denote atomic events. One way the requirement that a symmetric event be atomic can be satisfied is through irreducible symmetry – the requirement that both participants engage in the event at the same time in the same way (consider Mark and Maria kissed). However, another possibility is also available in which the event becomes protracted with indistinct sub-events. We saw in (53) (repeated below), where two people visited each other, that an irreducibly symmetric interpretation is impossible – instead, the event is interpreted as being durative with an indeterminate number of visits.¹⁹⁸

197 A thorough corpus search would be required to strengthen this claim.

198 The same occurs in English in an example like “Bill had a fist-fight with Chevy”, where there must have been an indeterminate number of punches in the event.

- (76) *Juma a-li-tembel-e-an-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-VISIT-APP-REC-FV COM Halima
 “Juma mutually visited with Halima.”
 or “Juma and Halima visited each other.”

Contra Dimitriadis (2008, 2004), I predict that the dyadic reciprocal construction can have looser entailments with regard to symmetry, when compared to its monadic equivalent – even though these constructions are formed from a symmetric verb. This prediction is borne out in some situations in Swahili, Icelandic and Hungarian (above), where there are examples of the comitative entity not participating in the symmetric event to the same extent as the subject entity. Nevertheless, there is a strong association of these constructions with irreducible symmetry. I argue that this stems from the fact that the construction is formed in the lexicon, and an irreducibly symmetric interpretation of a symmetric event is compatible with the constraint that the event be atomic.

5.5.4 Symmetric versus reciprocal operator constructions.

Siloni (2008) notes that French reciprocal constructions, although having a superficial resemblance to the Swahili and Hungarian constructions, do not allow the formation of a dyadic reciprocal construction:

- (77) French (Siloni 2008:482)
 **Jean s'-est embrassé avec Marie.*
 Jean REC-IS kissed with Marie
 *“Jean kissed each other with Marie”

Note that this is also the situation in the English (and Icelandic) bipartite reciprocal constructions:

- (78) **John saw each other with Marie.*

The analysis I presented for the dyadic construction occurs at the level of the lexicon, where a comitative entity associated with a symmetric verb is analysed by speakers as

an argument. *See* in English is clearly not a symmetric verb, and so the dyadic construction is disallowed.

Siloni's (2011) analysis of the clitic construction in the Romance languages is different again. She claims that they are formed via the mapping of two thematic roles to one grammatical function, but that this occurs in syntax – and not the lexicon. And as the reciprocal construction is formed in syntax, it can describe plural events. Thus the contrast in the countability of sub-events in (79) and (80) is explained:

(79) French (Siloni 2008:481)

Jean et Marie se sont embrassés cinq fois.

Jean and Marie REC are kissed five times

Sentence (79) could describe a game in which Jean kisses Marie five times and Marie kisses Jean five times (*i.e.*, there were ten separate kisses). Contrast this with the Swahili lexical reciprocal construction, where the only possible reading is that there were three shared kisses:

(80) *Juma na Halima wa-li-bus-i-an-a mara tatu.*

Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-KISS-APP-REC-FV times three

“Juma and Halima kissed each other three times.”

However, as I discussed in chapter 4.2.5, in all respects but quantifier ambiguity the French clitic construction patterns with reciprocal constructions formed via the application of an operator (albeit with the additional requirement that they be intransitive). This raises the possibility that the Romance constructions could be formed via suppression of the agent thematic role and the application of a RECIP operator (*c.f.*, Dalrymple *et al.* (1994) analysis of Chicheŵa). Under this analysis, the resulting reciprocated verb would be unaccusative – a view that fits with some analyses of these constructions (*e.g.*, Marantz 1984). One failing of this analysis, however, is that it does not provide a natural account of the reciprocal/reflexive polysemy of the Romance clitic construction. Furthermore, within the literature there is still much debate as to whether the Romance reflexive and reciprocal constructions should be considered as being

unergative or unaccusative – and I regard the problem as unresolved.¹⁹⁹ As such, I wish only to propose this analysis as a possibility, but note that I am nevertheless in close agreement with Siloni (2011, 2008) and Reinhart and Siloni (2005), in that the Romance clitic reciprocal constructions are certainly not formed in the lexicon, and so do not allow a dyadic alternation.

5.5.5 Intrinsically Symmetric Verbs

In English there exists a set of intrinsically (or “naturally”) symmetric verbs such as *quarrel*, *argue* etc. These verbs appear to participate in a dyadic construction, despite their not having any reciprocal morphology. For example, consider (81) below:

- (81) a. *Bill and Mary argued/quarrelled/chatted.*
 b. *Bill argued/quarrelled/chatted with Mary.*

This alternation is in fact predicted as a consequence of the above analysis of the dyadic construction. Recall that this construction takes a symmetric verb as its base, and reanalyses an associated a-adjunct as an argument. Thus far, we have examined reciprocated (monadic) verbs, which became symmetric as a result of their formation via theta-role synthesis. However, some verbs are already symmetric as basic lexemes (such as *quarrel* etc.). These verbs, then, are suitable candidates for participation in a dyadic construction because, like the derived symmetric verbs in Swahili, they can serve as a base for the dyadic lexical operation. And so, in (81b) above the comitative phrase is functioning as an argument (as evidenced by the fact that its absence either renders the sentence ungrammatical or its meaning is presupposed if absent, e.g., **Bill chatted in the morning*).

Interestingly, some symmetric verbs in English display idiosyncratic behaviour in not allowing the formation of a dyadic construction. For example, the verb *kiss* is a prime candidate for allowing a comitative a-adjunct to be understood as an argument, but it is not usually described as not participating in this process (e.g., *?I kissed with her*).²⁰⁰ Whatever the status of sentences like this (and note that there are many instances

199 Relevant literature is Alsina (1996), Reinhart and Siloni (2005, 2004) and Rákosi (2008).

200 For examples, Collins-COBUILD (1995) – a corpus based dictionary of English does not list *kiss* as allowing a comitative phrase – but it does so for other intrinsically symmetric verbs such as *meet*.

of *kiss* being used this way on the internet)²⁰¹, observe that words roughly synonymous in meaning *do* license this construction (cf *pash*²⁰², *pash on*²⁰³, *snog*²⁰⁴, *french-kiss*²⁰⁵, *make-out*²⁰⁶, *neck*²⁰⁷, *suck-face*²⁰⁸ etc).

5.6 CONCLUSION

The motivation for this analysis of the dyadic Swahili reciprocal construction is driven by speakers understanding a comitative a-adjunct, in the presence of a symmetric predicate, as being an argument. Recall that, in general, at the level of a-structure a predicate may be asymmetric or, less commonly, symmetric. Previously, we have explored a variety of mechanisms whereby an asymmetric predicate can be used to describe a symmetric situation. For example, the RECIP operator associated with a reciprocal pronoun does just this; it is applied to an asymmetric predicate to generate a symmetric meaning. Conversely, some predicates are symmetric at the level of a-structure – this means that, at the lexical level, they already describe a symmetric event. There are two types of symmetric predicates. Some are intrinsically symmetric – that is to say, the symmetry is encoded as part of the base lexeme’s semantics. However, in chapter 4, I described the reciprocation strategy of theta-role synthesis, that synthesises two theta roles together to form a predicate symmetric at the level of a-structure. In section 5.4.3, we have explored some of the consequences of this process – including atomic event construal and lexical drift.

Considering the semantics of a symmetric predicate from a thematic perspective, we see it requires two participants with (nearly) identical thematic roles. For example, *fight* in (82) requires that there be two entities, both of whom are fighters (generalised as

201 “Well, yes, I kissed with her ...” - <http://www.sheprofilers.com/joran.html>

202 “I pashed with my BF last time and it was really weird” - <http://answers.yahoo.com/question/index?qid=20080605031533AAYJP5W>

203 “Masterchef Matt Preston proved he's a master lover when he pashed on with Jackie.”
<http://www.facebook.com/kylejackieo/posts/134031346619255>

204 “he had only snogged with her nothing more” -
<http://www.thisisbigbrother.com/forums/showthread.php?p=67225>

205 “just could not bring myself to french kiss with him” -
<http://www.squidoo.com/HowToFrenchKissAGuy>

206 “... to make out with her” - <http://answers.yahoo.com/question/index?qid=20100501203219AAHVYUd>

207 “I might have necked with her a little bit one time” -
http://books.google.com/books/about/Archives_of_memory.html?id=hnVSmXr6bWYC

208 “Hayden Sucks Face with Her Hero” - <http://www.t TMZ.com/2007/05/01/hayden-sucks-face-with-her-hero/>

that lexically derived reciprocal constructions share cross-linguistically:

- Why the entity represented by the oblique grammatical function is typically marked as being a comitative phrase.
- Why these constructions are so strongly associated with high degrees of symmetry within a single event.
- Why languages with reciprocal constructions whose formation leaves the predicate unchanged in a-structure (*i.e.*, formed in syntax according to Reinhart and Siloni's (2005) terminology) are not compatible with the dyadic reciprocal construction.

Finally, this explanation provides a natural account for those symmetric verbs which are not marked with reciprocal morphology (*e.g.*, *quarrel*, *bicker* *etc.* in English or *onzea* – “chat” in Swahili, *bavardait* – “chat” in French *etc.*), but which allow the same alternation between a base and a dyadic form.

6 CONCLUSION

Typological classifications of reciprocal constructions are overwhelmingly presented structurally and grammatically (*e.g.*, Nedjalkov, 2007; König & Gast, 2008; Evans, 2008; Haspelmath, 2007; König & Kokutani, 2006; *etc.*)²⁰⁹ That is to say, they categorise a reciprocal construction by examining morphosyntactic features such as whether it is formed via the application of an affix or clitic to the verb, whether it utilises some sort of reciprocal pronoun or nominal, or indeed any number of other features. However, the reciprocal constructions I have examined have syntactic behaviour that cross-cuts these classifications. To illustrate this point, consider the Malagasy reciprocal construction. It is formed from an affix applied to a verb and its place in all the structural typologies listed above is clear – it is one of the verb-marking strategies, variously sub-categorised as synthetic (König & Kokutani, 2006), verbal (Nedjalkov, 2007), lexical (Haspelmath, 2007) or morphological (Evans, 2008). However, analysis in chapter 3 revealed its underlying reciprocation strategy to be pronominal/operator. This mechanism explains why the Malagasy reciprocal construction also shares properties with some “NP-marking” reciprocal constructions and is illustrative of the limitations of the structural typologies above. I argue that to capture the syntactic similarities and differences between different reciprocal constructions, we need to determine their underlying reciprocation strategies. I have

²⁰⁹ A notable exception is Evans *et al.* (2011) which categorised reciprocal constructions according to the symmetric situations they may describe.

described five reciprocation strategies: reciprocal operator – typically associated with a pronoun; argument unification; theta-role synthesis; compositional formation and the use of intrinsically symmetric verbs. The reciprocation strategies I have described are different solutions to the same problem: how to describe a symmetric situation with lexemes that overwhelmingly describe asymmetric events. I found two types of solution to this problem: (i) using a symmetric predicate to describe a symmetric situation (whether by utilising an intrinsically symmetric verb such as *quarrel* or deriving one through theta-role synthesis as in the case of the Swahili reciprocal construction) or (ii) using a modified asymmetric predicate to describe a symmetric situation (whether that be via the application of a reciprocal operator (as in Malagasy and the phrasal and fixed form reciprocal constructions in Icelandic) or through some other means such as argument unification – as in the Romance languages described by Alsina, 1996):

Figure 6.1 Reciprocal construction formation strategies

The table below summarises the reciprocation strategies found for the key languages analysed or discussed in this thesis:

	Expression	Strategy	Number of Operands		
			A-structure	F-structure	C-structure
'Quarrel' etc.	Verbal	Intrinsic	<i>mono</i>	<i>mono</i>	<i>mono</i>
Swahili _{mon}	Verbal	θ-role synthesis	<i>mono</i>	<i>mono</i>	<i>mono</i>
French	Verbal	Arg. unification	<i>bi</i>	<i>mono</i>	<i>mono</i>
Malagasy	Verbal	Operator (pro)	<i>bi</i>	<i>bi</i>	<i>mono</i>
Icelandic	Phrasal	Operator (pro)	<i>bi</i>	<i>bi</i>	<i>bi</i>
Old Icelandic	Sentential	Compositional	<i>bi</i>	<i>bi</i>	<i>bi</i>

Table 6.1 Reciprocal constructions and reciprocation strategies

The asymmetric reciprocation strategies (exemplified by French, Malagasy and Old and Modern Icelandic) have in common an asymmetric predicate in a-structure whose valency is unchanged when reciprocated. These languages describe the symmetric sense of a situation by combining a collection of asymmetric events. Many of these asymmetric reciprocation strategies result in constructions with countable sub-events whose accessibility is made possible by their formation as a collection of asymmetric events. For example, compare the Icelandic (pronominal operator) with the symmetrically formed Swahili (theta-role synthesis) reciprocal construction which does not have countable sub-events:

- (1) a. Icelandic
- Þau kysstu hvort annað þrisvar.*
 they.N.PL.NOM kiss.3PL.PST each.N.SG.NOM other.N.SG.ACC thrice
 “They kissed each other three times” = There were three or six kisses.
- b. Swahili
- Juma na Halima wa-li-bus-i-an-a mara tatu.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-KISS-APP-REC-FV times three
 “Juma and Halima kissed each other three times.”
 = There were three kisses, or three sessions of kissing, only.

I have argued in this thesis that a construction's reciprocation strategy, and not its morphosyntactic expression, is crucial to understand its syntactic behaviour and even some aspects of the types of symmetric situations it may describe.

For example, two of these reciprocation strategies (compositional and operator) are integral to understanding the different forms of the Icelandic reciprocal construction. An extensive survey of Old Icelandic revealed that the Icelandic reciprocal construction was originally formed from a compositional strategy (see chapter 2, also Plank 2008).²¹⁰ The compositional strategy takes advantage of an existing mechanism within a language

210 In the case of the Germanic languages the reciprocal constructions' origins as being formed via a composition mechanism are often apparent in their morphology where “each” and “other” have fused (e.g., German *einander*) and in some cases have undergone reduction (e.g., the Dutch reciprocal pronoun *elkaar* from *elk* – “each” and *andar* – “other” was expressed as *elkandar* as recently as 50 years ago).

used to express symmetry through the interaction of a quantifier such as “each” with an indefinite pronoun or “alterity word”. For example, in (2) below *hverr* – “each” is functioning as the subject of the verb and it interacts with *annan* – “other” to create a symmetric interpretation of the event:

(2) Old Icelandic - Compositional reciprocal strategy

... *Þekkir þá hverr annan.*
 know.3SG.PRES then each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “Then each knew the other.”

Heim *et al.* (1991) demonstrated that a formal treatment of the semantics associated with the distributor (*hvárr* – “each”), reciprocator (*annan* – “other”) and scope (*Þekkir* – “know”) gives rise to a semantic representation of a strongly symmetric situation.

In modern Icelandic, however, there has been a marked change in word order. For example in the equivalent for sentence (3), *hver* now appears next to *annan*, and the pronoun *þeir* - “they” functions as the subject of the sentence:

(3) Modern Icelandic

Þeir þekkja hver annan.
 they.M.PL.NOM know.3PL.PRES each.M.SG.NOM other.M.SG.ACC
 “They know each other.”

This construction is characterised by unusual case marking and word orders (*e.g.*, *hver* can be in nominative or accusative case, and can occur either inside or outside a PP if present). However, when viewed from the perspective of reciprocation strategies, this seemingly opaque behaviour becomes clear. Central to this analysis is that the reciprocal construction in (3) can be formed from one of two mechanisms – and the differences between them are, for the most part, apparent only in certain syntactic environments. Despite the changes in word order and constituent structure between the Old Icelandic reciprocal construction and its modern counterpart, (3) can still be formed via the composition reciprocal strategy. This is possible because of the ability of quantifiers (such as *each*, *every* and *all*) in Germanic languages to appear in different places within a clause, while still quantifying their antecedent. In LFG, this is captured in both c- and

asymmetric predicate to produce a symmetric interpretation of an event. This operator is usually associated with a reciprocal pronoun (although Dalrymple *et al.* 1994 argue that it may also be associated with a detransitivising verbal reciprocal morpheme as well – see discussion in 4.3.6). This analysis of the different types of Icelandic reciprocal constructions situates them as being part of a continually and gradually evolving syntactic process where their reciprocation strategy is changing from compositional to operator based – and it is this ongoing transition which accounts for the wide array of reciprocal constructions in use in Iceland today, as well as their unusual case marking.²¹¹

The versatility of LFG in analysing these constructions is further demonstrated when considering the verbally marked Malagasy reciprocal construction. Many analyses of verbally marked reciprocal constructions (*e.g.*, Hebrew – Siloni, 2008; Chicheŵa – Mchombo, 1991; Catalan – Alsina, 1996) assume the detransitivisation of the reciprocated verb – and this is reflected in the structural typologies listed at the start of this chapter which have distinct categories for NP-marking and VP-marking reciprocal constructions. However, I analysed the Malagasy reciprocal construction as one where there is a mismatch between the number of phrases in c-structure and the number of grammatical functions in f-structure:

(4) Malagasy (Keenan & Razafimamonjy 2001:41)

M-if-an-aja *Rabe sy Rakoto*
 PRES-REC-ACT-respect Rabe and Rakoto
 “Rabe and Rakoto respect each other.”

211 I have included in appendix A an account of how the syntax and semantics of the phrasal reciprocal constructions can be formally linked. This is accomplished using “logical glue” - a formalism championed by Dalrymple (2001).

Under this analysis, the reciprocal verb retains the same number of operands in a- and f-structure (see table 6.1 above), but loses a constituent in c-structure. The reciprocal morpheme is associated with a reciprocal pronoun (one that is not associated with a constituent in c-structure) that serves as one of the grammatical functions required by the verb. This mismatch is easily accommodated in LFG and explains why an apparently intransitive verb can still form an object possession construction and host control constructions. The underlying reciprocation strategy of the Malagasy construction is still pronominal (reciprocal operator) and so even though the Malagasy and Icelandic (pronominal) reciprocal constructions have entirely different c-structures – their syntactic behaviour and associated f-structures are very similar.

This analysis addresses two further peculiarities. First, we can explain why reciprocal constructions are frequently associated with contradicting indications of transitivity. As illustrated in table 6.1 above, the Swahili, French and Malagasy reciprocal constructions require that we be more precise when talking about transitivity: simply considering a verb's transitivity as being whether it still has a full complement of NPs is inadequate. It is likely that many of the mysteries surrounding the transitivity of reciprocal constructions (such as how an apparently intransitive reciprocated verb can co-occur with object possession for example) will become clear if we properly analyse their valency at the different levels of syntactic structure LFG offers us. The second peculiarity is associated with the typological classification of the Malagasy reciprocal construction. Under existing morphosyntactic typologies of reciprocals, this construction should be listed as verb-marking as it is formed via the application of the reciprocal morpheme to the verb. However, we saw in chapter three that the reciprocal construction also engages in nominal processes such as possession, so there is good reason to also classify it as noun-marking. By categorising the Malagasy reciprocal construction according to its reciprocation strategy rather than by its morphosyntactic expression, we can assign it to a single category in which it has syntactic behaviour in common with the reciprocal constructions from other languages.

The French (verbal) reciprocal construction is formed via the application of a clitic to a verb whose interpretation gains a symmetric or reflexive sense. Its underlying formation is captured in LFG by mapping two arguments in a-structure to a single grammatical function in f-structure through a process called “argument unification”. Alsina (1996) used this mechanism to describe the syntax of the Romance reciprocal

constructions whose syntactic intransitivity was explained by the resulting loss of grammatical function in f-structure that such a process entails. Despite the fact that the morphosyntactic expression of these constructions is very different from that of the Germanic reciprocal constructions, in some respects they pattern very similarly with them. For example, Siloni (2011) observes that the reciprocated events in French have, like their English and Icelandic counterparts, countable sub-events:

(5) French (Siloni, 2011)

Le laryngologue et le dentiste se sont examinés cinq fois.

The laryngologist and the dentist _{RR} are examined five times

“The laryngologist and the dentist examined each other 5 times.”

= Five or ten examinations (potentially five by the laryngologist and five by the dentist.)

Siloni (2011) calls these types of verbally marked reciprocal constructions “syntactic reciprocals” in opposition to the “lexical reciprocals”. In terms of the reciprocation strategies I describe in figure 6.1, this is the same distinction we see between asymmetric and symmetric reciprocation strategies. Using LFG we can precisely characterise this distinction. If a reciprocated predicate retains its arguments in a-structure, the resulting reciprocal construction is formed from a fundamentally asymmetric predicate. That is to say, the symmetric sense of the event is formed through the application of a reciprocal operator, argument unification or a compositional strategy to the asymmetric predicate. As we have seen, the different asymmetric reciprocation strategies have different syntactic implications (mainly with respect to valency), but all share in a range of properties – such as being formed productively from a base with no idiomatic interpretations other than those available from the base verb, and disallowing a dyadic alternation (see Siloni, 2008, and discussion in chapter 4.3).

This is in stark contrast to the Swahili reciprocal construction. This construction, like its Malagasy equivalent, is formed via an affix to the verb. However, it behaves unlike any of the other verbally-marked reciprocal constructions considered in this thesis. Syntactic testing revealed that the reciprocated verb had lost a grammatical function – and so unlike Malagasy, it was not able to co-occur with object possession constructions. Having lost a grammatical function, we might assume that it behaves

similarly to the Romance reciprocal constructions – however this is not the case. For example, the Swahili reciprocal construction licenses a dyadic alternative formed from a comitative phrase; an alternation that is not (productively) available to any of the reciprocal constructions previously considered:

(6) Monadic reciprocal construction

- a. *Juma na Halima wa-li-tekeny-an-a.*
 Juma and Halima 3PLS-PST-tickle-REC-FV
 “Juma and Halima tickled each other.”

Dyadic reciprocal construction

- b. *Juma a-li-tekeny-an-a na Halima.*
 Juma 3SGS-PST-tickle-REC-FV COM Halima
 “Juma mutually tickled with Halima.”
c.f., English: *Juma tickled each other with Halima.

I argue that the differences between the Swahili reciprocal construction and its equivalents in English, French, Malagasy and Icelandic are due to its reciprocation strategy. The Swahili reciprocal construction is formed from theta-role synthesis – a mechanism which synthesises two thematic roles together to form a symmetric predicate in a-structure. This predicate has consequently one less argument than its base form and so is effectively intransitive like the Romance constructions. However, the difference between them is that the synthesised predicate has taken on a new symmetric meaning at a lexical level and so consequently its symmetric interpretation derives directly from it rather than from a reciprocation strategy applied to an asymmetric predicate. This analysis is in-line with work by Reinhart and Siloni (2005) who describe an “active lexicon” – that is that there are operations which can occur on a lexeme which affect its associated thematic roles, essentially changing its meaning before it enters the domain of syntax. In LFG, I analysed this mechanism as being situated in a-structure where theta-role synthesis creates a new symmetric predicate.

The lexical nature of the Swahili reciprocal construction has a profound effect on the nature of the symmetric semantics it may denote. This is because of the requirement that the synthesised predicate be, like other basic lexemes, atomic in its conception. In

terms of symmetry, this is realised as either irreducible symmetry (where both participants must be simultaneously engaged in the symmetric event) or by giving the predicate a repetitive or durative sense with indistinct sub-events (hence *tembeleana* – *visit*.REC in Swahili is best translated as “a period of mutual visiting” and *hit*.MV in (7) below is translated as *fight*).

As the Swahili reciprocal construction is formed from a symmetric predicate, we would expect that it would behave similarly to intrinsically symmetric predicates (such as *quarrel* etc.). This is found to be the case – with both denoting atomic events and both licensing a dyadic alternation. The existence of this dyadic construction is notable from a cross-linguistic perspective because its formation is remarkably consistent in completely different language groups. For example, the Icelandic middle voice construction (as opposed to the bipartite reciprocal construction discussed previously) and intrinsically symmetric verbs are formed in exactly the same manner as the Swahili construction:²¹²

- (7) a. Icelandic²¹³
Þeir börðu-st við þýska hermenn...
 3PL.M.NOM hit.3PL.PST-MV COM German.M.PL.ACC soldiers.M.PL.ACC
 “They fought (lit. *hit.rec*) with German soldiers.”
- b. English: *Paul and Mary quarrelled. / Paul quarrelled with Mary.*
- c. French: *Ils bavardaient. / Il bavardait avec elle.*
They were chatting. / He was chatting with her.

This cross-linguistic tendency was explained as resulting from the interaction between a comitative construction and a symmetric predicate (*e.g.*, a symmetric predicate that is derived through θ -role synthesis, or one that is already intrinsically symmetric). A symmetric event prototypically requires two entities whose participation in that event is thematically identical (for example, Paul and Mary in (7b) are both quarrellers). Comitative a-adjuncts add an optional participant to an event, but unlike typical

212 As well as; Hebrew, Hungarian, Greek, German and others. See chapter 5 for more details.

213 <http://is.wikipedia.org/wiki/Textel>

loss of this NP can be analysed as occurring in a-, f- and/or c-structure – each of which is related to a particular reciprocation strategy, and each of which has implications regarding the behaviour of the reciprocal construction in wider syntactic environments.

Beyond a few broad generalisations, the reciprocation strategies described above do not dictate the morphosyntactic expression of a reciprocal construction. For example, the operator process was linked to bipartite reciprocal construction in Icelandic, the (pronominal) verbal reciprocal construction in Malagasy and the intransitive verbal reciprocal construction in Chicheŵa. However, these mechanisms do, to a very large extent, determine the syntactic behaviour of a reciprocal construction – and even influence the types of symmetric situations they may denote. Because reciprocal constructions with the same or similar morphosyntactic expression can be formed from different reciprocation mechanisms, I argue that from a typological perspective the best way of categorising them is through these reciprocation strategies rather than by a catalogue of structural features.

Under normal conditions, all languages use asymmetric predicates (*i.e.*, those predicates with two distinct thematic roles) to describe asymmetric events or situations. However, with the exception of a limited number of intrinsically symmetric predicates, a mono-clausal reciprocal construction requires an asymmetric predicate to describe a symmetric situation. This is problematic as a symmetric situation differs from an asymmetric one because it is either formed from a collection of asymmetric events (*e.g.*, “they visited each other”), or because it no longer has two distinct thematic roles (*e.g.*, “they met.”). Thus, for a language to accommodate a reciprocal construction often demands that the normal processes that relate predicates to situations be suspended. One solution, used by the Germanic languages, is to abstract the symmetric interpretation of an event from syntax entirely by using a reciprocal operator. At the other extreme is the compositional strategy which is firmly rooted in the domain of syntax. Between these extremes are the reciprocation strategies of theta-role synthesis and argument unification which act at the boundaries of syntax and semantics by affecting the thematic roles of a reciprocated predicate (either by reinterpreting them, or by changing the way they map to grammatical functions). When viewed from this perspective, the clearest benefit of categorising reciprocal constructions by their reciprocation strategy is that we are afforded both the specifics, and the limits, to the means by which languages accommodate this most exceptional construction.

APPENDIX A – RECIPROCALLS AND GLUE LOGIC

1. INTRODUCTION

This section introduces the formalism used to link the syntactic form of pronominal reciprocal constructions with their semantic realisation using glue logic. The analysis here pertains to the operator/pronominal reciprocation strategy used for languages such as English and Icelandic. The ultimate purpose of glue logic is to provide a reliable way of linking the syntactic form of sentences like (1) and (2) below with their corresponding semantic realisations:

(1) *Joe hit Bob* hit(Joe,Bob)

(2) *Bob hit Joe* hit(Bob,Joe)

The semantic realisation of reciprocal constructions formed via the operator strategy (whether marked verbally or by some sort of phrase such as *each other*) is more complex but the ultimate goal is the same, to mechanically capture the differences between sentences like (3a), (3b) and (3c):

(3) a. *Joe and Bob hit each other.*

RECIP({Joe,Bob}, $\lambda x.\lambda y.\text{hit}(x,y)$)

b. *Joe and Bob gave money to each other.*
RECIP({Joe,Bob}, $\lambda x.\lambda z.\text{give}(x,\text{money},z)$)

c. *Sally introduced Joe and Bob to each other.*
RECIP({Joe,Bob}, $\lambda y.\lambda z.\text{introduce}(\text{Sally},y,z)$)

Despite the simplicity of the goal, the formalism is, at first glance, complex. So, in section 2 below, I introduce the formalism required to link the syntactic and semantic form of sentences like (3) above.

2. LINKING RECIPROCAL CONSTRUCTIONS AND SEMANTICS

In this section I examine a simple sentence ((4) below) and show how its semantic form is realised in (5). The formalism I have created here is built upon and extends a similar analysis of sentential adverbs by Dalrymple (2001).

(4) *Bob and Joe annoyed each other.*
(5) RECIP({Joe,Bob}, $\lambda x.\lambda y.\text{annoy}(x,y)$)

More generally, the semantic form of reciprocal constructions formed via the operator reciprocation strategy has three parts; a RECIP operator which takes two arguments; an entity set and a proposition:

(6) RECIP(Entity Set,Proposition)

For example, in (5):

Entity Set = {Joe,Bob}
Proposition = $\lambda x.\lambda y.\text{annoy}(x,y)$

The entity set lists the participants who are engaged in the reciprocal event and the proposition details the relationship between them. Note that the proposition embedded within the RECIP operator is not the abstract form of the predicate – it can contain other participants as required. For example, it is straightforward to capture the semantics of reciprocal/possession events such as (7) below:

- (7) *Joe and Bob kicked each other's cat.*
 RECIPIP({Joe,Bob},λx.λy.kick(x,POSS(y,cat)))

2.1 A basic example of meaning assembly

To begin, examine the simple transitive sentence below:

- (8) *Joe hit Bob.*

$$f : \begin{bmatrix} \text{PRED} & \text{'hit<SUBJ,OBJ>'} \\ \text{SUBJ} & g : [\text{PRED} \text{'Joe'}] \\ \text{OBJ} & h : [\text{PRED} \text{'Bob'}] \end{bmatrix}$$

The lexical entries for *Joe*, *Bob* and *hit* are below:

- (9) *Joe*: (↑PRED) = 'Joe'
 Joe : ↑_σ
- Bob*: (↑PRED) = 'Bob'
 Bob : ↑_σ
- hit*: (↑PRED) = hit<SUBJ,OBJ>
 λ X. λ Y. hit(x, y) : (↑SUBJ)_σ → [(↑OBJ)_σ → ↑_σ]

The definitions above are general. Before continuing I have instantiated the f-structure using the labels above. This means the lexical entries in (9) can be rewritten as:

- (10) *Joe*: (g PRED) = 'Joe'
 Joe : g_σ
- Bob*: (h PRED) = 'Bob'
 Bob : h_σ
- hit*: (↑PRED) = hit<SUBJ,OBJ>
 λ X. λ Y. hit(x, y) : (f SUBJ)_σ → [(f OBJ)_σ → f_σ]

or

$$\lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y) : g_{\sigma} \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$$

The definition for *hit* contains two parts. On the LHS of the ':' we see the lambda calculus definition of *hit*. Informally, the λx should be understood as taking an argument ('*the giant*' below), and wherever there is an x , replacing it with that argument. For example:

(11)

$$\begin{aligned} & [\lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y)](the\ giant) \\ & \lambda Y. hit(the\ giant, y) \end{aligned}$$

The argument need not be anything special – the process described above works just the same for (12) below:

(12)

$$\begin{aligned} & [\lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y)](PINEAPPLESPAM) \\ & \lambda Y. hit(PINEAPPLESPAM, y) \end{aligned}$$

The lambda calculus is used to formally add the entities in the hitting relation into the predicate *hit* – if we could instruct it to first insert Joe into the predicate, and then Bob, we would have the equation for (8) above:

(13)

$$\begin{aligned} & [\lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y)](Joe) \\ & \lambda Y. hit(Joe, y) \\ & [\lambda Y. hit(Joe, y)](Bob) \\ & hit(Joe, Bob) \end{aligned}$$

So, in order to make this meaning assembly work, we need a system which tells us what to add to our predicate and when. In other words, a system to tell the predicate *hit* which arguments should be applied, and in what order. Returning to the definition of *hit* above, this is exactly what all the formalism to the RHS of the ':' does:

$$(14) \quad \lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y) : (f \text{ SUBJ})_{\sigma} \multimap [(f \text{ OBJ})_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$$

or

$$\lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y) : g_{\sigma} \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$$

The $(f \text{ SUBJ})_{\sigma} \multimap [(f \text{ OBJ})_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$ part requires that: we first apply the meaning of the predicate *hit* to the meaning of the f-structure associated with the subject (*i.e.*, g_{σ} – the sigma subscript means “the meaning associated with”). Then this predicate is applied to the meaning associated with f-structure f’s object (*i.e.*, h_{σ}):

$$(15) \quad \mathbf{[hit]} \quad \lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y) : g_{\sigma} \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$$

$$\mathbf{[Bob]} \quad Bob : h_{\sigma}$$

$$\mathbf{[Joe]} \quad Joe : g_{\sigma}$$

Looking at **[hit]** we see it needs to consume g_{σ} :

$$(16) \quad \mathbf{[hit],[Joe]} \text{ gives } \mathbf{[Joe-hit]}$$

$$\mathbf{[hit]} \quad \lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y) : g_{\sigma} \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$$

$$\mathbf{[Joe]} \quad Joe : g_{\sigma}$$

$$\mathbf{[Joe-hit]} \quad [\lambda X. \lambda Y. hit(x, y)](Joe) : g_{\sigma} \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$$

$$\lambda Y. hit(Joe, y) : h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}$$

[Joe-hit] needs to consume h_{σ} . The result is f_{σ} , the meaning of the f-structure f :

$$(17) \quad \mathbf{[Joe-hit],[Bob]} \text{ gives } \mathbf{[Joe-hit-Bob]}$$

$$\mathbf{[Joe-hit-Bob]} \quad [\lambda Y. hit(Joe, y)](Bob) : h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}$$

$$hit(Joe, Bob) : f_{\sigma}$$

And so, we have the correct derivation for the meaning of “Joe hit Bob”.

2.2 Solving “Joe and Bob annoyed each other”

I use the following c- and f-structure for (18) below:

(18) “Joe and Bob annoyed each other.”

<i>Joe</i>	PN	(↑PRED)='Joe' <i>Joe</i> :↑ _σ
<i>Bob</i>	PN	(↑PRED)='Bob' <i>Bob</i> :↑ _σ
<i>and</i>	CNJ	(↑NUM)=PL λX.λY.[X,Y]:(↑∈) _σ →[(↑∈) _σ →↑ _σ]
<i>annoyed</i>	V	(↑PRED)='annoy<(↑SUBJ)(↑OBJ)>' (↑TENSE)=PST λX.λY.annoy(X,Y):(↑SUBJ) _σ →[(↑OBJ) _σ →↑ _σ]
<i>each other</i>	PRO _{rec}	(↑PRED)=PRO _{recip} (%ANT NUM)= _c PL λQ.λY.RECIP(Y,Q):[%ANT _σ →[↑ _σ →(GF %ANT) _σ]]→ [%ANT _σ →(GF %ANT) _σ]

I use the following f-structure:

$$f : \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{PRED} \quad \text{'annoy<SUBJ,OBJ>} \\ \text{TENSE} \quad \text{PST} \\ \text{OBJ} \quad h : \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{PRED} \quad \text{'PRO}_{rec} \end{array} \right] \\ \text{SUBJ} \quad g : \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{NUM} \quad \text{PL} \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i : \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{PRED} \quad \text{'Joe'} \end{array} \right] \\ j : \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{PRED} \quad \text{'Bob'} \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right\} \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right]$$

%ANT is the f-structure associated with the antecedent NP. In this case, it is the f-

structure associated with the SUBJ. More generally, this f-structure is defined on a language-by-language basis depending on various binding parameters. For English, %ANT can be substituted with the following definition (along with various other constraints, not detailed here):

$$(19) \quad \%ANT = (GF \ (GF^*) \uparrow) \ GF \\ \quad \quad \quad \neg(\rightarrow TENSE)$$

In this case %ANT is resolved to be the f-structure associated with the subject – in the sentence above, this f-structure is labelled as *g*. In other words, in the definition of *each other* above:

$\%ANT_\sigma$	The meaning associated with the SUBJ grammatical function (e.g., <i>g</i> above).
$(GF \ \%ANT)_\sigma$	The meaning associated with the f-structure which holds the SUBJ (e.g., <i>f</i> above).
\uparrow_σ	The meaning associated with the f-structure which holds the reciprocal pronoun (e.g., <i>h</i> above)

Before continuing, I will instantiate the f-structure labels.

(20)

<i>Joe</i>	PN	$Joe : i_\sigma$
<i>Bob</i>	PN	$Bob : j_\sigma$
<i>and</i>	CNJ	$\lambda X. \lambda Y. [X, Y] : i_\sigma \rightarrow [j_\sigma \rightarrow g_\sigma]$
<i>annoyed</i>	V	$(f \ PRED) = 'annoy < (f \ SUBJ) (f \ OBJ) >'$ $(f \ TENSE) = PST$ $\lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y) : (f \ SUBJ)_\sigma \rightarrow [(f \ OBJ)_\sigma \rightarrow f_\sigma]$
		or
		$\lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y) : g_\sigma \rightarrow [h_\sigma \rightarrow f_\sigma]$
<i>each other</i>	PRO _{rec}	$\lambda Q. \lambda Y. RECIP(Y, Q) : [g_\sigma \rightarrow [h_\sigma \rightarrow f_\sigma]] \rightarrow [g_\sigma \rightarrow f_\sigma]$

Step 1: solve the subject NP

part1: [Bob], [Joe] and [and]

[and] needs i_σ to give $[j_\sigma \multimap g_\sigma]$:

$$\begin{aligned} & [\lambda X. \lambda Y. \{X, Y\}](Bob): i_\sigma \multimap [j_\sigma \multimap g_\sigma] \\ & \lambda Y. \{Bob, Y\}: j_\sigma \multimap g_\sigma \end{aligned}$$

The result below now needs j_σ to give g_σ :

$$\begin{aligned} & [\lambda Y. \{Bob, Y\}](Joe): j_\sigma \multimap g_\sigma \\ & \{Bob, Joe\}: g_\sigma \end{aligned}$$

So we have the following result for **[Bob],[Joe],[and]**:

$$\mathbf{[Bob-and-Joe]} \quad \{Bob, Joe\}: g_\sigma$$

Having derived the meaning of the subject NP, we can now turn to the rest of the sentence. The definition of *annoyed* is formed in the same way as *hit* above. What is new is the definition of *each other*:

$$(21) \quad \mathbf{[each-other]} \quad \lambda Q. \lambda Y. \text{RECIP}(Y, Q): [g_\sigma \multimap [h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]] \multimap [g_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]$$

This tells us that our predicate needs to consume two things, one to place in Q and the other in Y. These things are our proposition (*annoy*) and our entity set $\{Joe, Bob\}$ respectively to give:

$$(22) \quad \text{RECIP}(\{Joe, Bob\}, \lambda X. \lambda Y. \text{annoy}(X, Y))$$

Again, the RHS tells us what to combine and in what order. Note there are two parts. First of all, we need to consume something that looks like $[g_\sigma \multimap [h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]]$. Reexamining the meaning constructor for **[annoy]**, we see that it has just this form. In other words, the first thing to be consumed is *annoy*:

$$(23) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{[each other]} & \lambda Q. \lambda Y. RECIP(Y, Q) : [g_\sigma \multimap [h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]] \multimap [g_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma] \\ \text{[annoy]} & \lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y) : g_\sigma \multimap [h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma] \end{array}$$

$$[\lambda Q. \lambda Y. RECIP(Y, Q)](\lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y) : g_\sigma \multimap [h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]) : [g_\sigma \multimap [h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]] \multimap [g_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]$$

$$\lambda Y. RECIP(Y, \lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y)) : h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma$$

giving us:

$$(24) \quad \text{[annoy-each-other]} \quad \lambda Y. RECIP(Y, \lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y)) : g_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma$$

What remains is fairly straightforward – the LHS needs to combine with one more argument to produce the final meaning. The RHS tells us that this argument is g_σ – the meaning of the subject f-structure:

$$(25) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{[annoy-each-other]} & \lambda Y. RECIP(Y, \lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y)) : g_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma \\ \text{[Bob-and-Joe]} & \{Bob, Joe\} : g_\sigma \end{array}$$

To give:

$$(26) \quad \begin{array}{l} [\lambda Y. RECIP(Y, \lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y))](\{Bob, Joe\}) : g_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma \\ RECIP(\{Bob, Joe\}, \lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y)) : f_\sigma \end{array}$$

Which is the meaning of f-structure f :

$$(27) \quad \text{[B\&J-annoy-each other]} \quad RECIP(\{Bob, Joe\}, \lambda X. \lambda Y. annoy(X, Y)) : f_\sigma$$

2.3 Non-subject antecedents

The previous example was a transitive verb with a subject antecedent. We need to ensure that the formalism developed is general enough to work with verbs of different arities and with different antecedents. For that reason, I examine sentence (28) below:

(28) *David introduced Bob and Jane to each other.*

The (instantiated) f-structure for (28) is below:²¹⁴

$$(29) f : \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{PRED} \quad \text{'introduce<SUBJ,OBJ,OBL>'} \\ \text{SUBJ} \quad g : [\text{PRED} \quad \text{'David'}] \\ \text{OBJ} \quad h : [\text{PRED} \quad \text{'Bob, Jane'}] \\ \text{OBL} \quad i : [\text{PRED} \quad \text{'PRO}_{\text{rec}}'] \end{array} \right]$$

Lexical Entries (showing only relevant formalism):

(30)

Bob and NP { *Bob, Jane* } : h_{σ}

Jane

introduced V ($\uparrow \text{PRED}$) = 'introduce <($\uparrow \text{SUBJ}$)($\uparrow \text{OBJ}$)($\uparrow \text{OBL}$)>'

($\uparrow \text{TENSE}$) = *PST*

$\lambda X. \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(X, Y, Z) : (\uparrow \text{SUBJ})_{\sigma} \rightarrow [(\uparrow \text{OBJ})_{\sigma} \rightarrow [(\uparrow \text{OBL})_{\sigma} \rightarrow \uparrow_{\sigma}]]$

each other PRO_{rec} ($\uparrow \text{PRED}$) = $\text{PRO}_{\text{recip}}$

($\% \text{ANT NUM}$) = $c \text{ PL}$

$\lambda Q. \lambda Y. \text{RECIP}(Y, Q) : [\% \text{ANT}_{\sigma} \rightarrow [\uparrow_{\sigma} \rightarrow (\text{GF } \% \text{ANT})_{\sigma}]] \rightarrow$
 $[\% \text{ANT}_{\sigma} \rightarrow (\text{GF } \% \text{ANT})_{\sigma}]$

Note that the definition for *each other* remains unchanged. To these definitions I apply the following substitutions:

(31) f = the outermost f-structure

$f \text{SUBJ} = g$

$f \text{OBJ} = \% \text{ANT} = h$

$f \text{OBL} = i$

²¹⁴ To simplify the notation, I will take the derivation of “Bob” and “Jane” as solved.

Within the definition of *each other* we can make the following substitutions:

$$(32) \quad \begin{aligned} \%ANT_{\sigma} &= h_{\sigma} \\ (GF \%ANT \uparrow)_{\sigma} &= f_{\sigma} \\ \uparrow_{\sigma} &= i_{\sigma} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll} \textit{Jason} & \textit{Jason} : g_{\sigma} \\ \textit{Bob and Jane} & \{\textit{Bob}, \textit{Jane}\} : h_{\sigma} \\ \textit{introduced} & \lambda X. \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \textit{introduce}(X, Y, Z) : g_{\sigma} \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]] \\ \textit{each other} & \lambda Q. \lambda Y. \textit{RECIP}(Y, Q) : [[h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]] \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]] \end{array}$$

We start by examining **[each other]**:

$$(33) \quad \mathbf{[each-other]} \quad \lambda Q. \lambda Y. \textit{RECIP}(Y, Q) : [[h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]] \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]]$$

[each-other] requires a resource of type $[h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]]$ in order to produce a $[h_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$, and from here, we can complete the deduction. The problem is that we don't have an $[h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]]$ available. But, we do have a g_{σ} that could be combined with *introduce*, to give a $[h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]]$:

$$(34) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{[introduce]}: & \lambda X. \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \textit{introduce}(X, Y, Z) : g_{\sigma} \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]] \\ \mathbf{[Jason]}: & \textit{Jason} : g_{\sigma} \end{array}$$

so:

$$\begin{aligned} & [\lambda X. \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \textit{introduce}(X, Y, Z)](\textit{Jason}) : g_{\sigma} \multimap [h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]] \\ & \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \textit{introduce}(\textit{Jason}, Y, Z) : h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}] \end{aligned}$$

which gives:

$$(35) \quad \mathbf{[Jason-introduce]} \quad \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \textit{introduce}(\textit{Jason}, Y, Z) : h_{\sigma} \multimap [i_{\sigma} \multimap f_{\sigma}]$$

So, **[Jason-introduce]** is a resource of type $[h_\sigma \multimap [i_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]]$, which is needed to be consumed by **[each-other]** to produce a $[h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]$:

$$(36) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{[Jason-introduce]} & \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(Jason, Y, Z) : h_\sigma \multimap [i_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma] \\ \mathbf{[each-other]} & \lambda Q. \lambda Y. \text{RECIP}(Y, Q) : [[h_\sigma \multimap [i_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]] \multimap [h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma]] \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} [\lambda Q. \lambda Y. \text{RECIP}(Y, Q)](\lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(Jason, Y, Z)) : h_\sigma \multimap [i_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma] \\ \lambda Y. \text{RECIP}(Y, \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(Jason, Y, Z)) : h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma \end{array}$$

[Jason-intro-eo]

$$\lambda Y. \text{RECIP}(Y, \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(Jason, Y, Z)) : h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma$$

Now all that remains is to consume h_σ to produce f_σ :

$$(37) \quad \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{[Jason-intro-eo]} \\ \lambda Y. \text{RECIP}(Y, \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(Jason, Y, Z)) : h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma \end{array}$$

[Bob-and-Jane]

$$\{Bob, Jane\} : h_\sigma$$

$$\begin{array}{l} [\lambda Y. \text{RECIP}(Y, \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(Jason, Y, Z))](\{Bob, Jane\}) : h_\sigma \multimap f_\sigma \\ \text{RECIP}(\{Bob, Jane\}, \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(Jason, Y, Z)) : f_\sigma \end{array}$$

So, the meaning of the f-structure f and hence the sentence is given by:

$$(38) \quad \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{[Jason-intro-Bob-and-Jane-eo]} : \\ \text{RECIP}(\{Bob, Jane\}, \lambda Y. \lambda Z. \text{introduce}(Jason, Y, Z)) : f_\sigma \end{array}$$

APPENDIX B – ICELANDIC SURVEY QUESTIONS

The survey was held from the beginning of 2009 and is now complete with 504 people completing it. The survey sign-up emails and questions are given below – both in the original Icelandic and translated into English.

1. SIGN UP EMAIL

Komið þið sæl,

Þið hafið fengið þennan tölvupóst:

- vegna fyrirsagnar varðandi verkefni Peter Hurst eða
- vegna þess að félagi ykkar gaf okkur netfang ykkar.

Ykkur er hér með boðið að taka þátt í verkefni þar sem leitast er við að skilja hvernig Íslendingar nota orðasambandið „hvor annar“. Ef þið samþykkið þátttöku, verðið þið beðin um að fylla út spurningalista á vefnum. Í þessum spurningalista eru 40 spurningar. Þið eruð beðin um að velja þá mynd eða myndir af orðasambandinu „hvor annar“ sem þið munduð nota eða teljið ykkur heyra aðra nota í slíkum setningum. Við gerum ráð fyrir að tíminn sem færi í að svara spurningunum sé um 20 mínútur.

Svör ykkar verða geymd sem trúnaðarmál í

Hi there – you have received this email because:

- * You requested information about this project from <http://www.peterhurst.com/survey> or
- * Your email address has been passed onto me by one of your colleagues.

This email is an invitation for you to participate in a project which seeks to understand how Icelanders use "hvor annar" in sentences. If you agree to participate in this project, you will be asked to fill out an online questionnaire. This questionnaire contains 30 sentences and asks you to choose the form or forms of "hvor annar" which you would use, or would hear others use to complete the sentence. We estimate that the total time to complete the questionnaire is about 20 minutes.

Your replies will be kept confidential within the fullest limits of Australian law. When you have

Appendix B – Icelandic survey questions

fullu samræmi við áströlsk lög. Þegar þið hafið útfyllt og sent listann, verða öll tengsl milli netfangs ykkar og svara rofin. Það þýðir að enginn getur sett svörin sem þið hafið gefið í samband við ykkur. Netfang ykkar verður geymt sérstaklega í verndaðri tölvuskra til þess að hægt sé að upplýsa ykkur um niðurstöður könnunarinnar þegar doktorsritgerð, sem byggir á þessari rannsókn, er lokið.

Þátttakan er ykkur í sjálfsvald sett. Ef þið óskið eftir að hætta þátttöku eða draga til baka gefnar upplýsingar, sem ekki hefur verið unnið úr, er ykkur það heimilt að fordómalaus. Hins vegar er ekki hægt að fjarlægja svör ykkar að könnun lokinni vegna þess að þau eru geymd án tilvísunar til netfangs sendanda.

Ef þið þurfið á frekari upplýsingum að halda, hikið þá ekki við að hafa samband við Peter Hurst (peter@peterhurst.com).

Smellið á tenginguna hér að neðan til þess að taka þátt í rannsókninni.

[link]

Þökk fyrir,
Mr Peter Hurst & Dr Rachel Nordlinger
Department of Linguistics (Málvísindadeild)
University of Melbourne
Australia

Verkefni þetta hefur hlotið samþykki Human Research Ethics Committee, Melbourne, Australia. (siðanefnd um rannsóknir á persónugreinanlegum gögnum)

completed the questionnaire, any link between your email address and the responses you gave will be permanently removed. This means that it will be impossible for someone to associate your answers to the questionnaire with your email address. Your email address will be kept in a separate, password-protected computer file for the sole purpose of advising you about the results of the questionnaire once the Ph.D. thesis arising from this research has been completed.

Your participation in the questionnaire is completely voluntary - should you wish to withdraw at any stage, or to withdraw any unprocessed data you have supplied, you are free to do so without prejudice. However, once you have completed the survey it is impossible to remove any of your responses because they are stored without reference to your email address.

Should you require any further information, or have any concerns, please do not hesitate to contact Peter Hurst at peter@peterhurst.com.

If you would like to participate in this research, please click the link below:

[link]

Kind Regards,
Mr Peter Hurst & Dr Rachel Nordlinger
Department of Linguistics,
University of Melbourne,
Australia

This project is approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee, Melbourne, Australia.

2. SURVEY QUESTIONS & RESULTS

Results

Number of records in this survey: 504

Summary for Section A

(i) *Maðurinn og konan sáu [??? ???].*

(The man and woman saw each other.)

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvor aðra</i>	1	0.20%
<i>hvora aðra</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvort annað</i>	498	99.80%

(ii) *Bræðurnir sáu [??? ???].*

(The brothers saw each other.)

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	126	24.32%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	388	74.90%
<i>hvor aðra</i>	4	0.77%
<i>hvora aðra</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvort annað</i>	0	0.00%

(iii) *Konurnar sáu [??? ???].*

(The women saw each other.)

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	2	0.39%
<i>hvor aðra</i>	283	55.49%
<i>hvora aðra</i>	224	43.92%
<i>hvort annað</i>	0	0.00%

(iv) *Raðaðu eftirfarandi setningum eftir því hvora er líklegra að þú notir sértu að skrifa í dagblað.*

Rank the following sentences according to which would be best in a letter to a newspaper:

“The problem is that politicians don't respect one another”

Appendix B – Icelandic survey questions

[Ranking 1]			
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Vandamálið er að stjórnámálamenn virða ekki hver annan.</i>	192	39.26%	
<i>Vandamálið er að stjórnámálamenn virða ekki hvern annan.</i>	297	60.73%	

[Ranking 2]			
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Vandamálið er að stjórnámálamenn virða ekki hver annan.</i>	253	62.62%	
<i>Vandamálið er að stjórnámálamenn virða ekki hvern annan.</i>	151	37.37%	

(v) *Raðaðu eftirfarandi setningum eftir því hvora er líklegra að þú notir eða heyrir á kaffihúsi eða bar.*

Rank the following according to which you'd most likely overhear in a bar or cafe:

“She said that they met each other”

[Ranking 1]			
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Hún sagði að þeir hefðu hitt hvor annan.</i>	119	24.24%	
<i>Hún sagði að þeir hefðu hitt hvorn annan.</i>	372	75.76%	

[Ranking 2]			
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Hún sagði að þeir hefðu hitt hvor annan.</i>	311	76.98%	
<i>Hún sagði að þeir hefðu hitt hvorn annan.</i>	93	23.01%	

Summary for Section B

(i) *Strákarnir tveir gáfu [??? ???] peninga.*

(The two boys gave each other money.)

Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>hvor annan</i>	0	0.00%	
<i>hvorn annan</i>	0	0.00%	
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	392	74.67%	
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	129	24.57%	
<i>hvor annars</i>	1	0.19%	
<i>hvors annars</i>	3	0.57%	

(ii) Strákarnir tveir skiluðu [?? ??] peningunum.

“The two boys returned the money to each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	2	0.38%
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	299	57.17%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	165	31.55%
<i>hvor annars</i>	11	2.10%
<i>hvors annars</i>	45	8.60%

(iii) Strákarnir tveir leyndu [?? ??] sannleikanum.

“The two boys hid the truth from each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	54	10.40%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	208	40.08%
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	176	33.91%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	80	15.41%
<i>hvor annars</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvors annars</i>	0	0.00%

(iv) Ég kynnti mennina tvo [?? ?? ??].

“I introduced the two men to each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor fyrir annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn fyrir annan</i>	2	0.35%
<i>hvor fyrir öðrum</i>	43	7.49%
<i>hvorn fyrir öðrum</i>	135	23.52%
<i>hvorum fyrir öðrum</i>	11	1.91%
<i>hvor fyrir annars</i>	1	0.17%
<i>hvors fyrir annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>fyrir hvor annan</i>	3	0.52%
<i>fyrir hvorn annan</i>	8	1.39%
<i>fyrir hvorn öðrum</i>	40	6.97%
<i>fyrir hvor öðrum</i>	221	38.50%
<i>fyrir hvorum öðrum</i>	110	19.16%
<i>fyrir hvor annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>fyrir hvors annars</i>	0	0.00%

(v) *Strákarnir tveir synjuðu [??? ???] leyfis.*

“The two boys denied each other permission.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	21	4.05%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	48	9.27%
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	264	50.97%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	136	26.25%
<i>hvor annars</i>	9	1.74%
<i>hvors annars</i>	40	7.72%

Summary for Section C

(i) *Maðurinn og konan töluðu [??? ??? ???].*

“The man and woman talked about each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvort um annað</i>	182	32.62%
<i>um hvort annað</i>	376	67.38%

(ii) *Maðurinn og konan hlupu [??? ??? ???].*

“The man and woman ran to each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>til hvort annars</i>	48	8.71%
<i>til hvors annars</i>	326	59.17%
<i>hvort til annars</i>	170	30.85%
<i>hvors til annars</i>	7	1.27%

(iii) *Maðurinn og konan hlupu [??? ??? ???].*

“The man and woman ran from each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>frá hvort öðru</i>	253	44.15%
<i>frá hvoru öðru</i>	81	14.14%
<i>hvort frá öðru</i>	234	40.84%
<i>hvoru frá öðru</i>	5	0.87%

(iv) *Konurnar tvær töluðu [??? ??? ???].*

“The two women talked about each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>um hvor aðra</i>	241	43.04%
<i>um hvora aðra</i>	116	20.71%
<i>hvor um aðra</i>	197	35.18%
<i>hvora um aðra</i>	6	1.07%

(v) *Konurnar tvær hlupu [??? ??? ???].*

“The two women ran to each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>til hvor annarrar</i>	246	44.48%
<i>til hvorrar annarrar</i>	118	21.34%
<i>hvor til annarrar</i>	183	33.09%
<i>hvorrar til annarrar</i>	6	1.08%

(vi) *Konurnar tvær hlupu [??? ??? ???].*

“The two women ran from each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>frá hvor annarri</i>	252	44.68%
<i>frá hvorri annarri</i>	113	20.04%
<i>hvor frá annarri</i>	197	34.93%
<i>hvorri frá annarri</i>	2	0.35%

(vii) *Strákarnir tveir töluðu [??? ??? ???].*

“The two boys talked about each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>um hvor annan</i>	55	9.91%
<i>um hvorn annan</i>	310	55.86%
<i>hvor um annan</i>	169	30.45%
<i>hvorn um annan</i>	21	3.78%

(viii) *Strákarnir tveir hlupu [??? ??? ???].*

“The two boys ran to each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>til hvor annars</i>	48	8.71%
<i>til hvors annars</i>	332	60.25%
<i>hvor til annars</i>	157	28.49%
<i>hvors til annars</i>	14	2.54%

(ix) *Strákarnir tveir hlupu [??? ??? ???].*

“The two boys ran from each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>frá hvor öðrum</i>	249	44.00%
<i>frá hvorum öðrum</i>	99	17.49%
<i>hvor frá öðrum</i>	216	38.16%
<i>hvorum frá öðrum</i>	2	0.35%

Summary for Section D

(i) *Elskhugarnir sem kysstu [??? ???] töluðu ítölsku.*

“The lovers who kissed each other spoke Italian.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annar</i>	10	1.93%
<i>hvor annan</i>	155	29.87%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	354	68.21%

(ii) *Hún sá [???] sem töluðu ítölsku.*

“She saw the lovers who spoke Italian.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>elskhugarnir</i>	0	0.00%
<i>elskhugana</i>	490	99.65%
<i>elskhugunum</i>	0	0.00%
<i>elskhuganna</i>	17	3.35%

(iii) *Hún sá elskhugana sem kysstu [??? ???].*

“She saw the lovers who kissed each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annar</i>	3	0.58%
<i>hvor annan</i>	146	28.08%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	371	71.35%

(iv) *Hún veitti elskhugunum sem kysstu ??? ??? blessun sína.*

“She gave the lovers who kissed each other her blessings.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annar</i>	6	1.34%
<i>hvor annan</i>	144	27.32%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	366	69.45%

<i>hvor öðrum</i>	3	0.57%
<i>hvorn öðrum</i>	2	0.38%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	2	0.38%
<i>hvor annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn annars</i>	4	0.76%
<i>hvors annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum annar</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum annars</i>	0	0.00%

(v) *Strákarnir tveir björguðu [??].*

“The two boys rescued the horse.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hesturinn</i>	2	0.40%
<i>hestinn</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hestinum</i>	498	99.60%
<i>hestsins</i>	0	0.00%

(vi) *Strákarnir tveir björguðu [??? ???].*

“The two boys rescued each other”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annar</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn annar</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvor annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	346	64.55%
<i>hvorn öðrum</i>	7	1.31%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	183	34.14%
<i>hvor annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvors annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum annar</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum annars</i>	0	0.00%

(vii) *Hún sá strákana bjarga [??? ???].*

“She saw the boys rescue each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annar</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvorn annar</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvor annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	291	53.89%
<i>hvorn öðrum</i>	19	3.52%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	225	41.67%
<i>hvor annars</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvorn annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvors annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum annar</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvorum annars</i>	1	0.19%

Summary for Section E

(i) *Strákunum finnst [??? ???] leiðinlegur.*

“The boys find each other boring.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	14	2.85%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	3	0.61%
<i>hvor annar</i>	433	88.01%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	6	1.22%
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	20	4.07%
<i>hvorn öðrum</i>	2	0.41%
<i>hvorum annar</i>	14	2.84%
<i>hvorum annan</i>	0	0.00%

(ii) *Elskhugana dreymdi [??? ???].*

“The lovers dreamt of each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	67	13.16%
<i>hvor annar</i>	3	0.59%
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	2	0.39%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	424	83.30%
<i>hvorn annar</i>	12	2.36%
<i>hvorn öðrum</i>	1	0.20%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	0	0.00%

(iii) *Hún sá [???] versna kvefið.*

“She saw the boy sicken from a cold.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>strákurinn</i>	2	0.40%
<i>strákinn</i>	83	16.77%
<i>stráknum</i>	407	82.22%
<i>stráksins</i>	3	0.61%

(iv) *Hún sá [???] sem björguðu hestinum.*

“She saw the boy who rescued the horse.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>strákarnir</i>	1	0.20%
<i>strákana</i>	489	96.45%
<i>strákunum</i>	1	0.20%
<i>strákanna</i>	16	3.16%

(v) *Þeir segja [??] [??] elska Maríu.*

They said each other loves Maria

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hver annar</i>	32	6.39%
<i>hvorn annar</i>	11	2.20%
<i>hver annan</i>	173	34.53%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	285	56.89%

(vi) *Þeir töluðu [??] [??] [??] (að tala e-n til í merkingunni að tala um fyrir e-m)*

“They persuaded each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hver til annars</i>	135	25.76%
<i>hvors til annars</i>	13	2.48%
<i>hver annars til</i>	4	0.76%
<i>hvors annars til</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hver annar til</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hver annan til</i>	102	19.47%
<i>hvorn annan til</i>	269	51.34%

Summary for Section F

(i) *Hún sá strákana sem björguðu [??? ???].*

“She saw the boys who rescued each other.”

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>hvor annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn annan</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvor annar</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorum öðrum</i>	183	34.14%
<i>hvorum annar</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvorum annan</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvorum annars</i>	1	0.19%
<i>hvor öðrum</i>	342	63.81%
<i>hvors annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvor annars</i>	0	0.00%
<i>hvorn öðrum</i>	8	1.49%

(ii) *Pétur og Páll eru að keppa í 800 metra hlaupi. Eftir 600 metra eru þeir hnífjafnir. Raðaðu eftirfarandi setningum eftir því hver þeirra lýsir best því sem næst gæti gerst.*

Peter and Paul are in a race - after 600 meters they are neck and neck - rank the following sentences:

- Peter and Paul are racing and could beat each other to the line**
- Peter and Paul are racing and could beat each other to the line**
- Peter and Paul are racing and each could beat the other to the line**

[Ranking 1]

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og gætu sigrað hvorn annan á endasprettinum.</i>	261	52.83%
<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og gætu sigrað hvor annan á endasprettinum.</i>	84	17.00%
<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og hvor gæti sigrað annan á endasprettinum.</i>	149	30.16%

[Ranking 2]

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og gætu sigrað hvorn annan á endasprettinum.</i>	116	27.42%

<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og gætu sigrað hvor annan á endasprettinum.</i>	229	54.14%
<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og hvor gæti sigrað annan á endasprettinum.</i>	78	18.44%

[Ranking 3]

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og gætu sigrað hvorn annan á endasprettinum.</i>	71	17.53%
<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og gætu sigrað hvor annan á endasprettinum.</i>	123	30.37%
<i>Pétur og Páll eru að keppa og hvor gæti sigrað annan á endasprettinum.</i>	211	52.10%

(iii) Nefnd sem hefur tekið þátt í ýmsum ólöglegum aðgerðum var að komast að því að enginn nefndarmanna lendir í fangelsi. Raðið eftirfarandi setningum eftir því hver þeirra lýsir best því sem næst gæti gerst.

A committee has just received the news that none of its members will go to jail on charges of corruption. Rank the following sentences:

The committee smiled at each other.

The committee smiled each at the other.

Each of the committee smiled at the other.

[Ranking 1]

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>Nefndarmenn brostu til hvers annars.</i>	129	25.75%
<i>Nefndarmenn brostu hver til annars.</i>	369	73.65%
<i>Hver nefndarmanna brosti til annars.</i>	3	0.60%

[Ranking 2]

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>Nefndarmenn brostu til hvers annars</i>	225	51.96%
<i>Nefndarmenn brostu hver til annars</i>	114	26.33%
<i>Hver nefndarmanna brosti til annars</i>	94	21.71%

	[Ranking 3]		
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Nefndarmenn brostu til hvers annars</i>	83	20.19%	
<i>Nefndarmenn brostu hver til annars</i>	7	1.70%	
<i>Hver nefndarmanna brosti til annars</i>	321	78.10%	

Summary for Section G

“Tveir læknar á sjúkrahúsi hafa lent í slysi þar sem nef þeirra skárust af. Fyrri læknirinn græðir nýtt nef á seinni lækninn og seinni læknirinn græðir nýtt nef á fyrri lækninn. Hvor eftirfarandi setninga lýsir ástandinu betur?”

At the hospital, two doctors have had an accident where their noses were cut off. The first doctor grafts a new nose onto the second doctor, and the second doctor grafts a new nose on the first doctor. Which of the sentences below best describes this situation?

“They gave each other a new nose.”

“They gave each other new noses.”

	[Ranking 1]		
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Þeir gáfu hvor öðrum nýtt nef.</i>	397	79.72%	
<i>Þeir gáfu hvor öðrum ný nef.</i>	101	20.28%	

	[Ranking 2]		
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Þeir gáfu hvor öðrum nýtt nef.</i>	82	20.76%	
<i>Þeir gáfu hvor öðrum ný nef.</i>	313	79.24%	

“Tveir læknar á sjúkrahúsi hafa lent í slysi þar sem nef þeirra skárust af. Fyrri læknirinn græðir nýtt nef á seinni lækninn og seinni læknirinn græðir nýtt nef á fyrri lækninn. Hvor eftirfarandi setninga lýsir ástandinu betur?”

At the hospital, two doctors have had an accident where their noses were cut off. The first doctor grafts a new nose onto the second doctor, and the second doctor grafts a new nose on the first doctor. Which of the sentences below best describes this situation?

“Each gave the other a new nose.”

“Each gave the other new noses.”

[Ranking 1]			
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Hvor gaf öðrum nýtt nef.</i>	474	95.95%	
<i>Hvor gaf öðrum ný nef.</i>	20	4.05%	

[Ranking 2]			
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Hvor gaf öðrum nýtt nef.</i>	18	4.63%	
<i>Hvor gaf öðrum ný nef.</i>	371	95.37%	

Nú eru lækarnir komnir á sjúkradeild þar sem allir sjúklingarnir eru að missa nefin. Læknarnir halda áfram að græða nýtt nef á hvern sjúkling. Hvor eftirfarandi setninga lýsir ástandinu betur?

Now the doctors have entered a ward where all the patients are missing their noses. The doctors proceed to graft a new nose on each of the patients. Which of the sentences below describes this situation:

They gave each patient a new nose.

They gave each patient new noses.

[Ranking 1]			
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Þeir gáfu hverjum sjúklingi nýtt nef.</i>	484	96.80%	
<i>Þeir gáfu hverjum sjúklingi ný nef.</i>	16	3.20%	

[Ranking 2]			
Answer	Count	Percentage	
<i>Þeir gáfu hverjum sjúklingi nýtt nef.</i>	13	3.34%	
<i>Þeir gáfu hverjum sjúklingi ný nef.</i>	376	96.66%	

Nú eru lækarnir komnir á sjúkradeild þar sem allir sjúklingarnir eru að missa nefin. Læknarnir halda áfram að græða nýtt nef á hvern sjúkling. Hvor eftirfarandi setninga lýsir ástandinu betur?

Now the doctors have entered a ward where all the patients are missing their noses. The doctors proceed to graft a new nose on to each of the patients. Which of the sentences below best describes this situation:

Appendix B – Icelandic survey questions

“They gave the patients a new nose.”

“They gave the patients new noses.”

[Ranking 1]

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>Þeir gáfu sjúklingunum nýtt nef.</i>	113	22.60%
<i>Þeir gáfu sjúklingunum ný nef.</i>	387	77.40%

[Ranking 2]

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>Þeir gáfu sjúklingunum nýtt nef.</i>	303	78.29%
<i>Þeir gáfu sjúklingunum ný nef.</i>	84	21.71%

Kyn - Gender

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>No Answer</i>	3	0.60%
<i>Kona (F)</i>	415	82.34%
<i>Karl (M)</i>	86	17.06%

Aldur

Age

Answer	Count	Percentage
<i>No Anser</i>	4	0.79%
<i>18-24</i>	137	27.18%
<i>25-30</i>	125	24.80%
<i>31-35</i>	46	9.13%
<i>36-40</i>	42	8.33%
<i>41-45</i>	35	6.94%
<i>46-50</i>	38	7.54%
<i>51-55</i>	24	4.76%
<i>56-60</i>	13	2.58%
<i>61-65</i>	18	3.57%
<i>66-70</i>	12	2.38%
<i>71-75</i>	6	1.19%
<i>76-80</i>	2	0.40%
<i>81-85</i>	1	0.20%
<i>86+</i>	1	0.20%

APPENDIX C – RECIPROCAL IN OLD ICELANDIC

1. CORPUS

Droplaugarsona saga – (“The story of Droplaug's sons” - 9600 words). From Jónsson 1947, vol. 10, based upon the text in Möðruvallabók (14th century) – the earliest extant text is from the mid 13th century. Available with Modern Icelandic spelling online at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/droplaug.htm>. English translation: Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 4:355-378.

Eiríks saga rauða – (“Eric the Red's saga” – 8000 words). From Jónsson 1947, vol. 1, based upon two texts from early 13th and 15th centuries. Available with Old Icelandic spelling online at: <http://www.heimskringla.no/original/islendingesagaene/eirikssagarauda.php>. Partial English and Danish translation at: <http://www.northvegr.org/lore/flately/001.php>. See also, Sephton, J. 1880 and Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 1:1-18.

Egils saga Skalla-Grímssonar – (“Egill's saga” – 65,600 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 2, based upon the text from Möðruvallabók (14th century), although the earliest fragments are from the early 13th century. Modern Icelandic spelling version at:

<http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/egils.htm>. English translations:

http://www.northvegr.org/lore/egils_saga/index.php and Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 1:33-177.

Eyrbyggja saga – (“The people of Eyri” – 40,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 3, based upon transcripts of *Vatnshyrna* and other manuscript fragments from the mid 13th century. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/eyrbygg.htm>. English translations: Morris & Magnusson (1892) - also online at <http://omacl.org/EreDwellers/> and Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 5:131-218.

Fóstbrœðra saga – (“The sworn brothers” – 33,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 5, based upon *Möðruvallabók*, *Flateyjarbók* and *Hauksbók* (late 13th century). Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/fostb.htm>. English translation: Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 2:329-402.

Fljótsdæla saga – (“The people of Fljótsdalr” – 27,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 10, based upon several paper manuscripts, the major ones from the 17th century. The earliest fragments are from the 14-16th centuries. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/fljotsd.htm>. English translation: Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 4:379-433.

Grænlandinga saga – (“The saga of the Greenlanders” – 6,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 1. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/graens.htm>. Translations in Danish and English at: <http://www.northvegr.org/lore/flately/001.php>. Also Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 1:19-32.

Grettis saga Ásmundarsonar saga – (“The saga of Grettir the strong” – 63,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 6, based upon four texts from the 15th century. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/grettir.htm>. English translation by Hight 1914 - available online at <http://omacl.org/Grettir/>. Also Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 2:49-191.

Gísla saga Súrssonar – (“Gisli Sursson's saga” – 20,000 words). From Jónsson 1946,

vol. 5, based upon one of the two versions of this text dating from the 15th century. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/gisl.htm>. English version by Dasent 1866, online at: <http://www.sacred-texts.com/neu/ice/gto/index.htm>. See also Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 2:1-48.

Gunnlaugs saga Ormstungu – (“The saga of Gunnlaug, Serpent Tongue” – 10,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 2, based upon two vellums from the 14th and 15th centuries. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/gunnl.htm>. English translation by Magnusson & Morris (1901) – available at <http://www.northvegr.org/lore/love/>. See also Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 1:305-333.

Gylfaginning – (“The tricking of Gylfi” – 18,000 words). By Snorri Sturluson (Ca. 1220). From Jónsson (1935) – available online at: <http://www.heimskringla.no/original/snorre/index.php>. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/snorri/gylf.htm>. English translation: Faulkes, A. 1987. Note that although this text is contemporary to the sagas (with respect to when it was written down), it is not actually a story of the settlement of Iceland. Rather it describes the Scandinavian creation myth and their deities.

Heiðarvíga saga – (“The story of the heath-slayings.” – 29,000 words). From Jónsson 1947, vol. 7. The earliest fragments of the text are from the mid 13th century. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/heidarv.htm>. English translation by Morris, W. & Magnusson, E. 1892. - available online at: <http://omacl.org/Heitharviga/>. See also Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 4:67-129.

Hallfreðar saga – (“Hallfreðr's story – The troublesome poet” – 11,000 words) From Jónsson 1947, vol. 7, based upon texts in Möðruvallabók and Flateyjarbók. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/hallf.htm>. English translation by Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 5:225-253.

Hrafnkels saga Freysgoða – (“Hrafnkell's story” – 9,000 words) From Jónsson 1947, vol. 10, based upon paper manuscripts from the 17th century. The earliest fragments are from the late 13th century. Modern Icelandic spelling version at:

<http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/hrafn.htm>. English translation by Pálsson 1971. Also Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 5:260-281.

Kjalnesinga saga - (“The people of Kjalarnes” - 11,000 words) From Jónsson 1946, vol. 12:313-358. Text is from a 15th century manuscript (AM 471). Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/kjalnes.htm>. English translation by Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 3.

Kormákr's saga – (“Kormakr's story” – 13,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 6, based upon text in *Möðruvallabók*. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/kormaks.htm>. Available online in English at: <http://www.worldwideschool.org/library/books/lit/epics/LifeandDeathofCormactheSkald/chap1.html>. Also see Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 1:178-224.

Króka-Refs saga – (“Saga of Ref ('Fox') the sly” - 11,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 4, based upon transcripts of the *Vatnshyrna* and other parchments from late 15th century. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/krokaref.htm>. English translation by Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 4:397-420.

Laxdæla saga – (“The people of Laxardalr” – 63,000 words). From Jónsson 1946, vol. 4, based upon text in *Möðruvallabók* and other texts. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/laxdal.htm>. English translation by Mangusson & Pálsson, 1969. Also see Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 5:1-120.

Njáls saga – (“Njal's saga” – 100,000 words). From Jónsson 1947, vol. 11, based upon the text in *Möðruvallabók* and other earlier sources. Modern Icelandic spelling version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/njala.htm>. English translation by Cook 1997. Also see Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 3:1-220.

Svarfdæla saga – (“The people of Svarfadardalr” – 21,000 words) From Jónsson 1947, vol. 8:119-215, based upon the text from the 14th and 17th centuries. Modern Icelandic version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/svarfd.htm>. English translation by Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 4:149-192.

Víga - Glúms saga – (“Killer Glum's saga” – 23,000 words) From Jónsson 1947, vol. 8, based upon the text in Mōðruvallabók. Modern Icelandic version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/vigaglum.htm>. English version by Head, B. 1866 - available at: <http://www.northvegr.org/lore/vigaglum/titles.php>. Also see Hreinsson *et al.* 1997, Vol. 2:267-314.

Vápnfirðinga saga – (“The people of Vápnafjord” – 10,000 words) From Jónsson 1947, vol. 10:17-61, based upon the manuscripts from the 17th century. Modern Icelandic version at: <http://www.snerpa.is/net/isl/vopn.htm>.

2. SURVEY RESULTS

a. Key to saga names

Code	Saga Name
DL	Droplaugarsona saga
ER	Eiríks saga rauða
ES	Egils saga
EY	Eyrbyggja saga
FB	Fóstbrœðra saga
FL	Fljótsdæla saga
GL	Grænlandinga saga
GR	Grettis saga
GS	Gísla saga
GU	Gunnlaugs saga
GY	Gylfaginning
HE	Heiðarvíga saga
HL	Hallfreðar saga
HS	Hrafnkels saga
KJ	Kjalnesinga saga
KR	Króka-Refs saga

KS	Kormáks saga
LS	Laxdæla saga
NS	Njáls saga
SV	Svarfdæla saga
VS	Vápnfirðinga saga
VG	Víga - Glúms saga

Total Corpus Size: Approximately 600,000 words.²¹⁵

b. Codes used to classify grammatical features

svo, vso	word order (Subj-Verb-Obj or Verb-Subj-Obj)
ante	antecedent case reciprocal construction (all other constructions are compositional reciprocal constructions)
sg/pl h	singular or plural form of <i>hver/hvor</i> (and hence the number of the reciprocal construction)
sg/pl verb	the number of the verb in the reciprocal construction. In nearly all cases of the compositional reciprocal construction, the number of the verb matches that of the number of the reciprocal construction.
bare	<i>hver/hvor</i> acting alone as the subject of the verb.
eot	words occurring with <i>hvor/hver</i> : <i>hvor þeira</i> “each of them”
eou	words occurring with <i>hvor/hver</i> : <i>hvor okkur</i> “each of us”
eotN	as above, but with additional plural noun in same case as pronoun
eN	When <i>hvor/hver</i> directly modifies a noun e.g. <i>Hver maður</i> - “each man”

c. Reciprocal Constructions in Corpus

	Saga	Codes	Text	Translation
1	GR:3	svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	En er þeir Þrándr ok Önundr kómu í Suðreyjar, fundu þeir þá Ófeig gretti ok Þormóð skafta, ok gerðist með þeim vinátta mikil, því at hverr þóttist annan ór helju heimtan hafa, þann er eftir hafði verit í Nóregi, meðan ófriðr ver sem mestr.	“But, when they, Thrand and Onund, came to the Southern Islands (the Hebrides) they found them, Ófeig Gretti and Þormóð Skafta, and a great friendship was formed, because each thought the other had risen from the dead...”
2	GR:19	svo, sg h,	Grettir var lengstum úti um daginn ok sá, at skip fóru suðr ok norðr með landi, því at <i>hverr</i>	“Grettir was mostly outside during the day and saw that vessels sail south and north along the

215 The size of each saga is given to the nearest 1000 words. More accurate numbers are somewhat meaningless because there are slightly different versions of each saga – each of different length.

Saga	Codes	Text	Translation	
		bare, sg verb	<i>sótti til annars</i> , þangat sem samdrykkjan var sett.	coast (of the mainland) because each went to visit the other where the feast was taking place.”
3	GR:29	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	En er það sá Hrótfirðingar ok Vatnsnesmenn, gengu þeir í milli ok urðu þeir þá skilðir ok fóru heim, ok höfðu hvárir ill heit við aðra ok sátu þó um kyrrt um hríð.	“...and each threatened the other...”
4	GR:31	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	Grettir sá ferð þeira ok sneri þegar fyrir þá ok er þeir fundust heilsa hvárir öðrum.	“...and when they met, each greeted the other...”
5	GR:33	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	Bóndi gekk út ok kom til nautanna ok <i>stangaði hvert annat</i> .	“The farmer went out and came to the bulls and each (bull) gored the other.”
6	GR:43	ante, sg h, bare, pl verb	Engi frami er í því, at vit drepum verkmenn <i>hvárr fyrir öðrum</i> ...	lit: “there is no fame in it if we kill workmen <i>each for the other</i> .” (There is nothing to be gained by each of us killing the other's followers). Note, 'for' here means 'against', (i.e., a malefactive. - see also (18) below).
7	GR:47	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Sá jafnan hvárr annars ferð</i> .	“Each always saw the other's path.”
8	GR:69	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Hann heilsaði þeim ok spurðu hvárir aðra at nafni</i> .	“He hailed them and each asked the other (their) names.”
9	GR:72	svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Eða sér þú eigi at hverr kjár nefinu at öðrum?</i>	“But can't you see that each puts their noses against the other.” <i>hverr kjár nefinu at öðrum</i> is idiomatic – Zoëga (2004:241) also translates it as “they put their heads together”. The sense here is that two men are talking secretly. Note that in some texts <i>þeirra</i> 'of them' was added after <i>hverr</i> (i.e., each of them...)
10	GR:72	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Gengu nú tveir ok tveir saman af héraðsmönnum ok ámælti hverr öðrum, en þeim mest, er fyrir griðunum hafði sagt</i> .	“The men of the district walked two and two together, each blaming the other, and most of all blaming him who had declared the peace.”
11	GR:72	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Hnipaði hverr kolli at öðrum</i> .	“They nodded significantly to each other.”
12	GR:72	ante, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>...jafnsáttir hverr við annan sem sonr við föður eða faðir við son í samförum öllum</i> .	“Now let us be ... each equally reconciled with the other, as a son with a father, or father with son...”
13	GR:72	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Þá leit hverr til annars, ok brá mjök vá fyrir grön</i> .	“Each looked at the other and they were startled.”
14	GR:86	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Þeir sögðu, er næstir stóðu, at sá hefði víst verit harðr í haus, ok sýndi hverr öðrum</i> .	“Those who stood nearest said he must have had a hard head and each showed the other (the sword).”
15	KR:13o r17	svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	En virkit allt mun gert stökkum holum ok mun hverr stokkr lúta eftir öðrum ok <i>hverr mun upp frá öðrum</i> ok mun svá fylla virkit uppi ok niðri af vatninu.	“but the whole fort will be made from hollow planks, and each plank will overlap (come up from) the other, and <i>each will be above the other</i> and in that way, fill the fort high and low with the water.” See http://saga.library.cornell.edu/img/618/jpg/618_25.jpg for the original manuscript. This text refers to the building of a complex fort where hollow planks filled with water are laid over each other on the walls to prevent fire.
16	KR:13o r17	vso, sg h, eN, sg verb	En virkit allt mun gert stökkum holum ok <i>mun hverr stokkr lúta eftir öðrum</i> ok hverr mun upp frá öðrum ok mun svá fylla virkit uppi ok niðri af vatninu.	“but the whole fort will be made from hollow planks, and <i>each plank will overlap (come up from) the other</i> , and each will be above the other and in that way, fill the fort high and low

Appendix C – Reciprocals in Old Icelandic

Saga	Codes	Text	Translation	
			with the water.”	
17	KR:16	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Refur og synir hans sneru þá til skips síns og urðu þar hvorir öðrum fegnir.</i>	Note:modern spelling (see note below) <i>urðu feginn</i> - “to rejoice” and so “each rejoiced at the other.” See original manuscript at: http://saga.library.cornell.edu/img/618/jpg/618_28.jpg
18	KS:10	svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Hjó hvárr þrjá skjöldu fyrir öðrum til ónýts.</i>	“Each hewed three shields of the other’s to pieces.” See (6) above for another example of <i>fyrir</i> being used as a malefactive.
19	LS:21	svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Síðan riðu þeir svá nær skipinu, at hvárir máttu skilja, hvað aðrir töluðu.</i>	“Then they rode so close to the ship, that each might understand what the other said.” (<i>i.e.</i> , that those on the shore and those on the ship can hear each other).
20	LS:44	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Skyldu sitt haust hvárir aðra heim sækja.</i> (before this sentence is: <i>Þeir Ólafr ok Ósvifr héldu inum sama hætti um heimboð.</i>)	“Each should visit the other on alternate autumns.”
21	LS:46	vso, sg h, eot, sg verb	<i>Bauð þá hvárr þeira öðrum til sín með svá marga menn sem þá þætti hvárum mestr sómi að vera.</i>	“then, each of them invited the other to their (house)...”
22	LS:59	vso, sg h, eot, sg verb	<i>Eftir þetta skilja þau Guðrún talið, ok bað hvárt þeirra annat vel fara.</i>	“After that, they (Guðrún and Snorri) ended the talk each bade the other farewell.”
23	LS:59	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Fagna þar hvárir öðrum vel.</i>	“each greeted the other well...”
24	LS:70	vso, sg h, eotN, sg verb	<i>Verðr hvárr þeira bræðra öðrum feginn.</i>	“Each of them (the brothers) becomes happy to meet the other.”
25	NS:5	svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Ok þegar er hvárir ná máli annarra, stóð Atli upp ok mælti:</i>	“...and when each managed (to hear) the other’s words...”. Translated as “and as soon as either side could hear the other’s hail, Atli stood up and said...” in http://omacl.org/Njal/1part.html
26	NS:17	vso, sg h, eot, sg verb	<i>Ámælti þá hvárr þeira öðrum ok...</i>	“Then each of them scolded the other...”
27	NS:35	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Það var siðvenja þeira Gunnars ok Njáls að sinn vetr þá hvárr heimboð at öðrum fyrir vináttu sakar.</i>	“It was the custom of Gunnar and Njál that on alternate winters, each accepted (þá) a home-invitation from the other because of their friendship.”
28	NS:52	ante, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Þeir váru beztir reiðhestar í heraðinu ok svá elskir hvárr at öðrum, at hvárr rann eftir öðrum.</i>	“They were the best riding horses in the area, so fond of each other that each would run after the other”. <i>elskir</i> – ‘fond’ here appears in the plural, meaning that the noun it refers to must also be plural (<i>i.e.</i> , the two horses). This in turn means that the verb must be plural. Given that the reciprocal construction is singular, the first instance of <i>hvárr</i> cannot be subject the sentence. And so, there must be an ellipted plural subject in this clause, thus, this reciprocal construction is an instance of the antecedent case reciprocal construction.
29	NS:52	svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Þeir váru beztir reiðhestar í heraðinu ok svá elskir hvárr at öðrum, at hvárr rann eftir öðrum.</i>	“that each ran after the other.”
30	NS:63	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Síðan eggjaði hvern annan.</i>	“then each egged on/incited the other.”
31	NS:66	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Eftir það átti hann hlut at við mótstöðumenn Gunnars ok kom því við, at þeir sættust allir, ok eftir þat veittu hvárir öðrum tryggðir.</i>	“and after that, each pledged loyalty to the other.”

	Saga	Codes	Text	Translation
32	NS:70	svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Gekk þá Njáll í meðal svá at hvárir handsöluðu öðrum grið ok sætt.</i>	“Then Njáll came between them, so that each pledged (with a handshake) peace and reconciliation to the other...”
33	NS:70	svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	Tók Njáll við þessu fé og varðveitti en <i>hvorir veittu öðrum tryggðir</i> og grið og mælti Njáll fyrir.	“...each pledged loyalty to the other”
34	NS:70	svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	“ <i>Eigi er þat sættarrof,</i> ” segir Njáll, “ <i>að hverr hafí lög við annan því at með lögum skal land vart byggja en með ólögum eyða.</i> ”	“There is no breach of settlement” said Njáll, “that each has sued the other...”
35	NS:82	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Gunnar var bróðurson Þráins ok hafði komit til hans ungr ok unni hvárr öðrum mikit.</i>	“Gunnar was Thrain's brother's son, and had come to him young, and each loved the other much.”
36	NS:83	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Spurðu þá hvorir aðra að nöfnum, hvað fyrirmenn hétu.</i>	“Then each (side) asked the other about names - what their chieftains were called”
37	NS:97	ante, pl h, bare, pl verb	“Vel er slíkt stofnað,” segir Flosi, “en <i>þó hafíð þér hættumikit hvárir við aðra</i> , eða hvað segir þú frá Höskuldi??”	“you have much danger/tension/peril between each other” (<i>i.e.</i> , they have had conflict with each other in the past).
38	NS:97	svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	Bjó Höskuldr í Ossabæ lengi svá at <i>hvárir studdu annarra sæmd</i> , ok váru synir Njáls í ferðum með honum.	“...each supported the other's prestige...”
39	NS:97	svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	Svo var ákaft um vináttu þeira, at <i>hvárir buðu öðrum heim</i> hvert (each) haust ok gáfu stórgjafar.	“...each invited the other home (to a feast)”
40	NS:105	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	...ok sögðust hvárir ór lögum annarra. Ok varð þá svo mikit óhljóð at Lögbergi, at engi nam annars mál.	“...and each declared themselves no longer bound to the law of the other”
41	NS:123	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb incon	Síðan mælti Hallr til Njáls, at hann skyldi ganga eftir sonum sínum “en ek mun ganga eftir Flosa ok veiti nú hvárir öðrum tryggðir.”	“...and now each may pledge loyalty to the other.”
42	NS:139	svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Ekki þarf þetta í hljóðmæli að færa því að þeir einir menn eru hér nú við er hverr veit annars trúnað.</i>	“There is no need to hush up because here are only men present where each has the other's confidence.”
43	NS:146	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	Nú sneri Þorgeirr í móti Leiðólfi sterka, ok <i>hjó þar hvárr til annars jafnsnemma</i> , ok varð svá mikit högg Leiðólfs, at allt tók af skildinum, þat er á kom	“...each swung at the other at the same moment.” The fuller text is “Then Thorgeir turned to face Leidolf the strong, and each swung at the other at the same moment, and Leidolf's blow was so strong that it cut off the shield where it hit.” (http://omacl.org/Njal/10part.html)
44	EY:9	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Griðum varð engum á komit, því at hvárgir vildu þau selja</i> , ok hétu hvárir öðrum aðförum, þegar því mætti við koma.	“No truce could be struck, because neither side would handsel it, but swore to fall on each other as soon as it might be brought about.”
45	GU:4	vso, sg h, eot, sg verb	<i>Lagði hvárt þeira góðan þokka til annars bráðliga</i> , sem raunir bar á síðan.	“Each of them quickly built good graces to the other, which soon became known from experience.”
46	GU:9	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Sagði hvárr öðrum frá ferðum sínum.</i>	“Each told the other of his travels”
47	GU:12	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Ok um morguninn í sólarroð, þá sá hvárir aðra.</i>	“and in the early morning light, each saw the other”. Note, the verb “to see” - <i>sjá</i> in Old Icelandic, appears to be the same in both the 3sg and 3pl.
48	GU:12	svo, sg h,	Ok þá börðust þeir tveir með stórum höggum ok öruggum atgangi, er hvárr veitti öðrum, ok	“...each attacked the other...” The fuller text is “Then they two alone fought together with

Appendix C – Reciprocals in Old Icelandic

Saga	Codes	Text	Translation
		bare, sg verb	sóttust einart í ákafa. fierce onsets and mighty strokes, which they dealt each the other, falling on furiously without stop or delay.” (Translation by Aaron Myer)
49	ES:27	svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	Þeim byrjaði vel ok heldu mjök samfloti, svá at hvárir vissu löngum til annarra. “They had a favourable wind and sailed together so each always knew of the other.”
50	ES:57	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	ok áðr þeir mættust, þá skaut hvárr kesju at öðrum. “and before they met, each hurled his halberd at the other.”
51	GL:4	vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	Nú andaðist Þorvaldur, en þeir gerðu allt eftir því, sem hann hafði mælt, ok fóru síðan ok hittu þar förunauta sína, ok sögðu hvárir öðrum slík tíðendi sem vissu ok bjuggu þar þann vetr ok fengu sér vínber ok vínvið til skipssins. “Now died Thorvald. And they did all according to what he had said, and went then to meet their comrades, and said to each other such tidings as they knew, and dwelt there that winter and gathered grapes and vine-wood for their ship.” (http://www.northvegr.org/lore/flately/001.php)
52	GY:34	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	ok seldi hvern öðrum ok treysti með handaflti, “...and each passed (it) to the others and test (it) by hand.”
53	GY:34	svo, sg h eoN, sg verb	En hvern ásanna sá til annars “and each of the gods looked to the other”
54	GY:41	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	Hvern dag, þá er þeir hafa klæðzt, þá hervæða þeir sik ok ganga út í garðinn ok berjask, ok fellir hvern annan. “Every day, when they are clothed, then they put on their armour and walk out into the court and fight, and each fells the other”
55	GY:42	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	Þá settust goðin á dómstóla sína ok leituðu ráða ok spurði hvern annan, hvern því hefði ráðið at gífta Freyju í Jötunheima, “Then the gods sat down in their judgement seats and consulted, and each asked the other who had decided to give Freyja away in marriage to Jötunheimar”
56	GY:49	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	Þá er Baldr var fallinn, þá féllust öllum ásum orðtök ok svá hendr at taka til hans, ok sá hvern til annars. “Then, when Baldr was fallen, words failed all the, Æsir, and their hands likewise to lay hold of him; each looked at the other”
57	GY:51	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	Hann á víg móti Tý, ok verðr hvárr öðrum at bana. “...and each become the other's slayer”
58	GY:51	vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	Loki á orrostu við Heimdall, ok verðr hvárr annars bani. “Loki shall have battle with Heimdallr, and each will be the slayer of the other.”
59	GY:54	vso, sg h, eN, sg verb	ok eftir honum sagði hvern maðr öðrum þessar sögur. “and after him each man told these tales to the other.”
60	VG:3	vso, sg h, eot, sg verb	Þá spurði hvárr þeira annan tíðinda eða hvar Hreiðarr hefði verit um vetrinn en hann lézt á Íslandi verit hafa. “Each of them asked the other for news...”
61	VG:3	svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	Vínátta var þar mikil í millum þeira bræðra ok Vígfüss, ok höfðu sinn vetr hvárir jólaveislu með öðrum, ok skulu þeir bræður nú búast við jólaveizlu. “...and on alternate winters at christmas, each would entertain the other.”
62	VG:12	svo, sg h, eot, sg verb	Hún kvað þat vel vera, at hvárr þeira var svá vel til annars. “She said it was good that each of them liked the other.”
63	VG:21	svo, sg h, eou, sg verb	hvárr ykkarr mun ljósta annan illum steini, áðr létti. “Each of you will smite the other with an evil stone before it is over.”
64	VG:21	vso, sg h, bare,	Ok er vit fundumst þá vildi hvárr ljósta annan en steinarnir kómu saman ok varð af brestr há. “and when we met, then each wanted to strike the other, but the two stones came against one another and there was a tremendous crash.”

Saga	Codes	Text	Translation
	sg verb		
65	VG:22 vso, sg h, eot, sg verb	<i>Veitti stór högg ok mörg hvárr þeira öðrum.</i>	“and each of them gave many big blows to the other”
66	VG:27 vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Síðan eggjuðu hvárir aðra atgöngu ok skutust á ok börðust grjóti ok varð hörð hrið ok urðu margir sárir.</i>	“Each side challenged the other and cast rocks and spears at each other and it was a hard battle and many became wounded.”
67	HE:11 vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Þekkir þá hvárr annan.</i>	“then each knows the other.”
68	HE:16 ante, sg h, bare, pl verb	<i>Því skaltu þessa menn heldr velja til farar með þér en aðra sveitarmenn að þessir eru nauðleytamenn hverr annars ok eigu allir góða kosti ok svo frændr þeira eigi síðr, ok er það því líkt sem þeir eru sjálfir.</i>	“...they are near relations to each other;”
69	HE:21 vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Fagna hvárir öðrum vel, ríða til þess er þeir koma til Þorgísl á Meðalheim.</i>	“they greeted each other well...”
70	HE:21 svo, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>ok hittust þeir brátt er hvárir riðu í mót öðrum...</i>	“and they met when each rode towards the other...”
71	HE:21 vso, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>Segja hvárir öðrum tíðindi.</i>	“Each told the other (their) tidings.”
72	HE:28 vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>ok þá mætti hverr öðrum segja þaðan frá.</i>	“and each might tell the others the news thereafter”
73	HE:33 vso, sg h, eou, sg verb	<i>Tekr hverr vórr tryggðir við annan fyrir sik ok sinn erfingja, alinn ok óborinn, ...</i>	“Each of us swears loyalty to the other for himself and for his heirs, born and unborn...”
74	HE:33 ante, pl h, bare, pl verb	<i>...ef þarfar gerast, jafnsáttir hverr við annan sem sonr við föður...</i>	“we are ... each equally reconciled with the other, as a son with his father”
75	FB:19 vso, sg h, eot, sg verb	<i>Ok er þeir finnast leggja hvárr þeira í gegnum annan ok falla jafnsnemma.</i>	“The two men clash swords and ran each other through and both died in the same instant.”
76	FB:5 vso, sg h, eot, sg verb	<i>...skiljast nú at svá mæltu, ok biðr hverr þeira vel fyrir öðrum.</i>	“...and each of them bid the other well.”
77	FL:10 svo, sg h, eotN, sg verb	<i>Fundu menn þat at hvárr þeira systra var yndi at annarri.</i>	“people saw that each of them, the (two) sisters loved the other.”
78	FL:18 vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Eggjaði hverr annan at eftir skyldi halda.</i>	“They each urged the other to get after him.”
79	FL:6 svo, sg h, eot, sg verb	<i>Váru góðar þeira samfarir, því at hvárt þeira veitti öðru vel,</i>	“Their married life was good because each of them treated the other well,”
80	FL:7 vso, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Við þenna mann leggja Þorvaldr heitt vinfengi ok svá hvárr við annan.</i>	“Thorvald forms a warm friendship with this and man and so did each with the other.”
81	FL:9 svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	<i>Þat er sem þú veizt, at vinskapr mikill var með okkr Þorvaldi, svá at hvárr unni öðrum.</i>	“As you know, there is a great friendship with Thorvald and me, each (of us) loved the other.”

Appendix C – Reciprocals in Old Icelandic

	Saga	Codes	Text	Translation
82	HS:2	ante, pl h, bare, pl verb	Fljótsdalsherað er yfirferðarillt, grýtt mjög ok blautt, en þó riðu þeir feðgar jafnan hvárir til annarra, því að gott var í frændsemi þeira.	“they always rode to each other.”
83	KJ:17	vso, pl h, bare pl verb	Eftir þat veittu hvárir öðrum tryggðir.	“After that, each (side) swore loyalty to the other.”
84	VS:20	vso, sg h bare, sg verb	Seldi svá hvárr öðrum grið	“and so each made a truce with the other.”
85	VS:5	svo, sg h, eot sg verb	...at hvárr þeira þóttist eiga marknað í annars garð...	“and so it happens that each thought he had claims on the other and their friendship suffered”
86	GS:6	svo, sg h, bare, sg verb	En síðan féllu þeir allir á kné ok sverja þann eið at hverr skal annars hefna sem bróður síns ok nefna öll goðin í vitni.	“Then they all fell to their knees and swore an oath that each would avenge the other as if they were brothers”
87	HE:14	ante, sg h, bare, pl verb	Háreks var ekki við kostur ok stóð honum elli, en hverr hinna, sem á þingi váru stungu höfðum hverr at öðrum ok fór allt á sömu leið sem it fyrra sumarit.	“...but each of them who were at the Thing (), put (their) heads together each with the others and...” Note, <i>stungu höfðum</i> has been translated as “putting heads together” but it might also mean something like “clashed heads” or argued.

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